

**The Impact and Potential of Change Management Models, for Successfully
Implementing e-Learning in Higher Education Institutions in Pakistan**

Submitted By

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Abstract

The research aim of this study is to provide recommendations for higher education institutes (HEIs) and Higher Education Commission (HEC) a regulatory body in Pakistan on implementation of e-learning through change management and motivational models along with stakeholder analysis. The objectives of the study were to conduct a comprehensive and critical literature review on organisational change management models and implementation of e-learning and to investigate relevant change management model(s) for the implementation of e-learning at HEIs in Pakistan. Thereafter, to examine the process of change management towards e-learning implementation, to explore the challenges that influence the individual stakeholder's perceptions in the implementation of e-learning, and to provide Pakistan's HEIs and the relevant regulatory body with recommendations on the implementation of e-learning with the help of stakeholder analysis.

To achieve the objectives, six research elements were identified using honeycomb research. The elements include research philosophy ("interpretivism" is the epistemology stance whereas "subjectivism" is the ontology of research), research approach (inductive), research strategy (qualitative methods), research design (case study design, the study includes five cases; four private HEIs and one public HEI from Punjab, Pakistan), data collection (semi-structured interviews as primary which contains 23 individual and 4 focus group interviews from Pakistani HEIs and documental analysis as secondary which includes HEC's policy guidelines, and data analysis technique (based on thematic analysis).

The findings reveal that the HEC and Pakistani government ordered HEIs to implement e-learning and conduct online classes without introducing regulative policies for e-learning use or implementation. This sudden implementation requires a planned approach to change, which the proposed framework can facilitate (based on stakeholder analysis, Leavitt's Diamond (macro-level), Maslow's hierarchy, and Kotter's eight step change model (micro-level)). HEIs only used training and motivational techniques to implement e-learning. Infrastructure, electricity, technological literacy, internet facility, cultural aspects, lack of engagement, online assessment, faculty pressure, resistance to change, quality of teaching, and module content creation are identified challenges of implementation and benefits of e-learning include ease of access to the module content, time management, and attending lectures. The analysis provided the basis for recommendations, including developing strategies and plans to transform teaching methods, overcoming challenges with the help of change management models, and suggesting that the Pakistani government increases education spending per GDP to improve infrastructure and technology in HEIs.

In addition to the identified challenges, the present study makes contributions towards the theoretical understanding of implementing e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. The findings reveals that the framework of the study i.e., Stakeholder analysis, Kotter's eight step model, Maslow's hierarchy and Leavitt's diamond model helps to explain the influence of internal

and external stakeholders on e-learning implementation. Based on stakeholder's analysis, it helped to identify the stakeholders and include them in the study such as managers, teachers, students, and regulatory body of Pakistan. It is also indicated that the motivational and change management models provide helpful insights about the recommendations for HEIs and HEC to help them in future implementations of change in HEIs of Pakistan. For instance, creating guiding coalition among stakeholders, motivating stakeholders, and informing the stakeholders about the requirements of the change which will enable them to manage the change during and post implementation process. The findings also show that HEC only provides instructions to the stakeholders for any change implementation rather than presenting them with proper change management plan, framework or model. However, the current study provides a framework to manage the change in HEIs.

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Contents

Contents

Abstract	1
Acknowledgment.....	3
List of Tables.....	12
List of Figures	12
List of Acronyms.....	13
Chapter 1 Introduction.....	14
1.1 Overview	14
1.2 Research Background	14
1.2.1 E-Learning.....	15
1.2.2 Change Management in relation to E-Learning	18
1.2.3 Change Management Models in Educational Setting	19
1.3 Rationale.....	21
1.4. Research Aim.....	22
1.4.1 Research Objectives	22
1.4.2. Research Questions.....	23
1.5. Research Overview	23
1.6. Institutions as Case Studies for Research.....	24
1.7. Thesis Structure Outlined.....	24
1.8 Summary	25
Chapter 2 Literature Review	26
2.1 E-Learning.....	26
Table 2.1 History of e-learning	27
2.1.1 E-learning in terms of organisations.....	30
2.1.2 E-learning in terms of HEIs.....	34
Table 2.2 Approach and Change from Aviram and Tami (2004)	37
2.3 Timeline of E-learning in HEIs of Pakistan:	39
2.4 Opportunities of e-Learning in Pakistan	42
Availability of Contents	42
Cost Effective.....	43
Local ICT Professionals	43
Partnerships Between HEIs and Governing Bodies.....	43
Popularity of Information Culture.....	44

2.5 Barriers towards e-learning in Pakistan	44
2.6 Theories & Models in e-Learning Implementation	46
2.7 E-Learning Implementation Models in Pakistan.....	48
2.8 Summary	51
Chapter 3 Theoretical Framework.....	52
3.1 Introduction	52
3.2 Organisational Change Management	53
3.3 Organisational Change Management and Higher Education Institutes.....	55
3.4 Other Change Forces affecting Higher Education	61
3.5 Stakeholder Analysis	63
3.5.1 Types of Stakeholders	64
3.5.2 Identification of Stakeholders.....	64
3.5.3. Identification of Stakeholders in HEIs	66
Table 3.1 Stakeholder Identification from Previous Studies.....	67
3.5.4 Identified Stakeholders	69
• Students	70
• Employees	70
• Educational Institutes	70
• Content Providers.....	70
• Technology Providers	71
• Regulatory or Accreditation Bodies.....	71
• Government.....	72
3.5.5 Breadth of Stakeholder Analysis.....	72
3.5.6 Key Features of Stakeholder Analysis	73
3.6 Successful Integration of SA with other Models	75
3.7 Integration of Models.....	76
3.7.1 Kotter’s Change Model.....	77
• Sense of Urgency	77
• Forming Guiding Coalition	77
• Developing/Creating Vision.....	78
• Communicating the Change Vision	78
• Empowering others to act and remove perceived barriers	78
• Short term wins	78
• Consolidating Change	79

• Anchoring Change into Culture	79
3.7.2 Relevance to the Study	79
3.7.3 Maslow’s Hierarchy	80
• Physiological	81
• Safety and Security	81
• Belongingness	81
• Esteem	81
• Self-actualisation	82
3.7.4 Relevance to the Study	82
3.7.5 Leavitt’s Diamond Model.....	83
• Task.....	83
• People.....	83
• Structure	84
• Technology.....	84
3.7.6 Relevance to the Study	84
3.8 Development of the Framework	85
3.9 Formation of the Groups.....	86
3.9.1 Drafting Change	86
3.9.2 Implementation.....	87
3.9.3 Confirming/Anchoring the Change.....	87
3.10 Justification for the Selected Framework.....	88
3.11 Functionality of the Proposed Framework	89
Figure 3a Graphical Representation of Theoretical Framework	91
3.12 Processes of the Framework	91
3.13 Summary	92
Chapter 4 Research Methodology	93
4.1 Introduction	93
4.2 Honeycomb of Research Methodology.....	94
4.2.1 Research Philosophy/Paradigm	95
4.2.1.1 Epistemology.....	96
4.2.1.2 Ontology.....	96
4.2.1.3 Objectivism	97
4.2.1.4 Subjectivism/ Constructionism.....	97
4.2.1.5 Axiology.....	98

4.2.1.2 Rationale for the Selected Paradigm.....	98
4.2.2 Research Approach.....	101
4.2.2.1 Deductive Approach.....	101
4.2.2.2 Inductive approach.....	101
4.2.3 Research Strategy.....	102
4.2.4 Research Design.....	104
Exploratory Studies vs Explanatory Studies.....	104
4.2.4.1 Case Study.....	105
4.2.4.2 Cases Selected.....	109
4.2.4.3 Factors for Case Study Selection.....	114
4.2.4.4 Testing Research Quality.....	114
4.2.5 Data Collection.....	115
Table 4a.....	116
4.2.5.1 Interviews.....	117
4.2.5.2 Other Data Collection Methods.....	118
4.2.5.3 Collecting Primary Data.....	119
Table 4.2 Internal and External Stakeholders Identified.....	120
4.2.5.4 Secondary Data.....	121
4.2.5.5 Documentation.....	121
Table 4.1 Policy Documents HEC.....	122
4.2.5.6 Interview Procedures.....	122
4.2.5.7 Sample.....	123
4.2.6 Triangulation.....	124
4.2.7 Transcription.....	124
4.2.8 Data Analysis Techniques.....	125
4.3. Summary.....	127
CHAPTER 5 Findings.....	128
5.1 Introduction.....	128
5.2 Emergent Themes.....	129
Tabel 5a Internal Stakeholders Thematic Table:.....	130
Table 5b External Stakeholder Thematic Table:.....	134
Table 5.1 Internal Stakeholders.....	136
Figure 5.1. Internal Stakeholders.....	137
Table 5.2 External Stakeholder (HEC).....	138
Figure 5.2. External Stakeholder (HEC).....	139

5.2.1 Sub-Themes.....	140
5.3 INTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS	141
5.3.1 Change Management Process/Models.....	141
5.3.1.1 Changing Nature of Academic Teaching (Teachers)	141
Use of E-Learning Before Pandemic.....	141
Use of E-Learning During/After Pandemic.....	144
5.3.1.2 Training and Motivational Strategies (Head of Department (HOD)).....	148
5.3.1.3 Training and Motivational Factors (Student Focus Group).....	150
Supporting Students’ Learning Approach.....	150
Accessible e-Resources	153
Management and Administrative Stakeholders.....	154
5.3.1.4 Training and Motivational Factors (Registrar and IT Manager)	154
5.3.1.5 Changing Nature of Academic Teaching (BDM).....	155
5.3.1.6 Resources	155
5.3.1.7 Training and Motivational Strategies (EC and BDM).....	156
5.3.2 Stakeholders’ Perception.....	157
5.3.2.1 Factors Compromising Learning Process.....	157
5.3.2.2 Stakeholders Attitude Towards the Use of E-learning and Resources (HOD).....	159
5.3.2.3 E-Learning Issues and Assistance (Student Focus Group).....	162
Managerial and Administrative Stakeholders.....	165
5.3.2.4 Managerial Perspective.....	165
5.3.2.5 Factors Compromising Learning Process and External Forces (EC and BDM).....	166
5.4 Change Implementation Process.....	168
5.4.1 Autonomous or Managed Change (Teachers).....	168
Directed by Higher Management	168
External Forces.....	170
5.4.2 Organisational Support (HOD).....	172
5.4.3 Technology Support (Student Focus Group).....	175
Management and Administrative Stakeholders	176
5.4.4. Levers of Change Management (LGU IT Manager and UOS Registrar).....	176
5.4.5 Teachers’ Attitude Towards the Use of E-learning (EC)	177
HEC Interview (External Stakeholder).....	179
5.5 Introduction	179
EMERGENT THEMES	180
5.6 Change Management Models/Process	180

5.6.1 Change Management	180
5.6.2 Resources	181
5.6.3 Training and Motivational Strategies	182
5.7 Change Implementation Process	183
5.7.1 Policies and Regulations.....	183
5.7.2 Collaborations and Explorations	183
5.8 Stakeholders' Perceptions	184
5.8.1 Changing Nature of Academic Teaching	184
5.8.2 Factors' Compromising Learning Process.....	185
5.8.3 External Forces	185
5.9 Documentational Analysis	186
5.9.1 Introduction	186
5.9.2 Guidelines for Management and Faculty	186
5.9.3 Implementation Guidelines.....	186
5.9.4 Assessment and Online Readiness	189
Table 5.3 HEC Support Teams	190
5.10 Summary	191
Chapter 6 Analysis and Discussion	192
6.1 Introduction	192
Table 6.1. Interviewees	193
6.2 Synopsis of Research Findings	194
Objective 3 To examine the process of change management towards e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan.....	196
6.3 Process of Change Management in HEIs of Pakistan	196
6.3.1 Internal Stakeholders	196
6.3.2 Training	198
6.3.3 Motivational Techniques	200
6.3.4 External Stakeholders	201
Objective 4- To explore the challenges that influence the individual stakeholders' perceptions in the implementation of e-learning	203
6.4 Stakeholders' Perception	203
6.4.1 Internal Stakeholders	203
6.4.1.1 Electricity	203
6.4.1.2 Infrastructure	204
6.4.1.3 Technological Literacy	205

6.4.1.4 Internet Facilities	206
6.4.1.5 Cultural Aspects	206
6.4.1.6 Lack of Interaction	207
6.4.1.7 Online Examination and Invigilation.....	208
6.4.1.8 Pressure on Faculty.....	208
6.4.1.9 Resistance towards Change	209
6.4.2 EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDER.....	210
6.4.2.1 Internet Availability	210
6.4.2.2 Infrastructure	210
6.4.2.3 Quality of Teaching.....	211
6.4.2.4 Module Content Creation	211
6.4.2.5 Benefits of E-learning	212
Objective 5 To provide recommendations on the implementation of e-learning to the HEIs and regulatory body with the help of stakeholder analysis.....	213
6.5 Recommendations	213
6.5.1 Autonomous or Managed Change (Teachers).....	213
6.5.2 Organisational Support (HODs).....	214
6.5.3 Technology Support (Student Focus Group).....	214
6.5.4 Levers of Change Management (LGU IT Manager and UOS Registrar).....	215
6.5.5 Teachers' attitude Towards the use of E-Learning (Examination Controller SU).....	215
6.5.6 Policies and Regulations.....	216
6.5.7 Collaborations and Explorations	217
6.6 Summary	218
Chapter 7 Conclusion and Recommendations	219
7.1 Introduction	219
7.2 Conclusion.....	219
7.3 Research Methods	225
7.4 Research Contributions	226
7.5 Contributions to Knowledge	226
7.6 Contribution to Practice	227
7.8 Theoretical Contributions	228
7.9 Research Implications.....	229
7.10 Recommendations	231
7.11 Limitations of the Study	232
7.12 Future Research Suggestions	233

References	234
Appendices	270
Appendix 1A	270
Nodes\\Initial Coding\\Nodes	270
Nodes\\Themes	274
Appendix 2	278
Ethical Approval	278
Consent Form	279
Participant Information Sheet.....	280
Appendix 3	282
INTERVIEW WITH SENIOR MANAGEMENT	282
INTERVIEW WITH DEPARTMENT HEAD OR MANAGER.....	283
INTERVIEW WITH TEACHERS OR STAFF MEMBERS.....	284
INTERVIEW SHEET FOR FOCUS GROUP (Students Only).....	285
INTERVIEW WITH HEC MANAGER	286
INTERVIEW WITH I.T. DEPARTMENT HEAD OR MANAGER	287
INTERVIEW WITH BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT MANAGER.....	288

List of Tables

Table 2.1 History of e-learning.....	25
Table 2.2 Approach and Change from Aviram and Tami (2004).....	35
Table 3.1 Stakeholder identification from previous studies	56
Table 4a Demographics of Interviewees	117
Table 4.1 Policy documents HEC.....	100
Table 4.2 Internal and external stakeholders identified	98
Table 5a Internal Stakeholders Thematic Table.....	131
Table 5b External Stakeholders Thematic Table	135
Table 5.1 Internal stakeholders	110
Table 5.2 External stakeholders.....	112
Table 5.3 HEC support teams.....	164
Table 6.1 Interviewees.....	167

List of Figures

Figure 3a Graphical representation of theoretical framework.....	75
Figure 5.1 Internal stakeholders	111
Figure 5.2 External stakeholders (HEC).....	113

List of Acronyms

- HEIs-** Higher education institutes
- HEC-** Higher education commission
- IS-** Information systems
- IT-** Information technology
- LGU-** Lahore Garrison University
- UOS-** University of Sargodha
- UOL-** University of Lahore
- UMT-** University of Management & Technology
- SU-** Superior University
- QEC-** Quality enhancement cell
- PERN-** Pakistan education and research network
- NAHE-** National academy of higher education
- EC-** Examination controller
- BDM-** Business development manager
- HODs-** Head of departments
- TSC-** Technology support committee
- QAA-** Quality assurance agency
- NKB-** National knowledge bank
- SA-** Stakeholder analysis
- CML-** Computer Managed Learning
- CAI-** Computer Assisted Learning
- CGI-** Competitiveness Global Index
- GDP-** Gross Domestic Product

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Overview

This chapter provides an introduction of the research topic, aims, and objectives. It will include the background of the study which allows the researcher to explain the context in which it is conducted. It will also shed light on the significance of the study and its rationale which will help to formulate the foundation of the study and elaborate on its wider perspective. Furthermore, the overall structure and contents of the study will also be discussed in this chapter.

1.2 Research Background

Online learning and digital advancements give rise to the need to embrace and accept the digital tools, platforms and consuming the education in new ways. This is seen as the era of technological advancements, globalisation, and digital literacy. The boost in the technological sector worldwide has created a new highly diversified, competitive, and dynamic operating environment for businesses and educational institutions around the globe (Ilic, et al., 2023).

Education is essential for any society to grow and prosper. Therefore, higher education institutes play a vital role in transforming the citizens in any society which further helps in the creation of a civilized nation (Ramos et al., 2015). Throughout the world, research related to the sustainable development in HEIs has been conducted which has led to new techniques of student assessments and changing the teaching methodology to overcome the mono-disciplinary barriers to change (Ramos et al., 2015).

As the involvement of technology cannot be neglected for the sake of learning in the current global environment, information, and communication technology (ICT) assists and supports educational institutes around the world (Bedanta, 2020). E-learning and its domain is vast and broad, it includes not only physical elements but also it encompasses various elements which are related to software from ICT, human nature and cultural aspects around the globe. Similarly, traditional teaching and learning processes are also being challenged by the new requirements due to the advancement in technology, therefore; many organisations and educational institutes are turning towards the use of ICT (Almseidein and Mahasneh, 2020).

E-learning is defined by various researchers and in different contexts. According to Oxford dictionary, the concept of e-learning is based on “learning conducted via electronic media,

typically on the internet”, whereas Canadian council on Learning briefly defined it as “the development of knowledge and skills through the use of ICTs, particularly to support the interactions of learning, interactions with content, with learning activities and tools, and with other people.” (Tirziu and Vrabie, 2015). It can be seen from the definitions that one is a general explanation of the term e-learning and the other specifically highlights interaction as the key feature. Therefore, the debate on the explanation and use of e-learning, and other associated terms such as Virtual Learning Environment, blended learning and web-based learning is similar to the earlier debates related to the area of educational technology. However, the new trend of technologies and the rapid changes in them, has introduced a broad range of innovations such as Computer Managed Learning (CML), Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI), Synchronous e-learning, Asynchronous e-learning, fixed e-learning, adaptive e-learning, linear e-learning and interactive online learning (Iqbal, 2020).

Due to the variety of technological advancements, ICT is helping to re-shape information gathering and its access for everyone in the field. For instance, in the United Kingdom, the percentage of purchasing online study materials by HEIs has increased from 8% to 11% from 2017 to 2019 (Statistia, 2020). Similarly, as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, 84% of the 30 countries from Latin America selected online learning delivery systems for delivering their course contents (Statista, 2020). It is also seen that, 97% of students in the district of Columbia enrolled in 2020 includes at least one online learning course (NCES, 2022).

Due to the increase in online learning and use of ICT, ICT provides a platform for teachers to upgrade themselves and help the students to increase their performance level. It allows peers to exchange information in real-time by networking with each other. As the flow of information grows, it improves the capabilities of the stakeholders involved in the system, restructuring the curriculum, and creating opportunities to enhance teaching and learning skills (Qazi, et al., 2021).

1.2.1 E-Learning

E-learning can be described as an educational activity which utilises information and communication technology to deliver learning resources and to support continued learning (Suzianti and Paramadini, 2021). It has become a new norm in society and due to this, it is the second most important method of teaching and learning in organisations and institutes (Galic et al., 2020).

In the past, information was exchanged through postal or face-to-face methods. With the

inception of ICT, e-learning can be used within and outside the boundaries of a traditional classroom (Farid, et al., 2014). There have been concerns about distance learning projects since the 1900s because of the fact that technology is integrated with the education system throughout the world (Sajjad, 2021). The first distance learning program was offered through radio in 1919 at University of Wisconsin which led to a distance learning program through TV in 1945 at University of IOWA, and after the introduction of internet in 1995, e-learning was finally revealed (Kentnor, 2015). During 2010-2020, the performance and utilisation of virtual education, namely online learning, reached new heights (Edelhauser and Dima, 2020).

While e-learning has its merits, there are also some challenges associated with it. For instance, the traditional values and structures of educational organisations will change with the use of e-learning, as the traditional face to face learning will be changed and revamped. For example, Open Universities which offer complete online degrees are growing to provide learning opportunities to students anywhere in the world (Oblinger and Rush, 1997). The fight between traditional learning and online learning will continue among the management of HEIs as their sole purpose is to make profit out of the educational market (Cunha, et al., 2020). Therefore, most of the traditional universities now utilise a combination of both methods of teaching which enables them to provide a blended or hybrid mode of teaching. As the admission level in the Open University of UK has decreased by 33% since 2010, it does not represent that the use of e-learning is reduced in HEIs (Cunha, et al., 2020).

The increase in ICT in the education sector allows students to adopt certain changes related to the learning process and ICT helps them achieve this by providing connectivity and interaction with teachers and peers which was not possible before (Jan, 2018).

Furthermore, e-learning has its implications related to the teachers in the universities. This new era of e-learning has also made academics learn a new skill set related to educational technologies and to become technologically literate. Developed countries such as the USA has institutes which offer 89% online courses and, in those institutes, more than 50% offer complete online degrees, whereas in developing countries including Pakistan, there were only a few open universities which were partly offering such programs (Mumtaz, et al., 2021).

The online features associated with e-learning can change the role of academics (Blass and Davis, 2003). It is because in traditional teaching, teachers can use their choice of methods, whereas, in the implementation of e-learning they might be directed to use specific teaching methods. For instance, in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, in Pakistan, the Higher

Education Commission (HEC) (regulatory body), directed the universities to convert on-campus classes to online classes in March 2020 to help to stop the spread of the virus (Anwar, et al., 2021).

Moreover, according to Nawaz and Kundi (2010), the institutes should also consider human diversities related to technological matters because, if the newly developed systems are not according to the end users' requirements, perception, characteristics and context of use then there will be problems related to its use and implementation (Davies, et al., 2004). For instance, Ramani (2015) concluded in his study that it is essential for the developing countries that the online contents are in the learners' own language. Further the study of Ali, Uppal and Gulliver (2017) highlights barriers towards e-learning implementation through systematic literature review, one of the barrier identified is individual culture which confirms that for the best outcome, it will be beneficial if the e-learning program matches the learning style of the learner (Ali, et al., 2017). It is also seen that adopting e-learning not only involves technological materials but also includes other factors like human contribution (Kundi, et al., 2010).

As management researchers have their theories related to understanding management concepts, similarly, e-learning revolves around four main learning concepts, namely behaviourism, cognitivism, constructivism, and emotional/social presence (Cooper, 1993), (Rienties and Rivers, 2014). According to **Behaviourism**- e-learning is based on deductive focus where learning happens when a person's behaviour changes as a result of provided stimuli and the change must be observable and measurable. **Cognitivism**- Introducing new techniques by bridging current and new knowledge or techniques (Ahmad, et al., 2019). **Constructivism**- emphasises on learners comparing the current and prior information provided to them and change the learning based on their analysis (Lockey, et al., 2021). It shows that learning should be an active process, therefore, learners should not be spoon-fed but they should be able to control their learning processes, availability of time and opportunity to reflect the time (Ananga, 2020). Lastly, **Social Presence**- allows an individual to be recognised as a "real person" in arbitrated communication. It is based on the interpersonal relationship among the communicators which makes the environment to be perceived as real, present, or there (Ananga, 2020). Ananga (2020) suggests that, in the global pandemic, researchers should consider this learning theory seriously because it helps to close the geographical gap between the teacher and the student.

According to Aini et al. (2020), e-resources designed for the current era will be more beneficial than traditional teaching methods and they will improve the teaching and learning process. Bernstein (2000) explains pedagogy as a process in which someone acquires new or develops existing forms of knowledge, practice, conduct and criteria from someone deemed to be an appropriate supplier and evaluator. Therefore, it is the need of the hour to combine traditional and new modes of teaching to ensure that the learner benefits from both methods.

1.2.2 Change Management in relation to E-Learning

There are different stakeholders involved in managing the change who are responsible for implementing those changes. The organisational structure of educational institutes is complex in nature which makes them difficult to adapt to change however, they are also subject to unpredictable changes such as technological change to improve current learning and teaching processes (Gkrimpizi, et al., 2023). Due to the complex structure of HEIs, researchers are studying the tools and techniques used for the strategic implementation of e-learning to adopt the change especially in the difficult time of pandemic. As COVID-19 is primarily an airborne virus, social distance measures have been put in place around the globe to help stop its spread. This has resulted in the introduction of online classes with the implementation and use of e-learning in almost every part of the world (Biswas and Debnath, 2020).

It is now becoming of immense importance to discuss and understand the factors, challenges and issues faced by the academics, students and other stakeholders of the HEIs, to understand them and to also study the strategic implementation of e-learning. The study of Findikli (2020) mentions the structure of HEIs in two ways of governance, one is *Republic of Scholars*, which explains that leadership of the institute and decision-making are based on collegiate decisions made by independent scholars. Whereas, in *Stakeholder organisation*, the institutional autonomy is considered for the basis of strategic decision making by higher management or leaders, who consider satisfying the interests of Primary stakeholders and the suggestions of academics are viewed as the voice of an ordinary stakeholder in the system.

With the help of individual academics, the academics help in providing their suggestions and expertise in the implementation of ICT in the education sector, however, it can also be the case that most of the academics have less interaction with other colleagues in different departments of the same institute while having better communication outside the organisation with other academics in their same field. Similarly, e-learning requires other experts which are stakeholders of e-learning such as different libraries, employers, educational technology

developmental companies etc. As each department or stakeholder requires a different level of strategy therefore, to adopt e-learning, various and complex strategies are required to help implement it. Stakeholder analysis, along with change management models, will help with the implementation and accepting the change process in the HEIs of Pakistan.

1.2.3 Change Management Models in Educational Setting

Higher education institutes are considered as organisations in our society in which research can take place but, they have their own unique culture and concerns due to which they are considered as complex organisations. There is growing focus on the strategic management of HEIs in which managers and administrators utilise different methods to administer the change process in their organisations to meet the changing criteria of the industry (Mader, et al., 2013).

In the current scenario, every university as an organisation is facing transformation around the globe. HEIs are transformed into educational corporations which requires them to adopt the corporate culture of society. The educational corporate systems include social systems which are based on quality products related to their uniqueness (such as new ways of distributing knowledge) and services (new modes of training and services), ethical principles of employees, rules of conducting the business and reputation of the organisation at national and international level (Blynova, et al., 2020).

Various structural changes have occurred in the field of education. The growth in managerialism leads to different change drivers in different universities such as the introduction of artificial technology, demographic change as a societal change, regulations imposed by direct stakeholders and power shifts (Heck & Luebkehan, 2023). However, traditionally, universities adopted a contingent or incremental approach towards change. In the author's opinion, both approaches can be used in the implementation of change in the organisation, especially in the context of e-learning. This is because, in developing countries such as Pakistan, there were some academics and teachers who initiated the process of e-learning in their classes and modules at individual level. Eventually, it became difficult for them to use e-learning with the passage of time because e-learning requires IT support, technical training, and financial support in terms of buying software licenses. However, this led to uneven spread of adoption of technological resources in the education industry. Considering the process of change through the lens of incremental approach, the change will then be considered to implement when the time is right for the management which becomes

problematic for the organisation.

In an educational setting, all the employees come under organisational management which is subject to the organisational strategies. Teachers are also a part of management, therefore, Mehra and Mital (2007) categorised teachers as Cynics- who are unwilling to change because of their negative perceptions, Moderates- they require training, and they are willing to adapt the change; and Adaptors- they already accept the change and use the new techniques for inner progress by involving continuous innovation. Similarly, Kanwal, Rehman, Bashir and Qureshi (2017) provided a literature review related to e-learning studies specifically conducted in the context of Pakistan. Their study represents that very little work has been done by researchers in the context of Pakistan. Although the adult literacy rate in Pakistan is 57%, however, in terms of adopting e-learning in HEIs in Pakistan it is challenging for the education sector because the government allocates roughly 2.3% of GDP to the education sector (Government of Pakistan, 2020).

With the help of the Global Competitiveness Index (CGI), we can see that the overall ranking of Pakistan in terms of higher education and training was 123 out of 138 which is very poor. According to Kanwal et al., (2017), Pakistan's educational rankings are poor and the implementation of e-learning in HEIs in Pakistan are still at the early stages. However, the Government of Pakistan and the ministry of education extended their invitations to the universities to establish and work on the learning management systems. It is seen that the cost of LMS or other e-learning systems are low therefore, it will also help to save cost for the HEIs, and it will benefit the students (Kanwal, et al., 2017). It is also seen that e-learning platforms are increasingly used by HEIs around the world. According to the statistics of Global E- learning Market, it was seen that in 2019 the global e-learning market was valued at \$144 billion, and it is expected that it will grow and reach \$374.30 billion by 2026 which is almost 14.6% compound annual growth rate (Facts & Factors, 2020). It is observed that all the successful organisations whether they are educational, professional or any type of business organisation, become successful due to the changes they adapted in their working environment, either strategic or cultural.

Various studies have also revealed that the adoption of e-learning in HEIs is affected by numerous variables such as demographics, human-computer interaction, cultural factors, no proper model for implementing e-learning, hardware, and technology support etc. As the change occurring in an educational setting is adopts the Top-Bottom approach related to

stakeholders, in this study the author is considering Top-Bottom approach in relation to stakeholder analysis. Therefore, in this study, the author will shed light on the stakeholder analysis along with other management models to successfully implement e-learning, and the author will also review the implications of COVID-19 in the implementation of e-learning.

1.3 Rationale

The introduction of communication and technology which is referred to as e-learning has brought drastic changes to the education sector (Baig, et al., 2021). It is becoming popular not only in West, but also the growth of e-learning is now more prevalent in Asian countries. Due to COVID-19, both developing and developed nations decided to conduct their education and learning through e-learning as it is a distance learning technique.

In Pakistan, the first case of novel coronavirus was confirmed by the Ministry of Health of Pakistan on 26th February 2020 in Karachi city, Sindh Province (Abid, et al., 2020). Within 15 days, the number of positive cases rose to 20 out of 471 suspected cases (National Institute of Health, 2020). On 12th February 2020, the National Institute of Health (NIH) presented their “National Action Plan for Preparedness and Response to Coronavirus Disease Pakistan” which aimed to slower down the spread of the virus and to strengthen the country in order to ensure a timely response to effectively and efficiently deal with COVID-19 (Waris, et al., 2020). Till 22nd April 2021, the total number of cases of COVID-19 in Pakistan rose to 778,238 (Johns Hopkins University, 2021).

In the western world, the United Kingdom closed its universities for traditional face-to-face classes on 16th March 2020 and they moved their teaching completely to online learning (Longhurst, et al., 2020). Similarly, Pakistan also responded to this threat with caution and HEC Pakistan, which regulated the education sector, instructed on 13th March 2020 to close all the educational institutes at all levels across Pakistan. On 18th March 2020, HEC announced the educational institutes at all levels to organise online learning and teaching classes (Khan, et al., 2020).

With the compulsion introduced by HEC, it became the need of the hour that the HEIs of Pakistan made themselves ready for the abrupt change. Although the change initiated was related with a Top-Bottom approach as the senior management of the institutes corresponds with the regulatory body (HEC), also, HEC directs the universities to ask their teachers and other employees to take part in different online courses which were offered by HEC free of charge (HEC, 2020). However, when any change is introduced by the higher management in

the organisation it may be opposed by the stakeholders in some way such as resistance, transfer of power etc (Basar, et al., 2013). It is also seen that the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan has not been fully studied in terms of providing models or frameworks for implementation of e-learning (Ali, et al., 2018). Therefore, the main motivation behind this study is the lack of research on providing models which show successful implementation of e-learning as a change in HEIs of Pakistan.

According to Kanwal et al., (2017), there were no research publications found about e-learning in Pakistan during 2001-2005 and in the next five years, only seven research articles were published. However, the trend of research related to e-learning is changing in Pakistan and the increasing trend confirms the importance and issues related to e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. Furthermore, the findings of Kanwa et al., (2017) reveals that to adopt e-learning, it requires in-depth analysis of the policies of the government and bodies regulated by the government and authorities, student and faculty attitude towards the adoption, social norms, cultural values and technological advancements. It is also seen that various studies conducted in the context of Pakistan are mostly centred towards the students' satisfaction, the effect of e-learning on students and their perception towards e-learning; and the impact of e-learning on teachers. Therefore, this study will focus on the knowledge gap related to the role of change management models linked with the implementation of e-learning by developing guidelines utilising stakeholder analysis, along with the consideration of other management models, to successfully implement e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. It also introduces this new approach to the body of existing knowledge in terms of studies related to Pakistan only.

1.4. Research Aim

The aim of this study is to provide recommendations for HEIs and HEC Pakistan on implementation of e-learning through change management models and stakeholder analysis.

1.4.1 Research Objectives

1. To conduct a comprehensive and critical review of literature on understanding the potential of change management models and implementation of e-learning in HEIs.
2. To investigate relevant change management model(s) for the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan.
3. To examine the process of change management towards e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan.

4. To explore the challenges that influence the individual stakeholder's perceptions in the implementation of e-learning.
5. To provide recommendations on the implementation of e-learning to the HEIs and HEC Pakistan with the help of stakeholder analysis.

1.4.2. Research Questions

Following are the research questions of the study:

1. How the implementation of e-learning(change) managed by the stakeholders of HEIs of Pakistan?
2. What are the significant internal and external challenges that influence the stakeholders' perception in the implementation of e-learning in HEIs in Pakistan?
3. Which recommendations should be considered by the HEIs, and HEC Pakistan related to the change implementation with the help of change management models?

1.5. Research Overview

The current study is merged with the change management models in relation to the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. With the help of different factors to illuminate the issues and challenges in relation to the adoption of e-learning in the HEIs of Pakistan, the current study will explore how the change is managed in complex structure organisations such as Universities and the response of the individuals who will act when the change is implemented in their institute will be recorded.

Utilising the theoretical framework based on stakeholder analysis and with the explanatory power of change management models such as Maslow's hierarchy, Kotter's eight step change model and Leavitt's Diamond model, the author will understand and evaluate the nature of change which occurred in the HEIs of Pakistan at individual and organisational level. At organisational level (middle to high level management), the research will examine whether there are any change management strategies/models being used for the promotion and implementation of e-learning. Similarly, at individual level (teachers or students), the current study will explore the perceptions of the academics and students related to e-learning implementation, its use, challenges, and its outcomes.

1.6. Institutions as Case Studies for Research

When the research was initiated, the author had different plans related to which institutes would be included in the current study as a Case study on each individual basis. However, as research progressed, COVID-19 made it difficult for the researcher to continue with the initial plan of research and data collection. Initially, the researcher was considering five HEIs from the Punjab province of Pakistan; two from the public sector and two from the private sector. However, in the eventual data collection the universities included as case studies are Superior University (Private), University of Lahore (Private), Lahore Garrison University (Semi-Public), University of Management and Technology (Private), and University of Sargodha (Public).

The above-mentioned institutes are each considered as an individual case analysed based on thematic analysis. Semi-structured interviews were taken from the management and teachers and focus group interviews were conducted with the students. However, to include the opinions and suggestions of other stakeholders, interviews from external stakeholders (HEC) were conducted as well.

1.7. Thesis Structure Outlined

The thesis begins with chapter 1 which provides the introduction related to the research topic. In chapter 2, the literature review of the research will be discussed based on the previous research conducted on the implementation of e-learning in HEIs. It will include literature related to e-learning in general and in the context of HEIs, organisational change management in general and in the context of HEIs, and other factors affecting the change in HEIs.

Chapter 3 will shed light on the theoretical framework of the study and the models used in previous studies. It will provide insight about the models proposed for the current study and the use of those models in previous studies. Further, the integration of change management models will be discussed. Chapter 4 is related to the research methodology of the study. It presents the research philosophy, approach, methodology, design, data collection, and data analysis techniques identified through the honeycomb research approach.

Chapter 5 provides, with the help of thematic analysis and identified themes, valuable insights related to the data collected through semi-structured interviews. It will provide crucial information which will help to achieve the objectives of the study.

Chapter 6 is related to the analysis and discussions of the research. It reports how the objectives of the study will be achieved along with relating to the previous studies and theoretical framework of the current study.

Chapter 6 provides the basis of the last chapter 7, which includes the conclusion (final remarks of the study), contribution of the study towards knowledge, practice, and theory, recommendations, limitations and suggestions for future work.

1.8 Summary

The chapter presents the overview of the research related to the change management of the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. It also includes the research background related to the study which led towards providing grounds for the rationale of the study. The rationale helps to explain the aims, objectives and research questions of the current study. As the current research is based on a case-study approach, the research sites are mentioned. Lastly, the structure of the thesis is explained to provide details about the following chapters.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

This chapter presents the previous studies related to e-learning, organisational change and development, change management models such as Kotter's eight step model, motivational model such as Maslow's need of hierarchy model, a management model (Leavitt's Diamond Model), and stakeholder analysis. In this section, the author has also shed light upon the background and explanation related to the above-mentioned terminologies.

2.1 E-Learning

The history of e-learning is parallel with the history of the advancement of technology and its use in different sectors to make the learning and teaching process easy and affordable for the future. The purpose and definition of e-learning also varies at different organisations such as in schools it is related with the use of different software, applications, and machines (such as computers, projectors etc.) along-with online learning platforms. In relation to business, military, and higher education institutes it involves a range of online activities and programs (Nicholson, 2007).

The evolution of education and learning processes including technology changes regularly. Similarly, the adoption of e-learning starts from 1971 when email was invented. Table 2.1 below shows the trends, modifications and advancements in technology and its application over the time.

Table 2.1 History of e-learning

YEAR	INVENTION	EXAMPLE
1861	Telegraph is invented	
1876	Telephone is invented	
1922	Radio broadcast of courses	Pennsylvania State College initialises broadcast of courses via radio (Dawson, 2014)
1934	Television Broadcast used for learning purposes	University of Iowa (UIOWA, 2019)
1953	First Televised Courses	University of Houston (Fisher, 2013)
1969	Computer data networking is Invented (ARPANET), Open University (UK)	DARPANET/ARPANET. World's First Open University opened in UK.
1971	Email is Invented	
1971	Computer Conference is Invented	1971
Mid 70's	University Courses are Supplemented by Email and Conferencing	
Mid 70's	Virtual Communities of Practice	Scientists use EIES to collaborate
1976	Virtual College	University of Arizona established first virtual college.
1981	First totally online courses (Nonformal, Adult Education)	The Source; EIES
1982	First Online Program (Executive Education)	WBSI Executive Education (EIES)
1983	Networked Classroom Model Emerges (Primary and Secondary Schools)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICLN Research Project in 4 Countries

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RAPPI: Canada X-Cultural Project I Countries • SITP (1990)
1986	First totally online undergraduate classroom	Virtual Classroom (NJIT)
1985	First totally online graduate courses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect-ED (New School of Social Research) • OISE (University of Toronto)
1985	First totally online labour education network	Solinet (Canadian Union of Public Employees)
1986	First online degree program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect-ED (1986)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1989 University of Phoenix
1986	Online professional development communities Emerge	OISE Ontario Educators Online Courses
1989	Internet Launched	
1989	First Large-scale online distance learning courses	Open University (U.K.)
1992	World Wide Web is invented	CERN (Switzerland)
1993	First National Educational Networks	1993 SchoolNet (Canada)
1995	First online Ph.D.	Regent University offers first online Ph.D. in organisational leadership (Regent University, 2019)
1996	First Large-Scale Online Education Field	Virtual -U Research project
1997	WebCT predecessor of BlackBoard	WebCT 1.0 LMS platform (Bristol & Zerwekh, 2011)
1998	Black Board	Online learning systems (Bradford, et al., 2006)
2002	Moodle	First Virtual Learning Environment (Moodle, 2019)
2008	MOOC	Connectivism and Connective Knowledge (Marques, 2013)
2011	Canvas LMS, Udacity	Instructure introduced Canvas LMS system (Instructure, 2022), Udacity MOOC platform. (Udacity, 2022)
2012	EdX, Coursera,	MOOCs offering online courses platforms. (EdX, 2022) (Coursera, 2022)

Source: (Bradford et al., 2006; Weiss, 2006; Bristol and Zerwekh, 2011; Fisher, 2013; Marques, 2013; Dawson, 2014; Moodle, 2019; UIOWA, 2019; Li, 2018; Instructure, 2022; Udacity, 2022; Edx, 2022; Coursera, 2022).

With the advancements and achievements of technology, the delivery of e-learning or modes of e-learning is classified into two main branches, namely synchronous, or asynchronous. In synchronous e-learning, learners and instructors are required to engage in simultaneous interactions at different locations to deliver a real-time learning experience (Zhang, 2003). Similarly, Shahabadi and Uplane (2015) explain that synchronous refers to a scheduled, focused and learning-oriented process which enables its participants to interact live with each other while at different locations. The main roots of synchronous e-learning is based on three components; virtual classroom, e-meeting, and webcast (Classroom, Conference and Media respectively) (Hyder et al., 2007). The important, and increasingly popular, examples include Second Life, Blackboard, OpenSim and Moodle etc (Kotsilieris and Dimopoulou, 2013).

On the other hand, asynchronous e-learning can take place at any time because it does not require the learning event or learning process to happen in real-time. The best way of defining it is as an on-demand learning process which provides the learner flexibility, control and availability on their learning process and contents (Zhang, 2003). Put simply, it provides a platform to learn anytime and anywhere with the help of computer mediated communication (CMC), peer-to-peer interactions or distance learning (Shahabadi and Uplane, 2015). There are different forms of such learning style which include e-mails, public online forums, online materials which can be downloaded or accessed online, the use of online databases, such as online libraries or portals etc, and interactive web tutorials (Zhang, 2003).

Both synchronous and asynchronous tools related to e-learning are in use by different educational institutes and especially in HEIs. Oztak, Zingaro, Brett and Hewitt (2013) discussed the use of both terminologies in educational institutes in order to evaluate whether or not it would be helpful for the students. In that research, the researchers studied nine courses. Their results showed that both of the tools will help the students and the instructors to fill the necessary roles in the evolving era of technology which will ultimately help the students to develop better communication with their instructors and class fellows.

In HEIs, e-learning courses can be categorised using two terms:

- **Online Courses-** These courses are completely conducted online and there are no face-to-face interactions.
- **Blended Courses-** Blended or Hybrid courses are those in which part of the classes are conducted in traditional face-to-face sessions and part of them are conducted online (Sumallika et al., 2022).

2.1.1 E-learning in terms of organisations

In this section the researcher highlighted the previous studies related to the use of e-learning in business organisations. It covers the barriers, challenges and issues faced by the organisations during the implementation and use of e-learning. E-learning is not only conducted in educational institutes, but business organisations also utilise and benefit from the use of e-learning systems to not only enhance the dynamic capabilities of their human resources but also to train their employees to be adaptable to change. Iris and Vikas (2011) discuss dynamic capabilities, knowledge sharing, knowledge management and e-learning. Their study shows that knowledge sharing across the organisational boundaries with the support of new technological measures such as e-learning results in a continuous increase in the dynamic capabilities of their employees. They conducted their research on three organisations which implemented synchronous and asynchronous methods of e-learning but mostly the organisations utilised asynchronous because it allows the end user to gain knowledge according to their free time and availability through e-portals and servers (Iris and Vikas, 2011).

E-learning platforms for staff training and development are considered to be the most efficient instrument in the business sector. In the corporate world, managers and executives are continually searching for measures that are not only cost-effective but also result in improved performance or outcomes. Some managers are also eager to utilise e-learning to enhance their training and development initiatives. Similarly, input is required from colleagues and other employees who wish to participate in the system. Bikupi et al. (2015) found that workplace barriers, cultural motivation, and learner motivation are the most relevant elements when considering e-learning for training in organisations. The study also demonstrates that asynchronous assessments are more prevalent since they are readily accessible to candidates (Beamish et al., 2002).

With the advancements in technology, different common businesses use e-learning to teach

soft skills such as leadership, management, customer service, quality management and human resources. In one study, the researcher discussed the tools used to deliver e-learning and also the advantages and disadvantages of synchronous and asynchronous methods. The study provided insight about the combination of both tools according to their benefits to promote effective learning (Lim, 2017).

Although the ubiquity of e-learning is growing rapidly in the training and development sector, either it is related with the educational institutes or with the corporate sectors. The use of electronic tools is increased for the developmental and training purposes of the employees but different internal factors (such as user satisfaction (Esterhuyse, et al., 2016)) and external factors (such as social influence, computer anxiety and experience (Abdullah and Ward, 2016) affect the implementation of e-learning in the corporate sector, resulting in restricted adoption of e-learning which requires the management to put in place change strategies to overcome the resistance and barriers to adoption of e-learning.

E-learning in the organisations can be affected by the internal and external factors related to its implementation. Various research projects such as that conducted by Chen (2014) have seen that the application of government of Taiwan stipulated policy makes it compulsory for the civil service employees to get 40 hours of learning or training per year which includes five hours from e-learning resources. It showed an increase in the e-learning programmes for training purposes and 220 public sector employees indicated e-learning as a practical, satisfying, and effective tool for training and development purposes. Although the external factor that is governmental policies affects the implementation because it acts as a catalyst for implementing e-learning and also the internal factors such as employee's learning behaviour, information technology systems and infrastructures and availability of other resources made it possible to achieve successful implementation (Awan et al., 2021; Kasani et al., 2020).

Navimipour and Zareie (2015) identified four important internal factors which affect the employee's satisfaction related to e-learning systems, namely technology, educational content, motivation, and attitude towards e-learning (Fatima et al., 2021). Their study shows that technological factors include sub-factors which are important to consider while implementing e-learning, for instance the learning systems must be of good quality i.e. the speed of loading interface, availability of different databases, knowledge of how to use the system and making it easier to use and understand with the help of technical support (Holsapple and Lee-Post, 2006; Malik, 2010; Capece and Campisi, 2013; Belaya, 2018).

Motivation plays a vital role in implementing any program in any organisation. If the employees, managers, and other stakeholders are not motivated towards the implementation of new programs, facilities, or technology then it will result in catastrophe for the organisation as the implementation will fail. The 3D environment is attractive, and it provides the learner with understanding the environment and its practical approach in real life. It motivates the learner as they can consider and apply their training and are able to see the results of their learning, but it also depends on their own self-motivation. If employees are self-motivated towards learning new techniques, then it will be easier for the organisation to implement those strategies. Organisations can motivate employees by providing them with financial and non- financial benefits which also serves as an internal factor towards the implementation process (Navimipour and Zareie, 2015).

In most of the studies, the role of management is crucial in terms of facilitating and implementing e-learning in their organisations as an internal factor. Employees' computer related skills also increase their confidence level to accept the change and also to overcome their own resistance to adapt to e-learning platforms. Conversely, when they do not have enough skills and knowledge related to information systems their motivation is reduced which results as a barrier towards the e-learning's implementation. Organisational Support, Management Supports, Computer Self-Efficacy, Individual's Experience with Computers, Task Interdependence, and Subjective Norms are considered as important external factors for the designing and implementation of e-learning in corporate organisations (Lee et al., 2011).

Some organisations have faced internal criticism and barriers while implementing e-learning as a change. Implementation of e-learning is considered as a change because it acts as a new strategical approach which not only manages the training and development of the employees but also it helps them to communicate and perform their duties and tasks more effectively. One of the studies, conducted in Kuwait, shows that management support, cost, time, technology, resistance towards change related to the use of technology, language, and culture are the prominent barriers in organisations which tried to implement e-learning (Ali and Magalhaes, 2008). Similarly, learning management systems (LMS) are most commonly and rapidly adopted by the health sector specifically in nursing around the world. There are also multiple factors which affect the implementation of e-learning to help nurses and doctors to train and educate them about certain topics or even full modules. White and Shellenbarger (2017) conducted their research on the effective and efficient use and implementation of LMS program to help nursing professionals around the world. In their research, they

indicated technological factors, access to computers, the health professional's computer knowledge and their own capabilities towards learning of LMS programs will affect the implementation. The most crucial part of their research is that they identified key stakeholders and suggested that the nursing professional development (NPD) practitioners form lead an implementation team which includes administrators, IT staff, end-user learners and managers as key stakeholders to act as a catalyst to implement the change or communicate the need of change (White and Shellenbarger, 2017).

Pre-existing organisational politics (OP) are an inevitable and unavoidable part of the organisation and these have a strong influence towards planned or strategic change in the organisation (Bouckenooghe, 2012). Organisational politics is a term which refers to the decisions of any stakeholder being influenced due to the environment in the organisation depending upon the power and control of the stakeholders in the organisation (Lampaki and Papadakis, 2018).

As e-learning is a form of planned change process in an organisation, it will also come up against organisational politics. Although the applications and criticism of e-learning is mostly researched in the area of education, it is now a growing concern of business organisations as well. This is especially relevant in developing countries such as Pakistan, where private and public institutions (e.g., NADRA) have such a high level of OP that it is common for employees at different levels in different departments to damage the image of co-workers in front of their managers or supervisors which then damages the transfer of training or managing any change (Khalid et al., 2017).

2.1.2 E-learning in terms of HEIs

Information Communication Technology (ICT) is the backbone of e-learning programs, and it plays a vital role in the development of various e-learning systems. As ICT itself is based on continuous research, innovation, and development therefore, educational institutes are considered as the support of research related to ICT as new generations novel ways to develop the global technology sector. In the developing world, ICT facilitates education and development in regions where previously it was hard to reach (Macleod, 2005).

E-learning in the context of HEIs is different compared to the context of business organisations. In HEIs, the impact of e-learning is not only on the staff members but also on students, management, parents (in terms of finances for fees) and providers of the hardware and software services. The abovementioned stakeholders are only a handful of the overall stakeholders. However, in the following Chapter 3 theoretical framework, the author will explain and identify the potential stakeholders in the process of stakeholder analysis.

Implementing e-learning as a strategy in educational institutes is itself a major challenge for the management because there are different stakeholders who will be affected by this strategy. Implementation of e-learning will affect the change of culture, structure, and other strategies, therefore careful consideration should be put in place. Initially if we start with the teachers, we can see them as employees and if employees are not satisfied with their work and with the change which management is about to bring then it will be chaos for other stakeholders too because if educators do not show their interest then it will lead towards the poor results of the students and the whole change process will be a failure (Isa et al., 2020). Therefore, management should ask the educators to apply the same skills which they want to apply on their students; continuous dialogue and sharing of experiences and knowledge along with becoming receptive towards situational differences (Juniu, 2005).

Schulz, Isabwe and Reichert (2015) discussed teaching resources, environment, salaries, support from management and policies which also relates to the politics in the organisation as well as the major variables affecting teachers towards adopting ICT tools. The study was mainly conducted in Europe, Nigeria, and the United Arab Emirates. It was also seen that certain ICT features related to gaming such as graphical ICT tools also motivated teachers and students to accept e-learning methods and to learn quickly (Schulz et al., 2015).

Although teachers utilise the techniques of e-learning, it is management that provides the platform, assistance, and policies for the implementation of the strategies. In various studies

(such as Torraco et al., (2005); Alhogail and Mirza, (2011); Kanwal and Rehman, (2014); Almaiah and Mulhem, (2018)) it is seen that management of the universities play a pivotal role in implementing new technology and programs because HEIs are based on complex mechanisms and the culture of the organisations not only varies from country to country but also between local areas within cities.

It also requires the management to assess the need of the technology in the organisation because the success rate of e-learning in HEIs is based on the fulfilment of needs and requirements of stakeholders by considering a timeline and budget (Ward et al., 2007). The acknowledgement of need results in planning about how to align the strategies of the organisation to achieve their objectives. Therefore, to implement e-learning, a strategic plan for the educational technology should be put in place which includes teaching, learning and practice policies of e-learning (Kanwal, et al., 2017). The strategic plan can be three-fold; top-down (initiated by top management), bottom-up (delivery of product or service through people) or a mixed approach (using both methods) (Stockley, 2004).

Integration of e-learning into the traditional educational approach is becoming popular not only in developed nations but also in developing countries as educating people will empower their nation. In 2002 a mini conference held in Melbourne, Australia, was conducted to investigate the teaching and learning initiative by the Australian universities and their staff members. It was seen that two major domains, namely individual (related to individual academics) and organisational (related to organisational policies, resources, and institutional systems) are the influential factors to accept the change of teaching methodologies (Lynch, et al., 2005).

The abovementioned two domains are considered as the internal context related to the adoption of e-learning whereas, for external context, government policies, governing bodies, and other stakeholders such as departments of education and technology and other training institutes also become a barrier towards e-learning implementation. As the commodification of learning resources of HEIs increases, many world economies have been forced to provide online courses which are also affiliated with top universities in order to sell their certificates. The commodification of resources puts pressure on the staff members of the HEIs to accept the change (Sharin, 2021).

In a university environment, top management, decision makers and academic staff are sometimes resistant towards curricula or any strategic change in the organisation. The major

reason for the resistance is related towards the traditional approaches, lack of motivation and incentives for using ICT and individual behaviour towards the change (Kundi and Nawaz, 2014). Furthermore, if proper incentive systems, either financial or non-financial, are in place, then it will also increase the use of technology by the staff members (Boe et al., 2020).

Salmon, Nie, and Edirisingha (2010) presented Salmon's five-stage model in their study to test the usefulness and relevance of the model in the adoption Second Life across three case studies. The model consists of five stages namely: access and motivation, online socialization, information exchange, knowledge construction, and development. The model informs about the delivery and design features of the implemented technology which helps the learners and teachers to improve their confidence level among them and enhance their productivity. This study also utilised a case study approach which is related to the current study's research design.

Another study of Salmon (2014) presented four quadrant model in her study which showed that the use of four quadrant framework will help to recognise the opportunities for new missions and markets and also, the improvement related to learning and teaching in universities whilst recognizing the transformation potential of new technologies. The educational institutions survive, successfully innovate, and thrive because their fundamental members are eagerly willing to do things differently (Salmon, 2014).

Communication is also key to success and often insufficient communication between the actual users of programs and ICT professionals leads towards failure because the implications related to the internal stakeholders have not been communicated to the external stakeholders (Juniu, 2005; Qamar and Bawany, 2021). Related to the cultural aspects, it is seen in both developed and developing countries that cultural factors are of greater concern than technological factors in the inception of e-learning (Jewels and Ford, 2006; Zhao et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022).

The cultural setting of every organisation is unique and because of this the change management issues related to the implementation of e-learning in HEIs are different in public and private universities around the world. If the involvement of government bodies regulating the educational policies are not put in place, then the inception of ICT will be difficult in public universities as compared to the private HEIs. The reason for the difference is that government bodies will provide goal-setting policies, funding, resources, evaluative measures for the performance and design the working conditions (Qureshi et al., 2009). For instance,

the Labour Government in the UK in 1997 put the globalisation factor at the front line to integrate ICT or e-learning in UK educational institutes to push forward the technological advancements to enhance the learning for students and make it easier for the teachers to teach (Islam et al., 2015).

In the context of the U.S., the Department of Education of U.S. introduced policies related to e-learning use in HEIs from 1996 to provide a roadmap not only for the public institutes but also for the private institutes to encourage the education and learning for all the citizens (Roumell and Salajan, 2016).

Furthermore, Aviram and Tami (2004) explained the attitudes and approaches related to the integration of ICT in HEIs. Their study not only includes different techniques and reaction of the stakeholders related to those techniques, but the research shed light on the concept of how and what to change in the educational institutes. Their concept is based on horizontal and vertical axis where the horizontal axis depicts the parameter of “*Approaches*” (one who accepts and adopts the change) and the vertical axis refers to the “*Attitudes*” (adoption of those actions which are necessitated by the introduction of ICT) (Brush and Saye, 2009).

Table 2.2 shows the concept of what to change and how to change proposed by Aviram and Tami (2004).

Table 2.2 Approach and Change from Aviram and Tami (2004)

APPROACH	WHAT TO CHANGE?
Administrative	Desire of technological change to get best quality and quantity of technology in the institute to stay up to date with the new trends
Curricula	Integrating technology with the curriculum. It includes two forms: disciplinary and integrative.
Didactic	Unavoidable and required change related to ICT. It helps to dictate the change.
Organisational	It includes the approaches towards organisational changes to make them viable, flexible, and robust.
Systematic	To bring change, the whole system needs to change, and the system will allow to adopt didactic and organisational change. The changes must be planned and defined before its inception.
Cultural	Change impacts on various aspects of our lives therefore, it requires cultural changes that is, organisational culture. It also recognises ICT revolution’s powerful impact on culture.

Ideological	It begins with the change from basic values by considering social and educational aims. Change should be in-line with social values of the society.
ATTITUDE	HOW TO CHANGE
Agnostic	It is a type of attitude when one does not have a clear indication or idea about the impact of ICT on organisation as a whole
Conservative	This type of people believe that educational institutes will survive with the minimum change in the organisation with respect to ICT and its inception.
Moderate	People with this type of attitude believe that for the sake of ICT integration, extensive change should be brought in their didactics.
Radical	Organisations have to go through major changes to survive the ICT evolution
Extreme Radical	It is considered as a concept of de-schooling. Brings major changes to the organisation and might be not able to survive those changes.

Source: (Aviram and Tami, 2004)

It is also explained in the study that there are some approaches which intersects the attitudes, and some are impossible to intersect such as organisational, cultural, systematic, and ideological approaches are completely incompatible with the Agnostic attitude (Aviram and Tami, 2004). While keeping in mind the above issues, remedies, approaches, and attitudes of different stakeholders, it was seen that Asia still has the highest growth demand rate in the world related to e-learning in 2018 of 17.3% per annum (Ali et al., 2018). Specifically, in Pakistan, there is a growing concern shown by HEIs about the demand and the barriers towards the implementation of e-learning. Most authors who conducted research related to e-learning in developing countries, including Pakistan, and the challenges of its implementation have explained the barriers and also offered suggestions to overcome those barriers (Iqbal, et al., 2016). In terms of change management strategies, Kotter's eight step model has been utilised by previous researchers (such as AlQudah, (2014); Chebbi et al., (2019)) to overcome the resistance from the participants and other stakeholders (AlQudah, 2014; Chebbi et al., 2019). Aini et al. (2020) refer in their study that change management models will help towards overcoming the barriers and resistance towards change.

In terms of bringing change, there are different variables considered by researchers in which culture is most discussed, as culture expresses the norms, values, and basic assumptions of any organisation. As the cultural parts of the HEIs are also linked with their educational systems and also their understanding with those systems therefore, it requires the development of ICT infrastructure which embeds with those systems and they become interrelated (Menchaca et al., 2003; Kanwal et al., 2017; Mushtaq et al., 2021).

2.3 Timeline of E-learning in HEIs of Pakistan:

The use of information and communication technology for the purpose of learning is not new to the general population of Pakistan. It has been used primarily to provide support towards learning and teaching such as adult learning for specific people such as farmers and skilled workers with the help of television programs (Siddiquei & Khalid, 2017). Radio and television were proved to be effective mediums for the sake of distance learning projects whereas radio was proved to be more fruitful for far and rural areas (Siddiquei & Khalid, 2017).

Initially the first mega distance learning project or online learning initiative was started with the establishment of Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU) in 1974 as the replica of the United Kingdom's Open University. This helped the government to co-op with the increased use of ICT in the field of education (Ellahi & Zaka, 2014). AIOU utilised the new modes of e-learning to keep updating its teaching and learning methodologies and update its Learning Objectives to facilitate the local students with the help of integrating e-learning. The drift from television and radio towards the use of ICT was started in Pakistan after the year of 2000 as the Government of Pakistan (GoP) was keen to establish IT infrastructure throughout the country. For this very reason, the GoP started the program of "Education for All", and this resulted in the formation of Virtual University (VU) of Pakistan in 2002 and National ICT R&D fund which was founded in 2007 (Farid, et al., 2015), (Farid, et al., 2017).

It is seen that VU has completed important milestones in the path towards accepting and introducing e-learning methods for teaching and learning purposes. With the Charter granted by the Government of Pakistan in 2002, VU placed its all lectures on YouTube by June 2008. VU also introduced their e-examination system in October 2008, VU also deployed their first LMS system known as VULMS and launched their VU Journal in September 2014 and lastly, they started provided PhD programs from September 2015 (Virtual University of Pakistan, 2024).

After the integration of ICT through VU online degree programs, the Government of Pakistan and ministry of education introduced the Higher Education Commission (HEC) in 2002 which encouraged the higher educational institutes of Pakistan to facilitate education at higher level. With the introduction of HEC, a visible change in the registration of students was seen due to the use of Digital Opportunity Initiatives (DOI) by introducing set of e-Reforms which ultimately helped to adopt ICT tools. Examples of those e-reforms includes e-Learning projects, digital library program, PERN and PRR (Siddiquei & Khalid, 2017).

The research of Siddiquei and Khalid (2017) shed light upon the developments and projects

conducted by HEC. It is seen that to increase the use of ICT, HEC initiated a project in 2006 entitled “Online Lecturing and Net-Meeting using IP-based Video Conferencing System”. It served the purpose of enhancing the interaction between students and teachers and to also reducing the impact of less number of teaching staff at the university level. Similarly, HEC introduced other programs such as National Digital Library Program which ensures the researchers in Pakistani universities got access to international literature via online delivery mode. HEC also introduced Pakistan Education & Research Network (PERN) and Pakistan Research Repository (PRR) which promoted the international visibility of research ongoing in Pakistani institutes (Siddiquei & Khalid, 2017).

The main purpose of PERN is connecting the universities for the purpose of research with the help of high bandwidth internet to facilitate the researchers and students to coordinate with each other with the help of video conferencing. Currently 228 universities in Pakistan are linked through the network of PERN which is also linked to international research and educational networks globally (PERN, 2024). Similarly, PRR is providing theses, research books, and journals for the purpose of research in Pakistan. These modes are considered asynchronous means of providing e-learning tools as these can be accessed anywhere at any time of the year.

In 2011, HEC emphasized more towards the online learning and initiated the distance learning project at six public universities in which AIOU was one of them. The study of Ellahi and Zaka (2014) informs about the initial use of synchronous type of e-learning method. AIOU utilised OLIVE program which used synchronous mode of e-learning for teaching and learning purposes (Ellahi & Zaka, 2014). Currently the enrolment figures at AIOU is at 1.027 million which is more than approximately 35,000 from previous year 2023 (AIOU, 2024), (Abbasi, 2024). It shows that students in Pakistan are seeking more accessible and cheaper options for their higher education. Furthermore, the GOP and Ministry of Education has also invited both private and public sector universities to incorporate Learning Management Systems into their current teaching and learning systems (Kanwal, et al., 2017). However, Memon and Rathore (2018) suggested in their research that Pakistan should incorporate Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) or MOODLE specifically to the medical field of education and promote blended learning options to the students and faculty to enhance their educational standards.

As mentioned above, the study of Siddiquah and Salim (2017) explains that the introduction of ICT such as LMS or MOODLE systems in HEIs of Pakistan (the case of AIOU) showed

that students have better skillset related to the use of Microsoft Office, internet browsing, utilising social media for personal use, and computer games etc. however, they do not possess proper skillset related to the use of blogs, digital libraries and online databases (Siddiquah & Salim, 2017). Further the study of Zubairi et al., (2021) reports that the higher education institutions are more teaching oriented i.e., the institutes are focusing on the pedagogical teaching methods rather than research. It is due to the fact that Pakistan's HEIs faces lack of research expertise at the academic level (Zubairi, et al., 2021).

A study of Nawaz (2011) indicated that all the projects and introduction of ICT in the education was utilised to enhance the literacy rate but most of the projects are ended up as the failures for the government and bureaucrats thus resulting the reason of why Pakistan's literacy rate is not improving (Nawaz, 2011). Another research of Qureshi et al., (2012) showed that universities across Pakistan gradually started to embed different modes of e-learning in which Learning Management System (LMS) and video conferencing is on the top of the list but there are still opportunities and challenges faced by the HEIs in relation to the use and adoption of e-learning systems (Qureshi, et al., 2012).

Furthermore, it is seen that HEC published the list of journals which are recognised by them, and it shows that the research related to e-learning is increasing in Pakistan. Some of those journals includes Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research (2006), Pakistan Journal of Distance and Online Learning (2015), and International Journal of Distance education and e-learning (2018) etc. (HEC, 2020).

It is seen that ICT programs can help to implement and adopt e-learning practices however, it also seen that joining different blogs with the help of social networking websites can help the teachers to improve their learning and teaching skills. The study of Khan (2017) suggests that teachers were able to improve their teaching methods when they discussed their methods at global level via English Companion Ning (ECN) which is an online global community for English language teachers (Khan, 2017).

The study of Mehmood et al., (2021) showed that the introduction of ICT and e-learning in the HEIs resulted in the mass digital division of the population. It is because of the least amount of GDP utilised for education in Pakistan. The pandemic struck as the compulsion of implementation and use of e-learning technologies in Pakistani HEIs, and it resulted to act as a catalyst to expediate the process of implementation of ICT and e-learning technologies in HEIs of Pakistan (Mehmood, et al., 2021).

However, Kanwal et al., (2017) argues that even with the increasing trend of research in the

field of e-learning and education in Pakistan, there is no model or framework for the e-learning adoption i.e., managing the change of e-learning that are specific to the cultural context of Pakistan.

2.4 Opportunities of e-Learning in Pakistan

Education provides the pathway for human development and competitiveness and with the help of ICT it can provide various opportunities which will help to accommodate the students, teachers and other stakeholders such as management of the HEIs to adopt and bear the fruitful results of e-learning in Pakistan (Kundi & Nawaz, 2014). ICT provides means to achieve and support the level of quality required in education. However, the quality of higher education depends on various factors such as learning environment, infrastructure, teachers, information feedback, research skills, and observation systems. The most common issues faced by the Pakistan's higher education are academic space for teachers, deteriorating research standards, inadequate infrastructure and facilities, low rate of student's enrolment, poverty, outdated teaching methods etc (Murtaza & Hui, 2021). E-learning can provide synchronous and asynchronous modes of technology which can provide different opportunities for the higher education sector of Pakistan to improve the way in which knowledge can be accessed, harnessed and shared (Hussain, et al., 2019). Following are some of the opportunities of e-learning in higher education sector of Pakistan:

Availability of Contents

Flexibility and availability of contents is the prime benefit of e-learning or virtual learning, and it is seen that due to the need of continuous learning, the demand of flexible educational learning environments is increasing rapidly (Hussain, et al., 2019). Furthermore, flexibility is linked with the global availability of ICTs because it helps to access the content as per the demand of the learner and teacher. It is seen that branded computers and new technology is transported to the developing and poor countries which will resolve the issue of hardware availability in developing countries such as Pakistan. Similarly, Free and Open-Source Systems (FOSS) provides free software which is available online and it has different variety to serve different purposes of applications in teaching, learning and administrative work (Kundi & Nawaz, 2014). An investigation by Cheema et al., (2023) after Covid-19 reveals that e-learning provided students with continuous learning opportunities as recorded videos, lectures, and other study materials were provided to the students which helped them to learn at their own pace. Similarly, the research of Butt et al., (2022) also confirms that with the help of e-environment i.e., ICT, flexibility was introduced with the help of online tools, and it helped to enhance the efficiency of the staff at university level in Pakistan as it reduced the

unnecessary steps and increased the competitiveness among the institutions.

Cost Effective

The cost effectiveness of e-learning provides opportunities for the people of rural areas and to those who cannot afford the higher education in Pakistan. Hussain and Sajjad (2018) presented in their study that e-learning is based on the concept of industrialization which results in the mass production of the study materials to lower down its costs. Their research also shown that students from AIOU finds it convenient and affordable to get education through distance education as it not only cuts down the costs of the education itself as the fee structure is cheaper, but it will also cut down the costs related to travelling and accommodation expenses if they live in different cities (Hussain & Sajjad, 2018). It is also seen that Virtual University has its own private virtual network which facilitates the learners as teachers from all around Pakistan were gathered to provide study materials for the online learning at affordable fee (Kanwal & Rehman, 2017) (Hussain, et al., 2019).

Local ICT Professionals

Kundi and Nawaz (2014) strongly suggested in their research that the major opportunity for the Government of Pakistan is to motivate and promote local ICT professionals and ICT industry. It will help the HEIs to implement e-learning effectively because they can design the software packages according to the local requirements of the learners and teachers. An official report from the government of Pakistan shows that there are 13 software technology parks and approximately 20,000 IT graduates and engineers are produced in Pakistan annually (Board of Investment, 2024). It confirms that the Government of Pakistan is not utilising the local ICT professionals at their full capacity who can help to promote the culture of utilising the local talent to produce effective and efficient tools for the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan.

Partnerships Between HEIs and Governing Bodies

The use of new technologies and software requires partnerships as teams will help each other in the case of any issue arising from technical or any other error. Kundi and Nawaz (2014) suggested that universities must create partnerships between them and at international level as well which will help to promote the smooth implementation of e-learning in the HEIs of Pakistan. Memon and Rathore (2018) indicated in their study that HEC is the official partner of International Network for the Availability of Scientific Publications (INASP) which promotes free online courses for biomedical students, such partnerships and collaborations will shape the future of e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan.

Popularity of Information Culture

With the introduction of ICT in the education sector, it gives rises to the educational societies, knowledge societies, and open information societies which help to share the knowledge and teaching and learning practices among its members (Kundi & Nawaz, 2014). The study of Khan (2017) mentions about the use of English Companion Ning (ECN) a digital literary society to connect with other English language teachers around the globe. It also mentions how one of the teachers got an idea to create Facebook page for Shakespeare's Othello where students can discuss about the characters of the play and share their knowledge about the literature. It confirms that different online societies help the students, faculty and management to generate innovative ideas which can be used to get benefits from the opportunity of digitization. It is also seen that in 2012 Virtual University of Pakistan also shared its course contents and module with other HEC recognised universities to create local culture of information sharing (Virtual University of Pakistan, 2024).

2.5 Barriers towards e-learning in Pakistan

There is good amount of research conducted in reference to Pakistan to identify the barriers towards e-learning implementation throughout the years. Such as (Nawaz, 2011) (Farid, et al., 2015), (Kanwal & Rehman, 2017), (Kanwal, et al., 2017), (Farid, et al., 2017), (Hussain, et al., 2019), (Murtaza & Hui, 2021) etc. Siddiquei and Khalid (2017) identified major barriers as internal (first order) such as equipment shortage, deficiency of support on technological grounds, problems related to the resources, and unreliable instruments. Whereas external (second order) includes human issues such as organisational culture, mental orientation of the teachers and students, and resistance to change. However, these enlisted barriers gives rise to negative influence towards the exercise of ICT which includes inadequate use of ICT, infrastructure of e-learning, financial issues, inadequate technical skills, insufficient time to develop e-learning content, people's behaviour towards resistance to change, frustration among users of technology, and mismatch between the culture, equipment and values (Siddiquei & Khalid, 2017).

Another research from Rauf and Shahzadi (2023) indicates that there are constraints which hinders the desired improvement in HEIs in Pakistan and those barriers can range from infrastructural limitations to bureaucratic inefficiencies. It also includes the low level of collaboration between different stakeholders such as policymakers, faculty, educational administrators etc. Such partnerships will result in the application of more coordinated policies towards the execution of change (Rauf & Shahzadi, 2023).

In an investigation by Ali, Uppal, and Gulliver (2017) seen that they identified 68 unique

barriers towards the implementation of e-learning with the help of qualitative content analysis of 259 research papers from 1990-2016. Those barriers are completed related to the context of Pakistan some of them includes language barriers, load shedding of electricity, faculty's acceptance of e-learning technologies, weak learning management systems, material accessibility, lack of credibility, faculty training, course contents, cost of using technology, inequality in access to technology, student and faculty readiness, lack of ICT skills, and sense of isolation due to less face-to-face interaction (Ali, et al., 2017).

Baig and Jamil (2020) raised similar barriers in their conference paper which highlighted the issue of having two different language mediums of teaching at school level in Pakistan. It is because of the two languages used at school level which are Urdu and English, when one student passed towards higher education/university level via Urdu medium school; where the main language is English then it becomes difficult for students to understand and communicate as a whole. Further barriers include outdated educational system, severe lack of digital resources, and low accessibility to quality education (Baig & Jamil, 2020).

The study of Kanwal et al., (2017) found that there is no universal model for the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. This highlighted the fact that ICT related policies of Pakistan are different as compared to the western side of the world. This requires the introduction of such model which is related to the cultural constraints of Pakistan, and it will adjust according to the social environment and user's organisational characteristics. This will help to overcome a major barrier of understanding the local market environment before implementing e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan.

Another research conducted by Naveed et al., (2022) indicates that the identification of stakeholders in the implementation of e-learning is crucial towards the success of its implementation. The study findings shows that if institutional management support is not provided by the stakeholders, then the e-learning system will fail to implement therefore, it is necessary to consider all the stakeholders to ensure the success of the implementation.

Similarly, the research of Jan, Sultana, and Adnan (2020) indicates the human factors as well in the process of implementation of e-learning during the covid-19 time-period. The study clearly indicates that self-inspiration, motivation, non-energetic input, and unwillingness to change from the pedagogical teaching methods are the core barriers towards the implementation process. Furthermore, the digital divide among the stakeholders or user of the technology results in the problems faced during and post implementation phase. As those who does not afford the technology fails to reap its benefits, similarly, those who do not have

enough know-how about the use of technology are in same condition as they cannot understand the use and benefits of it (Jan, et al., 2020).

2.6 Theories & Models in e-Learning Implementation

There are different theories, models, and frameworks proposed in research related to the implementation of e-learning globally. These models and frameworks are based on the concepts from different disciplines such as psychology, education, sociology and neuroscience (Graetz & Smith, 2010), (Grenway, 2021), (Aithal & Satpathy, 2024). Kotter's eight step change model is considered as one of the vital models related to manage the change in a dynamic environment such as the use of flipped classroom in the field of medicine studies (Hurtubise, et al., 2015). Kotter examined and observed processes of change in different organisations which led him to develop eight important steps to manage the change. These steps are the processes which are based on a sequence of change of phases and none of the steps should be skipped (Voigt, et al., 2021). These steps will provide guideline in the current study towards managing the change i.e., implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. It will also help to identify and overcome the barriers during and after the phase of implementing e-learning in Pakistani HEIs during the period of Covid-19 and also it will help to understand the situation of e-learning adoption before Covid-19 period. Further, it will help to include the identified stakeholders during the implementation process and allow the management to create a guiding coalition which will help to overcome the resistance during implementation. Kotter's change model is considered as the primary model in the current study as it will provide basis for the proposed framework in explaining and understanding the process of implementation of e-learning in higher educational institutes of Pakistan.

In addition to Kotter's change model, understanding the implementation of e-learning in the current study was also assisted through the use of Maslow's Hierarchy model. Maslow identified different types of motivation which are considered as the levels or hierarchy that drives human behaviour towards achieving their goals. According to Maslow, people are motivated by physiological, safety, belongingness, esteem and self-actualisation needs in which each level is supported by the previous level. Maslow believed that humans must satisfy their lower level of needs before they can move towards the higher-level needs. This model also highlights the factors which motivate the people during change implementation such as financial rewards to motivate towards the use of e-learning, social interaction between students and teachers during implementation etc. Maslow's hierarchy will identify the needs of the stakeholders in-addition to the Kotter's model which are based on psychological, cultural, social, and economical factors (Bandhu, et al., 2024). In the present study, managers,

administrators, teachers, students, and governing body is engaged in the implementation process of e-learning, therefore, this model will help to understand the motivating factors related to them during the implementation of e-learning.

The present study is also facilitated through the use of Leavitt's Diamond Model which is used to manage technological change in an organisation. Leavitt's model is based on four interrelated components of an organisation which includes people, tasks, structure, and technology. It is widely used to manage the implementation of technology or technological change occurred in the organisations because all four components are linked to each other, therefore, change in one element will result to adjust the other component as they are inter-related with each-other (Hau & Chang, 2021). In this study, Leavitt's model will help to analyse the macro-level factors of higher educational institutes such as the introduction of technology (i.e., e-learning) will require the structure (i.e., hierarchy and physical infrastructure for instance computer labs and internet facility etc.) to be upgraded as well. It will also help to analyse the impact of the technological change on people (i.e., stakeholders) and tasks which are related to the day-to-day operations and functions of HEIs of Pakistan.

Furthermore, these above-mentioned models will be linked with the stakeholder analysis which will help to identify the stakeholders involved during and after the process of implementation based on their category (i.e., primary or secondary) and attributes (i.e., power, legitimacy, and urgency). Stakeholder theory or analysis argues that a stakeholder is a group or individual which is affected by the achievement of goals and policies of the organisation. Further, an organisation has multiple stakeholders who can influence the organisation's performance. Due to this the stakeholders can be divided based on the level of their importance and influence in the organisation. Also, stakeholders' perceptions give insight about the stakeholder's capabilities and willingness to adopt the strategies of the organisation (Kant, 2019). Stakeholder theory was adopted in the current study because it helped to identify the stakeholders on the basis of their power and interest in the organisation which will help the implementation and adoption of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. The level of their interest and power determines their involvement during the process of implementation. The primary and secondary stakeholders were identified, and interviews were conducted to record their perceptions about e-learning implementation, challenges and barriers.

2.7 E-Learning Implementation Models in Pakistan

In specific terms of HEIs, the change related to the educational and knowledge system in them requires more systematic change which depicts the understanding of how educational parts are interlinked together, the pressure and management of stakeholders of HEIs and support of those critical elements which have specific goals, objectives, values and beliefs (Benathy, 1991; Menchaca et al., 2003). Therefore, researchers need to consider the culture, social impact of society, economic issues, effect of users' mindset, and technological issues related to the specific country where the implementation is to take place (Qureshi et al., 2012; Kasani et al., 2020).

“Education for all” was a dream for the Government of Pakistan in 2000 which resulted in the formation of one of the famous e-learning institutes of Pakistan, Virtual University, in 2002. The main aim was to provide affordable and quality education all around Pakistan to increase the literacy rate however, the enrolment of VU was at low level even during the covid-19. The study of Murtaza and Hui (2021) shows that the Government of Pakistan fails to achieve their goal of 20% enrolment in higher education in 2020 which confirms the need of better educational policies to support the new methods of learning which includes e-learning. Qureshi et al., (2012) utilised a mixed approach while considering different e-learning methods and face to face meetings with the students. Meanwhile other universities also tried to implement Learning Management Systems (LMS) because the need of e-learning and attracting students was becoming important for the universities (Qureshi et al., 2012).

Application of the theory is always different in reality and produces different results from those expected. In Pakistan, different bodies (various stakeholders include government bodies, educational institutes, and individual groups) take the example of developed nations and try to implement the same technology with the same strategy, which in reality produces different results (Qureshi et al., 2009). Extensive research has been seen previously on the barriers of e-learning however, limited research is seen towards consolidating those studies and providing a framework towards the implementation (Ali et al., 2018). It was also seen that success stories from industrialised countries such as from U.S. related to e-learning cannot be implemented in Pakistan because of various variables like culture and other environmental challenges (Qureshi et al., 2009).

Toor (2005) in her research discussed the implementation of a hybrid model with the introduction of Virtual University in Pakistan. The hybrid model consists of three

components, namely lecture through TV, physical campus for face-to-face meetings and tutoring through the internet by using LMS platform. In this study, change management issues are not discussed but room for development has been identified and issues related to the management of teacher and student relationship was discussed.

Iqbal and Ahmad (2010) explain that Pakistan is unable to take full advantage of e-learning due to organisational structures, culture, computer literacy level and access issues related to electricity, internet, and technology (Saidu et al., 2016; Siddiquei and Khalid, 2020; Song et al., 2017; Choudhary and Pattnaik, 2020). Iqbal, Naeem and Nayyar (2016) in their paper discussed the use and implementation of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) in Pakistan. Their research focussed on three universities in Pakistan. It concludes that the major barrier towards the implementation of MOOC is related to the issue of their use because it requires internet and electricity as the most important tools. In the rural areas there is a high level of power shortage whereas in urban areas it is still at low or moderate levels (Sarwar et al., 2020; Mumtaz et al., 2021).

In several studies, barriers, hurdles, and failures related to e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan are discussed explicitly in Farid et al., (2014); Farid et al., (2015); Ahmed et al., (2018). Most of the literature available is on the comparison between Pakistan and developed countries which shows how developed countries implemented and the identification of problems, barriers and how those barriers were overcome (Sana and Mariam, 2013) such as providing training and tutorials will increase the use of e-learning (Akhtar, et al., 2021). One of the surveys shows the issues related to the internet, 3G and 4G technology and availability of the technology such as software and hardware in Pakistan (Ahmed, et al., 2018). Ali, Uppal, and Gulliver (2018) used TIPEC framework (Technology, Individual, Pedagogy and Enabling Conditions) to identify 68 unique barriers to implementation of e-learning in the context of developed and developing countries including Pakistan. It allows the researchers to consider those barriers and utilise different organisational change management models to successfully implement e-learning and facilitate better understanding for the key stakeholders in the environment.

Basar, Rahatullah, Asad and Adnan (2013) studied the paradigm shift of e-learning 1.0 to e-learning 2.0 in developing countries like Pakistan. Their study includes the developmental and implementational issues of e-learning in Pakistan. It sheds light on various aspects such as model borrowing, poor local research, absence of local implementation models, change management (they did not mention any change management models but rather they

mentioned the issues related to change management such as resistance, transfer of power etc.) and political stability.

Similarly, Kanwal and Rehman (2014) mention considering different technological adoption models and from those models they proposed their model which will evaluate a student's behaviour related to e-learning systems. The difference between their model and other models is that they modified the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) model while considering the local constraints and made it adjustable to the local context of Pakistan. Their conceptual model is a way forward in the successful implementation of e-learning however, the change management side of the implementation of e-learning is still not discussed in detail because their study did not consider any change management strategies along with their modified TAM model.

Furthermore, government officials and policy makers should consider the local contextual and human factors to successfully implement the technology (Nawaz, 2012). Similarly, another study emphasised the technical, hardware and software support between teacher and student, and discussed the communication and knowledge gap between different stakeholders which will result in the failure of e-learning platforms (Nawaz and Khan, 2012).

Bashir (2016) explained about the communication and expectation gap in the use of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. Although in his research, different stakeholders were identified and interviewed in which includes students, faculty members, study centres, administrators, and staff members, those stakeholders were not properly analysed by any model or framework (Kattoua, et al., 2016). However, this study discusses the serious issues and remedies for those issues to improve the use of e-learning systems.

Another term, recommender system, is sometimes used in HEIs to recommend certain study materials to the students (Bourkougou, et al., 2017). Afridi (2018) conducted unique research in Pakistan related to recommender system algorithms which help the student to recommend them with study materials and remove any materials which are repetitive. In this research, 360-degree stakeholder analysis was conducted by using Mendelow's matrix to identify key stakeholders and discussion about their powers and attributes. The research concludes that study material recommender is a positive approach towards better study material, and it also considers the involvement of not only academics, but student participation as a key component.

2.8 Summary

In this section of Chapter 2, the researcher identifies the factors that influence the implementation process of e-learning in both developed and developing nations, with a focus on Pakistani research studies. Various approaches and studies illustrate the issues associated with the implementation of e-learning, such as organisational politics, the involvement of government policies, student behaviour in relation to e-learning and its adoption, the paradigm shift of e-learning itself from version 1.0 to version 2.0, technological factors, employee resistance to change, etc. (Qureshi et al., 2012; Farid et al., 2014; Iqbal et al., 2016; Ahmed et al., 2018). In a prior study on e-learning, organisational politics, failure to include stakeholders according to stakeholder theory (in the context of Pakistan), internal and external resistance to change, and exclusion of voices affected by the implementation process were cited as major concerns.

As transformative change necessitates an in-depth comprehension of social dynamics, structures, and the complexity of newly disseminated knowledge throughout the system, socio-technical systems should be studied alongside stakeholder analysis (Richey, et al., 2014). As the education system can be integrated with the socio-technical system, the educational system will be able to transition from a complex to a progressive system.

As in this study, the author will use three change management models (i.e. Kotter's change model, Maslow's hierarchy, and Leavitt's diamond model) along with the stakeholder analysis, which will not only improve the identification of the stakeholders, but also provide guidelines for the smooth implementation of e-learning, overcoming resistance from the stakeholders, and improving the decision-making process between different hierarchies.

As a result, the researcher has chosen stakeholder analysis as the conceptual framework for the study, which will provide a deeper knowledge of the stakeholders, their powers, their interests, and their capacity to accept change. Stakeholder analysis provides the researcher with multiple perspectives that contribute to the development of a more complete picture of the e-learning implementation process and to the comprehension of e-learning by considering the maximum number of environmental factors and actors (stakeholders).

Chapter 3 Theoretical Framework

3.1 Introduction

Globally, the integration and implementation of e-learning in HEIs is rising. E-learning provides a platform for schools and universities to continue the teaching and learning process during pandemic lockdown periods, allowing professors and students to continue teaching and learning (Almaiah, et al., 2020). However, e-learning has not been utilised effectively in developing nations due to hurdles experienced by teachers and students, such as lack of internet connectivity and electricity, reliance on face-to-face classes, etc. To achieve the study's objectives, it is important to view the implementation of e-learning through the prism of theories and models.

The second purpose of the study is to demonstrate the necessity to establish relevant models for the e-learning change management scenario. The selection of theories and models for this study, including stakeholder analysis, Leavitt's diamond model (socio-technical model), Maslow's hierarchy, and Kotter's eight step change model, was based on Chapter 2 literature evaluation (change management models). The selection of pertinent models and theories will help the research in establishing a sound basis for the study project.

Sections 3.3 and 3.4, highlights the use of stakeholder analysis in conjunction with change management models in the context of HEIs. Therefore, the applicable change management models were identified on the basis of change, which is related to information communication and technology, e-learning. Furthermore, the interview questions and themes generated will be based on the framework which will help to examine the process of change management used by HEIs in relation to the implementation of e-learning. The themes based on the framework will also help to identify the factors which will be based on the individual stakeholder's perception in the implementation of e-learning. Furthermore, the justification of the selected models will be given in section 3.7 which highlights the suitability of the previously mentioned models to the context of the current study. The following sections will shed light upon the organisational change management models used in the previous studies in the context of HEIs.

3.2 Organisational Change Management

This section depicts how the change started to manage in organisations around the world. It will help the reader to realise the need for change management models which will help to manage the change in an organisation and allow the stakeholders to adopt or accept the change. Companies and organisations are considered as separate entities as artificial creatures (Blumberg, 1990) which also makes them consider the element of change because in order to achieve the heights of success everyone has to consider changing the way of conducting their activities, policies and rules to become successful (Odor, 2018).

Organisational change, organisational development, change management and organisational transformation are almost the same terminologies with little difference between them. All of these terms are like commanding and controlling operations, activities, or organisations. Triscari (2008) mentions in their study that organisational change is an umbrella under which different terms come together including organisational development and organisational transformation. Burnes (2004) explains organisational change as a partial or complete adoption of a new strategy, concept, or idea by organisational colleagues. Similarly, the objectives of organisational change are improved leadership styles along with changed production techniques, vision, and mission, updated organisational structure and strategy (Odor, 2018). In other words, organisational change refers to continuous transformation of organisational technology, structure, and human resources (Sofat, et al., 2015).

To elucidate the term Change Management (CM) many researchers referred to it as systematic strategy to use the new information or knowledge given to the management by the change agent to improve their business or organisational process for the achievement of success or goals (Schachter, 2017).

Lewin has contributed towards organisational change management and is considered as the pioneer of change management because they believed that if social issues of humans related to religion, race, culture, and industrial are resolved then the individual human condition will become better which ultimately results in better and growing environment of the organisations as well (Burnes, 2020). Lewin wanted to bring social change among humans therefore, he started to analyse the concept of OD by conducting his studies on Harwood Manufacturing Corporation in 1939 in Marion, Virginia (Burnes, 2007). The first issue to resolve in that organisation was to tackle the high turnover of employees, even among those

newly recruited.

Similarly, Kotter introduced his eight steps which help to transform the organisation. With these eight steps, he also described the eight common errors which any successful CEO or high-level executive in an organisation can make while leading the organisation (Kotter, 1995). Kotter (1995) believes that if the top-level executives, managers, or leaders are not innovative, creative, change champions or great leaders then the initial phase of OD will become a challenge for the organisation to bring any change or transformation.

Organisational change is not only limited to the social change of the organisation (e.g., management change, staff change, structure change etc.), it is also concerned with the information system (IS) change which orchestrates the generation of deliberate change in an organisational technical subsystem structure (Swanson, 1994). Studies of change in the early research stages were mainly focusing on the linearity aspect of change, which progresses linearly with a new designed system, its adoption, and its modification in a stepwise manner (Lyytinen, et al., 1998).

The most important element which is constant in business is the *change* because to evolve, achieve new heights of success and to overcome any hurdles, change is considered to be crucial. The change always necessitates many minute or huge changes in prevailing organisational boundaries and structures, innovation in skills and duty distribution etc. These changes should be managed with great attention so that desired transformation can be achieved by supporting newly introduced procedures, risk management policies and plans for sustainable change. At the transformational stage, training is the crucial step which is often mishandled, resulting in unsuccessful implementation of changes and increases discomfort among stakeholders related to change (Andrade et al., 2016; Sarwar et al., 2020). Moreover, Dawson (1994) narrated that there should be an acknowledgement to the need of change management that how the change is being managed and handled in organisations, many of the queries regarding the matter of change and how the change will work are not resolved on time and lead to the failed implementation of change (Stacey, 1996).

It was seen that Tavistock and William Foote Whyte (in the US) were pioneer examples of considering socio-technical studies (Mumford, 2006). The concept of socio-technical models or theories are based on two broad terms; technological component (human created tool or technology which helps to serve and define human goals) and social component (such as social structures, economic systems, and best organisational practices) (Sarker, et al., 2019).

Sarker et al. (2019) highlights that every discipline in research has their axis of cohesion which normally refers to the central principles which help to align the study. Socio-technical studies are neglected as axis of cohesion in regard to the studies in the field of Information Systems (IS). Therefore, the research conducted by Sarker et al. (2019) refers to an extensive study of papers from two leading Journals in IS from 2000 to 2016 which suggested that the sociotechnical perspective should be considered as the axis of cohesion because it will provide long term vitality to the fundamental discipline.

Furthermore, in this study, the focus is on the change management due to the implementation of IS systems i.e. e-learning systems, therefore it will be fruitful for the researcher to maintain sociotechnical perspectives as the axis of cohesion which will not only help in the understanding of IS and change management terms, but it will also provide the mechanisms which are effecting the change, for example technology acts as a major influencer for change (Mumford, 2006). For instance, Keen (1981) introduces the classical approaches related to the sociotechnical perspectives which state that managing social change in the organisation requires the acceptance of political nature of information systems along with the need of suitable authority. It also states that politics provides the momentum for change, and it is inevitable to avoid. Similarly, understanding the concepts of digitisation which are engaged with innovation and organisational transformation leads to digital transformation with the help of IS and sociotechnical perspectives (Matt, et al., 2016).

3.3 Organisational Change Management and Higher Education Institutes

Higher education institutes must evolve comprehensively if they want to remain a crucial part of transformational change to avoid becoming obsolete. Leveraging the vast opportunities and potential offered by digital technologies is essential, but redefining business strategies is complex and challenging. Similarly, universities are facing the concern related to the adoption of new technology, but the management often lack the vision, capability or commitment to implement the technology (Benavides, et al., 2020). Higher education institutes play an active and vital role not only in spreading knowledge and the development of people but also the development of social, cultural and economic surroundings. Different metaphors have been used to discuss the development of HEIs for regional growth such as accelerator, catalyst, transmission centre, mediator etc. (Arbo and Benneworth, 2007). The acceleration related to the change in the world has increased over the last two decades in the corporate sector regardless of industry. The operating environment of businesses are becoming more dynamic and complex which requires executives and managers to manage

change more effectively as change has become a norm and it is being accepted as necessary for the survival of the organisation (Baumann, 2005).

It was seen that the earliest HEIs were established over 4000 years ago in 2000BCE in Egypt (Nampala, et al., 2017), although the modes and places of learning and teaching are as old as human civilisation. From the 1900s the work related to changing the education system and making it more effective was highly considered by the researchers. The higher education institutes are then considered to be as a business, requiring change to grow and become sustainable.

The education industry in USA experienced the requirement of scientific and experimental studies which resulted in the availability of more fields of subjects to be taught in the institutes. With the advancements not only in the field of technology but also in the field of education, new modes and methods were utilised to spread the power of knowledge to include those who could not reach the campuses physically.

Educational institutes have an extensive history of stability, growth and development, but higher education is now in the era where it is confronted with new challenges and various forces of change. Some of the major forces of change are related to the technology, competition, work-area, complexity in the processes and delivering their valuable processes to the end user (Storberg-Walker and Torracco, 2004).

The purpose, mission and vision of the HEIs makes it more complex to deal with any sort of change and it puts immense pressure on the management to carefully manage the change and implement it successfully. Storberg-Walker and Toracco (2004) explain key factors in HEIs which impacts the implementation of the planned change model, and it comprises of organisational leadership, diverse stakeholders, inner culture of the organisation, the governing structures and constituents of higher education. Due to the mentioned factors, it makes HEIs a democratic country rather than a business. Therefore, it is important to manage the change with the help of change management techniques and models to motivate the stakeholders towards the implementation of the change.

The study of Qadri et al., (2015) illustrates the role of change management models in the adoption of IT project at Malaysian Institutes of Higher Learning (IHL). It is seen that the use of ADKAR model can be useful to manage the change however, it more suitable for those who are managing the change in a small group or at individual basis. It is because the ADKAR model was unable to capture the emotional side of the people when addressing the

change.

There are different technological models from which technology acceptance model (TAM) is widely used in the studies where the implementation of technology is studied specially in higher education. The study of Ahmed et al., (2023) illustrates that the TAM model has been modified for different studies to capture the behavioural aspect which ADKAR model fell short to consider while studying the adoption of e-learning. TAM model is based on two basic concepts which are ease of use and perceived usefulness. However, there is a limitation of TAM where it lacks explaining the variation in user intention of the technology being implemented (Ahmad, et al., 2023).

It is also seen that learning is considered as the social process in the education environment and knowledge is co-constructed with the help of socio-technical networks facilitated by co-workers, academia and online environments (Richey, et al., 2014). The extensive use of IT in all fields, especially in education and research, promotes economic, social, political and behavioural change at all levels. Therefore, it is also necessary to understand this phenomenon from a multi-disciplinary approach which helps to bridge the different concepts and paradigms of similar phenomenon of change (Simon, et al., 2006).

Similarly, changes related to the information systems covers implementation, generation and adoption of new or updated components of the organisation related to the social and technical subsystems. Therefore, it is considered as ambiguous and difficult because the context of Information System (IS) change varies over time (Lyytinen and Newman, 2008).

The complex nature of the universities' organisational structures and their multiple hierarchies related to the different departments makes it challenging for the managers to direct the adoption of e-learning systems or technical change in them. Therefore, e-learning introduction poses potential threats and promises to the academics, students, managers and other stakeholders, and to accommodate the exploration of implementation, certain change management model will be required that enables the perceptions of stakeholders or change agents to be identified and communicated within the process of implementation of change.

Keen (1981) states in his research about the organisational change related to the information systems and the management of change which rely on incremental and facilitative approaches. The study provides a basis for classical approach for implementing an Information System (IS) in an organisation by considering Leavitt's diamond model which comprises four main components that is *Task, Technology, People and Structure* (Leavitt,

1964) (Keen, 1981).

The reason for considering the socio-technical model is because it not only covers the technical side of the change related to the systems and technology, but it also considers the social interaction side of it, also the main goal of these models is the joint optimisation of both social and technical systems (Mumford, 2006).

Lyyntinen and Newman (2008) discuss Information System related change in the organisation as multi-level change which involves change related to both organisational and environmental contexts. It considers the application of change strategies in two different levels, vertical and horizontal, in which vertical reveals the inter-dependencies between work system, building system and environment and horizontal expresses the interactions between two different level systems. Their research utilises the concept of Leavitt's diamond model and upgraded it to Punctuated Socio-technical change model to manage the change related to IS because the change was incremental in nature.

The social and technical part of Leavitt's model will help to capture the waves of change among internal and external stakeholders that occurred due to the e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan. Further, it will help to provide guidelines to the governing body (HEC) which will help them consider other incremental strategies such as providing licensed software, improved technological solutions, and better technological support during the course of acknowledging continuous technological change in the HEIs.

Furthermore, in another research it was seen that government policies, especially supranational unions such as the European Union, exert a substantial level of pressure and control on private and public universities (Selwyn, 2007). Another concern is shown related to the computer vendors, the supply of hardware, software and designing of platforms leading towards communication gap between these stakeholders. Similarly, students' strategic concerns, political, social and economic aspects of technology use in HEIs are also studied with the help of socio-technical concept and those aspects infers that change in HEIs related to technology is best understandable with the help of socio-technical concepts, namely by considering both constraints (Demir, et al., 2019).

It is noted that change in two organisations is never the same which becomes the main cause of why we have so many change management models such as Kotter's eight step change model, Kurt Lewin's change model, ADKAR, Force Field analysis and other models on going from 1947 to 2006 (Sidorko, 2008). Kotter's change model includes eight stages which

should be planned in the right order and at the right time to conclude successful change in an organisation. Those eight steps comprise *establishing sense of urgency, creating guiding coalition, developing a vision and strategy, communicating the updated vision, overcoming barriers or obstacles (empower broad based actions), creating short term wins, accumulating gains and following more change, Anchoring new approaches in the culture* (Kotter, 1995).

Dawson, Mighty and Britnell (2010) applied Kotter's model and concluded that the role of faculty developer is transformed into change agent, and the model provides rich resources related to the change at their institutions and in other institutes. However, utilising the model in HEIs faces criticism because it is more related to the corporate sector where top-level executives do not leave as frequently as compared to those in HEIs (Dawson et al., 2010). In one of the research projects, the concept of blended learning was introduced with the use of this eight-step model, and it resulted as a helpful tool for the course development teams as they try to overcome cultural barriers by collaborating with students with other institutes and also developing change managers in the same environment (Quinn et al., 2012).

AlQudah (2014) reviewed different frameworks and models for implementing change and managing the change effectively in HEIs for the implementation of Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) or e-learning. Charles Stuart University, a public university in Bathurst, Australia, used a modified version of Kotter's change model to implement learning management systems in the institute. It shows that although proper change management models direct the journey to a successful pathway, people are the most important ingredient in the implementation of strategies in an educational context (Uys, 2010).

Furthermore, a person's needs, and satisfaction also have a great impact on their acceptance towards change and those levels or hierarchies of needs or satisfaction lead towards the motivation for the stakeholders to accept the change in the organisation. The simplest way of understanding human behaviour related to the level of needs is explained by Abraham Maslow. Maslow (1943) created five levels of hierarchies of needs after observing the growth and development of the people (that is, stakeholders). Every single level is not fully accomplished until the first level is completely achieved by the person (Maslow, 1943).

The hierarchy is depicted in the shape of a pyramid which contains five different levels.

- **Physiological:** represents the basic human needs.
- **Security/ Safety:** the freedom from pain.
- **Social:** the sense of belongingness,

- **Self-esteem:** includes self-respect which represents one's desire for confidence and strength.
- **Self-actualisation:** the last level, and it includes the realisation of one's full potential and results in what a person wants to become (Mullins, 2007).

Maslow's motivational model has been used by researchers in different research projects, for example Freitas and Leonard (2011) studied the importance of nursing students' needs and their ability to meet those needs. It highlights that physiological and psychosocial needs are those categories which are important for students to perform better but they are not always easy for them to achieve, therefore they need proper guidance, consultation, channels and means to motivate them to achieve those needs.

Similarly, it was seen from research projects that for online teaching or e-learning, a university must create a proper infrastructure for it (Chandio, 2021). As Maslow's need model indicates the basic needs, the basic needs of the tutors related to e-learning in the university are well looked after with the help of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards which led them towards the achievement of self-actualisation where instructors feel confident about their work (Early and Murphy, 2009). Their study also considers other stakeholders and their motivational levels such as administration, students and technical staff (Early and Murphy, 2009). Milheim (2012) replaced the hierarchical levels related to the situation in e-learning to examine the needs of the students which motivates them in order to have a satisfying learning experience. It is seen that the use of Maslow's model in conjunction with other management models will help to increase the value of the framework because it will provide the aspect of motivating the stakeholders such as top-level executives, students, faculty, and executives from the governing body to keep motivating the institutes regarding upgrading and adopting e-learning technologies in HEIs of Pakistan.

Furthermore, to bring about change in an organisation, it is important to consider the involvement of different stakeholders with their powers and authorities related to that organisation. Presidents of HEIs also possess a high-level authority but they can also be controlled by other stakeholders to resist or prevent the change. In most of the institutes top-level executives act as a key person, or change agent, and they often face conflicts or stress from the governing bodies and external stakeholders such as the major sponsors of the organisation. The academic staff and fiscal issues faced by the executives of HEIs led to their departures while managing or bringing change to their organisation (Khan and Jabeen, 2019;

Tekniepe, 2014).

It is also seen that stakeholder analysis (SA) has been utilised in case study research. In Chozos et al., (2002) study, SA was applied to three different case scenarios and then each stakeholder was discussed in detail along with their responsibilities and contribution towards the implementation of e-learning. The conference proceedings also explain that stakeholder interests are interrelated and also shed light on the potential conflicts in stakeholders (Chozos, et al., 2002).

In Arab countries, especially in Bahrain, more women are enrolled in distance learning degrees than men such as in the case of Arab Open University (AOU). In Bahrain 37% of the candidates are female due to difficulty in finding enrolment in traditional classes due to cultural issues such as responsibilities as housewife (Essam and Al-Ammary, 2013). The findings of this study suggest that students are the main stakeholders of the university and motivation is the major factor affecting the success of e-learning in AOU. If the students are motivated towards e-learning then they feel encouraged and it will help them to succeed (Essam and Al-Ammary, 2013).

With the help of change management models (Kotter's eight step model, Leavitt's diamond model) and motivational model such as Maslow's hierarchy along with stakeholder analysis, it will provide the basis for the proposed theoretical framework of the current study. Combing these models will increase the exploratory power of the study because it will provide pathway for the HEIs and regulatory body to facilitate the implementation of e-learning in those HEIs where it is still needed to be adopted and to further manage the change in HEIs of Pakistan.

3.4 Other Change Forces affecting Higher Education

Senior (2002) asserted that rather than changes within the organisation there are also some known external environmental changes, namely Political, Economic, Social and Technological changes (PEST) that bring change in the organisational culture and affect the programming standards of the organisation. As in other organisations, these factors also have a substantial influence on HEIs. To understand the environment, outlining the main business goals, identification of opportunities, implementing the required innovative changes and evaluating the results are the prime tasks of strategic management (Drucker, 1980).

Gupta (2013) has argued about the change forces in his study that, to reflect the external environment of any organisation and for complete external environmental scrutiny, the best component of strategic management is the PEST analysis. The factors for change include

political regulation, law and legislation, economic cycles, world trade outlines, changes in the market, social-cultural changes, demographic fluctuations, intense situations such as war or natural disaster, innovation in technology, changes in production and distribution channels (Gupta, 2013; Dawson, 2003). Similarly, the global pandemic is considered in the external environment, and it has resulted in the immediate implementation of e-learning around the world (Hall, et al., 2021).

Devi (2014) narrated in her study that in the current era, one of the best indicators of a nation's development is its standard of higher education. Other than prominent barriers such as impact of globalisation of the educational organisations, HEIs face many other state-related challenges such as availability of funds, political strikes (unstable political environment between different political parties), terrorism, and irregular law and order situations. By analysing the views of the management and students this study concludes that these factors affect every aspect of life, but the education sector is one of those which are highly affected due to political instability.

In terms of resistance towards the change, it was seen that there are various factors, but they are majorly identified as internal and external ones which affect the implementation and act as resistance (Abdullah and Ward, 2016; Esterhuyse et al., 2016). Therefore, with the help of stakeholder analysis along with the consideration of motivational theory and change model, it will help the researcher to consider the important factors related to the identified stakeholders to successfully implement the change.

3.5 Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder Analysis (SA)/Stakeholder Theory (ST) is explained by many scholars and researchers (Bryson, 2005; Clarkson, 1995; Freeman, 1984). The term stakeholder means a group or person who claims the rights or ownership or shows interests in the activities of the organisation in the past, present and future (Clarkson, 1995). Freeman (1984) explains the term stakeholder as the influential beings who are in the position to control the achievement of organisation's goals and objectives which results in the wellbeing of the company. Many of the definitions are based on the seminal work of Freeman (1984) on stakeholder theory which is referred to active or passive stakeholders (Reed, et al., 2009).

Stakeholder analysis is the process in which the potential and important stakeholders are identified on the basis of their power, control and their contribution towards the achievement of the goals and objectives, because not all the stakeholders are of equal importance, and also prioritises the groups and individuals for the decision-making process (Freeman, 1984; Reed et al., 2009). Stakeholder analysis can be referred as a process in which identified individuals, groups or organisations can be affected by the aspects of social and natural phenomenon and those groups and individuals are involved in the decision-making process (Sapapthai, et al., 2020). Similarly, Mitchel, Agle and Wood (1997) also elaborate the need of identification and separation of stakeholders from non-stakeholders because relevant stakeholders should be represented systematically.

As the analysis includes different stakeholders therefore, their identification either as a group or individuals will be based on the purpose of conducting analysis. Stakeholders have their interests and stakes in the phenomenon which is considered under investigation therefore, it is still a confusion whether the phenomenon determines which stakeholders are involved or stakeholders identify themselves to be included (Reed, et al., 2009). Therefore, it is important to investigate the issues, problems, and phenomenon in depth to understand which stakeholders should be included in the process (Prell, et al., 2008).

As with other business organisations, HEIs are also organisations in society which are transforming due to globalisation, economic, social, and political factors (Maric, 2013). Therefore, they are also going through transformational changes and teaching and research operations are being reassessed (Mainardes, et al., 2010). The role of universities is being forced to change and update according to the changing environment of their business

structure and they have to reconsider their relationships and role with their different stakeholders, communities, and constituencies (Jongbloed, et al., 2008).

The communities in which HEIs operate are becoming more demanding which results in better articulated strategies to understand and manage the stakeholders of HEIs. The main consequence results in new governance and business concept of the universities either in developed or developing nations to create value in the region (De Boer, et al., 2007). It is also seen that theories influenced by stakeholders help to identify internal and external requirements of higher educational institutes to develop strategic planning about change (Falqueto, et al., 2019).

3.5.1 Types of Stakeholders

Clarkson (1995) identifies two group types of stakeholders. A primary group is one whose continued participation in the stakes of the organisation results in survival for the going concern of the business. Primary group includes government, customers, suppliers, and communities therefore, if any of the group such as customers or suppliers are not satisfied and they withdraw themselves from the operations then it will be catastrophic for the organisation and will result in the collapse of the business (Clarkson, 1995). A secondary group includes those members who are not engaged or related to those transactions which are essential for the survival of the corporation, such as media (Baric, 2017; Clarkson, 1995).

Stakeholders can also have direct or indirect interests related to the operations of the business and any change which occurs in the business process. Those groups can either be internal or external and can have a stake in the business (Khanyile, 2018).

As stakeholder theory has been discussed above, , discussion related to stakeholder analysis and identification will be presented in the next sub section.

3.5.2 Identification of Stakeholders

The identification of stakeholders is considered to be an important step of stakeholder analysis as it helps the researcher to identify which stakeholders should be included on the basis of their relevance to the study. Along with the identification, classification will be discussed because it will provide insight about the approach used to identify the stakeholders and put them in categories which will help to clear the ambiguity related to the effectiveness of the stakeholders in the organisation.

In common practice, identification is conducted through a top-down approach which might include the team's biases rather than reflecting the interest of the stakeholders (Varvasovszky and Brugha, 2000). The purpose and approach used for identification of stakeholders also dictates who should be important and what really counts (Mitchell, et al., 1997). Similarly, if the purpose of the analysis is to equally distribute the benefits and cost of the project then inclusion of all the stakeholders will be beneficial (Grimble and Chan, 1995). Therefore, it is better to categorise and differentiate the stakeholders when the process of analysis is planned to start.

Reed et al., (2009) mention two broad approaches for the classification of stakeholders; top-down or analytical approach, and bottom-up or reconstructive approach. In the analytical approach, people who investigate the phenomenon carry out the classification according to key players, context setters or main subjects. On the other hand, the reconstructive approach represents that, stakeholders categorise themselves according to their structure and interactions between stakeholders (Hare and Pah-Wostl, 2002; Sharpe et al., 2021).

Identification of stakeholders is the most important part in utilising the stakeholder model/theory. Clarkson's (1995) identification of primary and secondary groups of stakeholders identifies the internal and external stakeholders according to their relevance, importance, rank, the level of affecting the business and also the level of being affected by others. Similarly, there are also three factors; power, legitimacy and urgency which help the management to identify and distinguish between potential and real stakeholders of the company (Mitchell, et al., 1997). Another widely accepted and used methodology is the power and interest grid which maps stakeholders according to their power and salience, that is, interest in the organisation and their level of effectiveness (Johnson and Scholes, 2002).

The power and interest grid is also explained in other terms where managing stakeholders can be identified as key players, context setters, subjects, and crowd (Eden and Ackermann, 1998). Key players are those stakeholders who have the maximum interest, and they have the influential power or key place in the organisation. Context setters have high interest similar to key players, but they have less influential power. Whereas subjects are those who are initially regarded as those who have less capacity to make an impact but with the help of coalition and team building, they can become key players as they have high interest and low power. Lastly, crowd refers to those who have least interest and power in the organisation, but they form alliances to result in the failure of any particular outcome therefore, in the grid we can also

label stakeholders as supportive or unsupportive to capture their impacts (Eden and Ackermann, 1998; Reed et al., 2009).

3.5.3. Identification of Stakeholders in HEIs

This section describes the most important component of theoretical framework which is the identification of stakeholders in the context of HEIs. As the author is considering SA in this study, the identification of stakeholders will be based on the previous studies.

Mainardes et al. (2010) found in their study that in terms of HEIs, the best practice to identify stakeholders is not only from the top executives or directors but also from different levels from the hierarchy. Their study identifies the stakeholders from the top layer of the management therefore the results are not definitive due to the fact that the traditional methods for identifying the stakeholders supported by the stakeholder's theory are not applied in the practical approach of identification in terms of universities (Mainardes, et al., 2010).

De Boer et al. (2007) mentions one of the causes of changing environments in Dutch universities is that the government granted independent borrowing powers to the universities which resulted in less support from the government in terms of property management. Therefore, universities can borrow from the commercial banks which makes them also stakeholders of HEIs in The Netherlands. Similarly, the importance of non-academic stakeholders such as the finance department, human resource department, information technology, career service department etc. is increasing because they are referred to as gatekeepers for external stakeholders of HEIs (Jongbloed, et al., 2008).

Since the business environment of the universities is changing. Watson (2003) states that universities are expected to be excellent in their teaching, to become entrepreneurial (towards their students and communities), to become competitive, and attract local and international focus (related to teaching and research) all at the same time. It shows that the list of stakeholders to analyse in HEIs is continuously changing and transforming (Jongbloed, et al., 2008).

Another method of identification of stakeholders is through their stakes and influence, that is, the type of interest an individual or group has in the organisation. Burrows (1999) utilised Freeman's (1984) three types of stakes in his study (ownership, economic dependence and social). Furthermore, other stakes are also identified such as institutional stake, economic stake, scholarship stake and moral stake which leads to personal stake. Freeman (1984) also

specified three types of influences which are used by the stakeholders to consider in the SA; formal influence (contractual and regulatory relationship between stakeholders and institute), economic influence (stakeholder's ability to generate required resources) and political influence (stakeholder's ability to affect the institute's decision to negotiate) (Burrows, 1999).

Table 3.1 below shows previous researchers who have identified different stakeholders in the context of HEIs.

Table 3.1 Stakeholder Identification from Previous Studies

Researchers	HEIs Publics/ Identification
Weaver (1976)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - Institutional management - Teaching staff - Consumers (students, their families, employers, and society in general)
Smith and Cavusgil (1984)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suppliers of funding, products and services and regulatory agencies - Actors (the media, and public relations professionals conveying the university message whether to students or to employers) - Student parents
Owlia and Aspinwall (1996)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students - Employers - Teaching staff - Government - Families
Rowley (1997)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students - Parents and family - Local community - Society - Government - Institutional management team - Local authorities - Current and future employers

Franz (1998)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The student - The family - The employer - Society
Aparicio, Bacao, and Oliveira (2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students - Teachers - Accreditation Bodies - Content Providers - Technology providers - Education Ministry <p>Educational Institutions</p>
Falqueto et. al., (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Student Body - Faculty - Technical and Administrative staff - Top management - External Audit entities - Government
Choudhury and Patnaik (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learners - Content Developers - Instructors - Accreditation Bodies - Employers - Educational Institutes - Technology Providers

Source: (Aparicio et al., 2016; Choudhury and Patnaik, 2020; Falqueto et al., 2019; Mainardes et al., 2010)

The changing environment of higher education has highlighted the immense need of distance education (e-learning) which is resulting in the re-examination of the mediums of education being delivered. Therefore, e-learning is becoming more popular, growing rapidly around the world and creating new opportunities for institutes and students (Wagner, et al., 2008).

Wagner et al. (2008) utilised stakeholder analysis as an important tool to successfully implement e-learning in the university context. They modified it by applying the stakeholder responsibility matrix which shares crucial information related to the stakeholders such as motivational factors, major concerns, and reasons to consider those stakeholder categories. The identification process is conducted by considering the previous literature related to stakeholder theory. The matrix also shows the combination of different stakeholders and how

they can work together to ensure the success rate of implementation of e-learning (Wagner, et al., 2008).

In another theoretical framework study, it was seen that an e-learning theoretical framework with three main components of information systems, namely people, technologies, and services, was used. As people interact with the technologies and services therefore, stakeholder analysis was conducted and stakeholders were identified on the basis of previous literature (Aparicio, et al., 2016).

As e-learning includes changes in the IT systems of a university, leaders who facilitate the change and management of change in the HEIs should have high emotional intelligence skills (such as when and how to emphasise about the change and revert back from the decisions) to proceed with the right decision and in the right direction, otherwise it will become disruptive for the organisation (Ryan, et al., 2012). It also shows that if those stakeholders who have less power and high interest are neglected then it can also affect the implementation of the e-learning as they can link up with other stakeholders to influence their decision-making powers.

From the examples discussed above, the author will introduce the identified stakeholders for the sake of the current study.

3.5.4 Identified Stakeholders

In this section, the author will mention the identified stakeholders on the basis of previous research. As stakeholder analysis allows the researcher to identify and manage the stakeholders which will result in smooth implementation of the e-learning in HEIs, it will also help to understand the responses of the stakeholders related to its implementation (Anwansedo, et al., 2018).

There are various studies such as Melewar and Akel (2005), Maric (2013) and Jongbloed et al. (2008) which divides the groups of stakeholders on the categorical basis such as primary, secondary, internal, external, commercial, and non-commercial (Labanauskis and Ginevičius, 2017). Furthermore, Anwansedo et al. (2018) and Horton and Pilkington (2014) also divided the stakeholders on the basis of their roles in the implementation of a change process. These divisions and allocation of stakeholders into their respective groups allows the researchers to understand their functionality and operability related to the implementation of change, specifically in terms of HEIs.

As shown above, the previous research related to the identification of stakeholders in the context of HEIs, the author will utilise those studies to identify the stakeholder groups and individual stakeholders for the current study. The current study will also categorise the stakeholders on the basis of their roles and then on the basis of group too to capture the effect of each stakeholder's group on the organisation.

Initially, beginning with the identification, the author will present the stakeholders. Following are the stakeholders of the current study:

- ***Students***

Students are recognised as the customers for the HEIs. This stakeholder group includes four sub-groups; current students, potential students, alumni, and international students (Lagrosen, et al., 2004). Furthermore, students can also communicate with their parents about the new tools and learning methodologies which will enable their parents to support the idea of e-learning methodologies.

- ***Employees***

Employees are a broader group of stakeholders which includes the internal part of the organisation. They may also be referred to as organisational stakeholders as they are taken from inside the organisation. This group includes top executives, rector, vice chancellor, heads of departments in the university, professors, assistant professors, faculty related to exchange programmes, part-time faculty members, and visiting faculty.

- ***Educational Institutes***

They are the most influential in terms of external stakeholders as there are two different aspects of this type of stakeholder. First, there are those educational institutes which are signed Memorandum of Understanding (MOUs) to increase the quality, value, and strength of their services in the industry. They are also recognised as competitors in some research such as that of Maric (2013) who refers to competitors as direct, potential and substitutes in the study. Therefore, educational institutions will be looked at from both perspectives in the current study.

- ***Content Providers***

Content providers are those stakeholders who provide knowledge sharing techniques, that is they can be internal or external stakeholders who provide the e-learning course content to the HEIs, and they interact directly with the organisation (Aparicio, et al., 2016).

- ***Technology Providers***

These stakeholders are a combination of internal and external stakeholders because HEIs have their own IT department which might assist the HEI with the hardware side of the technology. However, the software development is mostly conducted by external stakeholders (Nawaz and Qureshi, 2010). Nawaz and Qureshi (2010) also mentioned leading-edge and bleeding-edge syndromes in their study which refers to the use of cutting-edge technologies which are tested but their cost and learning issues will result them into bleeding-edge technologies which becomes a barrier to the implementation of e-learning. Bleeding-edge technologies refers to those technologies which consumes the allocated budget of the institute and provide no special results therefore, the reduction in financials will result as a barrier towards the implementation of e-learning in HEIs.

- ***Regulatory or Accreditation Bodies***

The current study is conducted in Pakistan, therefore, the main regulatory body for HEIs is the Higher Education Commission (HEC). It is the responsibility of the HEC to provide authorisation to the institutions which are HEIs in Pakistan to grant degrees in any particular field or subject (Khawaja, et al., 2011). Recognition from the HEC indicates that an institute fulfils the basic criteria set by the HEC to promote quality education. There are a further nine accreditation bodies which are set in place independently to overview the quality of education in some fields such as Pakistan Medical and Dental Council (PMDC) for medical studies, Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC) for engineering studies etc. There are five other accreditation councils works under HEC which are also put in place for business studies, technology, agriculture, computing, and training teachers.

The HEC also introduced the Quality Assurance Agency (QAA) in 2004 to measure the quality of education in Pakistan which resulted in the establishment of Quality Enhancement Cells (QEC) which include all the stakeholders related to HEIs to practice the international standards and frameworks for quality evaluation of academia and its enhancement (Batool and Qureshi, 2007).

However, the purpose of including a regulatory or accreditation body as a stakeholder in the current study is to analyse their level of input, that is, how they will affect the implementation of e-learning by influencing the perceptions of stakeholders. Therefore, they are considered as valuable external stakeholders who have both power and interest related to the implementation of e-learning.

- ***Government***

Government includes the departments related to education such as the Department of Education or Ministry of Education. This is because if government issued new legislations or rules then both the private and public sector both have to adopt those changes. Therefore, the government plays a vital role in external stakeholders.

As the key stakeholders are identified in this research, the researcher will explain the concept of combining different models with stakeholder analysis to understand the breadth of the model used for the theoretical framework.

3.5.5 Breadth of Stakeholder Analysis

Furthermore, to understand the concept of the above-mentioned models by combining it with stakeholder analysis, the author will also utilise previous studies which have used different models along with stakeholder analysis to understand how different researchers have managed to enhance the application and use of the original SA model.

In some cases, implementing organisational change through change management models is not enough therefore, combining those models with complementing models will help the researcher to enhance the functionality and the explaining power of the original model. Chebbi, Yahiaoui, Sellami, Papasolomou and Melanthiou (2019) concluded in their study that if Kotter's change model is applied to any organisation along with the stakeholder management model it will help the organisation to overcome the resistance by understanding the interests of the internal or external stakeholders. Further, specific to their study it was revealed that the success of the change programme significantly depended on considering their employees (internal stakeholders) as the customers with high importance to implement successfully corporate entrepreneurship.

In a case from Latin America, SA was conducted to understand the needs of the stakeholders either internal or external, with the help of a change actor strategy (one who helped in excelling the change and overcoming the resistance between the stakeholders and acted as a medium between them). It also showed that by considering different management strategies with the combination of SA, positive results will be produced while implementing any change in the context of universities (Sucozhanay, et al., 2016).

In terms of HEIs, stakeholders have a distant relationship with the organisation and also with other stakeholders. The distant relationship not only increases to more resistance, but it will

also lead the stakeholders to the conclusion that they are not important for the organisation (Pollock and Cornford, 2004). Therefore, different management strategies are also used to increase the involvement of the stakeholders which promotes motivation and satisfaction in them if they are involved at the earliest stage in the project (Lechtchinskaia, et al., 2011).

In another research, it was found that if Kolb's experiential learning (management approach) is linked with the stakeholder analysis then it enhances the value of stakeholder analysis and it allows the smooth running of the operations and adds value to the system. Furthermore, industrial partners are also identified which explains the ideal situations, work environment, student environment and learning environment of the institutes (Clements, 2009).

3.5.6 Key Features of Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder analysis helps to identify and manage the stakeholders on the basis of their interest and power however, the key elements of stakeholder analysis include to understand the power dynamics, control mechanisms, collaboration between stakeholders, managing the goals and objectives, and dependencies among stakeholders.

It is important to understand the power dynamics among the stakeholders because it can influence other stakeholders which are involved in the process of change management. Power dynamics involved in managing multiple stakeholders is crucial because failure to recognise the existence of imbalanced power of the stakeholders will result in abusing or excluding those stakeholders with less power dynamics (Brouwer, et al., 2013). Similarly, stakeholders related to HEIs have different levels of power and they select different strategies to influence the decision-making by influencing the availability of resources. The study of Falqueto et al., (2019) identified that different level of power results in different university-stakeholder relationships, these relationships are important because HEIs are sensitive to external stakeholders and their level of power will influence the implementation of strategic planning. In current research, the power dynamics can be identified among the different internal and external stakeholders in the process of implementing e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan with the help of stakeholder analysis.

The study of Nordberg and Andreassen (2020) shows that the control of societal stakeholders can influence the decision-making process of HEIs. It is seen that the Higher Education Learning Outcomes (HELOs) involves stakeholders other than professional stakeholders who threatens their control on the basis of their power over expertise from their professions (i.e., internal stakeholders of HEIs). It is because HELOs oversee the comparability of standards

and the quality of higher education qualifications in central European countries, therefore, they can regulate the policies in the HEIs and give directions to the management of HEIs which can violate professional autonomy and control (Nordberg & Andreassen, 2020). The situation of covid-19 shows that the regulatory body (HEC external stakeholder) in Pakistan utilised their controlling mechanism to direct the HEIs to implement e-learning tools during the lockdown phase. Therefore, the control mechanism among different stakeholders will help to manage the change as it will help to manage the strategic planning among different stakeholders.

Stakeholder collaborations are an important aspect of stakeholder analysis because it will help to provide support to different stakeholders at different levels. The study of Khadim et al., (2022) refers that to develop curriculum to improve the quality of education in Pakistan, there is a need to encourage the collaboration among stakeholders such as educators, policy makers, technology providers etc. to share best educational practices among different institutes to improve the curriculum. In the current study, the collaboration of HEC with Microsoft is an example of providing e-learning tools to the HEIs of Pakistan however, the success of the implementation of e-learning will depend on better and more collaborations among different stakeholders as it will provide more opportunities and advantages to the stakeholders to accept the change.

Pan et al., (2013) presented an important part of stakeholder analysis which is often neglected by generic models of stakeholder analysis. It is known as the stakeholder dependencies, and it can be studied and analysed with the help of four grids i.e., critical stakeholder, mutual benefit stakeholder, replaceable stakeholder, and easy-care stakeholder. With the help of this grid, organisation can better manage its relationships with its primary stakeholders because it allows to manage the stakeholders according to the grid which is based on the level of interest of stakeholder's involvement in the decision-making process the organisation. It shows that the stakeholders can be dependent on other stakeholders as their level of interest and power can influence the decisions related to the organisation. As the dependencies of the stakeholders become balanced, then stakeholders will be able to achieve the goals and objectives of the organisation with the help of their collaborations and understanding among them. The stakeholder analysis provides pathway towards managing the stakeholders on the basis of their power and interest which ultimately results in managing the change because stakeholders with higher level of power can enforce the implementation of change such as HEC enforced the HEIs in Pakistan to implement and use e-learning tools during covid-19.

3.6 Successful Integration of SA with other Models

As the debate of how to manage the stakeholders through stakeholder theory continues to increase, various studies and research have been conducted to explain these terminologies. It shows how researchers have combined different concepts with stakeholder analysis/theory to effectively manage their stakeholders to achieve the goals and objectives of the organisation. This also helps the author to firmly select SA as the conceptual framework for this study.

Ackermann and Eden (2011) explore the power of stakeholder power grid/matrix by utilising Top Management Teams (TMTs) and combining them with the concept of stakeholder analysis which shows the application of the concept in theory and practice. It shows that SA produces effective results when combined with TMT as it gives insight to the management that who are inclined towards supporting the management and who are against the management decisions.

Similarly, to enhance the understandability of SA, the term Network Analysis was combined with it to explain the intensifying relationship between tourism companies and policy makers. It shows that public stakeholders have more importance than private ones due to their higher position in the preference scale (Presenza and Cipollina, 2010).

It is also seen that stakeholder identification and classification, if combined with the identity and social identity theories, will help management teams to analyse the stakeholders in terms of economic and social categories (Crane and Ruebottom, 2011). Both identity and social identity theories explain the concept of social roles and category-based identities which are attached with the stakeholders (Stryker and Burke, 2000). Therefore, the matrix is re-designed into social identities and traditional stakeholder roles which not only captures the effect of the standard stakeholders but also captures specific stakeholders (Crane and Ruebottom, 2011).

While considering the social part of the organisation for SA, social learning is also considered as an important tool which is formed on the basis of experience learning (Kolb (1984) in Prell et al., (2008)), transformational learning (e.g., Alexander (1999) in Prell et al., (2008)), action research seeking transformative change by taking action (Lewin, 1946) and collaborative learning of the stakeholders (Prell, et al., 2008). This can be used to identify the stakeholders related to the social aspects of the organisation and help the management to manage them according to their needs.

Orndoff (2005) shows that combining contingent value method and Delphi model with the stakeholder analysis allows the management to direct the stakeholders and helps to improve the decision making of the stakeholders. It also concludes that two separate models with their limitations and drawbacks when combined with the stakeholder analysis empowers the application of the models (Orndoff, 2005).

Similarly, SWOT analysis can be linked with the SA to create a stakeholder analysis matrix which helps to understand the strengths and weaknesses of the stakeholders according to their interest and power. SWOT analysis shows that it provides better insight about the stakeholder and the analysis can be done in depth (Deglane, et al., 2017).

3.7 Integration of Models

In this study, the author is combining four models, namely Kotter's change model, Maslow's hierarchy, Leavitt's diamond model and stakeholder analysis to come up with a theoretical framework for this study. The theoretical framework for this study is mainly consisted of stakeholder analysis as it will provide insight about the management of stakeholders which will provide beneficial results related to the successful implementation of e-learning in the HEIs of Pakistan.

It has been seen that if stakeholder analysis is linked with other management models it will produce better results as one model complements the other/s and overcomes the weaknesses of other models in their relative processes.

Neumeier (2013) has shown in her study that Kotter's change model can be used in combination with another model such as Innovation Diffusion Model, in her case if the eight steps of Kotter's change model are combined and arranged as a group. For instance, the first four components of the change model indicate the communication of change with the stakeholders and describe the new objectives, mission or vision of the organisation related to the new change.

Stouten and Rousseau (2018) integrated seven change models and proposed that integration would allow them to understand those elements which are overlapping in the change management models and to realise the flaws between those models.

Similarly, the author is also utilising the same concept, with three models to manage the stakeholders in the change implementation process. As Leavitt's diamond model consists of four main components (Task, Structure, Technology and People), therefore, it will be utilised

as a macro level (industry level) model, whereas the integrated Maslow's and Kotter's models will be used as micro-level models to manage the change implementation at departmental level.

The author will also explain the other three models; Kotter's change model, Maslow's hierarchy model and Leavitt's diamond model, to create understanding about them and also to explain how they will be connected with the stakeholder analysis.

3.7.1 Kotter's Change Model

John Kotter's eight step change model is applied by many institutions and organisations around the globe. Kotter is considered an expert in the field of leadership and change management. In 1996 Kotter introduced his famous change management model which directs to lead the change rather than manage the change in the organisation and provided eight steps to successfully implement and lead the change.

Those eight steps are discussed below:

- ***Sense of Urgency***

The first step in this model is to initiate the change by creating and understanding the importance of change within the organisation. The sense of urgency can be created only when the factor(s) necessitating the change are considered by the leaders and top-level management and communicated to the employees so they can understand the need of change (Calder, 2013; Sidorko, 2008).

- ***Forming Guiding Coalition***

The establishment of a sense of urgency can result from the internal or external problems or issues faced by the organisation as a whole or by the leaders of the organisation. Therefore, the change can be successfully implemented if leaders of the organisation, that is, leaders or managers of different departments of the organisation, come together and contribute through their knowledge, skills, and expertise to implement the change (Sidorko, 2008). Kotter (1996) also explained that several guiding coalitions can be formed during the process of change, as needed by the change process, to provide clear purpose and direction for the implementation of change.

- ***Developing/Creating Vision***

The third step is to motivate the people to accept the change and understand the need for it. This will be achieved through creating new or updating any existing vision for the teams or groups in the organisation. For instance, creating a short video clip for the staff and students to introduce blended learning in HEIs to communicate the purpose of the change and to understand the development required (Quinn, Amer, Lonie, Blackmore, Thompson and Pettigrove, 2012).

- ***Communicating the Change Vision***

Kotter (1996) believes that a vision should be feasible, achievable, desirable, imaginable, focused, and communicable. The definition of vision shows that after developing the vision it should be effectively communicated to the audience or the stakeholders. In the case of change in HEIs, vision should be communicated to the all the members of the guiding coalition by means of news forums, discussion forums, websites etc. (Quinn, et al., 2012). Another example is communicating through new integrated departments within the organisations which will allow the leaders and other members of the organisation to communicate with each other or to listen to the views of other stakeholders (Sidorko, 2008).

- ***Empowering others to act and remove perceived barriers***

This step identifies the barriers to change as it is difficult for the leaders to provide power to those stakeholders who did not have power of decision making before in the organisation to overcome the resistance so that change will be implemented smoothly. The change might result in the opportunity for employees to improve themselves and learn more whereas some employees might think that they will lose their power and status due to the introduction of change (Kotter, 1996; Sidorko, 2008). Management must realise that successful change can only result when human elements in the change process are effectively managed (Sidorko, 2008).

- ***Short term wins***

Employees may be motivated by considering their short-term wins as this will help them to feel motivated to adapt to the change. On the other hand, others might feel demotivated because of the change in the services or circumstances such as in 1996 the University of Newcastle, Australia, when the top management installed digital librarians (self-service desks), some of the librarians took it personally and considered it as clash of cultures (Sidorko, 2008). Therefore, those employees/stakeholders who accept the change should be encouraged and rewarded accordingly (Quinn et al., 2012).

- ***Consolidating Change***

The recognition of previous short wins will make the change agents believe that they have completed the job successfully, which will make them consider adapting to the change quickly in future. It will result in smooth implementation of change in the organisation (Sidorko, 2008).

- ***Anchoring Change into Culture***

It explains that whoever is in the line of succession of leadership should introduce a process which reinforces change in the organisation over time to time so that it becomes the culture of the organisation. It will only result if previous steps are fulfilled and successful because cultures cannot be manipulated or changed (Kotter, 1996; Quinn et al., 2012; Sidorko, 2008).

3.7.2 Relevance to the Study

The study of Quinn et al., (2012) utilised Kotter's eight step model in two Australian universities (Australian National University and University of South Australia) where Hubs and Spokes project model was already in place for implementing the change within health and engineering disciplines in both universities. Their research identifies that with the help of Kotter's model they were able to make guiding coalition between internal stakeholders (i.e., technical, academic, and managerial staff) to implement blended learning technologies among both universities. They have identified that the first three steps of Kotter's model provide the purpose and motivation for the stakeholders to implement the change as they form solid foundation for the change in higher education (Quinn, et al., 2012).

Similarly, Van Twembeke and Goeman (2018) utilised the concept of change management models which includes Kurt Lewin's change model and Kotter's eight step model to manage the change of traditional classroom to flipped classroom. The study includes three Flemish educational centres where two of the centres provide specific teacher training through flipped classrooms i.e., online learning. To embrace the educational change related to digital learning, the study findings indicate that a guiding coalition would be beneficial for the lecturers which addresses the need for relatedness, and it would help to acknowledge the change by facilitating the peer exchanges which will eliminate the fear of interference among colleagues related to the teaching practices.

Further, the study of Voigt et al., (2021) is based on the sudden implementation of e-learning in German higher education institute. Their study focused on the Kotter's eight step change management model which helped them to identify the important stakeholders involved in the

process of implementation of e-learning. The research confirms that covid-19 worked in the favour of the change while the change was managed through Kotter's eight step model. Furthermore, their study confirms that the higher educational institutes can successfully implement the change managed with the help of Kotter's eight step model because the eight steps helps to trace the tasks given to the stakeholders and they can re-visit those steps which were missed during the implementation phase to ensure the successful implementation (Voigt, et al., 2021).

Similarly, the study of Khamis et al., (2021) utilised Kotter's eight step to capture the impact of catalysed environmental situation of Covid-19 which resulted the implementation of e-learning techniques in Agha Khan University (AKU) and its international campuses across East Africa as well. Their study pointed out that the first step (creating urgency) of Kotter's model was not followed in the campuses of AKU because of the sudden implementation of online learning tools ordered by HEC. However, it was seen that there was collaboration between the international campuses which followed the step of guiding coalition. With the help of Kotter's model, the research analysed its use for the implementation purposes. However, the study also confirms that once the pandemic was over then the university went back to face-to-face delivering of lectures. These studies shows that the implementation of e-learning can be successfully managed with the help of Kotter's change management model because those steps in the model helps them to understand the importance of each stakeholder involved in the process of implementation.

3.7.3 Maslow's Hierarchy

Motivation affects an individual's life in every possible way throughout the process of growth and learning. Motivation is considered to be an important element not only to learn anything but also to perform work properly (Hubackova, 2014). Motivation towards e-learning or in educational institutes may consider a set of intrinsic and extrinsic set of factors to motivate the stakeholders in the educational institute environment. Therefore, in this study the author is also utilising Maslow's hierarchy of needs to understand the motivational factors for the stakeholders related to the implementation of e-learning. In terms of motivation, there are two approaches: content theories and process theories. Maslow's theory is an example of content theory which explains those elements or actions which motivate people (Leatherbarrow and Fletcher, 2019).

Maslow's hierarchy of need is based on a pyramid which shows the classification of five human needs, and it is important to fulfil one by one through a step-by-step process to

motivate people. Considering passing higher level of needs without satisfying one need at a minimum level will not possible (Maslow, 1943). Following are the classification of needs:

- ***Physiological***

This is considered as the basic biological needs which are essential for survival. It highlights about the basic needs such as food, supplies etc. whereas in terms of HEIs and individual stakeholders, physiological component works as basic professional development workshops, pedagogy courses in the colleges, better equipment, accessibility to basic requirements related to e-learning, personal space etc. (Fisher and Royster, 2016; Leatherbarrow and Fletcher, 2019; Oluwunmi et al., 2018).

- ***Safety and Security***

Safety and security refer to the need of a safe and danger free, non-threatening environment. In terms of HEIs, this includes job safety, feelings related to injustice, unfairness, tangible benefits like bonuses, salary increase, awards, trainings, strong policies, safety from physical and emotional threats etc. (Biskupic et al., 2015; Fisher and Royster, 2016; Turabik and Baskan, 2015).

- ***Belongingness***

This level of hierarchy includes a sense of attachment to other individuals in the organisation or in general. At the workplace, it represents an individual is attached with a prominent group or with a friendly team in the organisation. In terms of HEIs, it will include the reviews of teachers, head of departments, administrators, students, and chancellors to promote the association as a group within the structure of the HEI. It provides the members of the group to sense the feeling of belonging and allows them to discuss their feelings and thoughts about the processes and changes (Fisher and Royster, 2016).

- ***Esteem***

Esteem refers to where an individual can see where they stand in terms of relationships with others in the organisation. It is also reported as respect which shows that other people or stakeholders consider solid reputation of their group members rather than the stakeholders consider themselves as reputed. Esteem is based on other people's perceptions which motivates and encourages the employee to achieve more in the organisation (Fisher and Royster, 2016; Leatherbarrow and Fletcher, 2019).

- ***Self-actualisation***

This is defined as the possibility and capacity of an individual to become the person, he/she wants to become. In terms of HEI, it will be a point where stakeholders continuously improve themselves and make the best use of their potential, power, and interest as a stakeholder in the organisation. A person will only reach this status if he/she has successfully reached the stage of respect in the organisation or in their respective field (Fisher and Royster, 2016; Turabik and Baskan, 2015).

The author will now move towards Leavitt's diamond model and explain the functionality of this model in general and also related to the socio-technical change within HEIs which will help to create an understanding of the concepts and functionality of the models.

3.7.4 Relevance to the Study

The study of Yildiz (2021) used Maslow's hierarchy of needs motivational model to facilitate the use and implementation of Web 2.0 technologies in Turkish government university. The study focused on academicians as the most important stakeholder of the university and the model was adjusted according to Web 2.0 which resulted in Maslow's 2.0 Digital Needs Pyramid model. The results of the study indicated that academics preferred YouTube and Instagram as the tools of Web2.0 to realise their self-actualisation needs. It confirms that these tools motivate the academics to bring out their creativity technological skills for teaching and learning purposes (Yildiz, 2021).

Similarly, Abbas (2022) focused on students' motivation during covid-19 in which the researcher utilised Maslow's motivational model to indicate the basic needs of the students while implementing e-learning technologies during lockdown in Iraqi Universities. There are 35 motivational strategies outlined with the help of Maslow's model in the study which includes directions for the teachers as well to motivate students to adopt e-learning systems during covid-19. The explicit use of specific online platforms such as UDEMY, Khan Academy, and EDX was recommended in the study to achieve the self-actualisation needs (Abbas, 2022).

Furthermore, the study of Khan et al., (2024) studied the impact of covid-19 on single stakeholder i.e., teachers towards the adoption of technology and attendance in higher educational institute while utilising Maslow's model. The study also referred to that during pandemic teachers faced difficulties related to their basic physiological and safety needs such as health related issues, job security, and personal safety. This leads to the notion that

Maslow's model can be used to understand the needs of the stakeholders. Another investigation of Jawed and Fatima (2021) used Maslow's hierarchy to explore the factors which affects the student learning in an online learning environment in a Pakistani higher education institute. The study pointed out the learning enhancing factor for students was student engagement, as students get motivated when teachers help them, and the use of relevant applications also motivate the students which enhance their learning (Jawed & Fatima, 2021). However, other stakeholders such as regulatory bodies, teachers and managers in the university were not studied. Therefore, in the current study, the author can use it to view the needs of different stakeholders to motivate them to facilitate the future implementations of e-learning technologies and also to point out the challenges faced by the stakeholders during the implementation phase. Maslow's model will help to identify the significant factors as well which are influencing the stakeholders' perception with the help of thematic analysis. Lastly, the model will help to provide the recommendations to motivate the stakeholders such as teachers, students, managers, and HEC (regulatory body) to further implement and enhance the e-learning technologies in HEIs of Pakistan.

3.7.5 Leavitt's Diamond Model

Leavitt's diamond model is considered as one of the most important techniques with explanatory power to analyse, understand and explain the technological interventions in the organisation (Coffie, et al., 2018). Leavitt classified the organisation in the shape of a diamond because the four components of the model are also interrelated, inter-connected and mutually adjusting in nature (Keen, 1981). The model also explains that all four elements should be reviewed with equal importance at any point of organisational change as all four components are interconnected.

Following are the four core elements:

- ***Task***

Task or process represents the primary tasks related to the change and it also includes the process for the execution of the change process. It also shows which goods or services are delivered by the organisation, tasks can be purely IT related or IT-driven. Further, tasks include expectations of the staff related to the process, business processes and mechanism related to the work accomplishment (Blumberg et al., 2014; Coffie et al., 2018).

- ***People***

This element of the model deals with the social part of the change. It includes skill levels, expertise of the people at different levels of hierarchy, shifting ideologies, attitudes, belief

systems and unpredictable social behaviours. It is considered to be problematic at various occasions which can result in the discontinuity of knowledge management if the change is related to IS. It is because some people learn a skill set and take the knowledge with them rather than providing any successor to the organisation (Coffie et al., 2018; Okunoye and Karsten, 2002). The element of people also refers to the people who will use e-learning in HEIs. In the current study, the most important set of people are the internal stakeholders of the organisation such as heads of departments, professors, and assistant professors.

- ***Structure***

This dimension emphasises the level of involvement of the stakeholders related to the proposed change in the organisation. It also explains the specified tasks of the stakeholders during the transformational change process (Coffie, et al., 2018). The change in structure refers to the change in process of sharing teaching and learning activities with the use of e-learning. It also identifies implementing structure such as hardware and software introduction will change the technological structure of the HEI. In this study, it will record the involvement of the identified stakeholders who will direct the implementation of the new technological structures related to the use of e-learning in HEIs in Pakistan.

- ***Technology***

Technology items are the tools which help the organisation to transform its inputs to outputs; it includes training seminars, rules and regulations related to the new IS to be put into place in the process of transformation (O'Sullivan, 2008). It also helps the organisation to accomplish its work, objectives and mission which is updated in the process of transformation (Okunoye and Karsten, 2002). In terms of this study, technology will be the implementation of software related to e-learning or the platforms which is related to e-learning. For instance, the implementation and use of Blackboard, Moodle, MOOCs, VLE etc.

3.7.6 Relevance to the Study

The study of Maharani et al., (2024) utilised PPT model which is an extension of Leavitt's diamond model to manage the change of implementing Knowledge Management System (e-learning system) in HEIs with the help of Kitchenham systematic literature review system. The study shows that the element of people of Leavitt's model's extension indicates three main problems namely user participation, motivation, and human aspect behaviour. The study mentions the motivational technique of using gamification tools to motivate the KMS users. Similar issues were identified with the help of other elements of the model where the need of

centralised systems and integrated data was identified (Maharani, et al., 2024).

Another investigation of Gorrell (2023) used Leavitt's Diamond model to explore the teacher's experiences of working and teaching in an online environment in HEI of UK. The study showed that ICT was the driving force for using more technology post covid-19. Furthermore, only one stakeholder was analysed i.e., teachers in the study, therefore, the study acknowledges that no senior managers were interviewed which results in not knowing the intentions of the senior managers behind their decision-making related to the use of more technology in the university. The current study considers internal and external stakeholders of the HEIs and view them through the lens of proposed framework which includes diamond model to help identify the change in the structure, tasks, people, and technology being implemented during covid-19 in HEIs of Pakistan. The Leavitt's model will also help to manage the change when it will be used in-conjunction with other models i.e., Maslow's hierarchy needs, and Kotter's eight step model and ultimately guide the author to provide recommendations to the HEIs and regulatory body of Pakistan to facilitate the future implementation and manage change.

3.8 Development of the Framework

As mentioned in sections 3.3 and 3.4, it can be seen that the grounds of developing the framework in the current study is based on the integration of the management models. The framework is proposed and developed through the process of integrating four models: Kotter's eight step model, Maslow's hierarchy, Leavitt's Diamond model and stakeholder analysis. With the help of the proposed framework, it will help HEIs to manage the change effectively and efficiently.

The framework is developed on the basis of techniques explained by each model to manage the change which are explained in sections 3.4.1., 3.4.2. and 3.4.3. With the help of the functionality of the models explained above, the author proposes the formation of the groups in section 3.6. which will show that Kotter's and Maslow's management models will be merged together. Stakeholder analysis will be used to analyse the behaviours, contributions, and the use of their powers to manage the change in HEIs of Pakistan that is to implement the change effectively and efficiently.

The following section will shed light upon the groups formed from two models, Kotter's eight step and Maslow's hierarchy model, and it will also highlights the functionality of the formed groups.

3.9 Formation of the Groups

In this part, the author will describe the sections formed which link the management models along with the rationale of why those sections have been formed and on what grounds.

3.9.1 Drafting Change

In this group the major planning initiatives will take place related to the change in the HEIs. This section will represent the blend of the first four components of Kotter's change model and the first three from Maslow's hierarchy model. On the other hand, Leavitt's model will be analysing the change in all four quadrants and helping the author to equally consider the social and technical parts of the implementation.

Initially it is really important to know what stakeholders are thinking about the change and what they require from the organisation in terms of any proposed change. Therefore, it is essential to conduct surveys, interviews with focus groups or with stakeholders with high power and high interest and understanding the attitudes of the end users towards the change.

As the first step is to create awareness about the change, therefore, the leaders or top-level managers will be suggested to provide information related to the change to the stakeholders and at the same time analyse the needs of the stakeholders too because it will help the leaders to know what motivates them and which level of needs are satisfied. It incorporates the physiological needs of motivation to understand the basic needs of the stakeholders according to their position, power, and interest. Urgency can also be created by providing examples to the stakeholders of the HEIs where e-learning platforms are successfully implemented either in developed or in developing countries. The data from those research projects and examples can then be used to provide unique motivational techniques that would be applicable in the context of Pakistan.

The second part of this phase is mainly linked with the SA as it requires creating a guiding coalition which mainly requires forming an alliance of the stakeholders with the right blend of early adopters and motivators. The early adopters/motivators will be the opinion leaders who will help the stakeholders to continue to be a part of the change once the need for change is communicated (Neumeier, 2013). The early change adopters will be those stakeholders who have knowledge related to e-learning and its platforms because those change adopters will help the leaders to use them to explain the benefits of e-learning implementation.

The next step in the initial stage includes the creation of vision and strategies in line with the

proposed change which should be completed by considering the representations from all the stakeholder groups by utilising the data gathered from them.

While communicating the new proposed vision and strategies to the guiding coalition, it should show the element of love and belongingness, Maslow's third step, to keep motivating the stakeholders. Motivating stakeholders can be done by communicating to them the importance of their respective new teams they are assigned and to express the amount of trust placed in them to make the project successful so that the barriers to change will be removed. It will also be achieved by constantly describing the benefits, updated vision, strategies and goals.

3.9.2 Implementation

The second phase is the implementation of the actions by removing the barriers through motivating those stakeholders who accomplished their short-term goals. The achievement of short-term goals will give them the sense of accomplishment and they will, in turn, motivate others to remove the barriers to create more short-term wins. Short term wins should be celebrated at group or organisational level and in some scenarios, they should be celebrated on an individual basis too.

In terms of Leavitt's model, the impact of technological change will require to adjust the structure, business processes such as mode of learning and people who are stakeholders of the organisation. As can be seen, Leavitt's model will help the author to fine tune the integration by adjusting all four components of the diamond model and it will result in successful implementation of the change.

3.9.3 Confirming/Anchoring the Change

The final phase is to confirm the change by accumulating the gains through short term wins. It is of immense importance that the urgency of the change should be communicated at regular intervals so that the change should be incorporated into the organisation culture. It can be done by continuing support for identifying new potential stakeholders and providing them with updated training to keep the stakeholders on the right track towards achieving the strategic vision of the organisation. The early change adopters play a crucial role because when they achieve the step of self-actualisation, they will feel motivated to achieve further milestones.

Furthermore, the author will discuss the use of stakeholder analysis in the educational sector around the globe. In the next section of this chapter, the author will discuss literature related

to the previous studies conducted in an educational environment.

3.10 Justification for the Selected Framework

Theoretical or conceptual frameworks can be used in conjunction with different models or adding other variables to the existing models to increase the understanding of the topic under research. For instance, Tarhini, Hone and Liu (2014) highlights in their study the differences of users' behaviour related to e-learning in developing countries that if additional variables are included with Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), then it will increase the explanatory power of the original TAM model related to the use and implementation of e-learning.

The above explained models have strengths and weaknesses related to their functionality and their applicability. Therefore, the proposed models are used in conjunction to increase the explanatory power and benefits of utilising these models. In this section justification will be provided for each model used as a theoretical framework.

Initially stakeholder analysis (SA) will be used as the first model because it will help the researcher to identify the stakeholders of HEIs. It is seen that SA is being used increasingly in different fields of research such as management, environmental, governance, and international organisations and businesses (Raum, et al., 2021). Stakeholder analysis is used to identify the stakeholders of the organisations through different options in which power and interest factors are used to identify the potential stakeholders (Ackermann and Eden, 2011). With the help of stakeholder identification, it will allow the management to understand the needs of the stakeholders to manage the responses of the stakeholders towards change of strategies (Ackermann and Eden, 2011).

Leavitt's diamond model is famous for its use for managing technological change that is related to information systems because it studies the influence of technology on an organisation (Hau and Chang, 2021). It helps to maintain the balance between other components of the model, namely people, structure, and task to accomplish the implementation of the change (Magnaye-Laylo, 2020). Therefore, the model will help the researcher to overview the change in the organisation at macro-level to adjust the four pillars of Leavitt's model which are essential towards managing the change.

With the help of the motivating model that is Maslow's hierarchy integrated with change management model of Kotter's eight step model, the researcher will be able to enhance the

potential of both models to evaluate and provide solutions towards managing the change at micro-level/departmental level through a top-down approach. Maslow's model identifies the fundamental needs of employees which help to attain their self-satisfaction status which ultimately helps them to achieve the status of self-actualisation (Khan, et al., 2021) whereas Kotter's model also focuses on top-down approach where the step-by-step approach helps the management to implement the change. It requires strict following of the steps because skipping any step will result in a waste of effort and time. It is seen that integrating Kotter's model with other elements or models will help to overcome the shortcomings of the model such as providing necessary instructions related to the empowerment stage of change (Bekmukhambetova, 2021).

E-learning initiates the change in organisation related to the activities of the stakeholders which mainly focuses on the users of the systems, that is students and teachers. It helps to assist the faculty and students to make the process of teaching and learning more effective and efficient. The research aim is to examine the role of change management model in the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan which can be fulfilled with the help of the above-mentioned models used in conjunction with stakeholder analysis to provide educational findings to enhance the understanding of the stakeholders of HEIs. Lastly, these proposed models will help to shape the selection and type of data, provide process related to data interpretation, form the boundary of the research, and provide future research suggestions.

3.11 Functionality of the Proposed Framework

With the utilisation of the proposed theoretical framework, it will allow the researcher not only to implement the proposed models in combination with each other, it will also provide understanding that in terms of any proposed change, is there any model used by the HEIs in Pakistan to tackle the resistance arising from the change? With the help of the interviews with the identified stakeholders, it will also allow the author to analyse the process of selecting certain strategies by the HEIs when they need to implement any change in the organisation.

As there are already some strategies and policies put in place to manage the change in the HEIs therefore, this theoretical framework creates understanding for the researcher about whether or not either of those strategies are bringing any fruitful results. There are some occasions when organisations are using some specific form of management or strategic models, but the management do not realise the use of models until it is carefully studied.

Therefore, with the help of this study it will also help the HEIs to understand their managerial environment in the organisation.

Furthermore, there are always certain actions of the stakeholders which prove to be influential on other stakeholders and it affects their ability to accept the change. Those actions can be a part of the internal or external environment of the organisation which ultimately affects the successful implementation of e-learning. Therefore, those actions, strategies and factors will be studied in detail simultaneously with the data collection which helps the author to provide guidelines for the HEIs to consider while implementing e-learning in their institute.

As the theoretical framework is based on four different models it not only enhances the understandability of the situation under consideration but also helps the author to understand the resistance to and favour for the implementation of e-learning in HEIs in Pakistan. Furthermore, the graphical representation of the conceptual framework is provided below which shows that the whole process is not flowing from one side. It depicts that the information will be processed to and from the models combined together to successfully implement e-learning.

Figure 3a Graphical Representation of Theoretical Framework

Source: Originated by the researcher

3.12 Processes of the Framework

With the help of figure 3a, the author will explain the processes shown in the figure and also the relationship between the factors shown in the figure. The framework depicts the stages of its operation, that is P1 is the stakeholder analysis or identification of stakeholders will be the initial process which will help the researcher to collect data through interviews. After the stakeholder analysis, the utilisation of micro level integrated models will be used to identify the stages of planned change considered by the HEIs which depicts P2, process 2. The planning stage includes the communication of the proposed change that is informing the stakeholders about the new vision and objectives of the organisation. It will help the management to create guiding coalitions between stakeholders and the sense of urgency of the change will be communicated to them by satisfying their physiological needs through training and motivation.

The macro model, namely Leavitt’s model, represents the third process, P3, which will balance the task, structure, and people of the organisation with the introduction of technological change. The implementation stage will then highlight the challenges faced by the stakeholders during implementation, and it will help the management to assist their

stakeholders in achieving the esteem stage of needs by celebrating their short-term wins. Lastly, the management can confirm the change by helping the stakeholders to achieve the level of self-actualisation through highlighting the early adopters and communicating the urgency of change at regular intervals. Therefore, the accumulated process proposed by the framework will lead towards the management of change implementation in HEIs of Pakistan.

3.13 Summary

In this chapter, the basis and background of the framework has been defined by the author. The defined models, namely Leavitt's diamond model, Maslow's hierarchy, Kotter's eight step change model and stakeholder analysis help to describe the functionality of the framework in relation to the current study. As the change management models are used in combination with each other, therefore, the integration of models is discussed in terms of previous studies and also the formation of the groups is explained related to the current study. Further, the graphical representation of the framework provides a pictorial explanation of the framework along with in-depth details about the processes of the framework. Lastly, the use of the framework is combined with the objectives of the study to show how the proposed framework will achieve the objectives and aims of the current study.

Chapter 4 Research Methodology

4.1 Introduction

The previous chapters highlight the previous studies related to this research, the models and theoretical framework used by the author. Therefore, this chapter elucidates about the research methodology, that is, the selection of research paradigm, research approach, research strategy, data collection and interpretation of data collected. The objective of this chapter is to provide the rationale and logic behind the use of certain research techniques and the result of those techniques related to this study.

It is also seen that the theoretical framework that is stakeholder analysis will be the most suitable framework for the current study because it helps the researcher to observe and analyse the different stakeholder views related to the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. Moreover, it will also help the researcher to not only consider the internal factors but also the external factors which affect the implementation process through qualitative analysis which will be discussed later in this chapter. Also, the identified internal and external stakeholders will be analysed through the viewpoint of change management strategies if they consider any change management models while the implementations occurs, or they just follow managerial direction of the top-level executives.

The nature of the research problem in the current study called for the adoption of qualitative research methods which used to examine the realities of e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan. The qualitative study involved research sites where the data was collected through semi-structured interviews to determine if any change management models were used in the implementation of e-learning. Also, those interviews shed light on the internal and external factors which influence the stakeholders' perceptions in the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. This chapter provides details of other modes of data being used such as policy documents of HEC were being analysed. The chapter concludes with the description of data triangulation such as the consideration of reliability, validity and generalizability of the collected data.

At this point, the author also describes the meaning of research; there are different definitions for research but people define it differently. From one common definition, research can be explained as a process of collecting, recording, analysing, and interpreting the gathered

information to improve our existing knowledge and also to enhance and broaden the scope of knowledge (Wilson, 2013). As research is systematic and methodical, therefore, it can be conducted by various methods and techniques (Williams, 2007).

Therefore, in order to gain an in-depth understanding of this chapter, the author will be using Honeycomb of Research methodology which provides step by step instructions to explain the research terminologies. It will also help to provide the rationale behind the selection of specific research terms in this study.

4.2 Honeycomb of Research Methodology

In this study, the researcher is using the Honeycomb method to identify and elaborate on the components in the research methodology chapter. Honeycomb model will provide pathway to the researcher to follow the research methods in sequence which will help to include and consider the most appropriate methods for the current research. Other tools, strategies and models are also available and used widely to assist in the research process such as the research onion by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2015), but research onion only explains the typical structure of research which does not show the relationship between the research components.

It is important to understand the linkage between each research component because they are not only in sequence to each other, but they are also inter-related. The honeycomb method is in the shape of a honeycomb which shows the starting point of research from research philosophy (also considered as research paradigm) leading it towards the last step which is data analysis techniques (Wilson, 2013).

Honeycomb of Research consists of six main elements: research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, research design, data collection and data analysis techniques. These steps are non-linear and unlike in research onion, these steps show that the information gathered through them can be used at any step and at any stage.

Source: (Wilson, 2013)

From the above diagram we can see that the first three components of the honeycomb are the most important ones, but we can also see that all of these components are interlinked to form research methodology. Further, the author will discuss all the steps one by one and explain them as well with the rationale for the selection made.

4.2.1 Research Philosophy/Paradigm

The first phase of the research procedure is concerned with selecting the appropriate research philosophy, which will provide the right direction for the research strategy. Research philosophy can be defined as a set of beliefs governing the collection, analysis, and application of research data (Saunders, et al., 2015). Similarly, Guba and Lincoln (1994) describe it as different sets of beliefs that describe how knowledge is acquired (epistemology), how we perceive the world to be (ontology), and how methods will be applied (methodology).

The research paradigm is considered as a lens through which a researcher aligns his research (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Therefore, it is defined as a set of beliefs, values, and practices, including world views, that influence the researcher (Morgan, 2007). Similarly, it is also defined as fundamental belief systems that deal with the first or fundamental principles that represent the researcher's world view. These systems are described in the following order: ontology, epistemology, methodology, and axiology (Guba and Lincoln, 1994).

The current study employs qualitative research methods in exploring the potential and impact of change management models for the successful implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. However, to comprehend the research paradigm and the selection of the appropriate paradigm according to the current study, it is important to better understand the paradigm's components, namely epistemology, ontology, and axiology. The author will be able to choose the appropriate paradigm from positivism, post-positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism by understanding these components.

4.2.1.1 Epistemology

Epistemology represents the assumptions, claims or acquisition of knowledge, that is, how the knowledge is obtained or gathered, and it describes the relationship between the researcher and the data (Kamil, 2011). It also clarifies the objective of epistemology which is the production that is creation or gathering of knowledge and reflection on various knowledge claims about certain phenomenon (Sefotho, 2015).

In terms of Positivism, it explains Objectivity or Quantification; that is, it provides the basis that through experimentation and observation, researchers can reach understanding (Sefotho, 2015). Furthermore, objectivity highlights that the researcher and the reality being researched are independent of each other. Whereas Interpretivism explains Subjectivism/ Constructionism based on different realities which contribute towards multiple world views (Sefotho, 2015). The interviewer and interviewee are interactively linked together to provide constructions which are associated with different realities (Guba and Lincoln, 1994).

In the current study, the research questions laid out the basis for the selection of epistemology. According to the research questions, the study will utilise Interpretivism epistemology stance. It is seen that interpretivism allows to conduct research first and then interpretations form the theory rather than development of hypotheses prior to conducting the research. This will help to explore the management of the implementation of the change in HEIs of Pakistan.

4.2.1.2 Ontology

Ontology represents the nature of reality, or how the researcher perceives the universe from their perspective. It aids the researcher in comprehending how things actually exist and function in the real world (Scotland, 2012). It is based on the researcher's subjectivist and objectivist perspectives. The researcher's perspective should correspond with the sort of research methodology (quantitative or qualitative) employed in the study. Qualitative

research methods make researchers increasingly reliant on discovering and accepting multiple realities. Furthermore, reality is acknowledged to be subjective in character and comprised of different ideas; hence, subjectivist ontology is more likely to be employed in the research (Bahari, 2010; Creswell, 2007). The following is a detailed description of both perspectives.

4.2.1.3 Objectivism

It is predicated mainly on the premise that social phenomena and objects exist independently of social actors or knowers (Bahari, 2010). According to Bryman and Bell (2011), objectivism is grounded in reality, and in order to comprehend it better, we might view it as an organisation. The organisation has clear rules and regulations, as well as standardised procedures. The procedures followed by employees are based on the organisation's mission statement. Therefore, employees and employer(s) in the organisation use these values to comprehend the organisation's aims and conduct their tasks effectively.

It also demonstrates that the sole aim of the objectivist researcher is to obtain the object's reality (Scotland, 2012). It is primarily associated with Positivism, which describes the reality that positivists think facts may be demonstrated through reality because it is observable and quantifiable (Ryan, 2018).

4.2.1.4 Subjectivism/ Constructionism

Subjectivism is the alternative ontological premise in research for objectivism. Subjectivism is also known as social constructionism and constructionism (Saunders, et al., 2015). It demonstrates that social phenomena and their meanings are accomplished by social actors, that is, the world's existence is contingent on knowledge that varies from person to person and is in a constant state of revision (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Constructivism is founded on relativity, which is subjective in nature and varies from person to person in terms of how individuals interpret their understanding of particular social situations (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). It also includes the interaction between the participants and the researchers, as it permits the individuals (that is, the researchers) who are engaging in the study to interpret the participants' understandings and give it significance (Scotland, 2012). It is associated with the concept of Interpretivism, which asserts that relativist or non-positivist realities exist in multiple forms because nothing is "true" in any sensual construction, whereas it is associated with multiple realities that result in changeable constructions due to the participation of the researcher and participants in the research (Guba

and Lincoln, 1994).

4.2.1.5 Axiology

The term axiology often relates to ethical concerns associated with the researcher's perspective on the research. It also covers the evaluation and comprehension of fundamental principles of right and improper conduct in research (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Four pillars support the concept of axiology: teleology, deontology, morality, and fairness. These four pillars indicate that the researcher's outcome will be significant for the community or society, that actions taken during the research process will benefit the community as a whole, that the researcher must uphold the community's moral values, and that the researcher must be fair to all research participants (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017).

It offers the researcher the means to be value-free or biased. Positivists, for instance, are people who observe from the outside, therefore they are more likely to be value-free. In contrast, interpretivists are not value-free since they include their cultural or problem-solving values into data collection and interpretation (Wilson, 2013).

As each portion of the research philosophy section is described, it is preferable to compare the research philosophies or paradigms. It will not only enable the reader to comprehend their functionality, but it will also assist the researcher in choosing the most applicable paradigm for the current study.

4.2.1.2 Rationale for the Selected Paradigm

The thorough explanation of the components indicated in the research philosophy/paradigm section facilitates the researcher's selection of the most applicable paradigm for the current investigation. In the preceding section of the literature review, I addressed prior research in which the implementation of e-learning was explored not just in industrialised nations but also in Pakistan.

Previous studies demonstrate that implementing e-learning and its use in HEIs is affected by overcoming resistance, politics within the organisation, motivation, IT-related skills, literacy of both students and professors, ease of use of the e-learning programmes, and involvement of other stakeholders such as the government, parents, and employers, among others.

It describes the purpose of my research, which is to combine the change management models with stakeholder analysis as a theoretical framework to examine the change processes, investigate any challenges associated with the implementation of e-learning, and make the implementation of e-learning as smooth as possible with the help of this framework.

Through the prior literature, the researcher is also able to investigate difficulties at the organisational, individual level, i.e., student and academic, and larger community levels. At the top-level of management, implementation of e-learning is difficult due to a lack of funds and resources for HEIs. This is because the majority of HEIs are unable to undertake e-learning on their own and require money from the HEC or government to provide platforms and financial support (Farid, et al., 2015).

However, at the individual level, face-to-face instruction is preferred over e-learning among medical and dentistry students, according to a study by Abbasi et al. (2020). Additionally, it becomes more complicated if we add more stakeholders in the research, such as university departments with divergent views on the implementation of e-learning (Kanwal and Rehman, 2014). In addition to this, the prior literature discusses the challenges surrounding a lack of IT skills, such as an unprepared IT department, untrained staff members, and employees who prefer the traditional teaching method. The aforementioned research questions are intended to provide a deeper knowledge of the internal and external factors that influence the perceptions of HEI's stakeholders. Understanding these stakeholder perceptions will provide insight into change management issues, which will ultimately aid the researcher in using the proposed framework.

The complexity of the implementation was determined by the academic literature on change management, including Leavitt's model, Maslow's hierarchy, Kotter's change model, and stakeholder analysis relating to both general scenarios and HEIs. In Pakistan, more quantitative research has been conducted using questionnaires and surveys, but because it focuses more on the objectivity of the problem, it produced ambiguous conclusions because stakeholder analysis has not been properly implemented. To hear the opinions and impact of stakeholders involved with HEIs, it is preferable to do a stakeholder analysis that encompasses multiple realities and the engagement of influential individuals.

In one of the most recent research projects on e-learning in Pakistan, it was shown that gender plays a significant role in the intention to utilise technology and adopt e-learning. The study used quantitative methods to comprehend the link between the variables, demonstrating the positivist paradigm at work (Kanwal, et al., 2020). As the majority of quantitative studies undertaken in Pakistan are not conducive to hearing the unheard voices of academics and other key stakeholders, it is of utmost importance that new methods be developed to communicate with the key stakeholders in order to understand their needs.

The current research philosophy recommends that the relativist ontology, subjectivist epistemology, and balanced axiology will be useful for the current study after examining the necessity of communication with key stakeholders, the lack of qualitative metrics, and conducting stakeholder analysis on a case-study basis. These components are associated with an Interpretivist or Constructivist paradigm. Interpretivist paradigm should be considered because, as stated previously, it enables the researcher to think subjectively and enables the researcher to analyse and create the meaning of the collected data through their own subjective thought processes and cognitive processing of the information gathered from the participants (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017).

Another rationale for choosing interpretivism is that it is vital to consider the experiences of the main stakeholders, which include not just academics, students, and upper management, but also other stakeholders in the HEI setting such as the interview from HEC professional will provide the involvement of regulatory body in the implementation process. Further, the views of the respondents such as teachers, head of departments, administrative managers, and student focus group interviews will provide the perceptions on the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan and this can only be best investigated through qualitative methods (semi-structure interviews) as it will provide in-depth knowledge and views of the respondents. Interpretivism also made me realise that there will be multiple realities that will assist me in comprehending the opinions and perspectives of key stakeholders and ensure the smooth implementation of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs. Furthermore, the exploration of the significant factors can be identified with the of subjectivist nature i.e., asking open-ended questions through semi-structured interviews because then respondents provide additional information related to the implementation and adoption of e-learning in Pakistani HEIs context.

The aforementioned elements indicate that the methodological orientation of the research should be qualitative research consistent with the constructivist paradigm, which will be explained in further detail below.

4.2.2 Research Approach

The second step of the Honeycomb method is to identify and select an appropriate research technique, which determines the research strategy and leads to the study's research design. As is commonly known, there are two types of research methods, namely *inductive* and *deductive*.

4.2.2.1 Deductive Approach

This is the most common approach used to view the relationship between the theory and research which allows the researcher to deduce the hypothesis, test the hypothesis and re-validate the theory (Bryman and Bell, 2011). It starts from the theory which allows the researcher to absorb the general idea leading towards the creation of hypotheses to test them and then reduce them to specific ideas which either verifies the theory or falsify it (Saunders et al., 2016; Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018).

Bryman and Bell (2011) mention the process of deductive approach starting with generalising the theory, creation of hypothesis, data collection to test the hypothesis, analysing the collected data, analyses to confirm the acceptance or rejection of hypothesis and lastly the revision of theory.

4.2.2.2 Inductive approach

The inductive reasoning or inductive approach is defined as the opposite of deductive i.e., theory building approach which starts with the careful observations through interviews to establish generalised theory related to the phenomenon under discussion or proposes or builds a conceptual framework to contribute towards the social sciences (Saunders et al., 2016; Wilson, 2013).

Inductive approach provides the in-depth understanding towards the meanings which are attached to human events because it provides a flexible structure to allow changes as the research progresses. It is also less concerned with the generalisability context of the research i.e., unlike deductive approach, it allows the researcher to explain a generalised concept from the specific concepts (Saunders, et al., 2016). Furthermore, it helps the researcher to understand the human interpretations related to their social involvement around their environment which shows that it does not follow the rigid methodology like deductive approach (Saunders, et al., 2016).

From the above explanation of both approaches, it is evident that in the current study inductive approach will be used as it provides the researcher an open hand to collect the

information from the participants on the basis of their social constructs around the research context. As the researcher will observe the findings and observations from different stakeholders through interviews and focus groups, it will help the researcher to validate the proposed framework for the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan more effectively. The investigation of Qamar et al., (2021) showed important factors while exploring the perceptions of students and teachers related to the use of e-learning in public sector medical higher education institute in Pakistan during covid-19. The study used a mixed method approach however, for qualitative side, inductive research approach was used. It provided beneficial results related to the themes which identified the challenges faced by the teachers and students during covid related to the use of e-learning in Pakistan. This recent study of Qamar et al., (2021) provides basis for the use of inductive approach in the current study as the author will be able get more information from the respondents due to semi-structured and focus group interviews. Furthermore, the current study is not developing hypotheses therefore, inductive approach is the most suitable approach for this type of research. Also, it will help the researcher to collect additional information from the respondents as the interviews are open-ended and the respondents gave their suggestions as well towards the better use and adoption of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan.

4.2.3 Research Strategy

In general, the research plan describes how the research will be conducted and which strategy the researcher will employ to conduct the research (Bryman and Bell, 2011). It gives the researcher a research orientation, aids in the selection of instruments or procedures that are appropriate for the subject and enables the researcher to conduct research.

It is evident from the research approach and paradigm that the researcher will employ the Qualitative Strategy for the current study. The argument for employing this technique is that it will allow the researcher to solicit the opinions of the participants regarding e- learning and its application in Pakistani HEIs. This form of data will also aid the researcher in subjectively reviewing the reality, considering the current theoretical framework based on stakeholder analysis. This is due to the fact that stakeholder analysis will enable the researcher to record the perspectives of all possible stakeholders associated with HEIs, which will not only help to streamline the implementation process in the future, but also provide insights about organisational politics, teacher-student interaction, scarcity or availability of resources, potential employer's reaction, motivation for students, teachers, management, and other stakeholders related to e-learning, etc.

The highly inductive nature of the research methodology that led to the interpretivist or constructivist paradigm is a further justification for choosing qualitative research. In their research, Kivunja and Kuyini (2017) provide the example that if a researcher wants to comprehend the teacher's engagement in the decision-making process in schools, the interpretivist paradigm should be considered. The choice of paradigm also demonstrates that the qualitative research technique is the most appropriate. Furthermore, there are no hypotheses or studies of relationships between variables in the current study, indicating its qualitative nature.

In Qualitative Strategy, the researcher produces a high degree of detail due to the high involvement of the participants in their actual experiences, since it places a greater emphasis on the words than on the quantification of the analysed data (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Due to the greater amount of detail examined in the study, it also permits the researcher to become closely linked with the actual events (Creswell, 2007). The study of Baig, Zaidi, and Alam (2019) confirms with their result that qualitative study enables in-depth simultaneous exploration of students' and teachers' perceptions of using e-learning in Dow Dental College of Pakistan. The study used a similar method of data collection to the current research i.e., semi-structured interviews from 35 respondents and it identified the theme framework by mapping the interviews. The results show that the use of mobile technology in e-learning is very limited as the faculty mostly use computers such as laptops for research and reading articles. Therefore, the study of Baig et al., (2019) supports the notion of utilising qualitative research methods as it will help the researcher to gather more information about the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan.

As the amount of researcher involvement is high, this strategy takes an inductive approach because it gives observational data for in-depth analysis. It also demonstrates a strong relationship between the researcher and the collected data since, unlike the deductive method, the observer's level of involvement in the study is elevated (Williams, 2007).

4.2.4 Research Design

Research design is a process that assists the researcher in achieving their study's research objectives. It is based on a framework or plan that leads the researcher throughout the data collection and analysis phases of the research process (Bryman and Bell, 2011). In addition, it demonstrates that the factor of time or difficulties connected to the time horizon are crucial in selecting an appropriate study design (Wilson, 2013). In addition, there are various sorts of research studies that allow the researcher to select the appropriate research design for their study.

Exploratory Studies vs Explanatory Studies

Explanatory studies are ones in which the researcher establishes relationships between variables so they can comprehend or investigate a situation in order to explain the link between variables in depth (Saunders, et al., 2016). It is based on statistical instruments that assist the researcher in evaluating or explaining the relationship between dependent and independent variables (Benitez, et al., 2020).

In contrast to explanatory studies, exploratory investigations offer the researcher a valuable opportunity to investigate and question participants in order to find and gain insight into the issue of interest. The most significant advantage of this sort of study is that it allows the researcher to be flexible and adaptive during the study period (Saunders, et al., 2016). Causal studies are related to confirmatory and explanatory studies because their primary objective is to establish the relationship between two variables. Consequently, it always involves hypothesised causes, which are independent variable(s), and their association with outcomes, which are dependent variable(s) (Oppewal, 2010).

Exploratory research is necessary when there is insufficient knowledge or data available about the problem's background. It is also ideal for investigations that require information about a specific area to clarify the issues in the study (Burns and Bush, 2000).

Based on the preceding discussion, it is indicated that the appropriate research study for the current investigation would be an exploratory study since it would allow the author to investigate the notion of stakeholders in terms of e-learning implementation in Pakistan's HEIs. Furthermore, with the help of non-probability sampling technique, the researcher can collect, explore and analyse in-depth data with the help of interviews to explore the context of implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. Also, the purposive sampling technique will be employed to gather information-rich data from the head of departments and managers

of the universities. Other crucial stakeholders such as students, HEC (regulatory body) and teachers were also selected to serve the purpose of providing important information about the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan.

With the help of research study, the appropriate research design selected is case study research design. There are different research designs which include narrative, phenomenology, grounded theory etc. However, the appropriate research design is case study because it will allow the researcher to collect more information about the case of implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan as semi-structured interviews will help the researcher to identify the factors and study the potential of change management models with the help of different stakeholders such as teachers, students, administrative managers, and regulatory body.

4.2.4.1 Case Study

There are various research designs accessible for the researcher to adopt and execute in their study. Which research design will be most appropriate for their investigations will depend on their research methodology, research strategy, and research approach.

Case Study research design is one of the research designs. Case study investigates contemporary phenomena when their boundaries are not well defined and is grounded in a real-world context. It offers in-depth knowledge and information regarding particular challenges or problems (Wilson, 2013). The term case denotes the study of an object within a boundary made up of functional elements, such as a workplace or an organisation (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

There are various case study designs based on single or multiple cases, and they may also be categorised based on the type of analysis, such as holistic analysis for a single unit of case study or embedded analysis for multiple units of case study (Wilson, 2013).

Case study design is mainly divided into four categories which are based on two major principles. Those four categories are single holistic, multiple holistic, single embedded, and multiple embedded case studies. The two aspects or principles are the contextual boundary of the research entities and the number of unit analysis (Yin, 2015). When research has only a single unit analysis then it is deemed as holistic however, if there is only one case to analyse single unit, then it will be single holistic and with multiple cases it will know as multiple holistic case study. An embedded case design has more than one unit of analysis which will be known as phenomenon therefore, to analyse the phenomena of single unit will be single

embedded case study design and for multiple cases will be known as multiple embedded case study design (Yin, 2015).

In addition to the single and multiple case study approaches, there are additional justifications for case study design, including idiographic and nomothetic designs. The first is an in-depth analysis of a single unique situation to acquire the maximum level of comprehension possible. The second displays the universal law of behaviour for huge groups that applies to everyone, independent of time or location (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Wilson, 2013).

However, Stake (1995) also advises that researchers should select cases from which they can learn the most. According to Stake (1995), there are three distinct sorts of instances: intrinsic -use to obtain insights about the general particularities of the case; instrumental -use case to comprehend larger issues and question generalisations; and numerous -use collective cases to examine general phenomenon (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

As in the current study, multi-case study will be considered in which five universities have been selected as case sites, all of which are located in the Pakistani province of Punjab and will be represented by multiple case sites. The selection of these cases can be categorized as holistic multiple case study because all the case sites are selected to examine the issue related to manage the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan with the help of stakeholders analysis and change management models. Case study research is commonly used to study, understand, and explore the implementation of technology which is known as phenomenon in higher education specially in the context of Pakistani HEIs. For instance, the studies of Baig et al., (2019), Qamar et al., (2021), Ahmed et al., (2018), and Akram et al., (2021) used case study design to understand the phenomenon of implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. The case study design used in the current study includes the collection of qualitative data with the help of semi-structured interviews at multiple sites, which leads to data-driven analysis for interpreting. This design enables the author to collect qualitative data which helps to determine the profile of respondents and patterns to understand the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. Also, what stakeholders think, communicate, and give opinion about the institutions will help to identify “reality” for them. Therefore, the interviews will provide the basis for understanding and developing the reality which stakeholders refers in their interviews.

The qualitative multiple case study design was used to achieve the aim of this study which is to provide recommendations to HEIs and HEC on implementation of e-learning through

change management models and stakeholder analysis. In order to use case study design, there is the need to identify the phenomenon which is the unit of analysis to analyse through the cases. The current study's phenomenon is the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan, HEC the regulatory body ordered the recognised universities during covid-19 to shift to online platforms to continue the process of learning and teaching without interruption. Considering the purpose of this study (i.e., providing recommendations to HEIs and HEC related to e-learning implementation), the recommendations can be provided by getting information and knowledge from the stakeholders with the help of interviews after the transition phase of implementing e-learning in HEIs amidst the pandemic. It will provide in-depth, rich data from the live experiences of the respondents to describe the phenomena of implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. Also, the research question included the focus on term *how* that Yin (2018) suggested were best answered through qualitative case studies. Further, when investigating a phenomenon that cannot be manipulated, and approaching it without preconceptions or a predetermined truth, the qualitative methodology ensured that participants' perceptions and experiences were heard and included in the findings (Yin, 2018), (Stake, 1995). Furthermore, to fully understand and explore the phenomenon, the findings of the study were explained using the words of the respondents in a meaningful and clear manner which is consistent with the nature of qualitative research. Communicating the problem of the study from true understanding of the implementation process of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan cannot be obtained without asking exploratory, open-ended, semi-structured questions that captured the phenomenon.

The multiple cases for this study includes one public university and four private universities to study the phenomenon of implementation of e-learning in them. The unit of analysis in the current study was the change process and the management of change process, the evolution of stakeholders such as teacher and students from face-to-face to e-learning mode of teaching and learning. Further, the cases of this study are bounded to singular phenomenon which is the implementation of e-learning and providing recommendations to HEIs and HEC therefore, all the cases was bounded by the geographical location of Punjab province in Pakistan. In such instances, the implementation of e-learning will be studied with the help of the framework of the study, stakeholder analysis, which allows the researcher to include potential stakeholders and their perspectives, thereby identifying the internal and external factors effecting the implementation of e-learning. In addition, it will clarify whether or not all five cases have identical outcomes. Especially with the effect of COVID-19, where

distance learning or online learning is being promoted in Pakistan by HEC, it will also help the researcher to capture the effect of this novel virus on the adoption process of e-learning, as HEC requires the recognised universities to conduct online classes on Zoom, Google Classroom, Skype, or Microsoft Teams etc (Higher Education Commission, 2020).

Due to the inclusion of a total of five cases, it is also evident that the study design will be based on holistic multiple case sites, allowing the researcher to assimilate as much information as possible. Case study design enables the researcher to conduct open-ended, semi-structured interviews that illustrate the complexities of a real-world sector of work that is currently being implemented, as participants are able to give their ideas.

As the case study design permits the research to be conducted in close proximity to the research environment in order to enhance natural generalisations based on personal interpretations, it also places the reader in the best position to evaluate the applicability of the research to other situations based on a variety of variables (Kyale, 1996; Stake, 1995).

Although the case study approach has a number of advantages over other research designs, it has been criticised for various concerns, credibility and generalisability of the results being the most prominent. Initially, it was criticised for the generalisation issue that Yin (1984) had identified. It raises concerns about the external validity of the acquired data, as the concept of generalisation implies that the conclusions of case study research can be applied to or generalised to other cases (Alnaim, 2015). The issue of generalisability stems from a simple misunderstanding regarding generalising a case study from a single study or generalising a case. George and Bennett (2004) clarify further that an incident is regarded as a case in the research environment and that the case study is derived from historical explanations. However, Yin (2015) argues that developing analytical generalisations will help in reducing the issue of the research's generalisability. It indicates that, with the help of analytical generalisability, it may be applied not just to similar cases but also to cases of various types in the same circumstances. (Yin, 2015).

Yin (2015) also explicitly describes the research in the teaching field where case studies are used to elucidate major issues in the course. However, they are mixed with the research case study but teaching case studies have a sole pedagogical motive. The research case study should satisfy the research motive rather than pedagogical motive which can be achieved by showing explicitly how data is collected and that it is complete and fair. Overcoming this challenge will produce a *credible* research case study. In order to increase the credibility of

the case study, there are three possible ways which are *creating trustworthiness*-by convincing the readers that data is collected from the fieldwork, *validity*- can be increased by examining core explanation and rival explanations as well; and *reliability*- be increased through triangulation which means that different sources of information provide the same finding which increases the reliability (Yin, 2015).

Subjectivity also presents difficulties in the realm of research since subjectivity might impact the results and trustworthiness of case study research. It can be overcome by considering several sources of information where the researcher has physical engagement, such as conducting interviews or visiting the location physically (Alnaim, 2015).

Moreover, being subjectively involved in case study research allows the researcher to have a comprehensive understanding of the research environment for that particular study. This interaction strengthens the naturalistic generalisation since it enables the reader to learn about additional examples with which they are already familiar (Stake, 1995).

In the current study, the case study method will assist the researcher in constructing naturalistic generalisations about each particular case; as data will be gathered through interviews, respondents will be able to contribute important information applicable to the present and future scenarios. As the education sector is always evolving, current study's results can be utilised in future research with the help of analytical generalisation.

4.2.4.2 Cases Selected

Introduction

In the current study, there are five major universities from Punjab Province of Pakistan. There are some additional interviews also conducted to gather the insights about other institutes, but those interviews are on individual basis therefore, they will be discussed separately as potential stakeholder of the HEIs of Pakistan. The research sites selected in the current study include Lahore Garrison University Lahore, Superior University Lahore, University of Sargodha, University of Lahore, and University of Management and Technology. There is also additional interview from the Head of Department from Beaconhouse National University Lahore, Head of Department of ICT from NUST University Rawalpindi, Professor from Punjab University, Professor from Arfa Technology Park University Lahore, Assistant HR Manager from Allied Bank Lahore, and Advisor Co-ordinator from HEC Islamabad.

Lahore Garrison University (Private) (LGU)

The first case to be presented in this current research is Lahore Garrison University (LGU). LGU is a Private Institute which is based in Lahore city, Punjab Province of Pakistan. LGU was founded in 2010 and within short span of time, LGU has increased the programs/ degrees offered to the Pakistani Students. It has a purpose-built campus which includes necessary labs, equipment, and library to cater to the needs of the students (Lahore Garrison University, 2021).

LGU has embedded in its core values that they want to contribute towards the community by providing the latest educational modes through innovation and research. Innovation and research are two main components on which LGU is focusing to produce entrepreneurial leaders (Lahore Garrison University, 2021). As it is a private institute therefore, it requires a Charter from the Provincial Government to allow the HEI to award degrees in different disciplines. For each level of studies i.e., Undergraduate, post-graduate, and MS/MPhil/ PhD programs, it requires different requirements set by HEC to allow the institute to continue their process of teaching and awarding degrees in the respected discipline. LGU is HEC recognised institute, according to EduRank, LGU stands at 86th position in national university ranking level and at 3277th position in Asia (EduRank, 2021).

At the current level, in LGU there are 5780 students with 400 Faculty members and offering 2000 courses at one single campus in Lahore (Lahore Garrison University, 2021). With the introduction of National Qualifications Framework of Pakistan by HEC in 2009, it provides Qualification framework for the public and private institutes in Pakistan from school level to higher education level. It is also managed by HEC, and the latest framework report was published in 2015. The National Qualifications Framework by HEC requires HEIs to have connectivity and computers as standard resources to implement framework. Therefore, e-learning methods were already being used by Lahore Garrison University. However, there are various e-learning modes available to use and implement, therefore, the findings from the data collection of this case will shed light upon the use and adoption of e-learning methods across the university. In terms of decision-making approach, the broader level of decisions such as conducting online exams, implementation of online learning activities in a traditional learning style university requires the approval from HEC. For instance, in the wake of global pandemic, HEC asked the universities to go online for the continuance of learning and teaching operations in universities. Lastly, the interviews conducted in Lahore Garrison University were from three currently working Professors, one Head of Department and a

Focus group interview consisting of three students from bachelor's degree.

University of Sargodha (Public) (UOS)

The second case in this research is related to the public sector and one of the renowned public universities in Punjab province. The University of Sargodha (UOS) is based in the city of Sargodha, Punjab province. The educational journey started in 1929 where it was first known as De'Montmorency College which was later renamed as Government College and further later it was awarded the University Charter in 2002 (University of Sargodha, 2021).

The university has currently 24000 students, 800 faculty member including visiting and other faculty members which also includes 300 PhDs and 1200 administrative staff members which is combined with the availability of well-resourced classrooms, laboratories and extensive collection of online resources along-with FM radio channel to provide infotainment and educational seminars and classes to the students (University of Sargodha, 2021).

In terms of global rankings, UOS has ranked among 401+ young universities in Times Higher Education 2020, 500+ in Emerging Economies rankings, 1000+ in World University rankings and 401-450 Asian University in the QS World University Rankings 2019-2020 (University of Sargodha, 2021). However, the proper e-learning measures were used in the institute during the pandemic such as the use of online classes and MOODLE.

Furthermore, productive research and creative learning is embedded in the vision of the university which allowed the university to overcome the challenge of sudden implementation of e-learning during Covid-19. The university management also offers different online webinars and seminars through zoom related to psychological services to cope with the difficult time of covid-19 (University of Sargodha, 2020). University also has different centres which provide different facilities to staff and students both to accommodate them related to scholarships, studies, and other day to day matters.

In this case, the total number of interviews conducted were three which includes Registrar, HOD and Senior Teacher from Business Management Department (all three were male respondents) and one Student Focus group interview. The student focus group interview includes four interviewees in which three of them were male and one of them was female student.

University of Lahore (Private) (UOL)

The third case used in this research is University of Lahore which was established in 1999 and currently have seven different campuses on national level in Pakistan. It is one of the well-known private universities which was awarded W4 category award from HEC which represents the quality and high ranking of the university. The courses offered in this institute are in the fields of social sciences, Arts, Sciences, Engineering, Medical and Dentistry (University of Lahore, 2021).

Currently, there are around 35000 students enrolled in seven campuses with eleven faculties and 35 departments. It has state of the art campus which includes well-equipped labs for engineering and medical students. In terms of ranking, it stood at 401-600th Impact rankings in 2021, 1001+ world university ranking in 2019, Young university rankings 251-300th in 2019, and on national level it is among top 5 universities in Pakistan (University of Lahore, 2021a), (Times Higher Education, 2021).

Further, there are 1535 faculty members in seven different campuses offering 3500+ courses along-with 200+ degree programs. UOL also has two dedicated research centres which help the university to accomplish their research mission. UOL's vision includes innovation related to education, creativity, research, and entrepreneur due to that they implemented e- learning systems during covid-19 and continued the valued process of online classes (University of Lahore, 2021b), (University of Lahore, 2021c).

UOL is also recognised from HEC and other accreditation bodies such as Pakistan Medical and Dental Council, Pakistan Engineering Council, National Business Education Accreditation Council etc., which helps the academic managers to maintain the quality of the courses offered at different campuses (University of Lahore, 2021d). The semi-structured interviews include the different viewpoints of different internal stakeholders, mainly, the Head of Department, three teachers and a focus group consisting of three current students.

University of Management & Technology (Private) (UMT)

University of Management & Technology was initially established as Institute of Leadership and Management in 1990 as a private institute in Lahore, Pakistan. UMT then progressed quickly towards getting the university charter status by the government of Punjab, Pakistan in 2004. Currently, UMT has strong connections around the globe including famous institutes from different parts of the world (UMT, 2021).

In terms of ranking, UMT is ranked currently in W4 category of HEC which is the highest

ranking of the universities. The university is placed at 601-800th in impact rankings 2021 and named in top 500 ranking in QS Asia university rankings 2021 (UMT, 2021) (Times Higher Education, 2021). Currently there are 25000+ students, 700+ faculty members in which more than 220 are PhD faculty members (UMT, 2021a). Furthermore, UMT is working with the vision of Learning and the mission of Leading which results in a society where stakeholders are partnered through strategic partnerships (UMT, 2021b).

The data is collected from respondents at three different levels i.e., one from Management department's Head (male), two professors from the same department (both are male), and a student focus group which comprises of three female students who are enrolled in MPhil programs at UMT.

Superior University (Private) (SU)

Superior university started as The Superior College in 2002 in the metropolis of Lahore, Punjab. With the exceptional growth and quality education, Superior College achieved recognition from provincial government related to the NOC and also it was awarded the status the degree awarding institute. With the continued hard work, in 2008 Superior College inaugurated their first purpose-built university campus in Lahore (Nusrat, 2020).

Currently there are 509 faculty members in which 65 of them are PhD faculty members. There are also 10 international visiting faculty members along-with 100 international connections and 55 international exchange programs which include split-degree programs through which the students can study half of their courses in the partner international universities. Currently there are 8,484 students enrolled in the university campus. The students enrolled in other campuses across Pakistan is different (Superior University, 2021).

Superior University has also initiated new degree courses such as 3U1M which includes three years of study and 1 year of practical experience in the market. It is a unique way as well to enhance the employability capabilities of their graduates (Superior University, 2021a). The current rankings of Superior University are 16th in Lahore, 8043rd in the world and 78th in overall Pakistan (EduRank, 2021).

In this case, the researcher has conducted different interviews with different persons. There are three interviews conducted from the teachers, one from the HOD, one from Director of Breeo International (Split-degree and Office for visas), and one interview from Manager of examination department. However, the student focus group interview was unable to arrange with this university therefore, it has not been conducted.

4.2.4.3 Factors for Case Study Selection

Five universities will be evaluated for their implementation of e-learning, and each will be considered as a separate case study. Initially, the availability of respondents is the most essential factor in determining which university will serve as the case study. In the province of Punjab in Pakistan, there are both public and private universities, but the pandemic has made it difficult to reach respondents for face-to-face interviews.

The universities were selected on the basis of their recognition status from HEC, implementation of e-learning in them, and the geographical location i.e., (city of Lahore) in Pakistan. Also, the category of institutes was considered i.e., W category institutes from HEC which is the highest ranking of HEIs in Pakistan. The primary criterion for selecting universities will be the institution's geographical location. Each city in the province of Punjab is home to a renowned university based on reputation due to good word-of-mouth and employer demand. However, the researcher will initially select examples from the city of Lahore and one from Sargodha city in Pakistan with prestigious universities.

Given that the identified stakeholders are specified in section 4.6.3, it will be evident which stakeholders may be questioned. Due to time constraints, only a limited number of interviews were conducted.

4.2.4.4 Testing Research Quality

With the selection of research design, it is of immense importance that the research should produce good quality results. It is based on two major components: reliability and validity.

Reliability- This is a process which shows constant and stable results of the measurements taken during the research process. It is more highly involved in quantitative measures but in terms of qualitative studies, the results can be checked or matched with other similar studies (Wilson, 2013).

Validity- Internal and external validity determine the research's validity. Internal validity describes the content and structure, which explains that the measures used to comprehend each instance should encompass all important areas, i.e., they should not be limited to a single area. For example, if a company's performance is being evaluated, sales, market share, and customer feedback should be considered in addition to profits. Similarly, if there are any translations included in the research as a result of bilingual research, they must be validated and examined to ensure the face validity of the questionnaires or interview sheets.

4.2.5 Data Collection

In the previous sections of Chapter 4 we have reviewed the research paradigm, methodology, approach, strategy, and design to put the research on the right track. This section will represent the data collection and the methods of collecting data which will be utilised by the researcher.

Initially we start with defining the term **Data**- it represents the information collected in terms of facts, suggestions, and statistics to process and analyse for the purpose of research (Saunders, et al., 2016). There are two main types of data which represent the data set in the research: **Primary and Secondary** data. **Primary data** is the first-hand data which is collected by the researcher himself only for the sole purpose to serve his own study, whereas **Secondary data** is that which is already published and is readily available to the researcher from various sources such as journal articles, books, graphs, published news etc. (Wilson, 2013).

Due to the qualitative research design, primary data is the most essential sort of data for the current study. Although Stake (1995) states that qualitative researchers need specialised knowledge to analyse data, this knowledge is only acquired through privilege and obligation. Privilege refers to focusing on the most important aspects of data, whereas obligation refers to selecting relevant options after consulting with mentors or colleagues (Stake, 1995, pg 50).

As the data is initially acquired using the Primary data approach, this study employs two distinct data gathering methods. Interviews and focus groups are included. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, online questionnaires will be supplied to respondents in lieu of interviews or focus groups if they are unwilling to participate in interviews or focus groups for the purposes of this study. Following table 4a represents the demographics of the respondents:

Table 4a

University (Case)	Position Interviewed	Experience	Gender	Mode
Lahore Garrison University	Head of Department	9 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor	9 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor	7 Years	Female	Interview
	Professor	4 Years	Female	Interview
	I.T. Department Manager	4 Years	Male	Interview
	3 Students from BBA degree Last year	Final Year Students	All Male	Focus Group
University of Sargodha	Head of Department	7 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor	5 Years	Male	Interview
	Registrar	9 Years	Male	Interview
	4 Students from bachelor's degree	Final Year Students	3 Male 1 Female	Focus Group
University of Management & Technology	Head of Department	10 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor	10 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor	10 Years	Male	Interview
	3 Students from Professional MPhil degree Students	Final Year Students	All Female	Student Focus Group
University of Lahore	Head of Department	5 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor	10 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor	1.5 Years	Female	Interview
	Professor	2 Years	Female	Interview
	3 Students from bachelor's degree	Final Year Students	2 Female and 1 Male	Student Focus Group
Superior University	Head of Department	7 Years	Male	Interview
	Business Development Manager	20 Years	Male	Interview
	Examinations Controller	9 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor	14 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor	12 Years	Male	Interview
	Professor and Administrative Manager	14 Years	Male	Interview
Other Interviewees				
HEC (regulatory body)	Advisor to Director	5 Years	Male	Interview
NUST University	Professor and Director of Research	5 Years	Male	Interview

Beaconhouse National University	Head of Department	2 Years	Male	Interview
Arfa Technology University	Professor	4 Years	Male	Interview
Allied Bank	Talent Acquisition Manager	4 Years	Male	Interview
Punjab University	Professor and Motivational Speaker	6 Years	Male	Interview

The above table shows that a total of 41 respondents were interviewed, including the students from the student focus group. It also shows the years of experience each respondent have which provides the basis for gathering valuable and relevant data from the respondents related to the implementation of e-learning. It also shed light upon the significant internal and external factors which affect the perceptions of the stakeholders towards the implementation process and to adopt the change.

4.2.5.1 Interviews

In qualitative research, interviews are regarded to be the most prevalent form of data collection. Particularly in case study research designs, interviews are crucial because they allow the researcher to obtain insight into the beliefs and attitudes of the participants towards the topic under examination (Saunders, et al., 2016). In-depth interviews give the researcher the opportunity to glean as many details from the respondent as possible. Interviews offer a number of advantages over other data collection methods. There are three distinct interview formats, structured, unstructured, and semi-structured (Wilson, 2013).

In the present study, semi-structured interviews will be conducted because the chosen research design and method deem them to be the most practicable. This is because semi-structured interviews enable the researcher to ask the same questions in a different order and collect more data on the same issue. Additionally, inductive methods and exploratory research benefit from in-depth interviews for context understanding (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

In this study, the author considered interviews conducted using teleconferencing systems such as Zoom and Skype, telephone interviews, and focus groups (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Telephonic, or electronic interviews using Skype or video conferencing are low-cost options for a semi-structured approach because they require fewer resources to conduct. Due to the risks associated with COVID-19, travel may not be the best option for data collection, and

participants may not feel comfortable delivering face-to-face interviews, thus telephonic or online interviews was scheduled based on their availability and practicability.

Identical criteria will also apply to the focus group interviews and they were conducted via online medium such as zoom and skype; these focus groups are referred as online focus groups. An example of an online focus group is provided by Stewart et al. (1998), whose research included geographically distributed online focus groups in which members contributed from various locations (Stewart and Williams, 2005). In light of the global pandemic, the online focus group facility will be utilised.

However, the selection of interviewers will be critical, as internal stakeholder interviewees will supply vital information based purely on their influence and interest in the university. As the stakeholders are divided into internal and external groups, the interviews will be chosen from the internal and external groups' top line managers. As the sampling technique explored in this research is purposive sampling for individual interviews, which will be detailed in a separate section of this chapter, the precise selection will depend on the top leaders who will help to launch the implementation or promotion of such a trend at the university. It will also be kept in mind that there will be a group of individuals who are resistant to adoption; hence, these managers and employees will also play a crucial role in this study.

The interviews are also constructed differently for various stakeholders, based entirely on their participation in the implementation of e-learning. As it has also been observed that case study research rarely advances in the proper direction by asking each respondent the same questions (Stake, 1995), multiple interview sheets are developed to address this issue and collect as much meaningful information as possible.

4.2.5.2 Other Data Collection Methods

In qualitative analysis, there are other methods for collecting data, such as observational data, documentation, and artefacts (Polkinghorne, 2005). It is also observed that field notes are a significant piece of data collection that, when combined with qualitative data gathering, enhance the depth of qualitative findings (Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018). Therefore, the researcher in the current study will additionally apply other data collection techniques that will increase the credibility of the research and the number of available data sources.

Observational data- Observation is a sort of data in which the respondent and the researcher are directly linked, i.e., they are practically in the same location, allowing the researcher to see the environment, behaviour, and qualities of the area or object (Polkinghorne, 2005).

Patton (1987) argues that the abilities, experience, and competence of the researcher have a substantial impact on the quality of observational data. It indicates that if the researcher is skilled and experienced, it will enhance the research's credibility by contributing to the clarification of the interviews (Polkinghorne, 2005).

However, while performing observational research, there are two distinct methods for collecting observational data: disguised and undisguised observation. In the first category, the research subjects are unaware that they are being observed for scientific purposes, and they are observed in their natural environments. In the second alternative, the objects' observations are known, and it is possible that their reactions will differ. However, with the first alternative, there is an ethical concern that could also undermine the research's credibility (Wilson, 2013).

4.2.5.3 Collecting Primary Data

Both categories for gathering primary data have been described previously. The number of in-depth interviews will be determined by previous studies, such as at the UK's Anglia Ruskin University Cambridge, where five interviews were conducted, Queen Mary University of London, UK, where ten interviews were conducted, and Superior Polytechnic School of University of Alicante (Spain), where twelve interviews were conducted. Furthermore, Baker and Edwards (2012) mentioned in their review paper that twelve interviews will be suffice in thematic analysis (pg 21). Therefore 23 interviews will be considered by the researcher in the current study. Similarly, five focus groups were performed at the University of Alicante, Spain, and two at the University of Salamanca, Spain; hence, four focus groups will be evaluated (Lasakova et al., 2017).

Although the primary data will be obtained from the selected stakeholders and dependent on the availability of the stakeholders for interviews, the primary data will be acquired from the designated stakeholders. Internal and external sources are used to identify the stakeholders, who are then categorised into Primary and Secondary stakeholders according to their responsibilities, importance, and contribution to the HEIs of Pakistan. Table 4.2 below lists the identified stakeholders based on prior studies and literature review.

Table 4.2 Internal and External Stakeholders Identified

INTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS	EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS
<p><i>Primary-</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students, sub divided into current, alumni or prospective students. (In some universities there may be international students due to student exchange programs). • Teachers or Professors, sub-divided into full time teachers and part time or visiting faculty members. In full-time teachers they are again mentioned according to their experience, level of education and position in the university. Same process has been taken into consideration for the part-time faculty member but visiting faculty members will be considered on the basis of their experience and level of education. • Higher Management that is the higher management board which includes VC, Chancellor, HODs who will approve the ruling or decision made in their meetings. • Parents. As they are the ones who will be providing funds for the education. • Other academic staff members. (library) • (Dept. of HR, ICT & RND) <p><i>Secondary-</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assistant Professors. • Student Unions- those which are managed inside the university premises. • Non-academic staff members. • Administration apart from higher executives. • (Interviewing stakeholders in person some of them depending on their contribution towards e-learning, political power, power of their positions inside the organisation) 	<p><i>Primary-</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HEC (Government Body) • NGOs, funding private universities. (Owners of the organisation) • Examination Board authorities. • Department of Education • Department of Innovation and Technology. • Training institutes for teachers or management. <p><i>Secondary-</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tuition Centres • Private/ home based/ local institutions facilitating small number of students. • Supplier of Technology. • Trade unions related with teachers & student unions.

Source: Originated by the researcher

4.2.5.4 Secondary Data

Secondary data will be collected when it is required, and it will be collected through reliable sources. The main concern while collecting this data will be the validity and reliability of the sources. Therefore, the sources from which the data will be generated will be from authorised and reliable journal articles, e-book and books related to academic knowledge and statistical data from government publications e.g., HEC website to gather policy documents related to COVID-19 policies for the HEIs.

4.2.5.5 Documentation

The documentation consists of several types of documents associated with the research or the cases utilised for the investigation. Bryman and Bell (2011) suggested that memos, autobiographies, internal reports, policy schedules, and letters might be used as sources for documentation. In the current study, the policy booklets of the HEC are used to assess the extent of e-learning tool adoption guidance they offered to HEIs during the pandemic. Therefore, organisational documents, such as press releases, annual reports, mission statements, public relations materials, and policy documents for stakeholders, will be utilised (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Nonetheless, Bryman and Bell (2011) note that accessing the records will be challenging; so, the researcher must rely solely on documents in the public domain. In the present study, the HEC's website will be utilised to collect policy guidelines for stakeholders on the implementation and utilisation of e-learning tools for online classes and assessment. The following Table 4.1 lists the sources used for this study.

Table 4.1 Policy Documents HEC

Type of Document	Explanation
Covid-19 guidance No 2	Guidelines for faculty and management of HEIs related to the use of LMS or MOODLE and video conferencing tools.
Covid-19 Guidance No 3	Technology Support Committee was introduced to help the management of HEIs in the adoption of e-resources. Includes which software HEIs consider using and their annual subscription fees.
Covid-19 Guidance No 5	The online readiness of the HEIs were mentioned
Covid-19 Guidance No 6	Guidance related to the assessment and procedures and methods for online examination were included

4.2.5.6 Interview Procedures

After receiving approval for the interview sheets from the supervisor, the first step in the current study will be to obtain ethical approval from the UWS ethics committee, which will take approximately two weeks. The ethical approval also includes the committee's comments regarding the use and protection of interview data. Meanwhile, the researcher addressed emails to universities in Pakistan's Punjab province, the study area, requesting permission to conduct interviews with teachers, students, and a management representative, who are considered prospective stakeholders. Appendix 3 presents the ethical approval document, and Appendix 4 contains the interview sheets.

The data collection was delayed until April 2021 because the researcher tested positive for COVID-19 in January 2021, which disturbed and delayed the data gathering. Due to the pandemic, the teachers, administration, and students were overburdened, resulting in delayed responses to interview requests. Additionally, an HEC official delayed the interview by three weeks due to his COVID-19 infection. Due to the pandemic and the unavailability of the students, the student focus group interview was not completed in one of the cases involving Superior University.

The purpose of the interviews was to collect first-hand information about the knowledge of e-

learning, the use of e-resources, the implementation of e-learning during and before the pandemic, any strategies used by the management to assist faculty and students, such as trainings or motivation, and the role of the HEC in the implementation of e-learning.

The current study focuses on how HEIs manage change (implementation of e-learning); therefore, interviewees were provided with a consent form and participation sheet that included a brief introduction to the research and its purpose, allowing them to provide key information for the study.

The interviews began with a paragraph informing the interviewee of their rights and that the interview would be recorded. As stated previously, the interviewer encountered some difficulty in scheduling the interviews on time, which slowed down the gathering of data. However, due to the increasing workload of the teachers and students, they gave limited time for the interviews. The average duration of an interview was between 25 - 35 minutes, and the average duration of focus group interviews was 40 minutes.

4.2.5.7 Sample

There are different sampling techniques used in different studies based on the relevance of the study. Using a random sampling technique, a large number of samples were gathered from the population in quantitative studies. Random sampling or probability sampling is a sampling strategy in which each respondent has an equal chance of being selected for the study (Wilson, 2013). Non-probability sampling, on the other hand, employs subjective methods to pick samples, meaning that respondents do not have an equal chance of being selected (Etikan et al., 2016).

In this study, non-probability sampling was employed to collect data and semi-structured interviews were conducted with respondents. In non-probability sampling, the probability of the sample selected is unknown; hence, the study is biased (Acharya et al., 2013).

In addition, the current study adopted the approach of purposive sampling, which serves the purpose to answer the research question therefore the respondents from the cases selected based on their level of interest and power and it will verify the attainment of the research objectives (Saunders et al., 2015). Patton (2015) emphasised the importance of studying information-rich examples to provide a thorough understanding of the case scenarios. Furthermore, diversification of the respondents was also considered because participants selected were on the basis of their age, experience, and gender. Interviewees were selected on the basis of providing the most appropriate and rich information on e-learning and its

implementation.

The cases were selected through a process which includes identifying W4 category (W4 is the highest-ranking category of universities in Pakistan) universities in Punjab through the HEC's website. Emails were sent to the Vice Chancellors of the HEIs on the basis of the W4 category which includes Private and Public universities and represents the highest level of HEIs in Pakistan. Emails included the request to conduct interviews by specifying the needs of the study such as an interview from one Head of Department or Dean, two to three teachers from the same or different departments and a student focus group interview. As registrars were also asked to be interviewed, however, only one public university registrar was interviewed and from the private sector other employees from management were interviewed, such as IT department manager, examination controller, and business development manager. Further, a bank's HR assistant manager and three other teachers from different universities were also interviewed to obtain rich information about the topic of this study.

Regarding the student focus group, the snowball sampling technique was used because, when teachers were interviewed, they were asked if they could provide students who used e-learning techniques in their learning, and then students were asked if they could ask their classmates to participate.

4.2.6 Triangulation

Triangulation refers to the utilisation of multiple sources of data collecting to raise the reliability of the data collected (Bryman and Bell, 2011). In this study, the application of thematic analysis alongside the documentation of the HEC's policies and guidelines throughout the pandemic, which was officially published on their website, was examined in order to produce more accurate analytical results (Muzari, et al., 2022).

4.2.7 Transcription

The current study focuses on data collection in Pakistan, where the first language is Urdu; nevertheless, the majority of interviews were conducted in English to facilitate interview transcription. The interviews with student focus groups were conducted in both English and Urdu because the student population in Pakistan consists of both rural and urban students, resulting in a lower overall level of English proficiency. Due to the issue of English language proficiency, the transcription of the student focus group was carried out manually by listening to the audio recordings of the files, and interviews with university staff and registrar were

also conducted in Urdu. In addition, the remaining interviews were transcribed using Microsoft Word's Dictate service, which allows users to upload an audio file and generate a transcription of the audio file. However, the audio files were listened to again and compared to the transcribed files to eliminate any transcription problems caused by the pronunciation of the words.

4.2.8 Data Analysis Techniques

In qualitative analysis, researchers employ a variety of analysis methodologies, the most common of which is thematic analysis to explore the environment through case study design. Thematic analysis is considered in relation to qualitative analysis as a basic method (Braun and Clarke, 2006). It is used to identify codes and themes that appear across the data, such as in interviews (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

The current study employs thematic analysis because it will provide a credible, realistic, and impartial comprehension of the data (Boyatzis, 1998). Thematic analysis is useful for managing huge data sets by summarising significant characteristics with the help of themes and codes to generate unexpected insights (Nowell et al., 2017). With the help of a systematic or structured approach, the raw data including a variety of responses from respondents can be turned into explanations that are relevant.

In Chapter 5, the researcher has therefore selected potential themes at various stakeholder levels. There are two primary methodologies used in thematic analysis to find and construct topics for research in order to determine the themes. Inductive and deductive approaches are mentioned as the two approaches. The *inductive* approach is employed in grounded theory, where themes are created from data acquired by the researcher through interviews or other means, whereas the *deductive* approach employs a pre-existing framework and is based on prior research (Kiger and Varpio, 2020). Furthermore, inductive thematic analysis also refers to coding style, whereas deductive thematic analysis refers to assigning a word or phrase to the interviewees' data relevant to the topic based on the participant's own language (Xu and Zammit, 2020).

In the present study, the raw data was obtained from five distinct cases, 21 individual semi-structured interviews, and four focus group interviews including useful information. The study also contains one interview with an external stakeholder, HEC staff, as well as four more interviews, one with a bank (talent acquisition manager) and three with educators from different institutions. However, additional interviews were not analysed for this particular

study. With the use of a systematic approach to thematic analysis, the data will be transformed into meaningful themes using an inductive method of theme formation (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The researcher organised the acquired data by creating separate files for each case before beginning the translation and transcription process. As mentioned previously in the data transcription section 4.2.7, some of the interviews were conducted in Urdu or in a mix of English and Urdu; therefore, the researcher transcribed and translated all the interviews into English for the purpose of conducting analysis and understanding the interviews through NVivo. In order to simplify the explanation and analysis of the data set in NVivo, the interviews were further categorised according to hierarchical levels such as registrar, heads of departments, professors, and students. The researcher conducted a basic thematic analysis using NVivo software by categorising codes and themes within the software. Appendix 1A includes the codebook from NVivo which shows the initial codes at the beginning of the thematic analysis process and the themes generated with the help of initial codes.

The researcher reads the obtained data to familiarise himself with the data's contents, which helped in connecting the collected data to the research questions and objectives, so achieving the purpose of the current study. After the initial phase of acquainting himself with the data, the researcher began a literature review to further his comprehension of the emerging themes. The researcher highlighted significant material in the transcripts to generate codes in NVivo pertaining to the usage of e-learning, implementation of e-learning, problems and benefits of e-learning, the reaction of stakeholders to the change, and how the administration and management managed the change.

With the help of initial codes obtained from the interviews, the researcher compared these codes to the study's objectives in order to get to the point of developing significant themes for the study.

The researcher used a separate notebook to record the initial themes that can be related to the research objectives and questions, and then revisited the interview sheets to improve them. The themes were then identified independently for each stakeholder, primarily as internal and external stakeholder themes, e.g., teachers, management, and students each had their own themes. These themes were then utilised to describe the data collected as Chapter 5's findings. Some of the themes had subthemes because they were broader, enabling the researcher to assess the data at all levels. Each theme is also accompanied by a brief

introduction containing information about it and what to expect from it.

As this is the first time the researcher has performed completely qualitative research, the procedure of qualitative data analysis was time consuming; consequently, thematic analysis was chosen to capture and analyse the raw data on a broader level. The findings chapter, which is Chapter 5, contains the themes for which the researcher used quotations from the collected data to demonstrate the originality of the data highlighting the function of change management in e-learning implementation.

4.3. Summary

This chapter describes the research methodologies employed in the current study and how they will fulfil the study's objectives. Explaining the step-by-step procedure of research methodology, the honeycomb method was utilised. The researcher explained and justified the use of researcher philosophy (interpretivism), research approach (inductive), research strategy (qualitative research), research design (case study research), data collection (primary methods based on interviews, focus groups, and documentation), and data analysis techniques (interviews, focus groups, and documentation) (that is thematic analysis). Using semi-structured and open-ended interview questions, the researcher was able to obtain as much information as possible regarding the implementation of e-learning and the role of change management in HEIs of Pakistan. In addition, the ethical considerations were presented with the consent form and participant information sheet, which are shown in Appendices 3 and 4, respectively. The following chapter is devoted to the findings, which are based exclusively on the responses of the respondents to the interview questions.

CHAPTER 5 Findings

5.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, the researcher explained the approaches towards managing change in devolved organisation such as HEIs. Furthermore, the theoretical framework (Chapter 3) includes the utilisation of three different change management models along with stakeholder analysis which will give the reader a better understanding about the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. In this chapter, the author will share the viewpoints of the interviewees related to the use, implementation, and adoption of e-learning before and during COVID-19. When this research was initiated and the proposal was approved, at that time, the concept and use of e-learning was vague in Pakistan. As Pakistan, is a developing nation, therefore, with the issue of the pandemic and with the directions of the government authorities to enforce lockdown nationwide, the HEIs' operations were brought to a halt. Due to this reason, the HEC, the regulatory body in Pakistan, directed the HEIs to conduct online classes and where possible to conduct online examinations too. Still, the objective of this research was related to the stakeholders of HEIs, that is, to observe the change management process and strategies used in HEIs, to understand about the internal and external factors facilitating the adoption of e-learning, and, to recommend any guidelines considered by the HEIs related to the change management approach through the lens of stakeholder analysis.

In order to understand the introduction and adoption of e-learning in the HEIs of Pakistan, the author considered two main approaches towards the governance of the universities. These approaches helped to identify the themes related to the research context. There are two well-known university governance models referred to by the scholars, namely the Collegial and Managerial models/approaches (Nybom, 2008). In ***Collegial Approach***, there is a high level of staff autonomy, and the decision-making approach goes from bottom-up. It was popular in the 1970s with academics and its authority is based on the virtue of collective agreement. The main challenge in this type of approach is that there is a lack of flexibility related to the challenges of the external environment such as external stakeholders. Whereas, in ***Managerial Approach***, the top-down approach is used which results in less autonomy to the academics and it reduces their participation in the decision-making process (Mueed, 2016). However, most of the universities of Pakistan are currently considering a managerial approach because it provides an authoritarian style of leadership in the system. Furthermore,

it is also seen that the involvement and influence of owners of the institute weakens the managerial system although the private sector universities in Pakistan have more experienced managers because they mostly hire retired personnel from different disciplines (such as army or other industries) who have better managerial experience as compared to public universities (Khan et al., 2018; Mazhar and Akhtar, 2016).

In the next section, the author will explain the emergent themes related to the current study. It will also shed light on the process of identification of themes i.e., how themes were generated in the current study. The themes are identified on the basis of research questions, interview sheets and the stakeholders who have been interviewed. The research sites have been mentioned in section 4.2.4.2 above. From sections 5.3 to 5.4.5, findings based on the identified themes are mentioned along with the quotes from the interviewees of internal stakeholders that is faculty, students, and managerial staff. In section 5.5, the interview from HEC personnel will shed light on the findings deduced from the themes identified for external stakeholders. Section 5.9 represents the documental analysis which shed light upon the policies, rules, and guidelines shared by the HEC during the pandemic for the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. In the last section, the summary of the current chapter will present the overview of the chapter.

5.2 Emergent Themes

The current study considered thematic analysis which includes two types of thematic analysis approach namely: *inductive* and *deductive*. The inductive approach is used where the themes are derived from researcher's data collected through interviews or other forms whereas, the deductive approach utilise pre-existing framework and is based on pre-existing research (Kiger and Varpio, 2020).

Therefore, the current study considered an inductive approach and identified the themes through the collected data, research questions and interview sheets of the participants to gather understanding about the rich and complex collected data.

NVivo was used to analyse the data, therefore the transcript files from the interviews and focus groups were uploaded to NVivo. Initially 74 codes were created on NVivo which includes the subcategories as well as the main codes. Those codes were used in the process of coding where all files were linked to them. The codes provided the basis for the sub-themes as they were used to create the sub-themes which were clustered to provide meaningful themes of the study. Following two tables i.e., Table 5a and 5b will shed light on the use of

the nodes(codes) which were used to create each sub-theme and main theme of the study.

Also, the full list of nodes and themes generated from nodes are given in Appendix 1A

Table 5a Internal Stakeholders Thematic Table:

THEME	SUB-THEME	NODES
Change Management Process/Models	Changing Nature of Academic Teaching (Teachers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional Pedagogy • Types of e-Learning (Includes 16 nodes including Teaching Methods) • Plagiarism • Learning vs Knowledge vs Skills • Pandemic • Centralised Platform (MOODLE)
	Training & Motivational Strategies (HOD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff Readiness • Trainings • Technological Literacy • Centralised Platform (MOODLE) • Non-Monetary Motivation
	Training & Motivational Factors (Students)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological Literacy • Question Bank • Student Engagement • Motivated Teachers • E-Learning Benefits • Hybrid Classes • Use of MOODLE • Software • Teaching Methods
	Training & Motivational Factors (Registrar UOS, IT Manager LGU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-Monetary Motivation • Trainings • Acceptance of Change • Motivated Teachers • Technological Literacy • Multimedia use • Use of MOODLE • HEC • LMS System • Internal Factors

	Changing Nature of Academic Teaching, Resources & Training, and Motivational Factors (BDM & EC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LMS System • MOODLE • Online Database • Online Examination • Teaching Methods • Weak Infrastructure • Internet Issues • Connectivity Issues • Communication and Interaction
THEME	SUB-THEME	NODES
Stakeholders' Perception	Factors Compromising Learning Process (Teachers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electricity Issues • Cultural Issues • Online Examination • Online Invigilation • Communication and Interaction • Geographical Impact • Resistance to Change • Technological Literacy
	Perceived Potential Benefits from the use of e-learning & Resources (HOD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational Change • Use of MOODLE • Weak Infrastructure • Internet Issues • LMS System • Hybrid Classes • MOODLE • 2017 ERP System • Communication and Interaction • Trainings • Learning vs Knowledge vs Skills
	E-learning Issues and Assistance (Students)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological Literacy • Internal Stakeholder • External Stakeholder • Challenges • Issues and Problems (including all sub code categories) • No Resistance • Traditional Pedagogy • Teaching Methods

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Use of MOODLE
	Managerial Perspective (Registrar UOS & IT Manager LGU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LMS System • Pandemic • Facebook or WhatsApp • MOODLE • Trainings • Resistance to Change • External Factors • Connectivity Issue • Unfamiliar • Student Engagement
	Factors Compromising Learning Process & External Factors (BDM & EC SU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Student Engagement • Staff Readiness • Online Classes • Centralised Platform • External Factors • External Stakeholder • Policies
THEME	SUB-THEME	NODES
Change Implementation Process	Autonomous or Managed Change (Teachers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External Factors • External Stakeholder • Policies • Acceptance of Change • Software • Teaching Methods • 2017 ERP System • Change Implemented • MOU • Pandemic
	Organisational Support and Training, and Motivational Factors (HOD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Motivated Teachers • Resistance to Change • No Resistance • Non-Monetary Motivation • Pandemic • Acceptance of Change • Organisational Change • Technological Literacy • Weak Infrastructure

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-Learning Benefits
	Technology Support (Students)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT Department • Weak Infrastructure • LMS System • Communication and Interaction • Trainings • MOU • Internal Stakeholder • Change Implemented • Learning vs Knowledge vs Skills
	Levers of Change Management (Registrar UOS, IT Manager LGU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change Management • Internal Stakeholder • Pandemic • Acceptance of Change • E-Learning Benefits
	Teachers' attitude towards the use of e-learning (EC SU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issues & Problems (including all subcategories) • Challenges • Trainings • Plagiarism including Turnitin • External Stakeholder • External Factors • Learning vs Knowledge vs Skills

Table 5b External Stakeholder Thematic Table:

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	NODES
Change Management Process/ Models	Training & Motivational Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies • Trainings • Centralised Platform • Pandemic • Staff Readiness • No Resistance • Change Implemented
	Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical Courses • LMS System • MOODLE • Presentation Slides • Online Databases • Question Bank •
	Change Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Motivated Teachers • Non-Monetary Motivation • Teachers • IT Department • Policies
THEMES	SUB-THEMES	NODES
Stakeholders' Perception	Factors Compromising Learning Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External Factors • Issues & Problems (including all subcategories) • Challenges • Assessment
	Changing Nature of Academic Teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Databases • Software • Hybrid Classes • Case Based Questions • Traditional Pedagogy • Pandemic • E-Learning Benefits
THEMES	SUB-THEMES	NODES
Change Implementation Process	Policies & Regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies

	Collaborations & Exploration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MOU • External Stakeholder
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There are three main themes which are used for both internal and external stakeholders, however, there are sub-themes which are based on individual stakeholders and the responses collected from them. Tables 5.1 and 5.2 will explain the main themes and their sub-themes, which will ultimately show which theme is linked with which research objective. The three main themes are *Change Implementation Process, Stakeholders' Perceptions, and Change Management Models*.

The identified themes were categorised on the basis of internal and external stakeholders. Both of the stakeholder groups were mentioned in Chapter 4 Methodology where the identified potential stakeholders of HEIs in Pakistan are mentioned. The interviewed internal stakeholders in the current study are *Teachers (Users of Technology), Heads of Department (HOD, Managers), Managerial or Administrative Stakeholders (e.g., IT Manager, Business Development Manager (BDM), Examination Controller (EC), Registrar), and Student Focus Group*. In terms of external stakeholders, the major stakeholder is the Higher Education Commission (HEC) whereas to capture the viewpoint from employers' perspective, an interview was conducted with Allied Bank's HR Department Manager. The bank manager's interview was not used in the findings directly; however, any useful information will be used in the analysis chapter.

Table 5.1 Internal Stakeholders

Objective	Theme	Sub-Theme
To examine the process of change management towards e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan	Change Management Models/Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing Nature of Academic Teaching (Teachers) • Training & Motivational Strategies (HOD) • Training & Motivational Factors (Students) • Training & Motivational Factors (Registrar UOS, IT Manager LGU) • Changing Nature of Academic Teaching, Resources & Training and Motivational Factors (BDM & EC)
To explore the challenges that influence the individual stakeholder's perceptions in the implementation of e-learning.	Stakeholders' Perceptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factors Compromising Learning Process (Teachers) • Perceived Potential Benefits from the use of e-learning & Resources (HOD) • E-Learning Issues and Assistance (Students) • Managerial Perspective (Registrar UOS & IT Manager LGU) • Factors Compromising Learning Process & External Forces (BDM & EC SU)
To provide recommendations on the implementation of e-learning to the HEIs and Regulatory body with the help of stakeholder analysis.	Change Implementation Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous or Managed Change (Teachers) • Organisational Support and Training and Motivational Factors (H.O.D. & BDM SU) • Technology Support & Training and Motivational Factors (Student Focus Group) • Levers of Change Management (Registrar of UOS, I.T. Manager LGU) • Teachers' attitude towards the use of e-learning (Examination Controller SU)

Source: Self-work of researcher

Each of the sub-themes are explained below according to the identified stakeholders; teachers, HODs, Student Focus Group, and Management and Administrative stakeholders. Following is the map of themes which are mentioned above in Table 5.1.

Figure 5.1. Internal Stakeholders

Source: Self-work of researcher

Table 5.2 External Stakeholder (HEC)

Objective	Theme	Sub-Theme
To examine the process of change management towards e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan	Change Management Models/Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training & Motivational Factors • Resources • Change Management
To explore the challenges that influence the individual stakeholder's perceptions in the implementation of e-learning.	Stakeholders' Perceptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factors Compromising Learning Process • Changing Nature of Academic Teaching
To provide recommendations on the implementation of e-learning to the HEIs and Regulatory body with the help of stakeholder analysis.	Change Implementation Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies & Regulations • Collaborations & Explorations

Source: Self-work of researcher

Figure 5.2. External Stakeholder (HEC)

Source: Self-work of researcher

5.2.1 Sub-Themes

The core sub-themes identified for the interviews conducted from Teachers/Professors are as follows:

- ***Changing Nature of Academic Teaching***
 - *Use of E-learning before COVID-19.*
 - *Use of E-learning during or after the pandemic.*
- ***Autonomous or Managed Academic Work***
 - *Directed by the high-level management.*
 - *External forces*
- ***Negative Expectations/Resistance towards the use of E-Learning***
 - *Resistance from students*
 - *Students' expectations*
 - *Factors compromising the learning process.*

Similarly, the core sub-themes related to the interview conducted with the Head of Department or Dean of Department in the University is as follows:

- ***Organisational Support***
 - *University culture and support towards change implementation*
 - *Lack of resources (such as Turnitin or other technological resources)*
- ***Training and Motivational Strategies***
- ***Perceived Potential Benefits From the use of E-learning.***
 - *Teacher's attitude towards the use of e-learning*
 - *Constant communication (it can act as a pros and cons both)*

Interviews conducted with the focus group also includes their own sub-themes which are as follows:

- ***E-Learning (Issues and Assistance)***
 - *Stakeholder's Impact*
- ***Technological Support***
 - *Providing Software and Hardware Support*
- ***Training and Motivational Factor***
 - *Supporting Student's learning approach*
 - *Accessible e-resources*

5.3 INTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS

5.3.1 Change Management Process/Models

This theme focuses on the processes or utilisation of any strategies or models which will help the stakeholders in the organisation to manage and tackle the change (e-learning). It provides in-depth knowledge regarding any models used in managing the change which is collected from the internal stakeholders through semi-structured interviews. The sub-themes are mentioned according to the following structure.

1. Teachers
2. Heads of Departments (HOD)
3. Student Focus Group
4. Managerial and Administrative Stakeholders (includes Registrar, IT Department Manager, Examination Controller and Business Development Manager)

5.3.1.1 Changing Nature of Academic Teaching (Teachers)

With global breakthroughs in technology, every area in the corporate sector is touched by IT developments and advancements. These have also impacted teaching practices worldwide, from schools to universities. As teaching methods change and their mode of delivery therefore, interviewees were asked about the changing nature of academic instruction to see if their institute used a change management model or change strategy.

Use of E-Learning Before Pandemic

Most of the private universities of Pakistan, use PowerPoint slides in their lectures. Therefore, there is already some sort of e-learning implemented in the private HEIs, although in some cases there are some teachers who initiated the use of electronic resources in course delivery before the COVID-19 pandemic.

Lahore Garrison University (LGU) is one of the HEIs in Pakistan, where the use of e-resources is already in place and HOD confirms it.

“Well, when the pandemic was setting in, even before the pandemic, we were already using certain Management systems which were based on MOODLE and Google Classroom.”
(HOD LGU Dr SF)

In relation to knowledge about e-learning, the teachers from LGU gave mixed responses; some of them had knowledge about teaching utilising online tools but one of the teachers had only had experience of e-resources as a student when she was doing her PhD.

“In 2014, I guess when we were in the private university, they have centralised work module. There I used to upload some sort of assignments and quizzes, something like that but the main tool of teaching was physical classes.” (Teacher LGU, MR ZI)

“I myself is being a researcher. I am always looking forward for new developments and new methodologies which are being introduced in the domain. So, I keep sharing the links which I would come across on LinkedIn or somewhere else...” (Teacher LGU, Dr LEE)

At the University of Sargodha (UOS) Public Institute, the interviewee talked about the use of Facebook and WhatsApp groups at department level to communicate with students about important notices and to make sure they were circulating the information through these mediums properly.

“From 2010, some teachers are using Facebook groups in which they put their class assignments although they gave the assignments in their classes as well... In 2016, we created a group for the department, and we use that group for circulating the information such as we are doing any workshop at that date so that all the students in the department gets the vital information about the activities in their department.” (Teacher UOS, Mr ASD)

An important piece of information was given by the public university teacher that Turnitin accounts were provided to them before pandemic but there were no policies issued to them related to the use of it, therefore, the use was left at the discretion of teachers.

“From 2015 some universities provided to some teachers their Turnitin accounts. Because of that, few teachers only started to take assignments from the students on Turnitin...For our MPhil students, it is compulsory for them to submit their thesis on Turnitin. Otherwise, class presentations or assignments are not required by the department officially to take them on Turnitin, it is solely on the discretion of teachers... But there is no such policy issued by our department officially.” (Teacher UOS, Mr ASD)

From third case University of Lahore (UOL) private institute, the teachers had knowledge about e-learning tools, such as Zoom, but they did not used the e-resources prior to the pandemic. Moreover, the teachers shared their experiences related to online tools during their

teaching especially one of the teachers who took three online courses during the pandemic to learn about e-learning and online classes.

“I have not used any e-learning tool before. However, since this pandemic, we shifted to online learning... that was the time when I actually came across with e-learning.” (Teacher UOL, Miss RC)

“Honestly, when this pandemic started, we shifted towards to online system.” “But before that I did have such experience of any e-learning or online platform.” (Teacher UOL, Miss SB)

However, teachers still required training to implement the change successfully and also to accommodate the needs of the students.

“We took it difficult because there was so much training required and the tools and techniques were very new to us. So, faced some difficulty.” (Teacher UOL, Miss SB)

Responses from University of Management and Technology (UMT) (private institute) were similar to other private sector HEIs inasmuch as synchronous measures are considered e-resources whereas asynchronous resources such as PowerPoint slides were not mentioned by the teachers. However, one of the teachers in UMT actually have hands on experience in teaching at a virtual university but his teaching subjects are more based on numbers therefore, he prefers face-to-face classes over online classes.

“No, not really, of course we came to know about zoom when we had pandemic.” (Teacher UMT, Mr GH)

“Unfortunately, it is not a substitute for face-to-face or campus life.” (Teacher UMT, Mr IQ)

In the last case of Superior University (SU), it is seen that Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) software was used by the employees only to keep the students records rather than utilising it as a MOODLE-based platform towards e-resources.

“Earlier it was not available.” (Teacher SUP, Mr KS)

“It was like one-to-one interaction in the class and no online tools were being used.” (Teacher SUP, Mr IS)

“Not before this pandemic.” (Teacher SUP, Mr AL)

Also, e-learning was not fully utilised before the pandemic, however, the three teachers have knowledge about the use of different online learning tools for example Mr KS knew about the online game scenario related to the real-world business issues, Mr AL knew about video conferencing tools but only for business use and similarly, Mr IS also had knowledge about Zoom before the pandemic due to the use of it for business meetings.

It is seen that in all four cases of private HEIs, the use of PowerPoint slides, case studies and articles were being used by the faculty to support their teaching before the pandemic which is not the case in the public university.

Use of E-Learning During/After Pandemic

The use of e-learning was suddenly increased and some institutes in Pakistan decided to comply with the regulations of the HEC whereas some of them decided to shut their doors and gave their students some time off from the academic schedule (Tabassum et al., 2021).

As the HEC determines to introduce online classes in Pakistani HEIs, it enforced the use of online classes to continue the learning and teaching process in the universities of Pakistan (Mumtaz et al., 2021).

Most of the private sector HEIs were seen achieving the status of “online readiness” mentioned by HEC policies overnight after the announcement of commencement of online classes in all HEIs in Pakistan.

In Lahore Garrison University (LGU), initially, complete online classes were conducted during pandemic but later on, hybrid or blended modes of teaching were also utilised to accommodate those students who were facing difficulties in taking online classes. Teachers mentioned that the tools they used due to e-learning implementation were MOODLE, Google Classroom and Zoom. Further, teachers have specifically mentioned video tutorials used along with case studies and articles which helped the students to clear their concepts.

“We did have hybrid mode... I am glad we had those few sessions with the students... In E-learning primarily the platforms were something of concern... we have been exercising multiple tools or methodologies like experiential learning through case roles along-with some books and articles... But now in e-learning mode particularly, we are using heterogenous genre of content. We would give students some videos along-with some tutorials or articles on web.” (Teacher LGU, Dr LEE)

“The basic technique which we are literally bound to do because we had to produce, we had to give proofs of our teaching that is Power Point... I usually prefer to give video tutorial type thing... which students had to produce... so every task is related to some learning and objectives... it also let you know that if they are grasping the concepts of the module content.” (Teacher LGU, Miss F)

“MOODLE and Google Classroom is used and there are case studies given.” (Teacher LGU, Mr Z)

However, whereas the e-learning tools were helpful for business and management degrees and courses, for practical degrees, or subjects which involve numerical concepts, it became difficult for the teachers to teach online. In LGU, Mr Z took the initiative of buying equipment himself such as Whiteboard to facilitate the students and make sure they grasped the concepts of topics.

“Personally, I have purchased my own Whiteboard, and I have made my own classroom in my room, and I have received the words of appreciation from the university that I am the only one who is actually using my own will... so the feedback of the students is very much appreciating.” (Teacher LGU, Mr Z)

In UOS, they implemented e-learning due to the pandemic as a major factor because public campuses were closed initially with the outbreak, therefore the public institutes followed the guidelines of the HEC and Government of Pakistan to use both synchronous and asynchronous e-tools to continue teaching and learning during pandemic.

“There was no other option for us in covid therefore, at the end we conducted online classes at the end but in the beginning, we did not have any platform or software to conduct online classes therefore, we closed the campus. As soon as the meetings were held between Deans, Vice Chancellor, and other board members and also after it became mandatory by the HEC as well to conduct online classes then we started to conduct online classes. We used Zoom and Google classroom for it.” (Teacher UOS, Mr AS)

The university trained their faculty to use e-resources to conduct both examinations and classes.

“All the teachers were given training about that software. We also conducted mock test from the students as well so that they also know about it for their final exam.” (Teacher UOS, Mr AS)

In the University of Lahore , the management focused on its pre-existing MOODLE software, SLATE, by upgrading it and making it compulsory for the teachers to use it along with Zoom and Google Classroom. As mentioned earlier, UOL was already using e-resources before the pandemic. *“Our university organised on couple of platforms, there is learning management system that is basically MOODLE. MOODLE is being utilised to deliver assessments such as exams, quizzes, assignments, and as such lecture delivery is concerned, we are using Zoom.”* (Teacher UOL, Mr SK)

With the help of training, management created awareness about the change and created coalition between teachers who received the training to train other faculty members too.

“The training was arranged in a way that we could learn the thing step by step. First, we were taught that how to schedule a class and how to conduct class management... After two weeks of classes, then we started quizzes which were also done through training... in the third level we were taught about how to conduct assignments... the students were also trained that how they can take quizzes and how they can upload their assignments.” (Teacher UOL, Miss SB)

At the University of Management and Technology , the major e-learning tools were implemented with the notification issued by the HEC related to the closure of the institutes. UMT’s management acted fast, and they started to use the synchronous methods within three to four days of the notification.

“It was Saturday I guess when announced and so on Monday we were taking online classes.” (Teacher UMT, Mr GH)

“This online teaching methodology so our university was very quick Thursday. Perhaps it was the day when we received a notification that University would be closed, and Monday was the day we were using Zoom system.” (Teacher UMT, Mr IQ)

However, in terms of methods in use, teachers at the UOL shared different views as one of the teachers states that email was faster than their Learning Management System (LMS) due

to file size restrictions and the other teacher highlighted the use of WhatsApp groups to maintain the communication with the students rather than the LMS system.

“I think some teachers are using LMS some are not using LMS, but I am not very much fan of LMS and rarely used LMS for even teaching evaluations... Perhaps other things are faster.”

(Teacher UMT, MR IQ)

“To provide everything which is required by the student, we must make WhatsApp groups to keep in touch with the students... We have to be very vigilant as far as emails are concerned.” (Teacher UMT, MR GH)

The change introduced with the implementation of e-learning by the HEC and environmental factors, forced the institutes to upgrade their LMS system. Similar to UOL, Superior University (SU) also upgraded their LMS system, influenced by the needs of the policies updated by HEC. SU was also using Zoom, Google Classroom and YouTube videos to increase the learning of the students related to their course concepts and WhatsApp groups were used for communication circulation.

“LMS has been updated because of pandemic, they have done few updates, a few improvements.” (Teacher SU, Mr IS)

“We use PPT slides for the lecturing, and support the lectures with case studies, articles and YouTube videos... for communication WhatsApp groups.” (Teacher SU, Mr AL)

“This is a centralised platform where teachers and students can interact, and management can observe as well... we can interact with the people and even we can conduct examination through the MOODLE that we have right now... We were having with WhatsApp groups where class representatives were connected with the program coordinator, and they were floating their information.” (Teacher SU, Mr KS)

In developing countries like Pakistan, the major stakeholder, teachers or professors, utilised e-resources from time to time such as PowerPoint slides or use of online articles in the physical class. However, when asked specifically about the online tools they did not include these tools and methods. This is because they mainly consider online classes, live video sessions, recorded video sessions or virtual classrooms as e-resources and PowerPoint slides, or journal articles have slipped their mind to think of them as e-resources.

With the help of different techniques used by different teachers in different disciplines, it shows that the use of e-learning can be appreciated in the local community of Pakistan if external stakeholders and management work together to support teachers with proper mediums of delivering the concepts to the students in their online lectures. However, to deliver the learning concepts in the discipline of medicine and health is much more complicated, requiring more sophisticated and advanced technology. With the proper motivational techniques, along with management approaches such as fulfilling the psychological needs of the teachers related to lecture delivery, forming guiding coalitions within and also outside the university such as technology providers, will help the strong implementation of e-learning throughout the stakeholders of the HEIs in Pakistan.

5.3.1.2 Training and Motivational Strategies (Head of Department (HOD))

The structure of the organisation will be affected with the introduction of new technology and educational institutes are now utilising more technological measures to provide quality educational services to its stakeholders. Therefore, in order to balance the organisational environment, it is important to train the faculty (Magnaye-Laylo, 2020).

One of the motivational strategies used by the HOD in LGU is that he asked the faculty to understand and use MOODLE as it would help them increase the value of their CVs which would give them good results in the future. Also, cash prizes were awarded to faculties who performed well during the implementation of the change.

“I motivated them that having taught on MOODLE is something you can write in your CVs. So that is how we try to get them on board and there was absolutely no resistance... Some faculty members for doing exceptionally good work, they were given cash rewards or incentives.” (HOD LGU, Dr SA)

It was seen that the involvement of top-level management allows a faculty to be more productive and acceptable towards the change introduced in the organisation.

“Top management was stressing it so hard... and there were incentives... when the top management was involved, that strategy worked for us.” (HOD LGU, Dr SA)

In public institute, it seemed that the higher management used autocratic measures to implement the change because the HOD at the University of Sargodha (UOS) who acts as a representative of the top-level management, mentioned that teachers were simply teaching

physically and now they have to teach online which shows the level of concern of the management regarding the change.

“In terms of motivation, university does not provide anything to the faculty members. There is no such strategies used by the university management to motivate the faculty, they were delivering lectures before physically now they are doing it just online.” (HOD UOS, Mr HA)

However, UOS is a public institute therefore, HEC gave incentives to the faculty and management of public institutes by providing free of cost courses whereas HEC charges subsidised rates to the private HEIs.

“Here the concept is learning by doing. Similarly, for online teaching as well the process is learning by doing... In this regard teachers can take help from different websites such as COURSERA.” (HOD UOS, Mr HA)

In UOL, the change was managed with trainings and non-monetary motivational techniques which included counselling to make faculty motivated throughout the implementation process.

“That was one bad scenario that we had to stay motivated without getting any monetary incentive... We were properly counselled, and we did counsel to our junior fellows...The top management took great care of us, we the middle management, took great care of the teachers and the teachers took great care of the students.” (HOD UOL, Mr SR)

At the University of Management and Technology (UMT) private institute similar actions to UOL were taken by the management where they provided appreciation through feedback in the form of a letter of appreciation to the faculty. However, there were no cash prizes given to the faculty in these difficult times of the pandemic to increase their morale related to managing the change.

“In the last semester, we go through the teaching feedback of all the faculty members so are centralized and letter of appreciation was sent to those who performed above school.” (HOD UMT, Mr UM)

Furthermore, in Superior University (SU), their top-level management was working on providing monetary and non-monetary motivation to their faculty members. The Chairman also instructed the faculty and HODs to complete Harvard courses on EdX which were provided to them free of charge and those who completed the five instructed courses received

cash prizes for their achievements. Additionally, training and motivational seminars were conducted to motivate their faculty however, it was seen that faculty members in their 40s and 50s showed some signs of resistance due to their lower level of technological literacy and also due to the subjects they teach.

“We had about 85 teachers who did it who did five courses, and they got the bonuses for that... a person like me who is teaching English a person like me who is teaching films. I believe I am of the view that film and English or the language cannot be taught in this regard.” (HOD SU, Mr HS)

Training is beneficial towards adopting the change because it will help teachers to learn more about the technology. Therefore, in terms of developing countries, proper training on e-learning technology which will not only make the teachers ready for the change but also create awareness in the students, will help the management to implement the change successfully.

5.3.1.3 Training and Motivational Factors (Student Focus Group)

Students are the most important stakeholders in terms of accepting the change in a university scenario. This is because they are the main users of technology and they are affected by issues such as technological literacy, internet availability and availability of hardware and software etc. (Samsudeen and Mohamed, 2019). Therefore, it is the need of the hour to investigate their responses related to the implementation of e-learning in their institute.

This theme is based on two further sub-themes which are linked with the support students are receiving, mainly from the internal stakeholders, and also the accessible e-resources to help them to continue their studies during the pandemic. The two sub-themes are:

Supporting Students’ Learning Approach

With the help of e-learning, students continued their learning process in the difficult period of the pandemic. Further, in a developing country like Pakistan where students received limited support from their institutes, the pandemic made it difficult for them to continue their studies. In Lahore Garrison University (LGU), the management acted quickly on the government guidelines and initiated policies towards implementing and initiating the synchronous mode of e-learning which ultimately helped its students to continue their studies with the help of e-learning.

“During the pandemic situation, it helped us to not stop our studies and give us continuation because there were certain educational institutes which were holding on to their learning

process. In that sense we saved our time and we continued with the help of e-learning.”
(Student LGU, FS3)

“There were no issues with the theoretical subjects and our degree is also based on theoretical subjects therefore, with the help of e-learning our time was saved.” (Student LGU, SW2)

As the students are often more technological knowledgeable than their teachers therefore, some of the students felt that the teachers at LGU should have been trained better and should have related more easily to e-learning to remove the communication gap between teachers and students. Further, for communication purposes, the teachers mainly used WhatsApp groups to communicate with the students.

“Then there are teachers who are not well enough known about or the use of technology. There is a problem like communication gap.” (Student LGU, FS1)

“We only used WhatsApp groups.” (Student LGU, SW2)

“During covid, we text them on WhatsApp groups.” (Student LGU, FS1)

However, it was seen that trainings were only provided to the teachers by the management through the IT Department.

“IT department did provided training to the faculty members, but they did not provide any training to the students.” (Student LGU, FS1)

Unlike the private sector, the public sector UOS introduced online classes only during the pandemic which made it difficult for the students to understand and utilise the online learning tools. It was mentioned by one of the respondents that before the pandemic the teachers were not using any PowerPoint slides as study materials in the class. However, when classes were shifted online then the university created their own LMS system to provide course materials.

“When we went into this pandemic the university improved themselves first time related to course materials... As we went into pandemic, university developed their own LMS system on which all the teachers have put their full course contents and course materials. This was first time that such a positive thing happened.” (Student UOS, MAH4)

Furthermore, it was also highlighted by the students that they used WhatsApp groups before the introduction of LMS.

“WhatsApp groups were used before. In which teachers share the helping material related to the course which is time saving and helpful for us.” (Student UOS, AB1)

However, the students of LGU showed more knowledge related to online learning concepts because they knew about Udemy and other online platforms where they could take short courses online. This is because in the public sector the focus and priority was always given to face-to-face classes because they had never used PowerPoint slides or any other mode of e-resources.

Students from UOL (Private) showed more interest in online learning methodologies because with the help of e-learning they could also fulfil other commitments due to the flexibility provided by e-learning. This is because students received training from their institute related to online classes, assignment handling and examination.

“It provides a greater degree of flexibility like it can be less stressful to manage alongside with other commitments. Furthermore, there is less pressure on the students as we have the help of devices, applications, and multimedia tools to make learning more interactive... We had mock quizzes, mock exams before our actual exams, they supported us timely and enhanced the software as well.” (Student UOL, AM3)

“I think it was way easier for me because as a student I think the education system can be enhanced through online courses and I think engaging students online can engage students at a deeper level.” (Student UOL, KH2)

From the University of Management and Technology (UMT), the focus group included professional students, that is those who are working and studying at the same time, and they were studying for their MPhil degree. The interview showed that due to the introduction of e-learning they were at a better position of utilising their university’s resources because recorded lectures were available to them and also the management was helpful towards adopting the change.

“Our resource sharing is very easy. It became possible with the help of teachers.” (Student UMT, HU3)

“Even if your online lecture is missed due to electricity then you can still play those recorded lectures and cope-up with the lectures.” (Student UMT, UZ2)

“We can also use the search engines in a better way due to the introduction of e-learning.”
(Student UMT, HU3)

The above findings illustrate that with the support from the management, students can accept the change to e-learning because it provides them with better flexibility of managing their studies with job and other commitments.

Accessible e-Resources

With the help of e-resources, students become more inclined towards the use of e-learning which will help the institute to manage the change more effectively and efficiently. It is seen that in the private sector, the HEIs were providing similar e-resources to each other which includes LMS system, Zoom, Google Classroom, recorded lectures, WhatsApp and Facebook groups, and online examinations. However, the UOL managed to go one step further by using Google Drive as a backup for their course materials and getting approval for flight simulation software to use in their aviation management degrees.

“MOODLE is used as a backup where all your class material is available where you can go back and see what we have learnt over the semester.” (Student LGU, FS3)

“There are couple of teachers who lookout for good simulating software, and we took certain approvals from our higher management.” (HOD UOL, Mr SR)

“Teachers share their course outline, plans and any related work material on it ... this is an advantage that we are prepared beforehand due to LMS. Secondly teachers upload the quizzes and assignments for all the students on it like they upload the assignments after checking them.” (Student UMT, UZ2)

In terms of public institutes, UOS provided similar access to the e-resources as private institutes, however, there was no use of specific software which are used in different disciplines such as the flight simulation software or in business management the use of game simulation environments to let students experience the real-time management of the business in virtual environments. This is because, in public institutes, the approval for such software requires a lengthy process into which most teachers do not want to put their efforts and time.

Management and Administrative Stakeholders

In respect to internal stakeholders, the viewpoints of stakeholders from the management and administrative side are also collected from the HEIs. The management and administrative stakeholders include Registrar (UOS), IT Department Manager (LGU), Examination Controller (EC) (SU), and Business Development Manager (BDM) (SU).

5.3.1.4 Training and Motivational Factors (Registrar and IT Manager)

This theme includes findings from the IT Manager (LGU) and Registrar (UOS). This theme will state those measures which were taken by the management and administrative stakeholders to help the institute in the smooth implementation of e-learning.

From the private sector, the IT manager confirms that the initial step taken by the administrative and management side of the institute was to train and motivate the faculty to accept the change and adjust themselves with it. Faculty was appraised by promoting their level of anticipation to HEC in terms of their achievements.

“Initially conducted the training for the staff. We took the assessment of those trainings, and we evaluated the staff, praised the staff from there and was appraised by the management in terms of cash prizes, in terms of certificates, in terms of anything... upto the HEC level their names will be carried out to forward it.” (IT Manager LGU, Mr JN)

Due to the sudden implementation, the IT department also felt the burden of managing the change, therefore the manager also motivated IT department staff through motivational seminars and trainings.

“There was an extensive training and development programs, which were thinking about by different management sciences group personalities to make them prepared and to motivate them during the covid situation, to handle the issues and affairs or the circumstance to avoid them... that was a continuous process which was developed and used to be a recycle every week.” (IT Manager LGU, Mr JN)

In relation to public institutes, the registrar mentioned about the mock sessions given to the faculty to manage the process of e-learning implementation. Further, in public institutes, the change is always directed by higher authorities such as by government bodies therefore, there is no choice for the faculty except to accept the change.

“Demos were also given to them, and all their issues were addressed properly and now 100s of teachers are comfortably managing entire e-learning process.” (Registrar UOS)

Due to more complexity in public institutes, it is seen that employees either accept the change or leave their jobs when any change is introduced, but during the pandemic as the income streams of the general public were limited and there was resulting economic pressure therefore, they accepted the change rather than resisting it to save their jobs.

5.3.1.5 Changing Nature of Academic Teaching (BDM)

Under this theme, a Business Development manager’s (BDM’s) finding will be reviewed. It will show how management of Superior University reacted towards the implementation of e-learning in their institute. As the mode of teaching was shifted in March 2020 from traditional on-campus classes to online classes, this resulted in the different mode of academic teaching and taking exams. There were certain challenges and issues mentioned by the BDM which hindered and slowed the implementation process of e-learning. However, with continued support from their sister company, Infinite Connections, the SU managed the change effectively through trainings and motivational seminars for the faculty and management during the pandemic.

“The whole University is online. Except medical education because in medical education and engineering courses, there are more practical things then theoretical... I mean we shifted online but our students they did suffered in this whole transmission as well because net connection. Also, access to the e-devices is not common in Pakistan... Then prices of devices went high, and everybody in Pakistan is not in condition to afford this thing.” (BDM SU, Mr HUN)

As e-learning methodologies for teaching and learning were only used in traditional settings in Pakistan therefore, these systems were used on an experimental basis for which reason the medical department was not fully facilitated at the initial stage of the pandemic.

5.3.1.6 Resources

The EC (SU) mentioned about the resources used by the management to manage the implementation of e-learning during pandemic. Two different software, LMS and UMS were used to manage the course contents, course materials and student’s records such as attendance, results, and fee balance. Furthermore, initially when LMS system was not upgraded to the requirements and policies mentioned by HEC, SU utilised Google Forms to conduct online examination of May 2020 batch.

“As I have mentioned about both software in which one of them is UMS which monitors the student’s attendance, results, and outcome-based resources. Second is LMS which is learning based and checks the learning perspective... We conducted online exams in May 2020 because some of the batches at that time are also required to conduct their exams. At that time, we used goggle forms to conduct some exams, some we changed to project-based assessment and viva based through zoom as well.” (EC SU, Mr HR)

In relation to BDM, he mentioned about online courses offered by Harvard and MIT on EdX which are also directed by the Chairman of SU to the faculty and staff members to complete to get them trained for e-learning implementation. Furthermore, SU is also engaged in student and faculty exchange programmes which are partly managed by BDM as well. It is seen that the foreign partners of SU does not share their e-resources such as e-library access with them, but they do share the module contents to help them design their courses in a better way as well.

“Universities normally don't offer these things (access to e-library), but they do share their module handbooks” (BDM SU, Mr HUN)

Resources plays a vital part in the implementation of e-learning because e-resources such as online library and journals access provide better platforms for the students, and they feel inclined towards e-learning.

5.3.1.7 Training and Motivational Strategies (EC and BDM)

The most important elements used in the process of implementation by the HEIs are training and motivational strategies which helped the stakeholders to accept and manage the change. It is seen that staff members in private HEIs are more self-motivated towards the change rather than public institute because in SU, the benefits of the e-learning were clearly communicated to the faculty and other staff members. Training was given to the employees by professional trainers and motivational speakers. In terms of the examination department, the Examination Controller (EC) mentioned to his fellow colleagues about the benefits of the new system.

“We do inhouse training... For staff, motivation is about what staff members are learning new. Such as I have mentioned about automatic results of the exams, it will now allow them to do audit of the results rather than collecting the results and it will keep them motivated as they are learning something new... Second incentive is increased capability or personal development.” (EC SU, Mr HR)

The above statements are also verified by the BDM who also emphasised about communicating the benefits of e-learning not only to faculty but to students as well.

“First, and very important thing is to motivate your teachers. That was probably tell the benefits of E learning tools to your students because many people in Pakistan with very less knowledge of it, they think that E learning is scary.” (BDM SU, Mr HUN)

This shows that the management of SU was not explicitly using any change management model, but they are indirectly following Kotter’s eight step model process.

5.3.2 Stakeholders’ Perception

This theme is focused on the perception of the stakeholders which highlights the challenges, factors, barriers, issues, advantages and benefits of the implementation of e-learning in the context of the HEIs of Pakistan.

5.3.2.1 Factors Compromising Learning Process

In terms of factors, there are various hurdles in the process of course delivery of e-learning in the case of Pakistan. In LGU, the teachers have noted a few of the factors which hinder the process of e-learning and the flow of information in the process of lecture delivery.

The main factors mentioned by the teachers included electricity shortage, technological literacy, internet facility in Pakistan, cultural aspects such as living in a joint family system where a person does not have a separate or individual room, conducting online exams and invigilating them, reduced communication with the students due to not interacting with them in a physical environment, resistance towards accepting the change due to computer literacy such as from the Islamic Studies Department, and reduced social interaction with the students and employees.

“First was the electricity problem. Some and many of us were unaware of these technologies, so this was the first and fundamental problem which we have faced. To understand the latest problem or latest technology. Secondly, there was problem of internet. Thirdly, we are living in the community where many of us living in combined family system. So, there was no proper place where I can, or we can take the classes... If I talk about Islamic Department where there is not at all any kind of technology used, when they switch to MOODLE and something like that software, many teachers resigned their jobs because they were not familiar with these things and obviously the institution wants the teachers to be updated accordingly.”
(Teacher LGU, Mr Z)

“I missed the interaction point of view that come in two-way communication is somehow disturbed... Secondly the evaluation criteria, MOODLE we use for the evaluation, it is very good, but we are not monitoring them through cameras. Thirdly, teachers should be trained.”
(Teacher LGU, Miss F)

“I would primarily say that technology literacy, or digital literacy is a challenge... To technology literacy, there are some kinds of challenges with respect to cognitive load.”
(Teacher LGU, Dr L)

The situation in the public sector is different because in the culture of public institutes, they not even include PowerPoint slides in their mode of teaching. It is also seen that teachers used LMS system for the first time at institution level which required training and as well as time to accept the change. Further, the teaching culture in a public institute is quite different from a private one as was mentioned by the interviewee that teachers are more careful while teaching on campus as compared to conducting lectures online at home.

“There were some issues and for the time being there is no solution to those issues because we were on trial and run basis and we used it first time... We implemented the system first time in the university therefore, it will take time to bring the issues at the front and deal with it at maturity... We also have to look for the culture. There are cultural issues as well, such as teachers will think they have only one lecture today so they will deliver the lecture from home rather than going to the university. Secondly in university, teachers are more careful in the campus because they will think someone can watch them while delivering the lecture and they have to deliver the full 90 minutes lecture.” (Teacher UOS, Mr AS)

In UOL, the challenges and barriers highlighted by the teachers are similar to those experienced at LGU and UOS, however, the major difficulty faced was by those teachers who were teaching practical subjects apart from business management studies such as accounting and other practical subjects, because they find it difficult to explain the equations and write them for the students online. However, if they were trained properly and provided with better equipment then they can adopt the change quickly.

“One of the major challenges is that you know due to not being face-to-face with the students...In the beginning, the university also asked the teachers that for online you need a good internet connection in Pakistan, obviously this can be a challenge, especially for those teachers who do not live in the major cities.” (Teacher UOL, Mr SK)

“Since there is no actual board and we are not physically present, I think that was the biggest challenge that I faced, especially in writing equations... I could not find a suitable person who can train me for related to writing equations. So, writing one by one equations for every class right for every section was quite challenging for me.” (Teacher UOL, Miss RC)

Teachers from UMT believe that online learning is a temporary arrangement and assessment via online methods is challenging for the teachers due to the institutes not investing more in technology. Also, their Quality Enhancement Cell (QEC) department is working side by side with the IT department to provide crucial training to accept the change.

“First thing is I believe it is not the substitute. Unfortunately, it is not a substitute for face-to-face on campus life. This is something which is temporary arrangement... assessment is a major challenge... So, I guess these universities are conventional universities. They are not investing, not preparing for students assessment... The second problem, which is because of the assessment, is lack of student’s interest... Third is connectivity issues... The University was very proactive, and they have a very good IT department. So, they offered many trainings.” (Teacher UMT, MR IQ)

“The environment at home. It plays very vital role as far as learning of students during this pandemic using online tools using e-learning.” (Teacher UMT, MR GH)

The last case of Superior University presented issues which are consistent with the other four cases, and it emphasised more on the availability of technology to the students. Teachers were more concerned about the students because they believe it is difficult to maintain proper communication with the students via online lectures.

“There were internet issues, electricity issues, some pupils did not even have laptops or computers at home. The home environment was not conducive and supportive, in many cases.” (Teacher SU, Mr AL)

“Teacher doesn't know at times that even if the student is listening, even if the student is focused... if I talk about myself, I am facing two of these problems which is like lack of interaction, focus and connectivity issues.” (Teacher SU, Mr IS)

With the issues identified from teachers, it is the responsibility of the management to overcome those challenges.

5.3.2.2 Stakeholders Attitude Towards the Use of E-learning and Resources (HOD)

Under this theme, the response of internal stakeholders, such as faculty and students, towards the change will be reviewed, including showing any signs of resistance. In LGU, it is seen

that the HOD encountered resistance due to frustration and confusion with the use of technology. The reason behind is that the new technology came with technical issues and temporary system shutdown due to sudden overburden of internet traffic of faculty, management, and students on the computer systems.

“There was some technical related frustration when you are doing something it is not happening. Maybe that was a case with a few members but as we like went on with two or three weeks, this resistance withered away.” (HOD LGU, Dr SA)

However, the management of LGU conducted weekly meetings to listen to the issues faced by the faculty and to upgrade their LMS system to overcome those issues and make the change more acceptable for the faculty.

“Every week there were meetings, there were sessions and all the teachers, they were given time to develop themselves in smaller steps, but they were given assistance like MOODLE coordinator... the MOODLE team was there helping them round the clock.” (HOD LGU, Dr SA)

It is also seen that the management had asked employees to use MOODLE from 2019, that is before the pandemic, and Google Classroom was given preference by the faculty. Further, teachers helped to train other teachers in different departments and make them understand about the use of MOODLE.

In terms of a public university (UOS), the HOD mentioned about the difficulty from the teacher’s side related to the use of online resources to deliver lectures online. It was mainly because of the infrastructural issues and internet availability therefore, the management asked teachers to visit the campus and record their lectures in the university labs which has better equipment than they had at home.

“At university campus we have good internet facility because some teachers they do not have proper internet connection at home so they can come to the campus, and they use the computer labs for better equipment.” (HOD UOS, MR HA)

In terms of resources, UOS did not use their LMS or MOODLE system, rather they were solely dependent upon Zoom’s free version which provides limited functions to the users. Furthermore, the university did not help faculty related to the equipment because it is a public institute and they have a limited budget therefore, the HOD bought a digital whiteboard from his own money to facilitate the students during the lectures.

“At the moment we are not using any MOODLE platform and at the moment we are only using zoom because it is free... There is also a problem of infrastructure, if you use online techniques then you must have proper infrastructure. Such as I have purchased a separate drawing board for the sole purpose of online teaching, and it is an expensive device and mostly teachers they do not buy it therefore some teachers they use their mobiles so they cannot do it properly.” (HOD UOS, MR HA)

In private institutes such as UOL, some of the older teachers showed resistance towards the e-learning implementation due to their inability to understand the technology whereas the younger teachers were keen to learn the new methods of teaching via e-learning due to their better understanding of the technology.

“At 50+ age, 45 to 55 years of age, they were not cooperative. They were not intending to learn this new technology. They were having the view that if we resist, they will step back, and we will continue teaching in the conventional styles.” (HOD UOL, Mr SR)

In terms of resources, the University of Lahore (UOL) provided their faculty and students with an in-house built LMS according to the needs of the institute.

In UMT, teachers are in a better position with the implementation and use of e-learning because it helps them assess assignments without opening hundreds of emails or marking it on the page. Also, teachers can inform students of upcoming projects and assignments.

“Sometimes we ask students to upload their assignment on LMS, so you don't have to open 100 emails and download assignments.” (Teacher UMT, MR IQ)

“Teachers, can you know, put the reference of that material online onto LMS and can communicate to students that they are going to. You know, discuss such and such reading or case study or whatever they wanted to do.” (HOD UMT, MR UM)

UMT's management assigned a separate department, "EMT," to get faculty feedback and train them on teaching and learning. The EMT department was working before the pandemic as the LMS software was introduced before the pandemic, but it was not widely used before HEC introduced its aggressive policies.

“Those who are not performed well are provided with letters that you know there are certain deficiencies which they need to overcome, and they are recommended for the trainings.” (HOD UMT, MR UM)

However, the teachers had mixed reactions towards LMS such as Mr IQ who was more inclined towards the use of e-mails rather than LMS and Mr GH who was more happy to use the LMS software.

When the interviews from SU were studied, the same trend as UOL was seen, that teachers were asked to attend the campus to conduct online classes due to the internet connectivity issues in Pakistan. In terms of communication, the HOD made sure that constant communication was facilitated between the faculty and students so that they could be trained to present themselves online for virtual presentations.

“The Wi-Fi system there might be weak or much lower as far as in quality... we have asked our teachers to be in the University and they'll be taking their lectures there while they are in the University.” (HOD SU, Mr HS)

The HOD mentioned about the internal resources similar to other institutes however, he also referred to external sources for example that the HEC should provide seminars and trainings to teachers in both public and private sectors to train them to accept the change and make them able to provide trainings to their fellow colleagues.

“I think there should be some training or seminars or some training sessions.” (HOD SU, Mr HS)

Better e-resources will enable the stakeholders to achieve short-term goals which allow them to celebrate short-term wins. These short-term wins will pave the way towards managing the change by motivating the stakeholders towards implementing change.

5.3.2.3 E-Learning Issues and Assistance (Student Focus Group)

In terms of e-learning implementation, it came as a helping hand to some students and to some it created more issues for them to continue their learning process, especially in the period of pandemic.

If we observe the issues which arose because of the immediate application of e-learning from students' perspective, then we can see that most of the students who lived in rural areas or who did not use a laptop initially in their degree, had a common problem, namely technological literacy.

In LGU, students had connectivity issues which was more persistent than any other problem. The students of LGU also mentioned internal and external stakeholders where the internal stakeholder IT department was mentioned as being helpful in terms of resolving the issues

and providing answers to FAQs whereas the external stakeholders included the HEC, internet, and technology providers. HEC was criticised by the students due to their policies related to e-learning implementation and online examination.

“Before covid we were not acquainted with the term e-learning. After COVID-19 we become aware of zoom and google classroom and there were many students with me who did not even know how to use a laptop but now they know how to use a laptop... This sudden covid period was a challenge for the IT department and for our system.” (Student LGU, SW2)

“As they have discussed about external stakeholders they were at benefit because demand was high. As for internal stakeholders, they were not good initially but with the passage of time we adopted everything...HEC did not allowed university to exam flexibly. I think they should have provided some contents for e-learning.” (Student LGU, FS1)

In respect to UOS, the students faced similar issues such as internet connectivity, home environment, timings of the classes, and studying subjective courses like calculus and finance etc. due to formulas. Due to the e-learning, the workload on teachers was increased and they were conducting classes at different schedules which was not a pleasant experience for the students.

“For us it is to manage our time at home. If we have to go to university then we have to be there at specific time for a specified time.” (Student UOS, SAM3)

While the HOD stated that there was no use of LMS, the students confirmed that the university had developed the LMS system but it was ineffective due to issues and bugs in the system. Additionally, the internal and external stakeholders identified by the students were the IT department and the HEC respectively. It is seen that the IT department was helping the students resolve their queries whereas the HEC was seen as the policy maker.

“Such as HEC externally gives any policy then according to that policy, department mould their policies and then our department reports to the VC and VC reports to the HEC” (Student UOS, AB1)

“Students were getting support from department and IT team both. First you forward your concerns to the department and then department forwards it to the IT department.” (Student UOS, MAH4)

UOL's students identified one of the critical factors related to e-learning, namely students' learning behaviour. In Pakistan e-learning creates ease of access to some students while for others it also created ease to dodge classes because of students' non-serious attitude.

“According to me e-learning is not as effective as the physical classes are because you know the people of Pakistan they are not much into studies and e-learning is helping a lot in making them not to study.” (Student UOL, MU1)

Students at UOL stated that the benefits of e-learning such as access to course contents, made them feel connected with teachers and this provided better understanding of concepts because students can listen to recorded lectures as many times as they like. It saves students' travel costs, but internet costs did add up.

“In my opinion, e-learning can lead to better retention because students nowadays would rather watch a video or listen to an audio rather than reading a whole manual or book... with our online classes, students were able to access the content anywhere and because in Pakistan most of the students are working, helping their families and stuff and they do not need to take time out from their jobs plus it is cost effective. You do not have to travel, and you do not have to worry about the accommodation or hostel.” (Student UOS, KH2)

In terms of stakeholders, the HEC and high-level management were scrutinised and students were expecting more from the HEC as they were the policy makers and also, they could provide institutes with the better means of technology and infrastructure to help students to accept the change effectively.

“If we talk about the external stakeholders then HEC or all the people in upper hierarchy, for me I think they had their own advantages that they were charging us full fee for everything, but I think they were giving very blank response to the students... they are not giving us any positive response from it.” (Student UOS, KH2)

Lastly, the students from UMT presented more benefits of e-learning such as taking classes from any location, assistance through online webinars, recorded lectures providing automated notes, completion of degrees during the pandemic when some of the institutes were closed and course content sharing even between students and teachers.

“In terms of course sharing, I believe it is better online because with the help of just one click you can get everything.” (Student UMT, HU3)

“For instance, we have some students from Afghanistan, and they can also join from there.”
(Student UMT, UZ2)

“It helped out us such as our university is not open for physical classes so our semester did not have any breaks in it and our degree will be completed in the same time period as it was scheduled to be completed and it all became possible due to e-learning.” (Student UMT, SK1)

With noted issues and advantages, e-learning will improve the teaching and learning processes, as well as students' and teachers' technological literacy, because it is a learn-by-doing process.

Managerial and Administrative Stakeholders

5.3.2.4 Managerial Perspective

It is important to know about the viewpoint of the management, that is, how the top and middle level management worked together to implement and manage the change. Under this theme, the interview data from the Registrar of UOS and IT Department Manager from LGU will be used to draw the findings relevant to this theme.

The IT manager reveals that top-level management introduced the LMS system before the pandemic, but the faculty was not using it because face-to-face communication was given preference. Further, it also shows that the pandemic played a vital role to increase the usage of the LMS system in LGU from 1% to 100% when the HEC made it compulsory for the HEIs to use e-learning methods for teaching and examinations.

“We already had an LMS but that was not effective at all, I can probably say like just out of 6000 users only 1% were using it. By the covid, it eventually raised to 100%. But pre-covid, it was like 1% of the content sharing was done to the WhatsApp groups or Facebook groups.”
(IT Manager LGU, Mr JN)

It also confirms that the management such as the Vice Chancellor promoted the LMS before COVID-19, but the faculty was using other means such as WhatsApp or Facebook groups at their convenience. This is because students face financial distress in developing countries like Pakistan and they have a limited budget with fewer jobs during their time of studies.

“They were not financially viable. They do not have laptops and they do not have proper education or training to use the laptop or resources like zoom and other things... They were very reluctant to do this.” (IT Manager LGU, Mr JN)

In relation to public institutes, it is seen that the management is more autocratic in nature, and they issued notices to the rest of the employees, that they must follow those instructions. In relation to managing the change, the registrar mentioned that the university has managed the change effectively however, the only concern he put forward was the internet connectivity due to which the students are facing difficulties in taking online classes.

“University of Sargodha is utilising e-learning effectively and efficiently which is providing benefits to the students at the university... Initially we had problems in distant areas due to signals issues (external factor), then there were issues related to attendance as well and how all the students will conduct their online exams and attend their classes online.” (Registrar UOS)

However, the teacher from UOS mentioned the irony of getting approval of implementing any change, policy or new method introduced by the faculty or staff from lower levels of the hierarchy. Approval is required from different boards and syndicates to officially implement any change.

“In order to create such platforms, we have to go through from various things such as if I want to create my separate web address or web domain then I need to get approval from seven different places.” (Teacher UOS, MR AA)

The managerial perspective of a private and public institute is totally different from each other because of different factors which include sense of responsibility, self-motivated employees, financial budgets, technological literacy levels and ease of managing and applying the change.

5.3.2.5 Factors Compromising Learning Process and External Forces (EC and BDM)

There are numerous factors which affect the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. The most frequently mentioned factors include technological literacy, the cultural aspect related to living in a joint family, priority to face-to-face environment, internet access, electricity shortage, and infrastructure availability. However, the examination controller stated that training seminars provided to the students helped them to understand about the e-learning tools which encouraged them take online classes.

“Due to activities (trainings) after some time students become available.” (EC SU, Mr HR)

Further it is seen that some of the HEIs in Pakistan from private and public sectors both halted their teaching facilities because the infrastructure and facilities in those institutes does

not meet the minimum requirements of online readiness mentioned in the HEC's policy guidelines documents.

“If you look at other universities in Pakistan, they became operational online in July or August 2020, but Superior University was the only university which shifted on online study from 16th March 2020.” (EC SU, Mr HR)

However, it is seen that Mr HR suggested a centralised software or platform for the HEIs where they can conduct educational activities effectively and efficiently through e-learning modes.

“I suggest that there must be a centralised software where everyone should put their data.” (EC SU, Mr HR)

Moreover, the BDM from SU spoke of the burden faced by the teachers during the pandemic due to the implementation of e-learning. E-learning provides a better platform for the faculty to continue their teaching in these difficult times. However, it increases the pressure because they need to be trained and update themselves for the current needs of the institute.

“The teacher role is getting crazy... Already our private sector teachers are working at their maximum capacity teaching so many classes, they've got extra burdens. So, at the same time when you see online E learning, so it means more work.” (BDM SU, Mr HUN)

Furthermore, in developing countries like Pakistan, policies which are put on paper are different from an actual scenario. This results in difficulty to implement change in the organisations as in theory the management considers different aspects whereas in practical implementation they react differently.

“In developing countries like Pakistan, most of the time Zaman things are put on a paper, either its Law or management and in practicality you do not see those things in implementation.” (BDM SU, Mr HUN)

In terms of external forces, three external stakeholders were mentioned by the BDM which are also considered as external forces during the implementation of e-learning. They were the HEC, local governing authority, and parents.

“There's one thing that is following rules, SOPs of HEC. Second thing to follow is following the rules of deputy commissioner of the town or local government. Third thing is parents' response.” (BDM SU, Mr HUN)

With the help of the factors identified above and the proposed framework in Chapter 3, the change can be managed in a more productive manner. It is seen that the HEIs managed the change without the use of any particular model or strategy however, this also resulted in extra

time taken because they were learning the change process by doing it rather than moving towards planned change.

5.4 Change Implementation Process

This theme sheds light on the steps taken by the HEIs which are in accordance with the proposed framework. The stakeholders revealed the steps used by them or other stakeholders to manage the implementation of e-learning in their institutes. Further it will also include any support given by the internal stakeholders, management and administration, and the external stakeholder, the HEC. Following are the sub-themes included under this major theme.

5.4.1 Autonomous or Managed Change (Teachers)

Directed by Higher Management

The universities' top management instructed online classes to continue learning and teaching without interruption. Some teachers accepted the change, but others resisted the direct implementation of e-learning. In some cases, higher authorities or management did not plan the change by educating stakeholders about e-learning. It also required communicating the institute's new vision and objectives to motivate employees and other stakeholders to achieve short-term wins that will anchor the change.

In the case of LGU, Miss F reported that strict decisions were made by the Vice Chancellor (VC) of the university, and faculty has been informed that if the system was not used by all the employees at the individual department level, then salaries will be deducted from those involved.

“Our Vice Chancellor took very strict stand like salaries would be deducted if you did not use the system.” (Teacher LGU, Miss F)

As the online classes policy was enforced by the HEC, Sir Z highlight the efforts of the VC and the involvement of the management related to the change.

“Vice Chancellor basically took initiative very enthusiastically and we were the only one or second university in the locality who designed and arranged online classes... You can say encouragement and enforcement both by the management.” (Teacher LGU, Mr Z)

In case of a public institute, it is seen that UOS is more autocratic in nature than a private institute. Employees have to accept every order from the top-level management such as the Vice Chancellor etc. because in the government sector the employees or faculty members have less say regarding their concerns.

“As we are in the government sector, we have to accept every order from the top management. We received this order from the vice chancellor through our dean, then being as the senior lecturer of the department we do not have any option or opinion to say about it.” (Teacher UOS, Mr AA)

Furthermore, it was also revealed that even the HOD does not promote that any faculty member under his supervision refuse to accept the change in the organisation.

“Even the Head of Department does not give power to the teachers that they can refuse to conduct online classes or examination and teachers on their end they also do not have such authority or power to resist towards it.” (Teacher UOS, Mr AA)

Further to the discussion, the respondent also shared his experience related to the influence of top-level management at departmental level across the institute.

“IT department will get the orders or request from top level not from departments. If we want to tell the IT department, they will not do anything extra, if any orders come from vice chancellor, then they have to do it at any cost.” (Teacher UOS, Mr AA)

The third case of UOL presented similar findings to LGU where the management restricted the use of software and tools for online learning. It is of benefit for teachers as well because it provide uniformity among the use of newly implemented change.

“There was a unifying, uniform method that was decided by the management of the university... The lectures that are going to be delivered, so it was not my choice, it was the choice of the university.” (Teacher UOL, Mr SK)

In UMT, teachers reported about how quick their management was to react to the change anticipated by the pandemic. In UMT, it was more related to managed change because the management even used Harvard-based guidelines to implement the change.

“So, they have been doing some efforts and relying on the material which is published on the international bases like Harvard... I know that GC University didn't operate for online

teaching for two months, UET for almost two months. When you have University for 2-3 months, they were waiting for the pandemic to be over.” (Teacher UMT, MR IQ)

From the last case of SU, it is consistent with UMT where the management is proactive, and the use of ERP systems were already in place, but they upgraded the systems to accommodate the change introduced due to the pandemic and in line with the orders of the HEC. The management of SU is different from LGU because the faculty was not threatened by the VC related to their jobs in SU if they did not accept the change. The management was proven to be helpful because they provided trainings and informative sessions to the faculty and other faculty members.

“Of course, internally we are being instructed by the management that these are the software you need to use, and MOODLE need to be connected with this part. So, I'll say that we follow the instructions of the management.” (Teacher SU, Mr KS)

Another positive aspect of the SU's management is that they did not restrict their employees to a specific set of software, and it was at the discretion of the faculty to use software with which they were familiar.

“It is the teachers who tries to choose the platform and the management never asks to like specifically use the zoom or Microsoft team.” (Teacher SU, Mr IS)

External Forces

There are various external factors which affect the adoption of e-learning in which the Higher Education Commission of Pakistan plays a vital role. Dr L explained how they have to follow the policies in order to comply with the rules and regulations of the accreditation body.

“We have to make sure that we are in compliance with all the policies, both if it is, whether it is on campus activity or it is e-learning, we have to comply with those protocols as well.” (Teacher LGU, Dr L)

Dr L. explains the involvement of the accreditation body by providing trainings and seminars to the teachers to prepare them for the implementation of e-learning on a country-wide scale.

“There is one accreditation body which keeps on organising different seminar and workshops and I recently attended two of them.” (Teacher LGU, Dr L)

In relation to teaching methodology and examination policies, the HEC provided policy guidelines to the HEIs to abide by, for those who conduct online classes and examinations to make it possible for the students to continue their studies during the pandemic. Additionally,

the change implementation required approval from the HEC which also delayed the process of implementation, and it also resulted in lower morale of the employees.

“It is being conveyed by the HEC that we are bound to adopt case study method... We cannot do anything until unless we get approval from HEC.” (Teacher LGU, Miss F)

To maintain the accreditation with the governing bodies, the institute had to follow the policies issued by HEC to maintain the quality of education. During the pandemic, the HEC directed the institutes to use specific software and tools to implement and use e-learning in traditional institutes. Also, it was suggested by the teacher that any support provided by the HEC will help the institute to implement e-learning more efficiently.

“If HEC gives ideas or any accreditation for it any support forum for e-learning, then universities will implement more e-learning.” (Teacher UOL, Mr AA)

It is seen that external pressure or forces, such as the pandemic and the HEC, made the management of UOL implement e-learning otherwise the use of e-learning was limited to asynchronous tools only and in the public sector those tools were not used.

“I think it was basically more of external factor that made us choose e-learning as an institute rather internal.” (Teacher UOL, Miss RC)

In regard to external forces, the teachers from UMT did not mention about the involvement of the HEC towards the use of software however, the HEC published guidelines from time to time to help the HEIs towards managing the change.

SU's faculty mentions that the HEC as an external factor did not provide facilitations to the private sector in terms of finances which could help them to use premium paid e-learning software.

“It is very hard in Pakistan to manage such kind of services. You know like hundreds and thousands of dollars I mean PKR160.00 for \$1.00. And when you ask for \$50,000 and \$60,000 or \$20,000, it's a lot of money. So private sector usually faces a lot of challenges. Obviously, yeah, that's actually a major concern.” (Teacher SU, Mr KS)

It is also noted that there have been significant mental health issues during pandemic related to online classes not only in students but also in teachers. Similarly, the pandemic has also resulted in lost or reduced income which also triggers anxiety, depression and stress in students which ultimately results in low morale hence, the motivation between the students is reduced.

5.4.2 Organisational Support (HOD)

HODs or Academic Managers act as leaders or managers in HEIs to manage the change, update policies, staff development opportunities such as arranging seminars or trainings either within the institute or, in the case of COVID-19, also online. They act as middle managers and provide management support related to technology or finance to motivate the academics to learn and adapt (Almaiah and Mulhem, 2018).

The interview from LGU shows that the top-level management provided training sessions for the faculty and also arranged weekly meetings which helped them to shift to online mode. LGU also provided MOODLE coordinators to their faculty which helped them to understand the use of e-learning tools.

“It was a vigorous training session like every week there were meetings, there were sessions, and all the teachers were listened and given time to develop themselves... they were given assistance like MOODLE coordinator, one MOODLE central team, our IT team, our ERP team.” (HOD LGU, DR SA)

Further, when questioned about resistance, it was seen that students were more resistant than the teachers towards the change due to issues and challenges they faced.

“They were not that resistant... teachers were trying to get it because it was a new norm and our faculty, especially my department, they are highly motivated people... The resistance was from the students, not from faculty.” (HOD LGU, Dr SA)

The second case of a public university depicts similar actions of support provided by the management, notably trainings to the faculty and also, they provided manuals to the students to learn about the e-learning tools and software.

“Initially we had university level training after that we had our own department level training such as using Zoom, how to conduct online classes. We also not only provided trainings to the teachers but also, we provided manuals for it for students.” (HOD UOS, Mr HA)

The data collected from public university shows that there was no resistance towards the implementation because a public sector faculty is more inclined towards saving their jobs by not showing resistance towards the change and secondly the management is more autocratic in public HEIs.

The third case of UOL provided similar findings to LGU because most of the staff in private HEIs are younger and they are self-motivated towards learning new technology. Additionally, the management provided non-monetary motivations to increase the morale of the faculty to accept the change and due to the pandemic, monetary support was not provided by the management.

“All the teachers were really happy to learn new things and some of them had some problems of learning, not cooperation, so they were motivated... I would be honest, non-monetary motivations, there were a lot of them... but as far as we talk about the finances, the situation was not good.” (HOD UOL, Mr SR)

It is seen that UOL adopted a different strategy to implement the change, the management there reviewed different universities at international and national level to explore the motivational and implementation models used in those institutes to help the implementation process.

“We made a strategy that every month we are going to explore a new technology which is used throughout the world, any part of the world in the education sector... we have learned couple of different models being used by different universities.” (HOD UOL, Mr SR)

The fourth case, from UMT, depicts that the management used two different departments to provide support through the implementation of e-learning during the pandemic. It is a different approach among other private and public institutes, and it provided them more focused trainings and certifications related to e-learning methodologies.

“One department is called SL, which is about the center of teaching and learning is constantly providing training programs to all faculty members... then we have another Department which is called EMT, so they are already working before this pandemic on. You know on making moves and you know offering degree not degree. Really you know certificates through this online portal.” (HOD UMT, Mr UM)

UMT was already engaged in online certifications provided to their faculty before the pandemic, but they were not recognised and approved by the HEC because before the pandemic HEC restricted the use of e-resources in conventional universities to provide any degrees. Therefore, zero credit hour certifications were provided to the faculty.

“We are already engaged in e-learning before this pandemic because some of our undergraduate programs they already offered courses which are completely online. So, because of you know HEC, we cannot offer credit hour courses at that time, so we are using mandatory zero credit hour courses which were

completely run online.” (HOD UMT, Mr UM)

Furthermore, the HOD confirmed that there was no proper strategy or structure used by the management to implement the e-learning.

“There is no as such formal structure” (HOD UMT, Mr UM)

Moreover, the HOD recognised the need of e-learning and to overhaul the educational system in Pakistan to offer competitive degrees and skills to the students.

The last case, of SU, provided important and different insights about the organisational support provided by the management. It is seen that the Chairman of SU provided the opportunity to the faculty and other managerial employees to complete different online courses offered on EdX by Harvard University and Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), both in the US, related to online learning and teaching. It helped the management to implement the change in a more sophisticated and strategic way.

“As for our leadership, they said you will be having some (online courses) ... four to five sort of online trainings they have to do in this pandemic... then we are talking about Stephen Covey’s the seven habits of highly effective people... Also, we had it from our Edx courses.” (HOD SU, Mr HS)

Furthermore, SU provided teacher assistants who had more technological literacy to help those teachers and HODs with lesser knowledge of the online systems and to accept the change.

“We with our teacher assistants, they help us, and they are just taking us along in these things because we are more prone to a physical classroom.” (HOD SU, Mr HS)

Also, to tackle the issues related to infrastructure, the SU’s management asked their faculty members to conduct their online classes from the university campus because they have better infrastructure at the campus. It helped those teachers who did not have the right infrastructure available at their houses.

“We have asked our teachers to be in the University and they’ll be taking their lectures there while they are in the University.” (HOD SU, Mr HS)

From the above findings, it is evident that management’s support is essential towards accepting the change because it will guide and help the faculty, students and other managerial and administrative employees to support the change and accept it.

5.4.3 Technology Support (Student Focus Group)

In order to support the implementation, the students must be provided with trainings, software and hardware support to better cope with the immediate need of implementing e-learning.

The first case of LGU provided insights about the management, it shows that students were not well communicated to about the change and minimum support was provided by the management. However, the IT department was seen working at optimum capacity by managing the queries of the students in a timely and efficient manner. The students still believe that if more trainings and better infrastructure were provided by the university's management then the students will be able to accept the change more quickly.

"I think they should have provided us training." (Student LGU, FS1)

The findings from public institutes shed light on more crucial matters such as students being neglected in public institutes in terms of sharing their views on the policy or any change implementation. Also, it was the first time e-learning methods were used in public institutes, therefore, there were many flaws and issues with the LMS system from which arose the problem of a communication gap between teachers and students.

"I guess the major flaw in the LMS was that it should allow students to leave comments directly for the teachers. There should be an option for course related comments, and you should have the option of direct link with the teacher... I guess in Pakistan it is still part of their mentality to not involve students. Students are not involved in anything in Pakistan. Their opinions are not mattered, especially in public institutes whereas in private they do little bit of importance." (Student UOS, MAH4)

As students are the main users of the technology apart from the faculty, the UOL's management focused on providing training and mock sessions to the students to accommodate them in relation to the implementation of e-learning systems in UOL. It also shows that UOL is different from LGU because in LGU a minimum level of technological support was provided to the students.

"Before moving on to SLATE we had our proper training sessions... on which they told us how to enrol your course, how you suppose to go for your exam and everything." (Student UOL, KH2)

"They used to show us an online tutorial before any enhancement like if they have enhanced their software." (Student UOL, AM3)

In comparison with the private sector, UMT's management collaborated with PTCL (internet provider) to provide student packages during the pandemic to accommodate the change. It shows that guiding coalition with external stakeholders provides additional help to the internal stakeholder to accept the change.

However, there was no guiding coalition between internal stakeholders which will assist the management to successfully implement the change. The faculty and management direct the students towards learning by doing concept to help the students to increase their technological literacy.

"As far as technological measures are concerned, I believe it is learning by doing." (Student UMT, HU3)

The above findings from this theme explains that even in private institutes, the levels of technological support provided to the students are different depending upon the management's consideration towards involving the students in implementation.

Management and Administrative Stakeholders

5.4.4. Levers of Change Management (LGU IT Manager and UOS Registrar)

The IT department manager of LGU highlighted the strategy which should be adopted by the HEIs to implement the change. However, he clearly identifies that a proper management model is required by the institutes to help them in managing and accepting the change.

"The change starts from the teachers. The first and foremost thing that we need is the teacher training, will need to prepare the teachers. We need to prepare the instructors about the upcoming structures to get through them to evaluate the students and to teach the students. The third parameter is the designing of the courses... We need to have a new framework, new strategy that needs to be adopted by the students and the teachers as well." (IT Manager LGU, Mr JN)

It is also noted that the manager called it a "*drastic change*" when e-learning implementation was started during the pandemic.

"That was a drastic change, not a marginal I can tell... It is the need of the hour to develop the strategy framework for work to go in such situations... Institutes, unfortunately or fortunately, you can say there is a lot of room to do that is being created that needs to be developed." (IT Manager LGU, Mr JN)

Furthermore, the involvement of the Registrar from a public institute is also studied. In UOS, the QEC department was used to evaluate and monitor the quality of education provided through online resources. It also helped the management to provide recommendations to the teachers to improve their teaching process to help the students to accept the change.

“We have our online system through which we take the feedback of the teachers, and our Quality Enhancement Cell produces a report on it which we discuss it with our teachers how they can improve the results of their students and we share ideas with each other. Due to this, students’ progression is also monitored by the report given by QEC.” (Registrar UOS)

The registrar also confirms that the only lever of change in his public institute was the pandemic because face-to-face classes are still prioritised which makes it difficult for other stakeholders to accept the change.

“Yes e-learning certainly is a very good way of spreading education in different areas, but classroom education cannot be replaced with online learning as face-to-face learning. But e-learning can be our second-best option.” (Registrar UOS)

The difference between private and public institutes can be seen clearly from the above theme. In private institutes, the use of e-resources were accepted because they were already using it in some form. However, the public institutes are already low on financial budget from the government therefore, it puts more burden on the management to implement technological change.

5.4.5 Teachers’ Attitude Towards the Use of E-learning (EC)

The examinations controller stated about the problems at the beginning of the implementation specifically the issues related with the use of the e-learning tools such as new LMS system, Zoom and Google Classroom. With the help of trainings provided to the students and teachers, it helped them to understand the use of e-resources which resulted in better communication between faculty and students.

“When we used E-Systems students are very confused teachers are not trained but due to activities after some time students are available and staff is trained. Now online classes there is no resistance and no issues for this.” (EC SU, Mr HR)

It also shows that open-book exams were conducted online, and those measures are also favoured by the examination department to help the faculty. The open-book exams are also

instructed by the HEC informing about the considerations and how open-book exams can be conducted (HEC Guide 6, 2020).

Further, the examination department of SU is now integrating Turnitin with their LMS and other online systems to check for plagiarism in online exams.

“Our next target is to link Turnitin with it so that as soon as the inputs come on Turnitin it will highlight to the students that it is copy pasted.” (EC SU, Mr HR)

It shows that with the proper help and resources from the management and external environment, the change can be managed in a more efficient and effective manner. It also motivates the employees to accept the change and adjust themselves with the new norm of the organisation or industry.

HEC Interview (External Stakeholder)

5.5 Introduction

The Higher Education Commission of Pakistan (HEC) is an independent regulatory body established through the Constitution of Pakistan to oversee, regulate and provide accreditation to the HEIs in Pakistan (HEC, 2021U). The HEC regulates according to the Higher Education Commission Ordinance 2002 which defines the functions, positions, appointments of executives and other staff members, resignations and allowances of the staff members, and meetings and powers of the commission. Further the audits, authorisations, delegations and representation of the commission are also included (HEC, 2002).

The HEC is considered as the most important stakeholder of HEIs of Pakistan, as it issues the guidelines and policies for the universities which they have to abide by to maintain their accreditation status. In the current research, the author contacted the Chairman of the HEC via email to conduct an interview. The Chairman advised Mr AW who acts as Advisor Co-ordinator in HEC Islamabad to participate on his behalf. The interview was conducted via Zoom and the interview sheet was sent prior to the interview to discuss any questions beforehand to make sure the respondent had a clear idea of the questions.

The interview was analysed using thematic analysis, and emergent themes were identified by carefully considering the interview's important topics. These themes help the researcher to answer the research questions.

EMERGENT THEMES

5.6 Change Management Models/Process

Under this theme are three sub-themes which are used to identify any change model or process has been used by the HEC to direct the universities while implementing the change that is e-learning during the pandemic.

5.6.1 Change Management

In this theme, the researcher will analyse how the change management strategies (if used) are selected and when the sudden change was introduced by the environmental factors due to COVID-19, then how the HEC manages to tackle the situation to communicate with its important stakeholders.

When it was questioned about how the HEC is making sure of maintaining quality of education both in private and public institutes, the interviewee responded with major concerns related to online learning and e-learning tools especially in pandemic situation.

“Particularly during the pandemic, actually online education or distance education has been one area where HEC was very worried about the quality of learning.” (Mr AW)

Before the pandemic, the HEC also asked the universities in both private and public sectors, apart from Allama Iqbal Open University and Virtual University (Pakistan), to stop their online projects which was due to the difficulty of maintaining and observing the quality of education providing in the institutes. Therefore, when the pandemic struck the world then the HEC allowed the universities to adopt e-learning methods to accommodate students.

“The pandemic actually forced us to review this area at a very much greater speed and try to facilitate the universities. To adopt or transit into the online.” (Mr AW)

In terms of managing the change, a comprehensive policy was drafted by developing an online portal and dashboard for the universities and their management to let the HEC know about the status of their online readiness. The HEC published policy guidance for HEIs which contains three tier levels to differentiate the universities on the basis of their online readiness. The “online readiness” policy is a step towards managing the change which includes the management of students by providing them access to the internet and technology via allowing them to visit the campus at a reduced capacity of 30% of their overall enrollment. It is because Pakistan is a developing nation and the availability and access to the technology and internet is not available to every student therefore to implement e-learning it is necessary to have access to both of these elements.

“Accommodating students, very limited number of students on campus in hostels where there is absolutely no possibility of getting them connected to the University online resources then these are the online readiness policies basically provided for these things.” (Mr AW)

When specifically questioned about the resistance faced by the stakeholders due to the introduction of e-learning, the advisor stated that there were challenges but not resistance from the stakeholders. However, the pandemic helped the HEC in terms of reducing the resistance and converting it into challenges because stakeholders such as faculty and students have a clear understanding that they do not have any other option if they wish to continue their studies in the pandemic.

“During the pandemic, in particular they don't have any choice as the institutions are mostly closed for face-to-face learning. Students were also well aware of these situations and the objective was to minimize the academic disruption.” (Mr AW)

Lastly, the HEC conducted a Vice Chancellors’ meeting which included VCs from private and public universities to discuss their issues related to the use of e-learning and to helping each other by providing training and sharing resources. However, during the interviews with private universities, it is seen that they do not share their resources such as any specific programs, however, they only share their ideas related to the use of technology.

“Last year or so we have had 13 vice Chancellors, Community meeting Vice Chancellors Committee comprises of Vice Chancellor of all public and private sector universities in Pakistan. So, we encourage universities not only to share best practices, but also support each other in terms of facilitating their students in terms of facilitating their faculty training, their difficulty, and providing maximum possible.” (Mr AW)

With the help of the above discussion, it can be seen that the HEC deploys different management techniques, however, they did not follow any particular management model to initially identify the issues and with the help of those identified issues plan the initial stage.

5.6.2 Resources

The resources provided by the HEC include digital courses offered in partnership with Coursera and EdX, and also includes financial support to the public universities to upgrade their digital systems and software. However, the LMS systems were not provided by the HEC as most of the private universities already have their in-house built LMS software but in terms of public universities, they had to form their LMS system during the pandemic which became very challenging for both the teachers and students.

The HEC initially collected data related to online readiness which allowed them to purchase licenses from Microsoft and other service providers such as Turnitin, to give those licenses to the HEIs at subsidised rates.

“We undertook agreements with Microsoft and other service providers so that we bought licenses and we facilitated universities to acquire learning management systems at economic cost.” (Mr AW)

The HEC recommended the HEIs to accommodate those students who did not have access to the internet, or to international students by allowing them to stay in their hostels during the pandemic so they could access the online classes to continue their studies without any disruption.

“What we have done to resolve this area is that at the moment we have allowed that 1/3 of the capacity in hostels designed capacity mostly can be used to accommodate students with a research and lab needs who have no connectivity, and for the foreign students.” (Mr AW)

Due to the pandemic, the HEC changed different policies related to the resources used by the universities to accommodate different stakeholders. However, completely online learning also has its demerits, therefore, hybrid modes are favoured by the universities for use in the future.

5.6.3 Training and Motivational Strategies

In terms of training strategies, the HEC created a Technology Support Committee which helps the HEIs related to training facilities and providing other online resources.

“We created Technology Support Committee for developing faculty in terms of teaching, research and governance.” (Mr AW)

The HEC also initiated the concept of Vice Chancellors’ meeting which includes VCs from private and public sector universities, and they share their views and issues related to current policies. The latest meeting was held on 29th October 2021 which included the introduction of the Online and Distance Learning Policy (HEC, 2021B). The HEC encourages universities to provide support to their fellow universities in relation to training during the difficult times of the pandemic.

5.7 Change Implementation Process

This main theme includes two sub-themes which shows that before the pandemic there was no policy in place for the use or implementation of e-learning in the HEIs of Pakistan.

5.7.1 Policies and Regulations

As mentioned above, the HEC issued different notices and regulations related to the online and hybrid modes of teaching during the pandemic. The HEC also published a special comprehensive policy related to online and distance learning to guide the HEIs with the use of e-learning tools. Before the pandemic, the HEC had no particular policy related to online programs apart from the two online universities in Pakistan. There were only some instructions in the early introduction of e-learning in 2002 but there was a need of comprehensive policy which was issued recently.

“There was no policy that mandated all the universities in Pakistan.” (Mr AW)

The HEC also published eight different COVID-19 guidance related to different programs, guidelines for faculty and administration of HEIs, related to assessments and examinations and re-opening of the campuses.

5.7.2 Collaborations and Explorations

With the help of partnerships and collaborations, the HEC can extend its support to HEIs not only in terms of policy guidance but also in terms of technical support through exchange programmes. The HEC is trying to create new partnerships with national and international stakeholders which will help the HEIs of Pakistan to benefit from them. For instance, The HEC collaborated with British Council Pakistan on a Knowledge Exchange Initiative program which will help the HEC to get a flow of knowledge exchange between the UK and Pakistani HEIs (HEC, 2021D).

“There are number of universities which are already collaborating for local programs.” (Mr AW)

Similarly, the HEC also have collaborations with Coursera, EdX, Microsoft and Google to provide different technical solutions and courses to the faculty, administrative staff and students of Pakistani HEIs. With the help of new partnerships, the HEC will explore new venues to welcome the new evolution of technology at macro level which can be managed with the help of proposed framework of the study to manage and implement change in the HEIs across Pakistan.

5.8 Stakeholders' Perceptions

With the help of stakeholders' perceptions, the HEIs can manage the change effectively because it will allow them to consider the factors, barriers, challenges, and positive aspects of the use of e-learning to implement the change. This theme includes two sub-themes which are as follows.

5.8.1 Changing Nature of Academic Teaching

The HEC helped faculties of both private and public institutes by providing them virtual resources such as courses offered by various international universities to assist them through the transition from traditional to online education. One of the major changes seen in Pakistani HEIs is that they are conducting classes in hybrid mode, namely one-week physical classes and one-week online classes, which helps the students to stay focused on their studies and also accommodates those students who do not have enough electronic resources.

"We have basically given that authority to the University with local health authorities to manage their classes, exams and resources in accordance with the prevailing situation." (Mr AW)

Further to that, the HEC is considering initiating different certified courses which will be introduced on a universal platform such as Coursera or EdX, but those courses will be certified by the HEC, and students will be eligible for credit transfer as well. Previously, online learning was not allowed by the HEC in a traditional university setting, however, the HEC advisor confirms that they will continue the use of e-learning in future because the future is related to information systems.

"I think the information age is coming and the future is I think it would be the way of learning." (Mr AW)

However, it will take time to fully implement the credit transfer courses which are online-based. In the light of the pandemic and shifting to online pedagogy, the major challenge faced by the teachers was assessing the online assignments, conducting online examinations and also providing evaluations to those examinations. The changing nature of academic teaching requires new methods to manage this change therefore, with the help of the proposed framework in the current study it will help the faculty and administrative management to overcome challenges and issues which have been posed by the forced implementation of e-learning during the pandemic.

5.8.2 Factors' Compromising Learning Process

The major factor which the HEC was most concerned about concerning online teaching and learning was to maintain the quality of education. It was also explained by the HEC advisor that during the pandemic, it allowed students to stay at home and take online classes for about five to six hours consecutively. The use of online tools does not allow students to socialise with each other in a similar fashion to face-to-face learning. Other factors include internet availability, infrastructure, quality of teaching, virtual lab resources, and content creation.

“There are difficulties in terms of assessments. In terms of development of content, a teacher who has never been used to teach online expecting that person to completely transform the same quality over a very short period of time is very difficult... there is difficulty in maintaining the attention span of the students in particular when you expect a student to have online classes for six to 8 hours... so there are challenges and there are challenges at the domestic level as well.” (Mr AW)

The above-mentioned factors can be minimised with the help of change management models which would help the HEC to make certain policies to overcome such challenges and minimise the negatively affecting factors.

5.8.3 External Forces

The only external force which made the HEC change its policies related to the use of e-learning tools was the pandemic. Due to the pandemic, the use of online classes or virtual environment tools were allowed to be used by the traditional universities whereas previously it was not allowed by the HEC due to concerns about maintaining the quality of education.

“What we did was that we started in pandemic to develop a comprehensive policy so that the universities then initiate their programs in accordance with the online policy.” (Mr AW)

As the HEC is the major player in creating and issuing policies and rules for HEIs therefore, the only external force which acts for the HEC in this regard is environmental because the HEC acts as an independent body.

5.9 Documentational Analysis

5.9.1 Introduction

In this section, the documents issued by the HEC will be reviewed and discussed to compare with the findings collected from the interviews. This chapter is based on three sections which includes the all eight policy documents issued by the HEC in the wake of the pandemic to provide directives to the HEIs for the use of e-learning tools and methods.

5.9.2 Guidelines for Management and Faculty

It is observed that before the pandemic, the HEC did not take prominent steps regarding the use or implementation of e-learning systems in pedagogical settings. However, the HEC published a report in September 2019 which refers to the implementation of project Smart Class in collaboration with PERN (Pakistan Education and Research Network) (HEC EOI, 2019). The main objective of issuing this policy was to upgrade the infrastructure and technological measures in public sector universities with the help of a grant from China. However, the published date of the document shows that it had just been introduced when the pandemic struck, it shows that before the pandemic the use of e-resources was not promoted by the HEC.

When the HEIs faced the difficult situation of COVID-19, the HEC came up with different policies in which it initially provided guidelines for the management and faculties of the institutes. In the first document, the HEC presented guidelines for the institutes to provide health and safety measure for their employees and students. The guidelines included measures related to the campus and hostel settings. Further it states about the blended mode of teaching where teachers should be rotated on weekly basis to provide and record lectures through campuses (HEC Guide 2, 2020). The findings related to the online classes and campus operations are consistent with the data collected through this study's interviews. The next sub-section defines those policies which provide guidelines towards the implementation.

5.9.3 Implementation Guidelines

This section contains directives issued by the HEC related to the implementation or use of e-learning in traditional campuses during pandemic lockdown. With the difficult scenario of COVID-19, the HEC initiated a committee to oversee the e-learning activities and provide assistance towards the use and implementation of e-learning tools in the HEIs of Pakistan. The *Technology Support Committee's (TSC's)* main purpose is to monitor the quality of

education through online means and maintain the continuity of teaching during any disruption faced by the HEIs.

The TSC policy document provided data of public institutes in terms of their online readiness which shows that only 40 public HEIs had a LMS system already in use whereas two institutes (Virtual University (VU) and IBA Karachi) had LMS, and video conferencing tools already implemented in their campuses. The data for private institutes were not included, however, it also reveals that the HEC recommended the use of Microsoft Teams due to its collaboration through PERN, during the pandemic and implementation of e-learning. In reality, the institutes utilised Google Classroom to conduct classes which is highlighted by the interviewees. However, the HEC directed that the use of third-party software is allowed, such as Zoom, Webex, Big Blue Button etc. (HEC Guide 3, 2020).

The HEC recommended that institutes which have more than 10,000 students should adopt VULMS which is provided by VU, and it includes video conferencing through Adobe Connect. However, the LMS is provided free, but Adobe subscription will be given for the first six months and after that institutes will have to pay \$500 per month. In comparison to MOODLE and Microsoft Teams, the VULMS costs around \$24,000 annually whereas the other two are free platforms. The cost of infrastructure and IT support is different depending upon the number of students in the campus. The HEC also provided PKR 10 million to each public institute to support their implementation of e-learning and provided infrastructural support for the first six months of the implementation. In relation to private institutes, no financial or subscription support is provided to them (HEC Guide 8, 2020).

Technical support is provided by the HEC for both public and private institutes through *TSC* and different videos were provided for the faculties to understand the use of e-learning software. Moreover, the HEC provided guidelines towards the technology implementation as follows:

- Institutes with fewer than 10,000 students should determine which virtual tools would be used and HEIs with more than 10,000 will be contacted by the VULMS team to implement the VULMS system.
- The QEC department of HEIs are instructed to carefully monitor the quality of the content uploaded online and provided during lectures.

- Use of social media such as Facebook and Twitter is recommended to maintain communication within the internal stakeholders and WhatsApp groups are especially identified to be used by faculties (HEC Guide 3, 2020).

With the implementation guidelines, the HEC also provided initial research related to the issues faced by the stakeholders through a complaints portal. The major issues were as follows:

- Connectivity problems- This comprised the majority of the complaints, about 30% complaints were regarding connectivity issues from rural and certain provinces such as Balochistan, Gilgit Baltistan, and Azad Jammu and Kashmir.
- Faculty Concerns- During the pandemic, faculties shared their concerns of visiting the campus for lecture recording and delivery of online lectures. The HEC therefore directed the management to exempt the faculties from on-campus attendance and to provide lectures from home.
- Quality of Education- As it was a new method for most of the stakeholders, the complaints received were mostly for ineffective online classes, understandability of audio lectures and teachers' experience and their training in providing online lectures. To overcome this issue, the HEC started the process of creating the National Knowledge Bank (NKB) for all HEIs. Further, the HEC directed HEMIS to provide framework for the HEIs related to online teaching and learning.
- Quality of Assessment- 13% of complaints received were related to the assessment criteria as it was new for the students to take online examinations.
- Fee Issues- students and parents shared their concerns about the value of money for online education, because the quality of education was not considered to be the same by the stakeholders and 10% of the complaints received by the HEC were regarding fees. In order to gain the students' confidence, the HEC directed QAA to undertake regular performance evaluations and instructed the HEIs on their fee criteria (HEC Guide 2, 2020).

The above guidelines helped HEIs implement e-learning and make changes over time to accept the change and use e-learning tools, but it is evident from the guideline document that institutes need a framework to successfully implement and use e-learning methods.

5.9.4 Assessment and Online Readiness

The faculties had issues with online assessment and exams. Due to concerns about examination and assessment, the HEC provided guidelines at four different levels where HEIs were instructed that the preferred method of conducting examination is open-book examination and the least preferred method is closed-book or traditional examination, after lockdown restrictions. STEM students had special exam and assessment instructions. Science students requires lab attendance, which was impossible during the pandemic. Further, connectivity issues were addressed to accommodate students with internet connectivity problems or mitigating circumstances such as health issues during COVID-19 (HEC Guide 6, 2020). For MS/MPhil and PhD students, video conferencing was recommended for the defence of vivas. Online submissions were made through university-designated authorities (HEC Guide 6A, 2020).

The above findings are related to assessments and exams, the HEC also provided guidelines for HEIs to show they are ready for online education. HEC uses six factors to determine HEIs' online readiness. HEIs are categorised as basic, effective, and exemplary. In the basic tier, HEIs may have LMS systems, but they are not functioning and used properly. Problems may include technological issues, communication problems between teachers and students, and sharing of module contents. Effective tier reflects better LMS system integration with online libraries and other equipment. Exemplary reflects that a HEI making continuous progress in online learning systems and student-teacher communications.

In terms of online readiness, the HEC introduced an online structure for the HEIs which also includes quality standards for online learning and teaching. The concept covers eight major areas which includes university (as a campus), the course (module contents), the faculty (requires training and certain certifications), the library (online and on-campus), the technology (equipment and software), the laboratory (online and on-campus), the examination (online assessment), and the student (connectivity). Furthermore, the HEC provided different supporting mechanisms which provide support through different departments and teams to help the HEIs to implement e-learning and this is shown in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3 HEC Support Teams

(Source: HEC Guide 5, (2020))

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due to copyright
restrictions

5.10 Summary

The transcribed interviews were carefully analysed using thematic analysis. With the collected data and analysis, infrastructural issues, technological literacy, cultural issues, and availability of e-resources in Pakistan were identified as challenges and barriers to change adoption. The five cases show how universities, their management, students, and other stakeholders implement change.

The findings also show that private and public universities use different operational models, which raises concerns about e-learning implementation. In private institutes, change can be implemented if higher-level management is satisfied with the proposed outcome, as in the case of UMT where simulation software was approved before the pandemic. Whereas in public institutes there is a long process for approving the proposal from syndicate and other board members of the university. It shows that managing and implementing change in the private sector would be easier if the direction was given with beneficial appreciation, such as the HEC providing software subscriptions at discounted rates. Private sector employees are more likely to be self-motivated, while public sector professors are more likely to be incentive driven. As the theoretical framework explains, private university faculties are more successful at creating guiding coalitions to boost the morale of their colleagues to accept change, whereas in the public sector it depends more on management or self-motivation. With the proposed theoretical framework, institutes can manage e-learning or any other change. Policy documents and their findings on e-learning in Pakistani HEIs are presented. Further, before the pandemic the HEC did not regulate online courses or teaching for traditional campuses.

In the next chapter, semi-structured interviews and documentational findings will be used along with previous studies to analyse and discuss the data collected.

Chapter 6 Analysis and Discussion

6.1 Introduction

In Chapter 5, interview transcriptions were analysed thematically. HODs, managers, professors, and other stakeholders were interviewed. Focus group interviews were also used to collect student information and hear the views of students. The inductive approach used in the thematic analysis expands the interviewees' perspectives. Analysing interviews from different angles helps deepen the understanding.

Chapter 5 provided comparison between private and public institutes which shows how e-learning is implemented across universities in the same Pakistani province. The thematic analysis helped the researcher to understand the barriers, challenges, and potential benefits of e-learning during and before the pandemic. Chapter 5 described the regulatory body's (HEC) role in implementing and managing change in public and private HEIs. HEIS lacks a framework to help HEIs effectively manage change.

The demographics of the participants are shown in Table 6.1 which provides their gender, approximate age, post in the institute as a stakeholder, and institute name.

Table 6.1. Interviewees

Respondents	No. of Interviewees	University/ Institute	Gender
Teachers	4	LAHORE GARRISON UNNERSIYY	Female2 Male 2
HOD	1		Male
Student Focus Group	3		All Male
IT Manager	1		Male
Teachers	1	University of Sargodha	Male
HOD	1		Male
Registrar	1		Male
Focus Group Students	4		Male3, Female 1
Teachers	2	University of Management and Technology	All Male
HOD	1		Male
Focus Group Students	3		All Female
Teachers	3	University of Lahore	Male 1, Female2
HOD	1		Male
Focus Group Students	3		Female 2, Male 1
Teachers	3	Superior University	All Male
HOD	1		Male
Examination Controller	1		Male
Business Development Manager-	1		Male
Professor& Director of Research Centre	1	NUST	Male
HOD	1	Beaconhouse National University	Male
Teacher	1	Arfa University of Technology	Male
Talent Acquisition Manager	1	Allied Bank L1D	Male
Teacher	1	Punjab University	Male

Source: Self-work of researcher

From the above Table 6.1, it can be seen that the total number of participants in this research is 41 however, the number of interviews used in the current study was 26 which includes four focus group interviews from students and one staff member from the HEC which is not included in the above table. In this chapter, the objectives will be reviewed and analysed in relation to the findings and previous literature which will help to provide the analysis of the current study. Following are the objectives of the current study:

1. To conduct a comprehensive and critical literature review on understanding the role of change management models and implementation of e-learning in HEIs.
2. To identify applicable model(s) to manage the change (that is implementation of e-learning) in HEIs of Pakistan.
3. To examine the process of change management towards e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan.
4. To explore the challenges that influence the individual stakeholder's perceptions in the implementation of e-learning
5. To provide recommendations on the implementation of change with the help of stakeholder analysis.

With the help of the above objectives, the current chapter is divided among sub-sections which includes *the process of change management in HEIs of Pakistan*, *factors affecting the implementation of change (e-learning)*, and *findings through the frame of applicable models*. In the next section, an overview of the research will be presented which includes the findings from the data collected through semi-structured interviews.

6.2 Synopsis of Research Findings

The results collected from the data through semi-structured interviews and documentation reveal the processes undertaken by the HEIs with the collaboration of the regulatory body (HEC) to implement the change (e-learning). The current study focuses on the implementation and managing the change that is e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. The results show that there are various factors such as technological literacy, infrastructure, language barrier, financial difficulty, internet availability, technology availability (that is software and hardware), and resistance from the staff aged over 45 are prominent factors to affect the implementation of the change.

Moreover, the data also reveals that in private HEIs, LMS systems were already introduced but they were not operational at full capacity. Furthermore, the pandemic made the HEIs implement both synchronous and asynchronous e-learning tools forcefully because before the pandemic even the regulatory body did not have any policies for online learning tools for pedagogical campuses. Cultural factors, such as living in a joint family household, makes it difficult for the students and teachers to conduct and take online classes from home. However, the HEC provided recommendations to the HEIs to allow teachers to give online lectures through campuses during pandemic restrictions. In terms of external stakeholder (HEC), the data reveals that HEC provided financial support to public HEIs and in terms of providing support through courses and training, it was provided to both private and public HEIs to train the teachers. Also, the collaboration between the HEC, Coursera and EdX gave rise to opportunities for students and teachers to take online courses at subsidised rates to accommodate the change. However, the whole process does not include any change management framework which helps the HEIs to manage the change more efficiently. Also, the HEIs did not communicate the change properly to their stakeholders, such as employees and students, to anchor the change. As Pakistan is a developing country, therefore, the priority is given to the traditional pedagogical methods instead online measures. However, the teachers and HODs of both private and public HEIs showed keen interest in the continued use of e-learning methods in their teaching and learning process.

The following section 6.3 will shed light on the process of change management showing how the HEIs managed the change when they were directed by the HEC to use online methods. Section 6.4 will report the challenges which are hindering the process of e-learning implementation and also any advantages mentioned by the stakeholders in relation to the use of e-learning, and section 6.5 discusses the change implementation process through the identified framework models to manage the change in HEIs of Pakistan.

Objective 3 To examine the process of change management towards e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan.

6.3 Process of Change Management in HEIs of Pakistan

In order to understand the HEIs response towards the change, it is important to learn about their methods of dealing with the introduction of change. One of the objectives of the current study is to check whether the HEIs considered any change management models or tools to manage the change as well as which processes or steps were taken by the management to implement the change in the organisation and which stakeholders were involved in the implementation process.

The current section is also divided among internal and external stakeholders to provide in-depth analysis of the findings from Chapter 6. Also, it will help to understand the processes and techniques which were considered by the external stakeholder that is the HEC. It will also help the researcher to pinpoint the views of the respondents according to their stakeholder groups.

6.3.1 Internal Stakeholders

The data will be analysed according to the internal stakeholders mentioned in section 5.4. Furthermore, as the study was initiated before the pandemic, the results will be analysed on the scenario of before and after it. The recorded responses indicate that professors in private HEIs are already familiar with the various e-learning technologies because private institutes were already employing asynchronous types of e-learning, such as, PowerPoint slides, articles, and case studies. In contrast, public institute teachers employed pedagogical methods prior to the pandemic.

However, with the environmental factor of the pandemic, the external stakeholder HEC and the Government of Pakistan issued the directives for implementing and using e-learning techniques (Mumtaz et al., 2021). It is observed that out of 205 HEIs, only 40 of them were capable of providing blended learning utilising online education (Ahmed, 2021).

According to qualitative data, private institutes have already implemented and used e-learning tools. Some private institutes were able to implement e-learning tools and deliver online lectures within days of the HEC's announcement. In contrast, public institutes were closed because management believed the pandemic would end soon. Teachers used WhatsApp and Facebook groups before COVID-19 to share important dates and news with

teachers and students, but they were not recommended by institutes and no formal directives were given to teachers about using social media tools.

Based on the thematic analysis of the data, the strategies used for implementing e-learning in the aftermath of a pandemic, both private and public institutions mentioned training sessions for teachers on the usage of common software, such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Google Meet. In addition to training, the Chairman of SU, required the teachers to finish free online Harvard University courses on EdX and Coursera that were connected to online teaching and learning. After completing the courses, they were awarded financial prizes for their achievements. Regarding public institutions, there was no financial incentive for teachers to quickly implement e-learning which increases user interest. First, this demonstrates that in developing countries like Pakistan, lack of financial support is the most significant barrier for higher education institutions to implement an ICT-related transformation. In private institutions, the e-learning programmes were either improperly implemented or the implementation process was slowed due to financial issues. All three private institutes had implemented a form of LMS, although these had not been fully deployed and utilised prior to the pandemic. This finding is consistent with the research of Aini et al., (2020) and Almaiah et al., (2020), in which lack of interest and understanding among technology users were cited as change management challenges.

When asked about the techniques employed by the administration in the adoption of e-learning, the IT department manager from the LGU explains that the institute and administration require new strategies and a framework to assist students and teachers in adopting the shift. The interviewee's reaction is comparable to the findings of Kanwal et al. (2017), which show the need for a universal framework to boost the successful implementation of e-learning in Pakistani HEIs. This is due to the fact that the fundamental concept of implementing change at Pakistani HEIs is viewed as offering training that consists of change-related instructions such as those mentioned in Kotter's model. The HEIs created a sense of urgency, but there was no strategic vision formulation, which further impedes the acceleration of transformation.

E-learning is being implemented in Pakistan's public HEIs by following the directives of top-level management and external stakeholders such as the HEC. The HEC is the primary stakeholder where e-learning implementation was aided by providing video conferencing technologies; however, the HEC should promote change management strategies to effectively

execute e-learning (Farid et al., 2015). Introducing any change by the instructors or HOD in public institutes takes a lengthy process, including the permission of the institute's board and syndicate. Therefore, public institutes undertake changes in accordance with the directives of regulatory organisations. This is comparable to the findings of Khan and Jabeen (2019), in which the self-governance of public institutions is reduced and regulating body intervention is increased. The HEC is primarily responsible for executing any change across public institutions. Also, networking in the government sector plays a crucial part in authorising change projects, such as the adoption of the tenure track system in Pakistan's higher education institutions, which was made possible through the Pakistani government's influential connections within departments (Khan and Jabeen, 2019).

Furthermore, there are two major components revealed from the findings in Chapter 5 which are considered to be the only strategies used by the HEIs and are also directed by the HEC.

6.3.2 Training

Training the faculty and other employees to accept the change is the first and most essential technique utilised by HEIs in the e-learning implementation process. Regarding private institutions, it is evident that frequent trainings were provided because LMS systems were already in use, while HEIs must update their systems. When the systems were updated, the management provided training to the faculty and administrative staff to assist them with the transition. In addition, students received online training in the utilisation of newly implemented systems.

Providing a faculty with ICT training will assist them in integrating technology into their teaching and learning approaches (Asad et al., 2020). However, the basic training will only assist the faculty with regard to the usability of the tools, whereas for them to become professional users of the technology, additional training is required related to the creation of module content, the full use of the software, and the administration of exams. As indicated by students in focus group interviews, the absence of trainings is a key problem for them because teachers lacked sufficient knowledge of the tools, and some teachers were unaware of other e-learning software, such as Microsoft Teams. The documents published by the HEC indicate that Microsoft Teams should be considered by HEIs for online classes.

In the context of Pakistan, the greatest challenge in managing the transition is providing adequate training to the stakeholders and technology users. Recent research by Sarwar et al. (2020) indicates that students are dissatisfied with the quality of training provided to teachers

in order to conduct online classes. Prior to the pandemic, trainings on the use of e-learning tools were not provided on a regular basis in private institutes that already had LMS systems in place, resulting in little or no use of those software and tools (Bhuasiri et al., 2012; Eze et al., 2018; Hadullo et al., 2017). In public institutes, in this study's findings, the faculty was not involved in the implementation, and the institution only raised awareness of the change after the pandemic struck; before pandemic, no effort was made to implement a change in the public sector related to ICT. Due to the abrupt introduction of ICT, the faculty received minimal training; nonetheless, according to the HEC documents, they were instructed to take free online courses offered by the HEC to the faculty of public institutes. It is similar to the findings of Kundi and Nawaz (2014), in which the study demonstrates that the majority of faculty trainings do not meet their demands and criteria.

Private and public institutes do not offer students proper training. In the private sector, UOL had notified students by contacting them through WhatsApp groups and supplying them with information regarding software and resources. In contrast to other private and public institutions, they did not provide any training sessions to students in order to raise their awareness. However, with the assistance of the current framework, which is to use Leavitt's model to adjust the stakeholders by considering the drafting change component of the integrated models, it will be possible to overcome resistance and enhance acceptance of the change. It is also supported by Akhtar, Aslam, and Hussain (2021), who argued that tutorials and trainings will assist students use e-learning platforms efficiently (Njenga and Fourie, 2010).

Students believe that if trainings are provided, they will be able to comprehend the new technology and embrace the change more readily. It is consistent with the *drafting change* element of the framework, in which management gives information to stakeholders and creates a coalition of early adopters/learners of the technology. The objective of forming a coalition is due to the fact that when individuals acquire a specific skill set, they take it with them instead of leaving behind a successor to continue the process of managing the change in technology. According to Nawaz and Kundi (2010), in order to increase the implementation of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs, it is necessary to train stakeholders so that their perceptions match with reality.

The next section is related to the motivational techniques used by the management of the institute to implement the change.

6.3.3 Motivational Techniques

Teachers in Pakistan lack motivation to attend professional development courses due to unawareness of the significance of courses. However, the HEC began many development initiatives for both public and private sectors, but instructors continue to lag behind due to a lack of commitment towards developmental programmes and acceptance of change (Aslam, et al., 2012).

In the private sector, management uses regular techniques to boost faculty and administrative morale to accept the change. The most prominent technique is to provide non-monetary motivation to stakeholders, such as weekly meetings to receive feedback, technical support through the IT team, communicating the benefits of e-learning tools to the faculty and administration, and providing free online courses to the faculty. All four private HEI respondents indicated the above non-monetary motivators. Respondents from UOS said there were no such measures taken by the management, besides the HOD, who said the QEC department took feedback to ensure the quality of instruction and motivate good-performing faculty members.

In this research, only two private HEIs, SU and LGU, provided monetary rewards to their employees during the pandemic. In public institutes, stakeholders have no opinion on changes proposed by the regulatory authority or the institute because employees are concerned about their jobs rather than the change. Khan et al. (2021) applied Maslow's hierarchy model in his study of Pakistani HEIs and cited job security as a way to motivate and increase job satisfaction among employees. According to Chetty and Plessis (2021) workload, work pressure, and change management create job security concerns, which leads to a lack of physiological safety needs.

Student focus group responses indicate that students favour the use of e-learning in pedagogical settings as part of the blended learning idea. This is especially prevalent among UMT students, who all come from professional backgrounds and work in the morning before attending MS/MPhil classes in the evening. They discussed the convenience of attending lectures and the availability of module materials through e-learning. The level of motivation is deemed to be lowest among students of public institutes, as all students in the focus group remarked that the lecturers' engagement was minimal. This is due to cultural factors, such as the students are inclined towards face-to-face classes and the turning off of cameras during

lectures, particularly for female students, due to cultural factors. These findings are corroborated by Biskupic, Lackovic, and Jurina (2015), who noted that intrinsic, personal, and extrinsic factors influence the students' motivation towards acceptance of e-learning.

The data collected through interviews indicates that the majority of faculties and employees in private institutes are self-motivated and eager to learn new skills, whereas in public institutes there were no motivational techniques used and the teachers were only performing their duties to ensure a steady income stream. This demonstrates that the lack of motivation among public institute faculty members makes it difficult for them to accept change and sustain the quality of online education (Fatima et al., 2021).

6.3.4 External Stakeholders

The primary external stakeholder identified in this study is the HEC, the regulatory body in Pakistan. In addition to the HEC, the internet, and technology providers (businesses or vendors providing hardware and software support) were identified through the focus group interviews as external stakeholders. However, the HEC is regarded as the most important stakeholder because it publishes regulations and policies for HEIs about any system-wide changes.

According to the HEC interview, there were no official regulations and policies for the implementation of e-learning technologies prior to the pandemic; this is also supported by the HEC website. Maqsood et al. (2021), discuss how the absence of policy guidelines during the pandemic exerted tremendous pressure on educators and other stakeholders. However, documentation analysis reveals that the HEC only provided the fundamental policy rules, such as which software and tools may be utilised and what their outcomes will be. In addition, the disadvantages of these instruments in respect to examination and evaluation standards are discussed. In terms of strategic guidelines, such as establishing a framework for the institutes, the wider picture of pandemic change management is lacking. The HEC only emphasised providing professors and students with trainings and online courses whereas the HEC exclusively offered funding to public institutes to enhance their hardware and technology labs in order to provide higher-quality education through e-learning.

The analysis in the preceding sections 6.3.1, 6.3.2, 6.3.3, and 6.3.4 demonstrates that the HEIs require a framework to manage the change by managing the institutes' stakeholders. The management of the private HEIs demonstrated a keen interest in managing the transition by implementing e-learning and gradually upgrading their tools. Training and motivational

techniques are also used to provide a faculty with support; however, students require the same level of attention as teachers, as both are the primary technology users. The student focus group of private higher education institutions reveals that the management provided them with online practice exams to prepare them for the transition, whereas public institutions lack such initiatives. In addition, Pakistan has a strong culture of face-to-face learning and teaching, necessitating the use of change management models to infuse the change into the system. These findings are consistent with Aini et al.'s (2020) study that resistance to change and problems associated with the implementation of e-learning can be overcome with the assistance of change management models.

In comparison to the proposed framework, it can be seen that the HEIs are considering partial elements of the framework such as from Leavitt's model, people and technology are mainly discussed whereas tasks and structure were considered less. From the integrated models, in comparison to the public institute case, private HEIs considered the drafting change stage. In the public case, the faculty members were not involved directly with the implementation process which lacks the use of the love and belongingness element from Maslow's model. Furthermore, there were no guiding coalitions made in public institutes whereas in private cases, teacher assistants and MOODLE co-ordinators formed coalitions between faculty members to train them with the use of new tools.

The presented analysis is also consistent with the studies of Nogrsek and Vintar (2011), Budiharso and Tarman (2020), and Voigt et al. (2021), which describe the use of Kotter's eight-step model, Maslow's hierarchy of needs model, and Leavitt's diamond model to successfully manage ICT change in organisations. The findings also indicate that, with the aid of this study's theoretical framework, the essential parts of change management are elucidated, hence enhancing the process and management of change implementation in Pakistan's HEIs.

In my opinion, the stakeholders should consider the use of the proposed model because it will highlight the key stakeholders and also their involvement. Further, it will help the HEIs, Ministry of Education and regulatory body to understand the viewpoint of the users of the technology to eradicate the problems in the implementation process such as culture, literacy, language barriers, and change management issues.

Objective 4- To explore the challenges that influence the individual stakeholders' perceptions in the implementation of e-learning

6.4 Stakeholders' Perception

The fourth objective of this research is to highlight the challenges faced by the stakeholders, including students, teachers, HODs, administrative personnel, and the HEC, during the implementation of e-learning. Interviewing internal and external stakeholders has revealed a number of aspects, which are detailed in sections 5.3.2 and 5.8, respectively. In the current study, a number of challenges that impede the implementation process and influence the opinions of stakeholders towards the usage of e-learning were identified. Electricity, infrastructure, technological literacy, internet access, cultural elements, lack of engagement, online examination and invigilation, faculty pressure, and resistance to change are among the obstacles mentioned by internal stakeholders. While the external stakeholder indicated internet accessibility, infrastructure (including virtual lab resources), quality of instruction, and module content generation. The benefits of e-learning in their pedagogical context have been illuminated by students and teachers. These advantages include ease of access to module content, time management, and attending lectures.

6.4.1 Internal Stakeholders

6.4.1.1 Electricity

In developing countries like Pakistan, load-shedding is the biggest obstacle to online lectures. Power shortages prevent stakeholders from implementing and accepting e-learning in their institutes since e-learning requires computers and technology which are powered through electricity. UMT students highlighted electrical issues during presentations and online lectures as a concern for e-learning implementation.

Electricity is a basic need for implementing ICT tools, at initial planning stage of integrated models it should create urgency related to e-learning implementation, which requires electricity as one of the main components and acts as a physiological need for stakeholders to accept e-learning implementation.

The results are congruent with those of Sarwar et al. (2020), who found that dentistry students in Pakistan also encounter electricity shortage, which hinders their ability to learn online. Moreover, the findings are consistent with other studies that discuss power difficulties and their impact on the deployment of e-learning in HEIs (Saidu et al., 2016; Satria, 2022;

Siddiquei and Khalid, 2020). Government can play a significant role in resolving the electricity problem by enhancing the electricity supply in both urban and rural areas. In addition, it mandates that HEIs make modifications to their systems so that they are mobile-friendly, i.e., they can be utilised on mobile platforms, so that when there is a power outage, students can continue learning using an alternative device to their computer system.

6.4.1.2 Infrastructure

With the help of the findings, internal stakeholders (faculty, students, and administrative staff) in both public and private HEIs view infrastructure as a significant challenge. Interviewees from UOS and SU emphasised the importance of infrastructure, and the effectiveness of e-learning deployment also depends on infrastructure. Considered an essential necessity for the implementation of e-learning, ICT infrastructure consists of hardware (equipment), software (LMS), and e-Labs. Infrastructure problems align with the findings of Kanwal et al. (2017), Mahmood et al. (2017), Mushtaq, Noor, and Sabahat (2021) and Aini et al. (2020), who acknowledged the infrastructure concerns of the stakeholders in the implementation of e-learning.

Infrastructure-related concerns can be managed with the assistance of both internal and external stakeholders, such as the Government of Pakistan, the Ministry of Education, and the HEC. Poor ICT infrastructure is seen as a significant barrier to the implementation process due to the fact that lack of infrastructure causes problems with the functionality of e-learning tools, frustration among stakeholders, i.e., technology users, and trouble with online assessments.

Interviews with faculty members and students suggest that e-learning tools assisted them in managing their learning and teaching activities throughout the lockdown phase. Administrative personnel from LGU and SU concur that e-learning is the future of education in Pakistan; hence, e-learning implementation in Pakistani HEIs requires improved infrastructure and cooperation from stakeholders. As there are additional challenges faced by the management and external stakeholders to implement e-learning, it also requires better infrastructure. For example, in the case of the pandemic, e-learning helped the stakeholders of HEIs in Pakistan to reduce the gap in halted educational activities (Chandio, 2021). The lack of infrastructure can also be addressed using cloud computing. Cloud computing offers numerous advantages, including reduced hardware investment, minimal maintenance costs, enhanced performance, and efficient and dependable e-learning module content (Bibi and

Sumra, 2017). Bosamia and Patel (2016) showed the benefits of cloud computing in the implementation of e-learning in India's HEIs, demonstrating that cloud computing is the optimal alternative for budget-constrained initiatives. Consequently, to reduce infrastructure and financial budget concerns, HEIs can adopt cloud computing to provide better solutions and round-the-clock support from experts in the field to increase the implementation and utilisation of e-learning.

6.4.1.3 Technological Literacy

The implementation of e-learning requires technological literacy to use it. The collected data indicates that faculty members over the age of 40 are less technologically knowledgeable, and some of them have left their positions as a result of the implementation of e-learning. However, self-motivated individuals such as the HOD in SU learned the system and tools with the assistance of trainings and a teacher assistant. In terms of students, the focus group interviews reveal that the majority of students from urban areas have a solid understanding of the use of technology, and that students from LGU, UMT, and UOL were familiar with other online teaching and learning software. However, students from rural areas demonstrated a lower level of technology literacy, but when they attended information sessions, they learned how to use e-learning software.

The study results are consistent with the findings of Sharaim and Khlaif (2010), Song, Park, and Park (2017), and Choudhury and Pattnaik (2020) where technology literacy is considered as an important factor affecting the implementation of e-learning. Wichadee (2014) also mentions that students have higher levels of technology literacy because they use technology on a regular basis, and they are ready to learn the educational technologies.

The problems associated with technology literacy can be mitigated by forming guiding coalitions between a faculty and students with higher levels of literacy so that they can motivate and educate their peers. The HEC's policy guideline number 8 suggests that recruiting technologically knowledgeable students will assist faculty members with technological issues. However, this can also cause problems if faculty members perceive it as a threat to their jobs and dignity. Therefore, training, and motivational sessions should be scheduled on a regular basis for stakeholders in order to increase their technology literacy (Choudhury and Pattnaik, 2020).

6.4.1.4 Internet Facilities

Lack of access to the internet and poor internet facilities pose the greatest obstacle to the implementation of e-learning in HEIs in developing nations. According to PTA (Pakistan Telecommunication Authority), the current broadband penetration rate is 52.79% and mobile internet penetration is 51.43%, indicating a 35% increase in the number of Pakistani internet users since 2019 (Kemp, 2022; PTA, 2022).

As internet penetration has increased, so have problems with internet connectivity. Internet connectivity issues and sluggish speeds are a source of frustration for both faculty and students, according to faculty members. During the pandemic, the HEC also permitted universities to allow students from rural areas to stay in their hostels so that they could access the internet. Faculty members also express concern about the inability to utilise video features during online classes due to slow internet speeds, which disrupts online sessions. Students have also expressed concern regarding the availability of the internet and the cost of internet packages. These concerns are consistent with the findings of (Farid et al., 2015; Farid et al. 2017; Kanwal et al., 2017; Mumtaz, Saqulain, and Mumtaz 2021; Sarwar, Akhtar, and Naeem 2020).

Internal and external stakeholders must collaborate to resolve issues relating to internet accessibility. This is possible using Leavitt's model, which is considered as a macro model in the present study. The model's structure supports the micro integrated model to address this issue by forming a coalition with internet companies and government organisations.

6.4.1.5 Cultural Aspects

Hofstede (1980) defines culture as the collective programming of the mind that distinguishes members of one group from those of another. The study reveals that stakeholders face cultural issues such as living in a joint family system (no dedicated rooms at home for faculty members and students to conduct and take lectures), the absence of video from female students taking online classes and exams, language, and a preference for in-person classes. Cultural factors hinder the stakeholders' ability to fully implement e-learning tools. Zhao et al.'s (2021) study confirms the effect of culture on the deployment of technology in HEIs, the implementation of e-learning, and the attitudes and behaviours of stakeholders towards e-learning. Khan, Ahmed, and Khan (2022) demonstrate that stakeholders' attitudes and cultures are the major hurdles to the successful completion of e-learning implementation.

With the help of planned change, cultural issues can be minimised by promoting the updated vision related to the change. However, with the help of a blended mode of learning, the issues faced by the female faculty members and students can also be minimised because it will allow them to take classes partially face-to-face and partially online. Furthermore, Kanwal et al., (2017) depicts that successful implementation of e-learning in Pakistan depends on the contextual cultural factors and the need of framework to guide the change (Basar et al., 2013). The macro and micro aspects of the proposed framework will manage the cultural factors according to the local situation. For instance, at macro level, the people and structure will be adjusted to entertain the elements from micro model of the proposed framework which includes planning, implementation and confirming the change.

6.4.1.6 Lack of Interaction

According to the findings, faculty members', and students' primary concern regarding the use of e-learning methods is the communication gap between teachers and students. According to the findings of Qamar and Bawany (2021), the lack of interaction between teachers and students is the most significant concern regarding the implementation of e-learning. Management and the HEC both encouraged the faculties and students to use social media tools such as WhatsApp and Facebook groups to maintain stakeholder communication. It is comparable to the study conducted by Khan et al. (2022), in which students joined Facebook pages and created WhatsApp groups to circumvent the problem of interaction.

The faculty members and students also mentioned the lack of interaction in on-going classes, that is, while attending the lectures online, stakeholders feel they are not having proper interaction because in online classes, teachers cannot judge the students because they cannot see them, which makes accepting e-learning difficult. Keeping in mind the benefits of e-learning, management can upgrade their LMS systems and incorporate motivational features, such as providing information and measures that encourage teacher and student involvement. Celebrating short-term achievements will boost employee morale, leading to improved teaching skills. For instance, Mr. Z from LGU bought a whiteboard to boost his skills and build better communication with the online students.

6.4.1.7 Online Examination and Invigilation

Online examinations and invigilation pose a challenge for the management, but the data indicates that students prefer online examinations. The administrative stakeholders discussed the problems they encountered during the invigilation process, such as issues with the camera, creating cheat-proof online examinations by putting restrictions on the LMS website, and providing online examination evaluations.

To help prevent cheating, the SU's examination department has implemented restrictions on their LMS website, such as preventing students from switching browser tabs once the exam has begun and monitoring their activities during the exam. Muzaffar et al. (2021) discovered in their research that HEIs used similar techniques to prevent cheating, as well as biometric authentication of the students prior to the start of the examination to prevent students from taking another's exam. Teachers are, however, more pleased with the online examination because, with the help of question banks, assessments can be generated as soon as the student completes the exam. Similarly, when assignments are submitted, teachers can evaluate them online via the LMS and provide feedback. Students and instructors confirm that only theses and dissertations are screened for similarity through Turnitin, which raises concerns about the copy-and-paste technique which could be employed by some students.

6.4.1.8 Pressure on Faculty

As stated by the BDM of SU, the faculty in the private sector was already overburdened with work, and the sudden shift towards e-learning further increased their workload. Teachers from other HEIs confirm that when e-learning tools were implemented and campuses were shifted to online mode during the pandemic, they faced tremendous pressure due to the extra work assigned to them, such as creating question banks, intellectual assignments based on the concepts of the lectures, and providing students with more reading material. Results are consistent with Sharin's (2021) study, which depicts the pressure placed on faculty by COVID-19 and the sudden implementation of e-learning tools.

In order to alleviate the pressure, the management should create a coalition of teachers who will help each other to improve their skills and train one another. This is possible with the framework's suggested implementation of the micro level integrated model. With the help of coalitions, teachers can share their work duties with other colleagues, thereby reducing their workload.

6.4.1.9 Resistance towards Change

Resistance is regarded as the most significant factor impacting the implementation of change in any organisation. Due to the pandemic, the most notable change in the faculty was that only teachers over the age of 40 exhibited resistance to the use of e-learning tools, whereas the rest of the faculty members were motivated to use e-learning. Especially in the context of private HEIs, it is observed that faculty members are self-motivated, and the management employed monetary and non-monetary motivational techniques to overcome any resistance from the technology's users. In public HEIs, the faculty did not raise any issues regarding the implementation of e-learning; however, the registrar and HOD of UOS reported that the faculty had only challenges while implementing e-learning, but no resistance. In addition, faculty members of both private and public HEIs expressed a fear of income loss during pandemic outbreaks, which reduced their opposition to the implementation. The research of Bibi, Ahmad, and Majid (2016) indicates that when academic staff receive management support in public institutions, their level of commitment increases. It also demonstrates that job security boosts morale, resulting in increased employee retention and enhanced commitment to their tasks.

Regarding students, teachers have mentioned resistance from students, EC from SU mentioning that students argued against the use of LMS and other e-learning tools during the pandemic, when the majority of HEIs in Pakistan were closed. In addition, students were more concerned with completing their degrees on time, so there was less student opposition to the implementation.

With the assistance of a micro level model, management can increase awareness of the implementation of change through motivation and training related to the benefits of e-learning, thereby reducing resistance and increasing the adoption rate among stakeholders. Chebbi et al. (2019) found similar outcomes in their research on overcoming resistance using Kotter's change model and stakeholder analysis to determine the internal and external stakeholders' interests.

6.4.2 EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDER

The HEC is studied as the external stakeholder of Pakistan's HEIs. The following are the obstacles mentioned by the HEC representative in the interview: internet availability, infrastructure, quality of instruction, virtual lab resources, and creation of module content.

6.4.2.1 Internet Availability

The HEC advisor emphasises the issue of internet accessibility, which significantly disrupts online teaching and learning. As stated in section 6.4.1.4, poor internet availability is a significant barrier to the implementation of e-learning. To overcome this challenge, the HEC requested that the telecoms industry provide students with subsidised internet packages that will allow them to take online classes. Due to the HEC advisor's assertion that e-learning is the future of education in Pakistan, various government agencies, including PTA, HEC, and PERN, should collaborate closely to expand internet access in Pakistan.

6.4.2.2 Infrastructure

The HEC advisor discusses infrastructure issues in the use and implementation of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs. HEC has also considered the impact of infrastructure on the behaviour of faculty members and students, which, depending on the quality of the infrastructure, either increases or decreases resistance. As a result, to improve infrastructure, the HEC allocated PKR 10 million exclusively to public HEIs, and when asked about funding for private HEIs, the advisor highlighted about providing discounted access to online courses as the only financial support. It demonstrates that the distinct funding policy and resource allocation of HEC will produce distinct outcomes in the public and private sectors. The findings are consistent with Naveed et al. (2017), in which the Saudi Ministry of Education proposed changes and the establishment of a National Centre of E-learning and Distance Learning to facilitate the integration of the e-learning system into the pedagogical setting.

In addition, the HEC intends to create virtual lab resources for a variety of programmes and to introduce a variety of centres that students can utilise if they encounter any issues while taking online classes. These policies will encourage stakeholders to promote the use of e-learning; however, the HEC must reassure the employers and parents of students who will graduate based on e-learning methods related to the acceptance of their degree in the marketplace.

Using the proposed framework, the reassurance factor can be addressed by communicating the new vision to stakeholders such as faculty members, students, management, the HEC, parents, and employers. However, the willingness of employers to offer online degree holders employment opportunities is limited. It is consistent with the findings of Engel's (2019) study that the business sector is reluctant to hire graduates of online degree programmes.

6.4.2.3 Quality of Teaching

The advisor to the HEC mentioned the aspect of quality that causes him the most concern. As a result of the sudden pandemic, the HEC was compelled to create effective policies and guidelines for online education while preserving the quality of education. The interviewee suggested that younger teachers find it easier to adopt new technology, whereas older teachers require more time to do so, which can affect the quality of their instruction.

The HEC and other stakeholders should invest in quality products, such as improved infrastructure and software support, to improve the quality of education. Moreover, a blended mode reduces the risk associated with using online mediums exclusively and helps the system maintain and improve the quality of instruction. Belaya (2018) discovered that e-learning plays a crucial role in enhancing the quality of education via a blended mode of instruction.

6.4.2.4 Module Content Creation

Creating module content is a significant challenge for the HEC and the management of Pakistan's HEIs. The interview with the HEC advisor reveals that the creation of module content is one of the most challenging aspects of the implementation of e-learning. Effectively creating module content for online courses and blended courses requires training and time. Through its partnership with EdX and Coursera, the HEC offered a variety of free educational courses to encourage and train the faculty of private and public institutes in module content development. As confirmed by the advisor, there is room for improvement as the HEC plans to create a platform similar to EdX to assist students and faculty members in promoting online education culture in Pakistan.

The need for a similar platform for Pakistani HEIs is a result of the language and cultural barriers faced by students and faculty when implementing e-learning. It is of the utmost importance that course materials reflect local culture (Tirziu and Vrabie, 2015). The research of Kasani et al. (2020) yields comparable outcomes when learning content is delivered with the support of incentives and educational requirements, and it will also reduce employee resistance to e-learning implementation.

6.4.2.5 Benefits of E-learning

Previous research has focused on the challenges and barriers of e-learning implementation, but there are also a number of advantages to using e-learning tools. The internal and external stakeholders have shed light on the benefits of e-learning, which will be discussed in the current section.

The ease of access to course materials is one of the major advantages of implementing e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs. Students are satisfied with the use of LMS software in all research cases during a pandemic because it allows them to access lecture slides and additional reading at any time. The faculties from all cases shared the positive comments regarding the use of e-learning tools. Even though they were implemented prior to the pandemic, LMS systems were not widely used in private institutions before the pandemic. The faculty member of the public institute had first-hand experience using LMS systems during the pandemic. If a teacher is unable to teach a physical class, he or she can still teach an online class without having to reschedule or skip the class. In addition, students are viewed as being more attracted to e-learning because it allows them to listen to recorded lectures at their convenience.

Despite the benefits of accessibility, students in all cases were dissatisfied with the scheduling of classes due to e-learning instructors conducting classes on Sundays, which demotivates students. However, professional students, such as those from UMT who are simultaneously pursuing an MPhil and a job, reported that e-learning helped them to effectively manage their time. Teachers should be assigned teacher assistants to help them understand the digital requirements of their updated work as a result of the implementation of e-learning in order to maintain time management. Due to the fact that SU has already provided a teacher assistant, the HOD confirmed in his interview that the assistance he received has helped him motivate and train for the new norm. LGU also utilised MOODLE coordinators to assist faculties and students in using e-learning tools effectively and efficiently for teaching and learning. According to Khan and Umair (2017) and Al-Azawei et al. (2017), e-learning helps to improve student-teacher interaction, saves time on learning, and provides flexibility to access the materials.

The benefits considered by the internal stakeholders should be highlighted to them frequently and be considered as an achievement of the short-term goals. It will motivate the stakeholders and their morale will be uplifted which will help the management to organise other aspects

such as tasks, structure, and technology at macro level to cement the change as they will achieve the level of self-esteem at micro level. E-learning will provide benefits to both internal and external stakeholders such as students will benefit from resource sharing, teachers will benefit of working from home, and the management can save time and financial resources (Awan et al., 2021).

Objective 5 To provide recommendations on the implementation of e-learning to the HEIs and regulatory body with the help of stakeholder analysis

6.5 Recommendations

Sub-themes from both internal and external stakeholders provide recommendations through the lens of the proposed framework of the study.

6.5.1 Autonomous or Managed Change (Teachers)

It is observed that the majority of university administrations in Pakistan are autocratic, creating obstacles for the implementation of any change. In three out of five cases, management took autocratic measures to ensure the implementation of e-learning, whereas at UMT and SU, management took a proactive approach by providing online courses to teachers to guide them through the implementation process.

According to the proposed framework, the initial stage at the micro level should be planning, during which the management should raise awareness of the change by providing examples of HEIs where e-learning has been successfully implemented. The sense of urgency related to e-learning should be communicated to stakeholders so that management can form a guiding coalition within the institute and with external stakeholders in order to achieve the updated vision. Turnbull et al. (2021) suggested that institutes can provide support through clear implementation planning and decisions. The research of Davies et al. (2020) indicates that when HEIs plan clearly and communicate a well-directed plan of action, it reduces anxiety among faculties and students and gives teachers sufficient time to plan their lectures. The only benefit observed from the management perspective was the teachers' participation in the feedback process, where they can suggest LMS improvements.

To effectively manage the implementation of e-learning, it is necessary to comprehend the faculty's behaviour through the micro and macro models of this study. It will increase the teachers' job-related safety needs and motivate them to achieve a sense of love and belonging, ultimately resulting in the formation of a coalition among teachers.

6.5.2 Organisational Support (HODs)

The study discovered that HODs provided adequate support to their teachers and students. Moreover, the management assisted the HODs in motivating their faculty by providing motivational techniques. For instance, the management of SU provided cash prizes, in UMT separate departments were engaged even before the pandemic to provide online courses, UOL explored other institutes' strategies, UOS provided trainings through the QEC department, and LGU provided certifications for work recognition.

Blumberg et al. (2014) support the notion that Leavitt's model is a model of planned change; it represents both the social and technical aspects of the change. In addition, it is stated that when technology is introduced, changes to other components, such as tasks, structure, and people, are neglected. Initiating the implementation process at the micro level will assist the organisation in addressing the change at the macro level by carefully adjusting the model's components.

HODs serve as middle managers in HEIs; consequently, they should be granted more autonomy because they can help design and shape change by communicating faculty members and student opinions. In some instances, they also have the means to communicate with top-level managers and external stakeholders; therefore, they can communicate the issues to internal and external stakeholders by employing the micro and macro level models proposed in the present study.

6.5.3 Technology Support (Student Focus Group)

Students are an important stakeholder group in HEIs because they are the primary technology users. The results indicate that students face significant difficulties with technical support and training. In two of the four private cases, UOL and SU, students received trainings related to online lectures and mock examinations. However, the issue was more critical in public institutes because students' participation was not considered in the implementation of any change. However, UMT demonstrates a coalition with external stakeholders, namely internet service providers, to provide special student internet packages during pandemics. Nonetheless, management and HEC disregard the importance of student training.

It is evident that, at the micro level, the planning stage was not properly initiated, meaning that students were not properly informed about the implementation of e-learning; instead, the

administration issued only notifications about going online. At the macro level, the structure of the organisations remained unchanged; however, HEIs were required to implement coordinators or student advisors in order to effectively manage the implementation. Chandio et al. (2019) provide results consistent with the current study, namely that a lack of training and limited ICT-related knowledge are the primary challenges to the implementation of e-learning. Awan et al. (2021) argue that training students will increase the use of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs.

6.5.4 Levers of Change Management (LGU IT Manager and UOS Registrar)

The IT manager of the LGU identified the need for a management model, and the results indicate that COVID-19 was the primary change agent in HEIs. Hall et al. (2021) support the notion that pandemics serve as the catalyst for change in educational institutions and provide new learning and teaching opportunities. As the pandemic was the driving force behind significant changes in the implementation of e-learning, HEIs require a framework or model. In addition, the Registrar of UOS confirmed that the increased use of e-resources is a result of the pandemic and that they only began using online tools when the HEC and the government mandated that HEIs use online tools to continue teaching and learning activities remotely. It also confirms the public institutes' financial difficulties, whereas private institutes were in a better position due to their use of e-resources.

The findings are consistent with Kattoua's (2016) assertion that the absence of a framework and appropriate e-learning strategies impacts the e-learning implementation process. Moreover, clear vision and objectives will aid the implementation process, and the absence of these elements is confirmed by the findings; these results are consistent with Farid et al. (2015), who state that the absence of an institutional vision, long-term goals and objectives, and a set of standards and procedures leads to implementation problems.

The proposed framework will assist managers of HEIs in overcoming challenges related to the implementation of e-learning. The micro level integrated models will assist internal stakeholders, while the macro model will pave the way for the successful implementation of e-learning among external stakeholders.

6.5.5 Teachers' attitude Towards the use of E-Learning (Examination Controller SU)

Due to a lack of training and unprepared faculty members and students, institutes encountered difficulties in administering the online examination. However, the HEC publishes guidelines for online examinations, but HEIs had difficulty adhering to these guidelines due to teacher

pressure, infrastructural issues, and cultural concerns. However, after the training was provided, SU's management motivated their faculty by awarding certifications and cash prizes; this enabled the faculty to confirm the change at the departmental levels. These initiatives were also observed in other private institutions, whereas the case of the public university demonstrates that the QEC department's feedback assisted them in preparing their teachers for online examination. In private institutions, management and other internal stakeholders encourage the use of Turnitin to enhance evaluation criteria.

On a macro level, it is evident that there have been no significant structural changes to the institutes, whereas the introduction of online examinations and presentations has altered the tasks. Cheating, plagiarism, invigilation of online examinations, and time limits are the primary problems encountered in online examinations and assessments. HEIs have restricted the switching of tabs during open-book and online MCQ-based exams in an effort to eliminate the challenges associated with cheating and plagiarism. However, problems associated with invigilating online examinations persist. Consistent with Muzaffar et al., (2021), whose study identifies integrity and security as the primary concerns of online examinations, the results are as expected. Mukherjee (2021) endorses the idea of encrypting online examination systems, which will improve invigilation by preventing students from switching between multiple browser tabs.

However, the issues with online examination will necessitate system modifications and ongoing enhancements to the online LMS systems utilised by HEIs. In addition, with government funding, both public and private institutes can construct centralised platforms that will improve the integrity of online examinations, and the faculty can form a coalition to provide support for the use of e-resources.

6.5.6 Policies and Regulations

The HEC is the governing body in Pakistan responsible for establishing rules and regulations for HEIs. The interview data suggests that the HEC did not issue any policy guidelines for traditional institutes to consider or to utilise online teaching activities prior to the pandemic. Two universities in Pakistan, Virtual University and Allama Iqbal Open University, are the only ones to offer online degrees; these are both fully online institutions. As COVID-19 acted as a change agent, the HEC issued policy guidelines pertaining to training, online examinations and assessments, and module content development. In comparison to the results based on internal stakeholders, the institutes did not adhere to the HEC-issued guidelines

properly. Students have confirmed that in public institutions, Turnitin is only used to check for plagiarism at the MS/MPhil level. In contrast, private institutions utilise plagiarism detection software at all levels, but only for final theses.

In relation to the future of online classes and degrees, a second major issue has been identified, namely whether or not the HEC will authorise degrees awarded by traditional institutions utilising online mediums, as degree validation is a further concern. The findings of the study by Lashayo and Md Johar (2017) are consistent with the findings of this study that the absence of policies is an impediment to the implementation of e-learning, and the study suggests that frequent updating of institutions' ICT policies will result in improved e-learning systems and their implementation (Awan et al., 2021; Kasani et al., 2020; Mosa et al., 2016).

6.5.7 Collaborations and Explorations

Creating coalitions, partnerships, and collaborations would enable internal and external stakeholders to adopt e-learning efficiently and enhance Pakistan's educational system as a whole. The HEC Advisor discussed collaborations and partnerships with Coursera, EdX, Microsoft, and Google for Pakistani HEIs.

The HEC manages technology change coupled with structure, duties, and people at the macro level. The structural adjustment will take time because the HEC gave PKR10 million to public institutes to modernise their infrastructure, whereas private institutes rely on student fees. The HEC can also investigate additional venues, such as international partner universities, to discuss policies, procedures, and regulations relating to synchronous, asynchronous, or a hybrid form of e-learning to strengthen and enhance policy guidelines for HEIs of Pakistan. These results are consistent with Farid et al. (2015) who recommend changing the HEC's methods and policies to promote e-learning in Pakistani HEIs.

6.6 Summary

This chapter highlights the analysis of the data of the present study. The chapter is structured in accordance with the study's objectives, which demonstrate the participation of stakeholders in the implementation of e-learning. Section 6.3 describes the models or strategies employed by HEIs to adopt e-learning, and it is evident that the HEIs relied mostly on training and motivation as the fundamental tactics, rather than a comprehensive change management model. Section 6.4 highlights the problems based on internal and external stakeholders, as well as the benefits given by interviewees about the deployment and utilisation of e-learning.

The recommendations are presented in the last section, 6.5, via the lens of the framework and past investigations. It is evident that the absence of management models, highlighted challenges such as infrastructure, technology literacy, and cultural factors, among others, play a crucial role in the successful implementation of e-learning. In addition, it is evident that students were not considered by other stakeholders when making changes to the educational system, and that student feedback is only considered after the change has been implemented. Therefore, the system must change its current strategies and policies for the development and implementation of e-learning in Pakistan's higher education institutions.

Chapter 7 Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the conclusions drawn from the data collected and analysed in the preceding chapters 5 and 6. It will comprise the important conclusions derived from the data analysed using semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis. Additionally, this chapter provides a contribution to both literature and practice. The chapter offers recommendations for stakeholders of Pakistani HEIs regarding the implementation of e-learning and the usage of change management models to improve the implementation process using the proposed framework. The limitations of the study will be highlighted, and suggestions for future research will also be explored.

7.2 Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to provide recommendations regarding the implementation of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs, including an examination of the role of change management models in the implementation of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs. To achieve this purpose, the study has five objectives and three research questions that will help achieve the research's aims. The first objective is *"to undertake a comprehensive and critical literature review on the role of organisational change management models and e-learning deployment."* This objective was accomplished by analysing the available literature on change management approaches and the deployment of e-learning in the context of higher education institutions. Literature reveals that the implementation of e-learning by Pakistani HEIs faces a variety of hurdles and challenges. It is also demonstrated that e-learning is not limited to educational institutions but is also utilised to train and encourage personnel within businesses. Literature-based data indicates that culture, technological literacy, digital literacy, infrastructure, management support, government policy involvement, students' attitudes toward e-learning, employee resistance, and organisational politics are the most significant obstacles to e-learning implementation. It is also observed that e-learning is not restricted to synchronous and asynchronous learning methods alone; due to the pandemic, a hybrid form of learning has prevailed to facilitate the transition of pedagogical activities.

The research questions of the study were also answered with the help of the achievement of the research objectives. The first question was *how the implementation of e-*

learning(change) managed by the stakeholders of HEIs of Pakistan?

The first question is linked with the second and third objective of the current study. The second objective was achieved with the help of reviewing the previous literature however, the data collected from the respondents showed that during the implementation phase of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan, the management of the HEIs did not use any specific model to manage the change. The implementation was directed with the help of direct orders from the regulatory body (HEC) and by utilising training and motivational techniques to implement the change as much as possible. The following paragraphs will shed light on the achievement of second and third objectives in detail.

The second objective of the study was to "*To investigate relevant change management model(s) for the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan.*" The literature assisted in identifying the models for this investigation. The majority of research on the implementation of e-learning in HEIs utilises the Innovation Diffusion Model, the Technology Acceptance (TAM) Model, or extensions of these models. However, when technology models are merged with motivational or change management models, the explanatory power increases and it becomes easier to comprehend the actions that will help to overcome the obstacles and challenges associated with e-learning implementation. As sections 3.3. and 3.4 presented the stakeholder analysis and change management models used in previous studies, it was helpful to review the combination of models that led to the selection of Leavitt's diamond model, Maslow's hierarchy, and Kotter's eight step change model as change management models. The literature indicates that combining stakeholder analysis with other management models increases the explanatory power of each model. In addition, Leavitt's diamond model will serve as a macro-level change management model that will help in e-learning implementation management. With the introduction of e-learning, the integrated models will be used on a departmental or micro-level to motivate, train, educate, and inform the stakeholders. The proposed framework will assist the HEIs in planning the change and overcoming the associated challenges. This demonstrates the achievement of the second objective by presenting the relevant framework for the study.

The third objective is to "examine the process of change management towards the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan." This objective relates to the actions taken by HEIs to implement e-learning. To achieve this purpose, data was collected through semi-structured interviews with Pakistani HEI stakeholders. The data was divided into internal and

external stakeholders, revealing that the internal stakeholders, namely teachers, students, and managerial and administrative staff from private sector institutes, were enthusiastic about e-learning and its implementation. However, teachers with many years of experience were at first reluctant to accept the implementation due to their lack of technology literacy and cultural issues. According to the research, during the implementation phase, HEIs were solely concerned with two aspects of change management models: training and motivation. In the private sector, the usage of LMS or ERP systems had already begun prior to the pandemic; however, stakeholders such as teachers, students, and department heads were not utilising them concurrently with pedagogical setting. Therefore, the private sector was more focused on training teachers, and this study identified two instances of private institutes offering training to students as well, such as how to attend online classes, submit papers, and take mock exams. In public institutes, professors were solely responsible for training and feedback, while students were left to learn by doing. Teachers were not aware of similar e-learning platforms, such as Microsoft Teams, when students mentioned them. However, while the younger generation is more driven towards IT systems, it is evident that teachers were not aware of these platforms.

The management utilised motivational techniques for the faculty, despite the fact that the data suggested that only the private sector employed motivational strategies. It contains both non-monetary and monetary incentives to improve teachers' motivation to accept the use of e-learning. It is evident that SU has outperformed other private institutes due to the fact that they not only encouraged their faculty and HODs to take courses related to online teaching and learning, but also awarded cash prizes to those who performed exceptionally well and completed their free online courses offered by Harvard University and MIT. LGU adopted the same strategy as SU, however the other two private institutes gave letters of appreciation and encouraging feedback to teachers in an effort to boost their morale in relation to the usage of e-learning tools. In public institutes, staff are more concerned about their salary, therefore implementing e-learning in a public institute needs a more planned approach towards the change than in a private institute. Consequently, the professors showed an interest in e-learning tools, whereas the registrar favoured face-to-face classes over blended and online classes. In addition, the teachers only received the feedback collected by the QEC department, which is required by HEC to maintain the quality of the teaching, and they did not receive any kind of recognition or motivation from the management.

The HEC, an external stakeholder, gave institutes guidance on which software to use and how

to administer online tests. In the HEIs, the fundamental ingredient of implementing change through a framework or model was missing. According to the data, some HEIs closed their doors to students throughout the pandemic and simply waited for it to end. Due to the fact that Pakistani HEIs are at different levels, not all were able to incorporate e-learning. Similarly, in Bangladesh, not all HEIs were quick to integrate e-learning (Al-Amin et al., 2021), however in industrialised nations such as the United Kingdom, where the use of e-learning tools is widespread, institutes were quick to transition their education systems to online platforms.

The utilisation of a framework is crucial because it assists stakeholders in comprehending the needs of other stakeholders and enables management to make deliberate decisions to execute e-learning effectively and efficiently. The data indicates that HEIs are only implementing e-learning in accordance with the HEC's directives as a regulatory body. Therefore, the research suggests that HEIs and regulatory body utilise a change management framework to assist stakeholders with the implementation of e-learning tools or any other change in Pakistan's HEIs. It will help HEIs, and the HEC understand the requirements of the contemporary period and enable them to educate and prepare for managing change in HEIs.

The second research question of the study is ***What are the significant internal and external challenges that influence the stakeholders' perception in the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan?*** This question is linked with the fourth objective of the study which was achieved with the help of identifying the internal and external issues faced by the stakeholders. The data was collected through semi-structured interviews and focus group interviews from internal and external stakeholders.

The fourth objective of the study is *"to explore the challenges that influence the individual stakeholder's perception in the implementation of e-learning."* This objective is achieved with the help of interview-collected primary data. The data was analysed using thematic analysis, and it reveals the challenges encountered by stakeholders during the implementation of e-learning. The highlighted challenges demonstrate unequivocally that these concerns influence the stakeholders involved in the implementation and acceptance of e-learning. The highlighted difficulties are categorised by internal and external stakeholders. Faculty members, students, management, and administrative personnel identify electricity, infrastructure, technological literacy, internet facility, cultural elements, lack of engagement, online examination and invigilation, faculty pressure, and resistance to change as potential

challenges. On the other hand, the HEC advisor as external stakeholder identified internet accessibility, infrastructure (including virtual lab resources), quality of instruction, and module content generation as potential challenges. However, the internal stakeholders also mentioned the benefits of e-learning, which include easy access to module content, time management, and the ability to attend lectures.

The findings indicate that electricity shortage and hardware availability are the main challenges faced by the rural faculties and students; consequently, the HEC and management have taken steps to accommodate some of the students in hostels with improved internet connectivity and electricity supply in order to resolve the problems associated with taking online classes. Similarly to the students, the staff were recommended to record their lectures on campus due to better infrastructure and IT assistance. With the help of identified challenges, it is clear that the pandemic played a crucial role in implementing and expanding the usage of e-learning throughout Pakistan, particularly in public institutes. COVID-19 worked as a catalyst and accelerated the implementation of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs. During the implementation phase, the data revealed the reality of cultural factors encountered by stakeholders. For example, female students were observed to feel uneasy when participating in online classes with their video turned on. Similarly, the invigilation procedure of online examinations was challenging for the management due to students' familiarity with IT systems and their ability to employ unfair means to pass exams. Therefore, the HEC only emphasised the usage of a secure website or web portal in its guidelines, whereas HEIs enforced navigational restrictions during examinations to prevent students from cheating. In addition, the research revealed that the HEC published rules for maintaining the quality of education during online sessions; nevertheless, there was no central platform for institutes at the introductory level to address this concern. Therefore, the QEC departments of both private and public institutes collected weekly input to upgrade their systems and make it easier for teachers and students to utilise the newly implemented system. However, the data demonstrates that the deployment process was unplanned, as the LGU IT manager emphasised the need for a framework or model. Therefore, the existing framework offers stakeholders a planned path for implementing and managing change in HEIs.

The findings reveal that stakeholders viewed the e-learning system as having some advantages. Time management has been emphasised by both instructors and students as the most essential benefit. The internal stakeholders are pleased with the implementation of e-learning and have noted that thanks to e-learning and the notion of blended learning, they are

able to better plan their time around teaching and learning activities because it minimises their travel time. E-learning also afforded students easy access to the module's content, since they could examine lecture recordings multiple times to cement their understanding. Students are able to attend class in the event of an emergency or other unanticipated incident, allowing them to continue their education uninterrupted. In the event that teachers are physically unable to attend the university, they can conduct online classes, hence eliminating the need to schedule a catch-up class.

The last research question is *Which recommendations should be considered by the HEIs and HEC Pakistan related to the change implementation with the help of change management models?* This question is answered with the help of attaining the fifth objective which is “to provide recommendations on the implementation of e-learning to the HEIs and Regulatory body with the help of stakeholder analysis”. To achieve this purpose, interviews were conducted to obtain primary data, which was then analysed using thematic analysis. The results gave an exploratory picture of the interviewees, as a result of which system-wide recommendations were proposed. The research demonstrates that management in HEIs is authoritarian in nature, which also includes an element of organisational politics. It is observed that management obtains orders from the regulatory body and subsequently imposes those directives on internal stakeholders. In private institutes, faculty can advise and implement changes pertaining to e-learning, however in public universities, implementing changes such as a faculty suggesting e-learning tools for implementation will require a lengthy procedure that requires syndicate and board member approval. Therefore, it demonstrates that the change implementation process is cumbersome and that internal stakeholders in public institutions did not bother to implement e-learning prior to the pandemic. The proposed model recommends that policymakers and management should initially prepare the transformation by communicating the new vision and objectives. This will assist management in educating stakeholders about the proposed change, and stakeholders will be enthusiastic about implementing and adopting it.

The data also indicates that students were overlooked in terms of training and motivation, therefore training students is regarded as equally essential as training faculty members. Creating a guiding coalition among the internal stakeholders, such as between professors and students, will enable the stakeholders to share their experiences and enhance the perspective of their colleagues and students on the implementation of e-learning. Furthermore, the suggested framework provides guidance for stakeholders, as no framework or model was

previously used to execute and manage change in Pakistan's HEIs.

Regarding external stakeholders, the data indicates that the HEC did not publish e-learning and implementation policies prior to the pandemic. During the pandemic, however, the HEC published policies and regulations concerning the implementation and utilisation of e-learning resources. The data also reveals that the policies do not include any plans or models, but rather merely supply stakeholders with instructions. Results also indicate that the HEC collaborated with foreign and domestic partners such as Coursera, EdX, Microsoft, and Google to provide faculties and students with software assistance and courses. Financial support is one of the key challenges to implementing e-learning, and the HEC has only provided financial support to public universities, leaving private institutes to rely on the revenue generated by their fees. The data offered evidence that the HEC should alter its policies regarding traditional institutions in order to encourage them to employ e-learning resources not only during the pandemic, but also in the future. However, the HEC advisor affirms that e-learning is the future, but it requires worldwide cooperation with other institutes to share structure and policies in order to transform Pakistan's current education system. The suggested framework helps stakeholders to overcome resistance and other challenges to implementation by communicating, educating, and assisting stakeholders related to change.

7.3 Research Methods

The research methods used in the study were based on qualitative research methods in which thematic analysis was used to study the multiple cases to view them from the lens of proposed theoretical framework. The data collection methods included non-probability purposive sampling technique which includes semi-structured and focus group interviews from the respondents. It also included the Policy guideline documents published on the official website of HEC to consider the facts disclosed by the HEC advisor in his interview. The number of respondents was 41 including HEC advisor to provide primary data. The utilization of literature i.e., past studies in conjunction with the policy guidelines, and collected data, it increases validity of the findings of the study. The data was collected from different universities which shows that the framework of the study can be applied in different environment i.e., cultural or geographical, in same field such as HEIs. This will help to prevent the issue of generalizability related to the current study findings. Furthermore, the data was collected from the current working professionals with years of experience in their relevant fields and current students in their final year study, to improve the trustworthiness of

the data collected. Table 4.1 shows the gender and years of experience of the respondents of the current study.

7.4 Research Contributions

Utilising qualitative research methodology and synthesising stakeholder analysis, Leavitt's diamond model, and integrating Maslow's hierarchy and Kotter's eight step change model into the suggested theoretical framework, the research aim has been achieved. The results of this study contribute to the current literature on the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan. This topic is concluded by the perspectives and experiences presented by internal and external stakeholders of Pakistani HEIs. The contributions of this work can be categorised as contributions to knowledge, contributions to practice, and contributions to theory.

7.5 Contributions to Knowledge

Aini et al. (2020); Akram et al. (2020); Kanwal et al. (2017); Khan, Ahmed, and Khan (2022); Maqsood et al. (2020) all of the studies addressed the lack of research and challenges in the area of change management connected to the implementation of e-learning in HEIs. The qualitative in-depth analysis of this research contributes to filling the gap regarding the role of change management models in the implementation of e-learning in HEIs by examining this issue from the perspective of internal and external stakeholders of HEIs in a developing country (Pakistan) and taking the cultural context of Pakistan into account. The literature guided the study through the challenges, barriers, and issues encountered by the teachers and students during the implementation process, which are then explored in the current study and shows that HEIs in Pakistan requires a framework to implement e-learning efficiently and effectively.

This study demonstrates how management, administrative personnel, teachers, students, and the regulatory body have attempted to integrate e-learning into pedagogy to continue and facilitate the teaching and learning process during the pandemic. It also contrasts the position of HEIs prior to the pandemic in terms of the implementation and utilisation of e-learning tools. Prior to COVID-19, only private higher education institutions had incorporated e-learning tools, and the teachers did not fully utilise these e-resources.

Previous research did not explore the combination of change management models in the context of the educational sector in Pakistan; hence, no specific answers from the external stakeholder, the HEC, were discovered in relation to e-learning implementation policies and

strategies. This study explored the consideration of change management models by HEIs during the implementation of e-learning in Pakistan, as well as the challenges and benefits of implementing e-learning and recommendations for the implementation of e-learning.

With the use of thematic analysis, it presented a complete and crucial perspective on the topic from related perspectives. The only two parameters employed by management to implement e-learning were training and motivation. Electricity shortage, lack of technological literacy, infrastructure, resistance to change, lack of engagement, internet access, quality of instruction, and module content generation are the challenges pertaining to various stakeholders were found. Stakeholders also conveyed the benefits of e-learning, which include easy access to content, time management, and attending lectures with ease.

Interaction with stakeholders has helped provide evidence regarding change management strategies and implementation of e-learning in Pakistani HEIs. The findings of this study will assist internal and external stakeholders, particularly policy makers and top-level administration of HEIs, in comprehending the benefits of e-learning and change management models in the field of education.

7.6 Contribution to Practice

Utilisation, implementation, and upgrading of e-learning systems and technologies in Pakistan's HEIs will be influenced by the components of advantages and disadvantages of e-learning.

The outcome of the study indicates that traditional institutions may assist students in rural areas through e-learning, and that e-learning technologies will pave the way for improved learning and teaching standards for students and teachers. E-learning can also provide opportunities for enhanced learning and instruction, the administration of online examinations, and the ability for students from distant locations to interact with their classmates and learn about future possibilities. The current study's findings and the benefits of e-learning will expedite the implementation of e-learning. The study also provides practical techniques to manage change, such as forming a guiding coalition among stakeholders, conveying the change's vision and objectives, and offering continual training to the stakeholders, including teachers, students, and administrative personnel.

In addition, stakeholders feel that e-learning can boost problem-solving, communication, innovativeness, content accessibility, and students' and teachers' self-learning. The findings of

the study also reveal that both students and teachers recognise the benefits of e-learning, and that management prefers e-learning approaches, namely blended learning, to support their learning, teaching, and training activities. Nonetheless, there are a number of concerns and problems associated with the use of ICT in education that might demotivate stakeholders and impact the implementation of e-learning. Cultural and technological aspects indicate that HEIs are required to update themselves in order to allow the learning of all stakeholders, it is essential that HEIs establish an environment that will promote the usage of e-learning.

This study is important for policymakers, HEI administrators, teachers, students, and other HEI administrative employees. It gives practical consequences for the macro and micro-environments of the education business using the proposed paradigm. This study demonstrates the functioning and use of e-learning tools in higher education institutions to enhance the learning and teaching process during challenging circumstances and fulfilling the vision “Education for all” of the government of Pakistan. The research emphasises the relevance of change management models that can be utilised to handle the issues experienced by stakeholders.

7.8 Theoretical Contributions

The research used stakeholder analysis, Leavitt's diamond model, Maslow's hierarchy, and Kotter's eight step change model, which served as the framework for the study on the implementation of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs. The research improved understanding of stakeholder analysis by identifying the study's potential and significant stakeholders. In addition, the change is evaluated at the macro level with the help of Leavitt's Diamond model, which suggests that a change in one aspect of the model necessitates adjustments to the other three components. Moreover, the integration of Maslow's hierarchy and Kotter's eight-step change model will be useful at the micro-level in institutes for informing stakeholders about the implementation of change, training them, and encouraging them to embrace the change by celebrating short-term successes.

The four components of the Leavitt model are technology, task, structure, and people which should be adjusted according to the change in any component. Private HEIs had already begun the development and usage of e-learning tools. However, the introduction of ICT change was not accommodated by modifying the structure and tasks of the diamond model. In public institutes, however, e-learning was introduced during the pandemic; consequently, the changes suggested by the model were not implemented appropriately; however, if the

change implementation was planned and followed the macro-level model, it would help the stakeholders of HEIs to understand and accept the benefits of e-learning, rather than simply accepting it as a single mode of teaching and learning. The results indicate that the amount of change to one component of Leavitt's model considered by the management of HEIs was not maintained at the same level as other components, i.e., technological change was implemented, but people (stakeholders) were not fully trained to accommodate the change. Similarly, the structure of the institutes necessitates modifications, such as the introduction of better equipment and internet connection, and tasks entail alterations to the stakeholders' learning and teaching methods.

The research also contributed to the micro-level model, which is comprised of integrated models that would assist stakeholders in overcoming challenges and resistance to change. The theoretical models overcome the challenges with the help of past literature, and it will be advantageous for stakeholders to examine them during the change implementation process. The research helps to understand the value of coalition building, a sense of urgency, training and motivating the stakeholders, creating a sense of belonging among the stakeholders by considering their perspectives on the implementation process, and anchoring the change by recognising the short-term wins, which are the accomplishment of objectives and goals associated with the institute's revised vision. To assist the implementation of e-learning, the research also adds to a knowledge of cultural issues, the support of governing bodies, and a changing technological environment.

In conclusion, the findings suggest that the study has contributed to theory-building in the field of ICT use in education by employing change management models to examine the implementation and use of e-learning in Pakistani HEIs from the perspectives of internal (faculty, students, management, and administration) and external (HEC) stakeholders. The study highlights the advantages of e-learning that stakeholders derive from its use, as well as the challenges that influence their perceptions of the implementation of e-learning in Pakistan. These models also aid in comprehending and refining the theory around the implementation of e-learning in HEIs.

7.9 Research Implications

Pakistan's HEIs are in the process of building e-learning technologies because the majority of institutions did not meet the HEC's criteria for online preparedness (HEC Guide 3, 2020). Therefore, HEIs are attempting to enhance their systems and infrastructure in order to adapt

to the changing environment and technology in the education industry. According to the literature review, the "Education for all" initiative launched by the government of Pakistan in 2002 was predicated on delivering quality and affordable education to all Pakistanis. Similarly, HEC's Vision 2025 highlights the greater use of ICT by professors and students in an effort to modernise the educational system (HEC F, 2017; Taylor, 2017). The findings of this study will assist policymakers, institutes' management and administration, teachers, and students in gaining a better understanding of the perceptions, challenges, benefits, and solutions to manage the change with which they are confronted regarding the integration and implementation of e-learning in the field of education.

These findings will help the management of HEIs to manage change by offering a clear vision and a planned approach. Prior to the pandemic, the use of e-learning tools in private HEIs was limited to PowerPoint slides, WhatsApp and Facebook groups, and emails. However, during and after the pandemic, both public and private institutes increased their reliance on e-learning tools by implementing them to continue the learning and teaching process in Pakistan. PowerPoint slides, Zoom, Google Classroom, online case studies, LMS and ERP systems, Turnitin, WhatsApp and Facebook groups, and EdX and Coursera are the key e-resources used by the teachers and students. The existing understanding of the tools will enable institutes to assist teachers and students in improving technology and expanding its usage in conventional education.

Literature also highlights the major concerns, issues, and challenges encountered by stakeholders in implementing e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs. To overcome the challenges, stakeholders must cooperate in such unison that they form a coalition among themselves. It will assist the stakeholders in training one another, such as the HEC's suggestion to institutes to hire students with superior knowledge of IT systems to train professors on the usage and execution of e-learning during the pandemic.

Consequently, implementing e-learning while considering the opinions of all stakeholders will improve the implementation process and help the institution in overcoming challenges. It will encourage instructors and students to increase their understanding of e-learning and e-resources. In the context of Pakistan, extra attention must be paid to the social and cultural factors that influence the perceptions of the stakeholders when implementing e-learning. Students, teachers, and other stakeholders of HEIs will be able to design better educational policies and courses of action regarding the implementation of e-learning without harming

cultural components if they are aware of the changing technological dimensions.

Lastly, the practical experiences shared by the stakeholders in this study will raise awareness among policymakers, governing bodies, and government officials, as well as the management of educational institutions, regarding the perceptions of the stakeholders about the use and benefits of e-learning in a pedagogical setting. It will also assist stakeholders in proposing and implementing important measures for the sustained use of e-resources in academic settings.

7.10 Recommendations

This research confirms that the use of e-learning has proven beneficial for Pakistan's HEIs, particularly during the pandemic, when educational facilities were closed worldwide. Where educational institutions are not online-ready, it will be difficult for stakeholders to implement e-learning. Therefore, the development of teaching methods should be revised and updated with the help of accepting new e-learning tools, such as Blackboard, social-media tools, virtual reality, and augmented reality technology, in order to promote the culture of utilising advanced technologies and to provide stakeholders with easy access to knowledge.

As the pandemic acted as an external force on the implementation of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs, the management should begin developing plans that emphasise the development of faculty and student skills and help administrative staff adapt to the digital revolution by adopting innovative technology to promote e-learning. With the use of micro-level models, management may notify their employees about the change, train them by forming coalitions and improving their training platforms and motivate them to achieve short-term objectives that will ultimately assist them in achieving the institute's revised vision. These plans should be established on an ongoing basis to assist both internal and external stakeholders in updating educational platforms and methodologies.

The study reveals the challenges faced by the stakeholders, which can be overcome by upgrading the infrastructure and internet facilities, providing continuous training on e-learning tools and programs, raising awareness about the advantages of e-learning, and motivating the stakeholders to overcome the cultural issues. When the challenges are eliminated, other HEIs that did not implement e-learning during the pandemic will also find e-learning implementation to be less difficult.

The management of HEIs should also be encouraged to provide their policies to the internal stakeholders, which will help them to clear up any ambiguity regarding e-learning and also

inform them of the benefits of e-learning, both in terms of using it and as an achievement, as the examination controller from Superior University mentioned. Therefore, it will enable internal stakeholders to use these technologies for their educational and learning needs.

In addition, the macro-model identifies the necessary adjustments required to manage technological change. The findings indicate that faculties from various disciplines, such as accounting and finance, medicine, and engineering, etc., lack the necessary equipment to conduct their lectures with ease, such as an electronic white board that would allow teachers to write equations more effectively during online lectures. Therefore, the teachers should be given specific equipment, regular training, and professional development programmes to enable them to update their knowledge.

Moreover, in order to address difficulties linked to professors and students from remote areas, HEIs could consider extending the opening hours of their computer laboratories and libraries in order to facilitate access to e-resources. Also, the HEIs and HEC should increase the number of new business partners by giving them new software licences, such as Blackboard, to improve the e-learning experience for students and instructors.

Finally, the government of Pakistan and the regulatory body should work on removing obstacles by providing financial support to both public and private institutions. The advisor to the HEC stated an effort in which Vice Chancellors of public and private universities are asked to discuss contemporary issues and challenges confronting the institutions. Pakistan spent 2.9% of GDP on education in 2019-2020, which is significantly less than the global average of 4%. (BTI, 2022). Therefore, it reveals that HEIs need more government funding to improve the education system by updating and integrating technology breakthroughs in the field of education.

7.11 Limitations of the Study

In addition to its contributions to knowledge, practice, and theory, the current study also identifies its limitations. Firstly, the current study is based purely on qualitative research methods, the use of mixed method approach will help in terms of collecting and analysing the data.

In addition to methodological limitations, other study limitations have been observed. Due to the fact that the current study was conducted during a pandemic, it was challenging for the researcher to obtain data from the specified stakeholders. Interviews were delayed as a result

of the pandemic's impact on the administration and faculty of HEIs. Similar challenges were discovered when collecting data from student focus groups due to the difficulty in availability of students at the same time.

Lastly, the study sample is from the Pakistani province of Punjab, but institutes from other provinces were not included; thus, sample size is limited in the study. In addition, given the study was focused on stakeholder analysis, employer and sponsoring NGO interviews were not included in order to assess their involvement in promoting the introduction of e-learning in Pakistan's HEIs. In addition, due to time constraints and the pandemic, interviews with the Vice Chancellors, Chairmen, and Rectors of HEIs were not included.

7.12 Future Research Suggestions

The limitations of the research are used to generate suggestions for further research, for instance, the same study might be conducted in other regions of Pakistan, or it could compare the implementation of e-learning in Punjab's and other provinces' HEIs. The current study focuses on HEIs in Pakistan; however, the same theoretical framework can be applied to other countries.

With the use of surveys, future research can be undertaken using quantitative or mixed methods to encompass a larger population. Future research can include top-level executives from the internal and external environment of HEIs, as well as executives from influential sectors such as businesses and NGOs, to record their perspectives on the implementation and significance of e-learning in HEIs.

References

- Labanauskis, R. & Ginevičius, R., 2017. Role of stakeholders leading to development of higher education services. *Engineering Management in Production and Services*, 9(3), pp. 63-75.
- Abbasi, S., Ayoob, T., Malik, A. & Memon, S. I., 2020. Perceptions of students regarding E-learning during Covid-19 at a private medical college. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Science*, 36(4), pp. 57-61.
- Abdullah, F. & Ward, R., 2016. Developing a General Extended Technology Acceptance Model for E-Learning (GETAMEL) by analysing commonly used external factors. *Computers in Human Behaviour*, Volume 56, pp. 238-256.
- Abid, K. et al., 2020. Progress of COVID-19 Epidemic in Pakistan. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Public Health*, 32(4), pp. 154-156.
- Acharya, A. S., Prakash, A., Saxena, P. & Nigam, A., 2013. Sampling: Why and How of it?. *INDIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL SPECIALITIES*, 4(2), pp. 330-333.
- Ackerman, D. & Ackerman-Anderson, L., 2001. *Beyond Change Management: Advanced Strategies for Today's Transformational Leaders*. 1 ed. San Francisco: Center for Creative Leadership.
- Ackermann, F. & Eden, C., 2011. Strategic Management of Stakeholders: Theory and Practice. *Long Range Planning*, 44(3), pp. 179-196.
- Ahmad, T. S. A. S., Hussin, A. A. & Yusri, G., 2019. *A review of learning theories for gamification elements in instructional games*. Kota Kinabalu Sabah, Malaysian International Conference on Academic Strategies in English Language.
- Ahmed, A., 2021. *Out of 205, 40 varsities equipped to teach online: HEC*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.dawn.com/news/1629752> [Accessed 14 April 2022].
- Ahmed, M. U., Hussain, S. & Farid, S., 2018. Factors influencing the Adoption of e-learning in an Open and Distance Learning Institution of Pakistan. *The Electronic Journal of E-learning*, 16(2), pp. 145-158.
- Ahmed, T. T., 2013. . Toward Successful E-Learning Implementation in Developing Countries: A Proposed Model for Predicting and Enhancing Higher Education Instructors' Participation. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(1), p. 422.
- Aini, Q., Budiarto, M., Putra, P. O. H. & Rahardja, U., 2020. Exploring E-learning Challenges During the Global COVID-19 Pandemic: A Review. *Journal of Information System*, 16(2), pp. 57-65.
- Akhtar, N., Aslam, N. & Hussain, S. Q., 2021. Impact of E-Learning on Students Performance and Expenditures Borne by Students and Virtual Degree Awarding Institutes in Pakistan. *Elementary Education Online*, 20(3), pp. 271-283.

- Akram, A. et al., 2021. Comparative review on information and communication technology issues in education sector of developed and developing countries: a case study about Pakistan. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 10(6), pp. 3489-3500.
- Al-Amin, M., Al Zubayer, A. & Hasan, M., 2021. Status of tertiary level online class in Bangladesh: students' response on preparedness, participation and classroom activities. *Heliyon*, 7(1), pp. 1-15.
- Al-araibi, A. A. M., Naz'ri Bin Mahrin, M. & Yusoff, R. C. M., 2019. Technological aspect factors of E-learning readiness in higher education institutions: Delphi technique. *Education and Information Technologies*, Volume 24, pp. 567-590.
- Al-Azawei, A., Paslow, P. & Lundqvist, K., 2017. Investigating the effect of learning styles in a blended e-learning system: An extension of the technology acceptance model (TAM).. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 33(2), pp. 1-23.
- Alhogail, A. A. & Mirza, A. A., 2011. IMPLEMENTING A VIRTUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT (VLE) IN A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION: A CHANGE MANAGEMENT APPROACH. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 31(1), pp. 42-52.
- Alhomod, S. & Shafi, M. M., 2013. Success factors of e-learning projects: A technical perspective. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 12(2), pp. 247-253.
- Ali, G. E. & Magalhaes, R., 2008. Barriers to implementing e-learning: a Kuwaiti case study. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 12(1), pp. 36-53.
- Ali, S., Uppal, M. A. & Gulliver, S., 2018. A conceptual framework highlighting elearning implementation barriers. *Information Technology & People*, 31(1), pp. 156-180.
- Ali, W., 2020. Online and Remote Learning in Higher Education Institutes: A Necessity in light of COVID-19 Pandemic. *Higher Education Studies*, 10(3), pp. 16-25.
- Ally, M., 2004. *Foundations of educational theory for online learning*.. Athabasca: Athabasca University.
- Almaiah, A. M., Al-Khasawneh, A. & Althunibat, 2020. Exploring the critical challenges and factors influencing the E-learning system usage during COVID-19 pandemic. *Education and Information Technologies*, Volume 25, pp. 5261-5280.
- Almaiah, M. A. & Mulhem, A. A., 2018. A Conceptual Framework For Determining the Success Factors of E-Learning system Implementation Using Delphi Technique. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 96(17), pp. 5962-5976.
- Almseidein, T. A. & Mahasneh, O. M. K., 2020. Awareness of Ethical Issues when using an e-Learning system. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 11(1), pp. 128-131.
- Alnaim, F., 2015. The Case Study Method: Critical Reflection. *Global Journal of HUMAN-SOCIAL SCIENCE: A Arts & Humanities - Psychology*, 15(7), pp. 29-32.

- Alpaslan, C. M. & Mitroff, I. I., 2021. Exploring the moral foundations of crisis management. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, Volume 167, pp. 1-9.
- AlQudah, A. A., 2014. Models and frameworks for a successful virtual learning environment (VLE) implementation. *American Journal of Software Engineering and Applications*, 3(4), pp. 33-45.
- Abrahim, W. M. et al., 2018. Use of E-Learning by University Students in Malaysian Higher Educational Institutions: A Case in Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. *IEEE Access*, Volume 6, pp. 14268-14276.
- Ananga, P., 2020. Pedagogical Considerations of ELearning in Education for Development in the Face of COVID-19. *International Journal of Technology in Education and Science*, 4(4), pp. 310-321.
- Anwansedo, A. E., Craig, S. F. & Noguero, J., 2018. *How to Survive a Learning Management System (LMS) Implementation? A Stakeholder Analysis Approach*. Orlando, SIGUCCS.
- Anwar, A., Mansoor, H., Faisal, D. & Khan, H. S., 2021. E-Learning amid the COVID-19 Lockdown: Standpoint of Medical and Dental Undergraduates. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 37(1), pp. 217-222.
- Aparicio, M., Bacao, F. & Oliveira, T., 2016. An e-Learning Theoretical Framework. *Educational Technology & Society*, 19(1), pp. 292-307.
- Aparicio, M., Bacao, F. & Oliveira, T., 2016. An e-Learning Theoretical Framework. *Educational Technology & Society*, 19(1), pp. 292-307.
- Arbo, P. & Benneworth, P., 2007. *"Understanding the Regional Contribution of Higher Education Institutions: A Literature Review"*, Paris: OECD.
- Argyle, M. & Dean, J., 1965. Eye contact and distance affiliation. *Sociometry*, 28(3), pp. 289-304.
- Arogundade, B. B., 2012. The influence of ownership and type of university on work environment in south west Nigerian universities. *Journal of International Education Research*, 8(4), pp. 329-334.
- Asad, M. M., Wadho, M., Khand, Z. & Churi, P., 2020. Integration of E-Learning Technologies for Interactive Teaching and Learning Process: An Empirical Study on Higher Education Institutes of Pakistan. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 13(3).
- Asiyai, R. I., 2015. Improving Quality Higher Education in Nigeria: The Roles of Stakeholders. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 4(1), pp. 61-70.
- Aslam, H. D. et al., 2012. A Review of Teachers' Professional Development Initiatives and Associated Issues and Challenges in Higher Education Institutes of Pakistan. *Journal of American Science*, 8(1), pp. 54-60.
- Aviram, R. & Tami, D., 2004. THE IMPACT OF ICT ON EDUCATION: THE THREE OPPOSED PARADIGMS , THE LACKING DISCOURSE.

Awan, R. K., Afshan, G. & Memon, A. B., 2021. Adoption of E-Learning at Higher Education Institutions: A Systematic Literature Review. *Multidisciplinary Journal for Education, Social and Technological Sciences*, 8(2), pp. 74-91.

Ayele, A. A. & Birhanie, W. K., 2018. Acceptance and use of e-learning systems: the case of teachers in technology institutes of Ethiopian Universities. *Ayele and Birhanie Applied Informatics*, 5(1), pp. 1-11.

Abbas, A. H., 2022. Motivating Students to Learn in Time of COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of the College of Basic Education*, 2(SI), pp. 32-43.

Abbasi, K., 2024. *AIOU admissions plummet during last five years*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.dawn.com/news/1807214> [Accessed 15 July 2024].

Ahmad, S. et al., 2023. eLearning Acceptance and Adoption Challenges in Higher Education. *Sustainability*, Volume 15, pp. 1-18.

Ahmed, M. U., Hussain, S. & Farid, S., 2018. Factors influencing the Adoption of e-learning in an Open and Distance Learning Institution of Pakistan. *The Electronic Journal of E-learning*, 16(2), pp. 145-158.

AIOU, 2024. *About Us*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.aiou.edu.pk/> [Accessed 15 July 2024].

Aithal, P. S. & Satpathy, C. P. D. J., 2024. Exploring Neuro Management: Bridging Science and Leadership – An Overview. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters*, 8(2), pp. 39-73.

Akram, H., Aslam, S., Saleem, A. & Parveen, K., 2021. THE CHALLENGES OF ONLINE TEACHING IN COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A CASE STUDY OF PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN KARACHI, PAKISTAN. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, Volume 20, pp. 264-282.

Ali, S., Uppal, M. A. & Gulliver, S., 2017. A conceptual framework highlighting elearning implementation barriers. *Information Technology & People*, 31(1), pp. 156-180.

Baig, M. & Jamil, N., 2020. *A Review on the Learning Technologies to Address the Issues of Education in Pakistan*. s.l., IEEE.

Baig, Q. A., Zaidi, S. J. A. & Alam, B. F., 2019. Perceptions of dental faculty and students of E-learning and its application in a public sector Dental College in Karachi, Pakistan. *JPMA*, 69(9), pp. 1319-1324.

Bandhu, D. et al., 2024. Theories of motivation: A comprehensive analysis of human behavior drivers. *Acta Psychologica*, Volume 104177, pp. 1-16.

Babbar, M. & Gupta, T., 2021. Response of educational Institutions to Covid-19 pandemic: An inter-country comparison. *Policy Futures in Education*, pp. 1-23.

Bahari, S. F., 2010. Qualitative versus Quantitative research strategies: Contrasting epistemological and ontological assumptions. *Jurnal Teknologi*, Volume 52, pp. 17-28.

Baig, M. I., Shuib, L. & Yadegaridehkordi, E., 2021. E-learning adoption in higher

education: A review. *Information Development*, pp. 1-19.

Baric, A., 2017. Corporate social responsibility and stakeholders: Review of the last decade (2006-2015). *Business Systems Research*, 8(1), pp. 133-146.

Basar, S., Rahatullah, Nawaz, A. & Adnan, A., 2013. Net generation, threats & opportunities for higher education institutes. *Life Science Journal*, 10(12), pp. 372-377.

Batool, Z. & Qureshi, R. H., 2007. *Quality Assurance Manual For Higher Education in Pakistan*, Islamabad: HEC.

Baumann, U., 2005. Managing change in an academic environment: the German programme at the OUUK.. In: T. D. Evans, P. Smith & E. Stacey, eds. *Research in Distance Education*. Geelong: Deakin University, pp. 98-107.

Baxter, G., Sommerville & Ian, 2011. Socio-technical systems: From design methods to systems engineering. *Interacting with Computers*, Volume 23, pp. 4-17.

Beamish, N., Armistead, C., Watkinson, M. & Armfield, G., 2002. The deployment of e-learning in UK/ European corporate organisations. *European Business Journal*, 14(3), pp. 105-115.

Bedanta, K. K., 2020. ICT support for distance learning. *International Journal of All Research Writing*, 1(9), pp. 5-8.

Bekmukhambetova, A., 2021. *Comparative Analysis of Change Management Models Based on an Exploratory Literature Review*. Budapest, Corvinus University of Budapest.

Belaya, V., 2018. The Use of e-Learning in Vocational Education and Training (VET): Systematization of Existing Theoretical Approaches. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(5), pp. 92-101.

Benathy, B. H., 1991. *Systems Design of Education: A Journey to Create the Future*. New York: Educational Technology.

Benitez, J., Henseler, J., Castillo, A. & Schuberth, F., 2020. How to perform and report an impactful analysis using partial least squares: Guidelines for confirmatory and explanatory IS research. *Information & Management*, 57(2), pp. 1-16.

Benson, S. G. & Dundis, S. P., 2003. Understanding and motivating health care employees: integrating Maslow's hierarchy of needs, training and technology. *Journal of Nursing Management*, Volume 11, pp. 315-320.

Benavides, L. M. C. et al., 2020. Digital Transformation in Higher Education Institutions: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sensors MDPI*, Volume 20, pp. 1-22.

Board of Investment, 2024. *Information Technology*. [Online] Available at: <https://invest.gov.pk/it-ites#:~:text=SECTOR%20BRIEF&text=Pakistan%20has%20more%20than%20300%2C000,with%20a%20rising%20startup%20culture>. [Accessed 15 July 2024].

Bhuasiri, W., Xaymoungkhoun, O., Zo, H. & Rho, J., 2012. Critical success factors for e-learning in developing countries: A comparative analysis between ICT experts and faculty.

Computers & Education, Volume 58, pp. 843-855.

Bibi, G. & Sumra, I. A., 2017. A Comprehensive Survey on E-Learning System in Cloud Computing Environment. *ENGINEERING SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 1(1), pp. 43-50.

Bibi, P., Ahmad, A. & Majid, A. H. A., 2016. The Moderating Role of Work Environment on the Relationship between Compensation, Job Security, and Employees Retention. *International Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 10(4), pp. 726-738.

Biškupić, I. O., Lacković, S. & Jurina, K., 2015. Successful and proactive e-learning environment fostered by teachers' motivation in technology use. *Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 174, pp. 3656-3662.

Biswas, P. & Debnath, A. K., 2020. Worldwide scenario of unplanned transition to e-learning in the time of COVID-19 and Students' perception: A Review. *Mukt Shabd Journal*, 9(6), pp. 2038-2043.

Blass, E. & Davis, A., 2003. Building on solid foundations: establishing criteria for e-learning development. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 27(3), pp. 227-245.

Bleiklie, I. & Kogan, M., 2007. Organization and Governance of Universities. *Higher Education Policy*, Volume 20, pp. 477-493.

Blumberg, M., Cater-Steel, A. & Soar, J., 2014. *An Organisational Change Approach to Implementing IT Service Management*. Auckland, ACIS.

Blumberg, P., 1990. The Corporate Entity in an Era of Multinational Corporations. *Delaware Journal of Corporate Law*, 15(2), pp. 285-314.

Blynova, O. et al., 2020. CORPORATE CULTURE OF A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION AS A FACTOR IN FORMING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY. *REVISTA INCLUSIONES*, Volume 7, pp. 481-496.

Boe, T., Sandvik, K. & Gulbrandsen, B., 2020. Continued use of e-learning technology in higher education: a managerial perspective. *Studies in Higher Education*, pp. 1-16.

Bosamia, M. & Patel, A., 2016. An Overview of Cloud Computing for e-learning with Its Key Benefits. *International Journal of Information Sciences and Techniques*, 6(1), pp. 1-10.

Bouckenooghe, D., 2012. The role of organizational politics, contextual resources, and formal communication on change recipients' commitment to change: A multilevel study. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 21(4), pp. 575-602.

Bourkhouk, O., Bachari, E. E. & Adnani, M. E., 2017. A Recommender Model in E-learning Environment. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 42(2), pp. 607-617.

- Boyatzis, R. E., 1998. *Transforming qualitative information: thematic analysis and code development*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Bradford, P., Porciello, M., Balkon, N. & Backus, D., 2006. The blackboard learning system: the be all and end all in educational instruction?. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 35(3), pp. 301-314.
- Braun, V. & Clarke, V., 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77-101.
- Bristol, T. J. & Zerwekh, J., 2011. *Essentials of e-learning for Nurse Educators*. Philadelphia: F.A. Davis Company.
- Brush, T. & Saye, J. W., 2009. Strategies for preparing preservice social studies teachers to integrate technology effectively: Models and practices. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), pp. 46-59.
- Bryman, A. & Bell, E., 2011. *Business Research Methods*. 3rd ed. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Bryson, J., 2005. What to do when stakeholders matter: stakeholder identification and analysis techniques. *Public Management Reveiw*, 6(1), pp. 21-53.
- Bryson, J. M., 2004. What to do when Stakeholders matter. *Public Management Review*, 6(1), pp. 21-53.
- Brouwer, H., Hiemstra, W., Vugt, S. v. & Walters, H., 2013. Analysing stakeholder power dynamics in multi-stakeholder processes: insights of practice from Africa and Asia. *Knowledge Management for Development Journal*, 9(3), pp. 11-31.
- Burnes, B., 2020. The Origins of Lewin's Three-Step Model of Change. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 56(1), pp. 32-59.
- BTI, 2022. *BTI 2022 Pakistan Country Report*. [Online] Available at: <https://bti-project.org/en/reports/country-report/PAK> [Accessed 15 May 2022].
- Buchanan, D. A., 2008. You Stab My Back, I'll Stab Yours: Management Experience and Perceptions of Organization Political Behaviour. *British Journal of Management*, Volume 19, pp. 49-64.
- Burnes, B., 2004a. Kurt Lewin and the Planned Approach to Change: A Re-appraisal. *Journal of Management Studies*, 41(6), pp. 977-1002.
- Burnes, B., 2005. *Managing Change: A strategic approach to organisational dynamics*. 4th ed. Harlow: Prentice Hall.
- Burnes, B., 2007. Kurt Lewin and the Harwood Studies The foundations of OD. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 43(2), pp. 213-231.
- Burns, A. C. & Bush, R. F., 2000. *Marketing Research: Online research applications*. 4th ed. s.l.:Prentice Hall.
- Burrows, J., 1999. Going beyond labels: A framework for profiling institutional stakeholders.

Contemporary Education, 70(4), pp. 5-10.

Butcher, D. & Clarke, M., 1999. Organisational politics: the missing discipline of management?. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 31(1), pp. 9-12.

Cagiltay, N. E., Yildirim, S. & Aksu, M., 2006. Students' Preferences on Web-Based Instruction: linear or non-linear.. *Journal of Education, Technology and Society*, 9(3), pp. 122-16.

Cao, W. et al., 2020. The psychological impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on college students in China. *Psychiatry Research*, Volume 287, pp. 1-5.

Capece, G. & Campisi, D., 2013. User satisfaction affecting the acceptance of an e-learning platform as a mean for the development of the human capital. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 32(4), pp. 335-343.

Chandio, A. R., 2021. Evaluating ICT utilization in education administration and management during the COVID-19 outbreak in Pakistan: An empirical review. *Journal of Research in Instructional*, 1(2), pp. 81-94.

Chandio, S. et al., 2019. An ICT Integration in Higher Education Institutes of Pakistan: A Critical Literature Review. *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, 19(11), pp. 17-21.

Chapelo, C. & Sims, C., 2010. Stakeholder analysis in higher education: A case study of the University of Portsmouth. *Perspectives*, 14(1), pp. 12-20.

Chapman, J. A., 2002. A framework for transformational change in organisations. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 23(1), pp. 16-25.

Chase, S. E., 2005. Narrative Inquiry: Multiple Lenses, Approaches, Voices.. In: s.l.:Sage Publications ltd, pp. 651-679.

Chebbi, H. et al., 2019. Focusing on internal stakeholders to enable the implementation of organizational change towards corporate entrepreneurship: A case study from France. *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 119, pp. 209-217.

Chen, C., 2021. *Distance Learning Statistics and Growth of Online Education in 2020*. [Online]

Available at: <https://blog.otter.ai/distance-learning-statistics/>
[Accessed 14 April 2021].

Chetty, M. N. & Plessis, M. d., 2021. Systematic Review of the Job Demands and Resources of Academic Staff within Higher Education Institutions. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 10(3), pp. 268-284.

Choudhury, S. & Pattnaik, S., 2020. Emerging themes in e-learning: A review from the stakeholders'perspective. *Computers & Education*, Volume 144, pp. 1-32.

Chozos, P., Lytras, M. & Pouloudi, N., 2002. *Ethical Issues in E-learning: Insights from the Application of Stakeholder Analysis in three e-learning Cases*.. Montreal, Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE).

Chung, E., Subramaniam, G. & Dass, L. C., 2020. Online learning readiness among

- university students in Malaysia amidst COVID-19. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 16(2), pp. 46-58.
- Clarkson, M. B. E., 1995. A Stakeholder Framework for Analyzing and Evaluating Corporate Social Performance. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), pp. 92-117.
- Clements, M. D., 2009. Connecting key stakeholders: sustainable learning opportunities. *Development and Learning in Organizations: An International Journal*, 23(2), pp. 12-15.
- Coffie, R. B., Boateng, K. A. & Asombala, R., 2018. Electronic Voucher Payment System: Toward A Leavitt Diamond Analytical Perspectives of Technological Change. *Journal of Economic Development, Management, IT, Finance and Marketing*, 10(1), pp. 40-58.
- Coffie, R. B., Boateng, K. A. & Asombala, R., 2018. Electronic Voucher Payment System: Toward A Leavitt Diamond Analytical Perspectives of Technological Change. *Journal of Economic Development, Management, IT, Finance and Marketing*, 10(1), pp. 40-58.
- Conley, C., 2007. *Peak: How Great Companies Get Their Mojo from Maslow*. 1st ed. San Francisco: John Wiley & Sons.
- Cooper, P. A., 1993. Paradigm shifts in designed instruction: From behaviorism to cognitivism to constructivism. *Educational Technology*, 33(5), pp. 12-19.
- Coursera, 2022. *Coursera's Mission, Vision and Commitment to our Community*. [Online] Available at: <https://about.coursera.org/> [Accessed 16 May 2022].
- Crane, A. & Ruebottom, T., 2011. Stakeholder Theory and Social Identity: Rethinking Stakeholder Identification. *Journal of Business Ethics*, Volume 102, pp. 77-87.
- Creanor, L. & Walker, S., 2010. *Interpreting Complexity: a case for the sociotechnical interaction framework as an analytical lens for learning technology research*. Aalborg, s.n.
- Creswell, J. W., 2007. *Qualitative inquiry and Research design*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J. W., 2013. Five qualitative approaches to inquiry. In: *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five approaches*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications, pp. 53-84.
- Cunha, M. N., Chuchu, T. & Maziriri, E. T., 2020. Threats, Challenges, and Opportunities for Open Universities and Massive Online Open Courses in the Digital Revolution. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 15(12), pp. 191-204.
- Davies, J. A. et al., 2020. Responding to COVID-19 in EAP Contexts: A Comparison of Courses at Four Sino-Foreign Universities. *International Journal of TESOL Studies*, 2(2), pp. 32-51.
- Dawson, D., Mighty, J. & Britnell, J., 2010. Moving from the Periphery to the Center of the Academy: Faculty Developers as Leaders of Change. *New Directions for Teaching and Learning*, Issue 122, pp. 66-78.
- Dawson, M., 2014. *We Are ... wherever you are: Penn State marks 125 years of distance learning*. [Online]

Available at: <https://news.psu.edu/story/496777/2017/12/11/academics/we-are-whenever-you-are-penn-state-marks-125-years-distance> [Accessed 23 July 2019].

De Boer, H. F., Enders, J. & Leisyte, L., 2007. Public sector reform in Dutch higher education: The organizational transformation of the university. *Public Administration*, 85(1), pp. 27-46.

Deglane, K. C. B. et al., 2017. Stakeholders analysis in complex projects. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 6(9), pp. 73-81.

Demir, F., Kim, S. M., Current, N. & Jahnke, I., 2019. Strategic improvement planning in schools: A sociotechnical approach for understanding current practices and design recommendations. *Management in Education*, 33(4), pp. 166-180.

DeRouin, R. E., Fritzsche, B. A. & Salas, E., 2005. E-learning in Organizations. *Journal of Management*, 31(6), pp. 920-940.

Devi, L. L., 2017. Political Instability and Its Influence on Higher Education: A Study of Students' Perceptions in Manipur University. *International Journal of Humanities & Social Science Studies (IJHSSS)*, 3(5), pp. 300-307.

Dutta, A., 2020. Impact of digital social media on Indian higher education: alternative approaches of online learning during COVID-19 pandemic crisis. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 10(5), pp. 604-611.

Dwyer, P. M., 2004. Leading Change: Creating a Culture of Assessment. *To Improve the Academy*, 23(1), pp. 38-46.

Early, J. O. & Murphy, L., 2009. Self-Actualization and E-Learning: A Qualitative Investigation of University Faculty's Perceived Needs for Effective Online Instruction. *International Journal on E-learning*, 8(2), pp. 223-240.

Edelhauser, E. & Dima, L. L., 2020. Is Romania Prepared for eLearning during the COVID-19 Pandemic?. *Sustainability*, Volume 12, pp. 1-29.

Eden, C. & Ackermann, F., 1998. *Making Strategy: The Journey of Strategic Management*. London: Sage.

EduRank, 2021. *Lahore Garrison University Ranking*. [Online] Available at: <https://edurank.org/uni/lahore-garrison-university/> [Accessed 16 May 2021].

EduRank, 2021. *Superior Group of Colleges Ranking*. [Online] Available at: <https://edurank.org/uni/superior-group-of-colleges/> [Accessed 27 October 2021].

EdX, 2022. *About us- EdX*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.edx.org/about-us> [Accessed 16 May 2022].

- Ellahi, A. & Zaka, B., 2014. *eLearning and Higher Education in Pakistan: What may hamper it.* [Online] Available at: <https://elearnmag.acm.org/archive.cfm?aid=2668882#:~:text=In%20Pakistan%2C%20the%20first%2C%20mega,introducing%20ICT%20in%20the%20education.> [Accessed 9 July 2024].
- Emon, E. K. H., Alif, A. R. & Islam, M. S., 2020. Impact of COVID-19 on the institutional education system and its associated students in Bangladesh. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 11(2), pp. 34-46.
- Engelbrecht, E., 2003. A look at e-learning models: investigating their value for developing an e-learning strategy. *Progressio*, 25(2), pp. 38-47.
- Engel, C. J., 2019. THE ACCEPTABILITY OF ONLINE DEGREES IN ACCOUNTING: A LITERATURE REVIEW. *Global Journal of Business Pedagogy*, 3(1), pp. 10-26.
- Essam, S. & Al-Ammary, J., 2013. The Impact of Motivation and Social Interaction on the E-Learning at Arab Open University, Kingdom of Bahrain. *Creative Education*, 4(10A), pp. 21-28.
- Esterhuysen, M., Scholtz, B. & Venter, D., 2016. Intention to Use and Satisfaction of e-Learning for Training in the Corporate Context. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Information, Knowledge, and Management*, Volume 11, pp. 347-365.
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A. & Alkassim, R. S., 2016. Comparison of Convenience Sampling and Purposive Sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), pp. 1-4.
- Eze, S. C., Chinedu-Eze, V. C. & Bello, A. O., 2018. The utilisation of e-learning facilities in the educational delivery system of Nigeria: a study of M-University. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, Volume 15, pp. 1-20.
- Fabian, F. H., 2000. Keeping the Tension: Pressures to Keep the Controversy in the Management Discipline. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(2), pp. 350-371.
- Facts & Factors, 2020. *Global E-learning Market Size & Trends Will Reach USD 374.3 Billion by 2026: Facts & Factors.* [Online] Available at: <http://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2020/12/17/2146962/0/en/Global-E-learning-Market-Size-Trends-Will-Reach-USD-374-3-Billion-by-2026-Facts-Factors.html> [Accessed 31 March 2021].
- Falqueto, J. M. Z., Hoffmann, V. E., Gomes, R. C. & Mori, S. S. O., 2019. Strategic planning in higher education institutions: what are the stakeholders' roles in the process?. *Higher Education*, 79(6), pp. 1039-1056.
- Farid, S., Ahmad, R. & Alam, M., 2015. A HIERARCHICAL MODEL FOR E-LEARNING IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES USING AHP. *Malaysian Journal of Computer Science*, 28(3), pp. 166-188.
- Farid, S., Ahmad, R. & Alam, M., 2015. A HIERARCHICAL MODEL FOR E-LEARNING IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES USING AHP. *Malaysian Journal of Computer Science*, 28(3), pp. 166-188.

- Farid, S., Ahmad, R. & Alam, M., 2015a. A Hierarchical Model for E-learning Implementation Challenges using AHP. *Malaysian journal of Computer Science*, 28(3), pp. 166-188.
- Farid, S. et al., 2015. Identification and prioritization of critical issues for the promotion of e-learning in Pakistan. *Computers in Human Behavior*, Volume 51, pp. 161-171.
- Falqueto, J. M. Z., Hoffmann, V. E., Gomes, R. C. & Mori, S. S. O., 2019. Strategic planning in higher education institutions: what are the stakeholders' roles in the process?. *Higher Education*, Volume 79, pp. 1039-1056.
- Farid, S. et al., 2015. Identification and prioritization of critical issues for the promotion of e-learning in Pakistan. *Computers in Human Behavior*, Volume 51, pp. 161-171.
- Farid, S. et al., 2017. Security Threats and Measures in E-learning in Pakistan: A Review. *Technical Journal, University of Engineering and Technology*, 22(3), pp. 98-107.
- Findikli, B., 2020. A republic of scholars or scholars of the republic? Reflections on the predicaments of academic freedom and university autonomy in Turkey. *Higher Education Quarterly*, Volume 76, pp. 537-547.
- Farid, S. et al., 2014. *Identifying Perceived Challenges of E-learning Implementation*. Nawabshah, First International Conference on Modern Communication & Computing Technologies.
- Farid, S. et al., 2014. *Identifying Perceived Challenges of E-Learning Implementation*. Nawabshah, First International Conference on Modern Communication & Computing Technologies.
- Farid, S. et al., 2017. Security Threats and Measures in E-learning in Pakistan: A Review. *Technical Journal, University of Engineering and Technology*, 22(3), pp. 98-107.
- Farid, S., Qadir, M., Ahmed, M. U. & Khattak, M. D., 2018. Critical Success Factors of E-Learning Systems: A Quality Perspective. *Pakistan Journal of Distance & Online Learning*, 4(1), pp. 01-20.
- Fatima, S., Ahmad, N. & Fatima, S., 2021. Impact of COVID-19 and Coping Policies Implemented by Higher Education Institutions in South-Asian Countries: Systematic Review. *Global Economics Review*, 6(1), pp. 11-23.
- Ferrer-Balas, D., Buckland, H. & Mingo, M. d., 2009. Explorations on the University's role in society for sustainable development through a systems transition approach. Case-study of the Technical University of Catalonia (UPC). *journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 17, pp. 1075-1085.
- Filho, W. L., 2000. Dealing with misconceptions on the concept of sustainability. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 1(1), pp. 9-19.
- Filho, W. L., 2011. About the Role of Universities and Their Contribution to Sustainable Development. *Higher Education Policy*, Volume 24, pp. 427-438.
- Fisher, J. E., 2013. *KUHT-TV: The University of Houston's Second Great Vision*. [Online] Available at: <https://houstonhistorymagazine.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/03/KUHT.pdf> [Accessed 23 July 2019].

- Fisher, M. H. & Royster, D., 2016. Mathematics teachers' support and retention: using Maslow's hierarchy to understand teachers' needs. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL EDUCATION IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 47(7), pp. 993-1008.
- Fletcher, B. R., 1990. *Organization Transformation Theorists and Practitioners: Profiles and Themes*. 1st ed. New York: Praeger.
- Freeman, R. E., 1984. *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Boston: Pitman.
- Freitas, F. A. & Leonard, L. J., 2011. Maslow's hierarchy of needs and student academic success. *Teaching and Learning in Nursing*, Volume 6, pp. 9-13.
- Galic, S., Lusic, Z. & Stanivuk, T., 2020. E-LEARNING IN MARITIME AFFAIRS. *Journal of Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering*, Volume 17, pp. 39-50.
- Gkrimpizi, T., Peristeras, V. & Magnisalis, I., 2023. Classification of Barriers to Digital Transformation in Higher Education Institutions: Systematic Literature Review. *Educations Sciences*, Volume 13, pp. 1-24.
- Graetz, F. & Smith, A. C. T., 2010. Managing Organizational Change: A Philosophies of Change Approach. *Journal of Change Management*, 10(2), pp. 135-154.
- Grenway, B., 2021. A Review and Application of John Kotter's Leading Change. *Journal of Sociology and Christianity*, 11(2), pp. 91-95.
- Government of Pakistan, 2020. *Pakistan Economic Survey (Education Chapter 10)*, Islamabad: Government of Pakistan.
- Graff, M., Davies, J. & McNorton, M., 2004. Cognitive Style and Cross Cultural Differences in Internet Use and Computer Attitudes. *The European Journal of Open, Distance and E-Learning*.
- Grimble, R. & Chan, M. K., 1995. Stakeholder analysis for natural resource management in developing countries. *A United Nations Sustainable Development Journal*, 19(2), pp. 113-124.
- Guba, E. G. & Lincoln, Y. S., 1994. Competing Paradigms in Qualitative Research. In: *Handbook of qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage, pp. 105-117.
- Gunn, C., 2010. Sustainability factors for e-learning initiatives. *Research in Learning Technology*, 18(2), pp. 89-103.
- Hadullo, K., Oboko, R. & Omwenga, E., 2017. A model for evaluating e-learning systems quality in higher education in developing countries. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 13(2), pp. 185-204.
- Hall, T. et al., 2021. COVID-19 and education: positioning the pandemic; facing the future. *IRISH EDUCATIONAL STUDIES*, 40(2), pp. 147-149.
- Hamburg, I., 2015. Improving E-Learning in SMEs through Cloud Computing and Scenarios. In: B. Gradinarova, ed. *E-Learning - Instructional Design, Organizational Strategy and Management*. s.l.:InTech, pp. 481-500.
- Hameed, T., 2007. *ICT as an enabler of Socio-Economic Development*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.itu.int/osg/spu/digitalbridges/materials/hameed-paper.pdf>

[Accessed 03 March 2019].

Hare, M. & Pahl-Wostl, C., 2002. Stakeholder Categorisation in Participatory Integrated Assessment Processes. *Integrated Assessment*, 3(1), pp. 50-62.

Hasan, N. & Bao, Y., 2020. Impact of “e-Learning crack-up” perception on psychological distress among college students during COVID-19 pandemic: A mediating role of “fear of academic year loss”. *Children and Youth Services Review*, Volume 118, pp. 1-9.

Hassan, R., 2021. FACTORS AND CHALLENGES THAT INFLUENCE HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS’ ACCEPTANCE OF ELEARNING SYSTEM AFTER CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 99(11), pp. 2554-2566.

Hau, Y. S. & Chang, M. C., 2021. A Quantitative and Qualitative Review on the Main Research A Quantitative and Qualitative Review on the Main Research. *Healthcare*, 9(3), pp. 1-13.

HEC, 2020. HEC Recognized National Research Journals of Social Sciences, Islamabad: HEC.

Heck, J. & Luebkehan, C., 2023. XPLORING GLOBAL DRIVERS OF CHANGE FOR HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. Linz, Taking care of our future: Foresight and innovation for a sustainable world.

Hurtubise, L., Hall, E., Sheridan, L. & Han, H., 2015. The Flipped Classroom in Medical Education: Engaging Students to Build Competency. *Journal of Medical Education and Curricular Development*, Volume 2, pp. 35-43.

Hussain, I., Hussain, I. & Ramzan, M., 2019. Future Prospects of Virtual Education in Pakistan: Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 7(1).

Hussain, I. & Sajjad, S., 2018. Role of Distance Education in Nurturing Learning Pursuance among Learners: A Qualitative Study. *Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 6(2), pp. 120-139.

HEC EOI, 2019. *Expression of Interest (EOI) Transformation of Higher Education Institutions through Smart Classrooms*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/news/Documents1/EOI-CSR.pdf#search=e%2Dlearning> [Accessed 11 March 2022].

HEC F, 2017. *F: Research, Innovation and Commercialization*, Islamabad: HEC.

HEC Guide 1, 2020. *HEC Policy Guidelines for Universities and DAIs on COVID-19*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/HEC-Policy-Guidelines-Universities-DAIs.pdf> [Accessed 28 February 2022].

HEC Guide 2, 2020. *Guidelines for Faculty and Staff of the Universities DAIs*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/Guidelines-Faculty.pdf>

[Accessed 28 February 2022].

HEC Guide 3, 2020. *TSC- Final Approved Working Paper*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/Approved-Working-Paper.pdf>

[Accessed 27 February 2022].

HEC Guide 4, 2020. *HEC Policy Guidance Series on COVID-19*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/Government-Directive.pdf>

[Accessed 28 February 2022].

HEC Guide 5, 2020. *HEC Covid-19 Policy Guidance No.5 (Online Readiness)*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/Covid-19-Policy-Guidance-No.5-Online%20Readiness.pdf>

[Accessed 28 February 2022].

HEC Guide 6, 2020. *Assessments & Examinations*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/Assessments-Examinations.pdf>

[Accessed 28 February 2022].

HEC Guide 6A, 2020. *HEC Covid-19 Policy Guidance No. 6a (PhD/MPhil/MS Defense & Final Juries)*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/PhD-MPhil-MSDefense-Final-Juries.pdf>

[Accessed 28 February 2022].

HEC Guide 6B, 2020. *HEC Covid-19 Guidance No.6b - O&A Level Admissions*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/OandA-Level-Admissions.pdf>

[Accessed 28 February 2022].

HEC Guide 7, 2020. *Strategy for Gradual Opening of HEIs*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/Reopening-of-HEIs.pdf>

[Accessed 28 February 2022].

HEC Guide 8, 2020. *HEC Policy Guidance Note # 8, Further Guidance*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/Further-Guidance-HEIs.pdf>

[Accessed 28 February 2022].

HEC, 2002. *Higher Education Ordinance- After Approval of Cabinet and Law Division*. [Online]

Available at: https://hec.gov.pk/english/aboutus/Documents/455_HECOOrdinance.pdf

[Accessed 08 December 2021].

- HEC, 2015. *National Qualifications Framework of Pakistan*, Islamabad: HEC.
- HEC, 2016. *5th Ranking of Pakistani Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)*, Islamabad: HEC.
- HEC, 2020. *Covid 19 policy guidance no 5 online readiness*, Islamabad: HEC.
- HEC, 2020. *Establishment of OACs*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/services/universities/QAA/Documents/Establishment%20of%20OACs.pdf> [Accessed 30 November 2021].
- HEC, 2020. *STEPS AFOOT TO AVOID EDUCATIONAL LOSS OF STUDENTS AMIDST CORONA CRISIS*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.hec.gov.pk/english/news/news/Pages/Corona-Crisis.aspx> [Accessed 18 April 2021].
- HEC, 2021B. *News-HEC*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/news/news/Pages/VC-Meeting.aspx> [Accessed 09 December 2021].
- HEC, 2021C. *HEC Covid-19 Guidance*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/Pages/Covid-19-Guidance.aspx> [Accessed 10 December 2021].
- HEC, 2021D. *Knowledge Exchange Initiatives*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/services/universities/kei/Pages/default.aspx> [Accessed 10 December 2021].
- HEC, 2021U. *About us*. [Online] Available at: <https://hec.gov.pk/english/aboutus/pages/aboutus.aspx> [Accessed 8 December 2021].
- Henderson, G. M., 2002. Transformative Learning as a Condition for Transformational Change in Organisations. *Human resource development review*, 1(2), pp. 186-214.
- Higher Education Commission, 2020. *HEC Covid-19 Policy Papers*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.hec.gov.pk/english/HECAnnouncements/Documents/nCoVirus/Covid-19-Policy-Guidance-No.5-Online%20Readiness.pdf> [Accessed 1 July 2020].
- Hofstede, G., 1980. *Culture's consequences: International differences in work related values*. London: Sage Publications.
- Holsapple, C. W. & Lee-Post, A., 2006. Defining, assessing, and promoting e-learning success: An information systems perspective. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education*, 4(1), pp. 67-85.
- Hoq, M. Z., 2020. E-Learning during the period of pandemic (COVID-19) in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia: An empirical study.. *American Journal of Educational Research* , 8(7), pp. 457-464.
- Horton, L. & Pilkington, A., 2014. Rolling Back from the Power/interest Matrix: A New

Approach for Role Based Stakeholder Engagement in Projects. *PM World Journal*, 3(5), pp. 1-5.

Hubackova, S., 2014. Motivation in eLearning in university study. *Social and Behavioural Sciences*, Volume 112, pp. 309-313.

Hyder, K., Kwinn, A., Miazga, R. & Murray, M., 2007. *Synchronous E-Learning*, Santa Rosa: The eLearning Guild.

Instructure, 2022. *Our Story- Canvas by Instructure*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.instructure.com/about/our-story> [Accessed 16 May 2022].

Iqbal, M. J. & Ahmed, M., 2010. Enhancing quality of education through e-learning: the case study of Allama Iqbal Open University. *The Turkish online Journal of Distance Education*, 11(1), pp. 84-97.

Iqbal, S., Naeem, M. A. & Nayyar, A., 2016. *Status of MOOCs in Pakistan: Optimism and Concerns*. Pisa, European Modelling Symposium.

Iqbal, T., 2020. MEDICAL STUDENTS' E-LEARNING DURING COVID-19 LOCKDOWN. *Pakistan Journal of Physiol*, 16(1), pp. 1-2.

Iris, R. & Vikas, A., 2011. E-Learning technologies: A key to Dynamic Capabilities. *Computers in Human Behavior*, Volume 27, pp. 1868-1874.

Isa, W. M. K. W., Nor, M. Y. M. & Wahab, J. L. A., 2020. Principal Change Facilitator Styles and the Effect on Teacher Technology Integration in School: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education & Development*, 9(3), pp. 26-40.

Islam, N., Beer, M. & Slack, F., 2015. E-Learning Challenges Faced by Academics in Higher Education: A Literature Review. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 3(5), pp. 102-112.

Ilic, M., Mikic, V., Kopanja, L. & Vesin, B., 2023. Intelligent techniques in e-learning: a literature review. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, Volume 56, p. 14907–14953.

Jan, A., Sultana, I. & Adnan, M., 2020. Digital Media and Smart Education in Pakistan: Challenges and Prospects for the Teachers in the Age of E-Learning. *Global Educational Studies Review*, 5(4), pp. 51-59.

Jawed, K. & Fatima, S. S., 2021. Exploring the Journey of Students in an Online CHPE Program of a Pakistani University: An Exploratory Qualitative Study. *JIIIMC*, 16(4), pp. 274-280.

Jan, S., 2018. Gender, School and Class-Wise Differences in Level of Digital Literacy Among Secondary School Students in Pakistan. *Issues and Trends in Learning Technologies*, 6(1), pp. 15-27.

Jewels, T. & Ford, M., 2006. The Development of a Taxonomy of Desired Personal Qualities for IT Project Team Members and Its Use in an Educational Setting. *Journal of Information Technology Education*, Volume 5, pp. 285-298.

Johns Hopkins University, 2021. *Coronavirus COVID-19 (2019-nCov)*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.arcgis.com/apps/opsdashboard/index.html#/bda7594740fd40299423467b48e9ecf6> [Accessed 22 April 2021].

Johnson, G. & Scholes, K., 2002. *Exploring Corporate Strategy*. Harlow: Prentice Hall.

Jongbloed, B., Enders, J. & Salerno, C., 2008. Higher education and its communities: Interconnections, interdependencies and a research agenda. *Higher Education*, Volume 56, pp. 303-324.

Juniu, S., 2005. Digital Democracy in Higher Education: Bridging the Digital Divide. *Innovate Journal of Online Education*, 2(1).

Kant, N., 2019. COMPETITIVENESS IN ODL FROM STAKEHOLDERS' PERSPECTIVE: A REVIEW AND RESEARCH AGENDA. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 20(3), pp. 59-72.

Kanwal, F. & Rehman, M., 2017. Factors Affecting E-Learning Adoption in Developing Countries—Empirical Evidence From Pakistan's Higher Education Sector. *IEEE Access*, Volume 5, pp. 10968-10978.

Kanwal, F., Rehman, M., Bashir, K. & qureshi, U., 2017. Critical Factors of E-Learning Adoption and Acceptance in Pakistan: A Literature Review. *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, 7(4), pp. 1888-1893.

Kanwal, F., Rehman, M., Bashir, K. & Qureshi, U., 2017. Critical Factors of E-Learning Adoption and Acceptance in Pakistan: A Literature Review. *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, 7(4), pp. 1888-1893.

Khadim, M., Jamil, S. & Rafiq, S., 2022. Emerging Trends in Curriculum Development and Evaluation in Pakistan at Higher Education Level: A Current Perspective of 21st Century. *Journal of Social & Organizational Matters*, 1(2), pp. 1-10.

Khamis, T., Naseem, A., Khamis, A. & Petrucka, P., 2021. The COVID-19 pandemic: a catalyst for creativity and collaboration for online learning and work-based higher education systems and processes. *Journal of Work-Applied Management*, 13(2), pp. 184-196.

Khan, A., 2017. Expanding Horizons: Contribution of an Online Community in the Professional Learning of Teachers in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Distance & Online Learning*, 3(2), pp. 25-40.

Khan, S. M. et al., 2024. Impact of COVID-19 on teachers, teaching profession towards technology adaptation and attendance at educational institute: Evidence from Pakistan. *Journal of Excellence in Social Sciences*, 3(3), pp. 95-116.

Kundi, G. M. & Nawaz, A., 2014. From e-Learning 1.0 to e-Learning 2.0: Threats & Opportunities for Higher Education Institutions in the Developing Countries. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 3(1), pp. 145-160.

Kamil, N. M., 2011. Ontology and epistemology in management research: An Islamic Perspective. *Post modern Openings*, 2(7), pp. 67-74.

- Kanwal, F. & Rehman, M., 2014. E-learning Adoption Model: A case study of Pakistan. *Life Science Journal*, 11(4), pp. 78-86.
- Kanwal, F., Rehman, M. & Asif, M. M., 2020. E-learning adoption and acceptance in Pakistan: Moderating effect of gender and experience. *Mehran University Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 39(2), pp. 324-341.
- Kanwal, F., Rehman, M., Bashir, K. & Qureshi, U., 2017. Critical factors of e-learning adoption and acceptance in Pakistan: A literature review. *Engineering, Technology and Applied Science Research*, 7(4), pp. 1888-1893.
- Kanwal, F., Rehman, M., Bashir, K. & Qureshi, U., 2017. Critical Factors of E-Learning Adoption and Acceptance in Pakistan: A Literature Review. *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, 7(4), pp. 1888-1893.
- Kasani, H. A. et al., 2020. E-Learning Challenges in Iran: A Research Synthesis. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 21(4), pp. 96-116.
- Kasani, H. A. et al., 2020. E-Learning Challenges in Iran: A Research Synthesis. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 21(4).
- Kattoua, T., Al-Lozi, M. & Alrowwad, A., 2016. A Review of Literature on E-Learning Systems in Higher Education. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 7(5), pp. 754-762.
- Kavanagh, M. H. & Ashkanasy, N. M., 2006. The Impact of Leadership and Change Management Strategy on Organizational Culture and Individual Acceptance of Change during a Merger. *British Journal of Management*, 17(1), pp. 81-103.
- Keen, P. G. W., 1981. Information Systems and Organizational Change. *Social Impacts of Computing*, 24(1), pp. 24-33.
- Kemp, S., 2022. *DIGITAL 2022: PAKISTAN*. [Online] Available at: <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2022-pakistan> [Accessed 02 May 2022].
- Khalid, M., Hanif, A. & Laila, U., 2017. Transfer of Training & the Challenges: NADRA A Case Study. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, 6(1), pp. 274-288.
- Khan, A. A., Niazi, S. & Saif, S. K., 2020. *Universities unprepared for switch to remote learning*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20200326141547229> [Accessed 16 April 2021].
- Khan, A. A. & Umair, S., 2017. Mobile Devices in Classroom. In: *Handbook of research on mobile devices and smart gadgets in K-12 education: IGI Global*. Hershey: IGI Global, p. 185.
- Khan, A., Egbue, O., Palkie, B. & Madden, J., 2017. Active Learning: Engaging Students To Maximize Learning In An Online Course. *The Electronic Journal of e-Learning*, 15(2), pp. 107-115.
- Khan, A. J. et al., 2021. Employee Job Satisfaction in Higher Educational Institutes: A

Review of Theories. *Journal of South Asian Studies* , 09(3), pp. 257-266.

Khan, M. A., Ahmed, S. K. & Khan, A. Z., 2022. Issues and Challenges Faced by Higher Education Institutions in the E-Learning Modes: A Systematic Literature Review. *Modes: A Systematic Literature Review* , 21(1), pp. 16-27.

Khan, N., Aajiz, N. M. & Ali, A., 2018. Comparison of Management Practices in Public and Private Universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(1), pp. 108-122.

Khan, T. A. & Jabeen, N., 2019. Higher Education Reforms and Tenure Track in Pakistan: Perspectives of Leadership of Regulatory Agencies. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 41(2), pp. 181-205.

Khanyile, M., 2018. ESSENTIALITY OF STAKEHOLDER MANAGEMENT FOR UNIVERSITY SURVIVAL. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 32(4), pp. 132-148.

Khawaja, A. A., Zafar, F., Aslam, T. & Hussain, A., 2011. *Quality Assurance and Accreditation Practices in Pakistan*, Islamabad: Quality Assurance Agency, HEC.

Kiger, M. E. & Varpio, L., 2020. Thematic analysis of qualitative data: AMEE Guide No 131. *Medical Teacher*, pp. 1-9.

Kim, A. J., 2006. *Community Building on the Web: Secret Strategies for Successful Online Communities*. s.l.:Peachpit Press.

Kivunja, C. & Kuyini, A. B., 2017. Understanding and applying research paradigms in educational context. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 6(5), pp. 26-41.

Kling, R., 2000. Learning About Information Technologies and Social Change: The Contribution of Social Informatics. *The Information Society: An International Journal*, 16(3), pp. 217-232.

Koo, A. C., 2008. Factors affecting teachers' perceived readiness for online collaborative learning: A case study in Malaysia. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 11(1), pp. 266-278.

Kotsilieris, T. & Dimopoulou, N., 2013. The Evolution of e-Learning in the Context of 3D Virtual Worlds. *Electronic Journal of e-Learning*, 11(2), pp. 147-167.

Kotter, J. P., 1995. Leading Change: Why Transformation Efforts Fail. *Harvard Business Review*, pp. 1-9.

Kotter, J. P., 1996. *Leading Change*. Boston: Harvard Business School.

Kundi, G. M. & Nawaz, A., 2014. From e-Learning 1.0 to e-Learning 2.0: Threats & Opportunities for Higher Education Institutions in the Developing Countries. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 3(1), pp. 145-160.

Kundi, G. M., Nawaz, A. & Khan, S., 2010. The predictors of success for e-learning in higher education institutions (HEIs) in N-W.F.P, Pakistan. *Journal of information systems and technology management*, 7(3), pp. 545-578.

Kvale, S., 1996. *InterViews: an introduction to qualitative research interviewing*. Thousand

Oaks: Sage Publications.

Lagrosen, S., Hashemi, R. S. & Leitner, M., 2004. Examination of the dimensions of quality in Higher Education. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 12(2), pp. 61-69.

Lahore Garrison University, 2021. *About us- Lahore Garrison University*. [Online] Available at: <http://lgu.edu.pk/about-us/> [Accessed May 16 2021].

Lahore Garrison University, 2021. *Lahore Garrison university- About*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/lahore-garrison-university/about/> [Accessed 16 May 2021].

Lampaki, A. & Papadakis, V., 2018. The impact of organisational politics and trust in the top management team on strategic decision implementation success: A middle-manager's perspective. *European Management Journal*, 36(5), pp. 627-637.

Lasakova, A., Bajzikova, L. & Dedze, I., 2017. Barriers and drivers of innovation in higher education: Case study-based evidence across ten European universities. *International Journal of Educational Development*, Volume 55, pp. 66-79.

Lashayo, D. M. & Md Johar, M. G., 2017. A REVIEW OF E-LEARNING SYSTEMS' ADOPTION IN TANZANIA UNIVERSITIES. *South East Asia Journal of Contemporary Business, Economics and Law*, 13(2), pp. 111-118.

Leatherbarrow, C. & Fletcher, J., 2019. *Introduction to Human Resource Management: A guide to HR in Practice*. 4th ed. London: Kogan Page Limited.

Leavitt, H. J., 1964. *Applied organization change in industry: structural, technical and human approaches*. Chichester, Wiley.

Lechtchinskaia, L., Uffen, J. & Breitner, M. H., 2011. *Critical Success Factors for Adoption of Integrated Information Systems in Higher Education Institutions-a Meta-Analysis*. s.l., AMCIS.

Lee, Y.-H., Hsieh, Y.-C. & Ma, C.-Y., 2011. A model of organizational employees' e-learning systems acceptance. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 24(3), pp. 355-366.

Levi, L. & Rothstein, B., 2018. *Universities must lead on Sustainable Development Goals*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20181106131352348> [Accessed 29 November 2019].

Lewin, K., 1946. Action Research and Minority Problems. *Journal of Social Issues*, 2(4), pp. 34-46.

LGU, 2021. *About Us- Lahore Garrison University*. [Online] Available at: <http://lgu.edu.pk/about-us/> [Accessed 30 July 2021].

LGU, 2021. *Conferences*. [Online] Available at: <http://lgu.edu.pk/conferences/> [Accessed 16 May 2021].

- Lim, F. P., 2017. An Analysis of Synchronous and Asynchronous Communication Tools in e-Learning. *Advanced Science and Technology Letters* , Volume 143, pp. 230-234.
- Lockey, A., Conaghan, P., Bland, A. & Astin, F., 2021. Educational theory and its application to advanced life support courses: a narrative review. *Resuscitation Plus*, Volume 5, pp. 1-7.
- Longhurst, G. J. et al., 2020. Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat (SWOT) Analysis of the Adaptations to Anatomical Education in the United Kingdom and Republic of Ireland in Response to the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Anatomical Sciences Education*, Volume 13, pp. 298-308.
- Lozano, R. et al., 2015. A review of commitment and implementation of sustainable development in Higher education: results from a worldwide survey. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 108, pp. 1-18.
- Lubbers, J. H., Repetto, J. B. & McGorray, S. P., 2008. Perceptions of Transition Barriers, Practices, and Solutions in Florida. *Remedial and Special Education*, 29(5), pp. 280-292.
- Lynch, J., Sheard, J., Carbone, A. & Collins, F., 2005. Individual and Organisational Factors Influencing Academics' Decisions to Pursue the Scholarship of Teaching ICT. *Journal of Information Technology Education*, Volume 4, pp. 219-236.
- Lyytinen, K., Mathiassen, L. & Ropponen, J., 1998. Attention Shaping and Software Risk- A Categorical Analysis of Four Classical Risk Management Approaches. *Information Systems Research*, 9(3), pp. 233-255.
- Lyytinen, K. & Newman, M., 2008. Explaining information systems change: a punctuated socio-technical change model. *European Journal of Information Systems*, Volume 17, pp. 589-613.
- Maharani, N. Z. et al., 2024. Motivations and Potential Solutions in Developing a Knowledge Management System for Organization at Higher Education: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Information Systems Engineering and Business Intelligence*, 10(2), pp. 270-289.
- Mehmood, N. et al., 2021. E-learning in the era of Covid-19 Pandemic: the Challenges and Opportunities. *Pakistan Journal of Medical and Health Sciences*, 15(11), pp. 3228-3232.
- Murtaza, K. G. & Hui, L., 2021. Higher Education in Pakistan: Challenges, Opportunities, Suggestions. *The Asian Institute of Research Education Quarterly Reviews*, 4(2), pp. 213-219.
- Macleod, H., 2005. What role can educational multimedia play in narrowing the digital divide?. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology* , 1(4), pp. 44-53.
- Mader, C., Scott, G. & Razak, D. A., 2013. Effective change management, Governance and Policy for Sustainability Transformation in Higher Education. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 4(3), pp. 264-284.
- Magnaye-Laylo, L., 2020. Technological Management Efficiency on Higher Educational Institutes Towards Organisational Performance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Academic Research in Social Sciences*, 5(2), pp. 35-51.
- Mahmod, M. A. et al., 2017. *E-learning in Iraqi universities: A review*. Kuala Lumpur, IEEE.

- Maina, M. K. & Nzuki, D. M., 2015. Adoption determinants of e-learning management system in institutions of higher learning in Kenya: a case of selected universities in Nairobi Metropolitan. *International Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 6(2), pp. 223-248.
- Mainardes, E. W., Alves, H. & Raposo, M., 2010. An Exploratory Research on the Stakeholders of a University. *Journal of Management and Strategy*, 1(1), pp. 76-88.
- Malawige, I. R., 2018. *Creating Value in E-learning: Beyond Triple Factor to Improve Teaching Learning Experience*. Colombo, IEEE Xplore, pp. 142-149.
- Malik, M. W., 2010. Factor Effecting Learner's Satisfaction Towards E-Learning: A Conceptual Framework. *OIDA International Journal of Sustainable Development*, 2(3), pp. 77-82.
- Mannion, R. et al., 2018. Understanding the knowledge gaps in whistleblowing and speaking up in health care: narrative reviews of the research literature and formal inquiries, a legal analysis and stakeholder interviews. *HEALTH SERVICES AND DELIVERY RESEARCH*, 6(30), pp. 1-189.
- Maqsood, A., Abbas, J., Rehman, G. & Mubeen, R., 2021. The paradigm shift for educational system continuance in the advent of COVID-19 pandemic: Mental health challenges and reflections. *Current Research in Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 2, pp. 1-5.
- Maric, I., 2013. STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. *Interdisciplinary Description of Complex Systems*, 11(2), pp. 217-226.
- Marques, J., 2013. *A Short History of MOOCs and Distance Learning*. [Online] Available at: <http://mooconewsandreviews.com/a-short-history-of-moocs-and-distance-learning/> [Accessed 23 July 2019].
- Maslov, I., Nikou, S. & Hansen, P., 2021. Exploring user experience of learning management system. *The International journal of Information and Learning Technology*, 38(4), pp. 344-363.
- Maslow, A. H., 1943. A Theory of Human Motivation. *Psychological Review*, Volume 50, pp. 370-396.
- Maslow, A. H., 1943. A Theory of Motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(5), pp. 370-396.
- Matt, C., Hess, T., Benlian, A. & Wiesbock, F., 2016. Options for Formulating a Digital Transformation Strategy. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 15(2), pp. 1-38.
- Mazhar, S. & Akhtar, M. S., 2016. Knowledge management practices: A Comparative study of public and private sector universities at Lahore. *Journal of Quality and Technology Management*, 12(1), pp. 81-90.
- Melewar, T. C. & Akel, S., 2005. The role of corporate identity in the higher education sector. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 10(1), pp. 41-57.
- Memon, G. R., 2007. Education in Pakistan: The key issues, problems and the new challenges. *Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3(1), pp. 47-55.
- Memon, G. R., 2007. Education in Pakistan: The Key Issues, Problems and The New

Challenges. *Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3(1), pp. 47-55.

Menchaca, M., Bischoff, M. & Dara-Abrams, B., 2003. *A Model for Systemic Change Management in Education*. Florida, International Conference on Education and Information Systems: Technologies and Applications.

Milheim, K. L., 2012. Toward a Better Experience: Examining Student Needs in the Online Classroom through Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Model. *Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 8(2), pp. 159-171.

Mishra, L., Gupta, T. & Shree, A., 2020. Online teaching-learning in higher education during lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, Volume 1.

Mitchell, R., Agle, B. & Wood, D., 1997. Toward a Theory of Stakeholder Identification and Saliency: Defining the Principle of Who and What Really Counts. *Academy of Management Review*, 22(4), pp. 853-886.

Moakofhi, M. et al., 2017. Challenges of introducing e-learning at Botswana University of Agriculture and Natural Resources: Lecturers' Perspective. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 13(2), pp. 4-20.

Modritshcer, f., Spiel, S. & Garcia-Barrios, V. M., 2006. *Assessment in E-Learning Environments: A Comparison of three Methods*. Chesapeake, Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE), pp. 108-113.

Moodle, 2019. *History-MoodleDocs*. [Online] Available at: <https://docs.moodle.org/37/en/History> [Accessed 23 July 2019].

Morgan, D. L., 2007. Paradigms lost and pragmatism regained: Methodological implications of combining qualitative and quantitative methods. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(1), pp. 48-76.

Mosa, A. A., Mahrin, M. N. b. & Ibrahram, R., 2016. Technological Aspects of E-Learning Readiness in Higher Education: A Review of the Literature. *Computer and Information Science*, 9(1), pp. 113-127.

Mseleku, Z., 2020. A Literature Review of E-Learning and E-Teaching in the Era of Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 5(10), pp. 588-597.

Mueed, M. I., 2016. The Reality of Academic Autonomy in Public-sector Universities of Pakistan: A Case Study of University of Education, Lahore. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies*, Volume 27, pp. 65-73.

Mukherjee, A. B., 2021. Implications of Online Education in COVID-19 Pandemic- A Review. *Online Journal of Netaji Subhas online University*, 4(1), pp. 1-6.

Mullins, L. J., 2007. *Management and Organisational Behaviour*. 8th ed. Essex: Pearson Education Limited.

- Mumford, E., 2006. The story of socio-technical design: reflections on its successes, failures and potential. *Info Systems Journal*, Volume 16, pp. 317-342.
- Mumtaz, N., Saqulain, G. & Mumtaz, N., 2021. Online Academics in Pakistan: COVID-19 and Beyond. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences* , 37(1), pp. 283-287.
- Mushtaq, M., Noor, A. & Sabahat, N., 2021. *Adoption Barriers of E-Learning in Higher Education Institutes (HEI's) of Developing Countries - A Systematic Literature Review*. Lahore, IEEE.
- Muzaffar, A. W. et al., 2021. A Systematic Review of Online Exams Solutions in E-Learning: Techniques, Tools, and Global Adoption. *IEEE Access*, Volume 9, pp. 32689-32712.
- Muzari, T., Shava, G. N. & Shonhiwa, S., 2022. Qualitative Research Paradigm, a Key Research Design for Educational Researchers, Processes and Procedures: A Theoretical Overview. *Indiana Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(1), pp. 14-20.
- Nawaz, A., 2011. The Challenges & opportunities of eLearning for Higher Education in KPK Pakistan, KPK: Gomal University.
- Nordberg, T. H. & Andreassen, T. A., 2020. Challenging professional control? Reforming higher education through stakeholder involvement. *Journal of Education and Work*, 33(2), pp. 169-183.
- Nampala, M. P., Kityo, R. & Massa, H., 2017. Tracing the evolution of higher education institutions and linkage to rural development in Africa. *African Journal of Rural Development*, 2(2), pp. 143-151.
- National Institute of Health, 2020. *COVID-19 National Institute of Health*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.nih.org.pk/novel-coronavirus-2019-ncov/> [Accessed 15 April 2021].
- Naveed, Q. N. et al., 2017. Barriers Effecting Successful Implementation of E-Learning in Saudi Arabian Universities. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning* , 12(6), pp. 94-107.
- Navimipour, N. J. & Zareie, B., 2015. A model for assessing the impact of e-learning systems on employees' satisfaction. *Computers in Human Behavior*, Volume 53, pp. 475-485.
- Nawaz, A., 2012. E-learning experiences of HEIs in advanced states, developing countries and Pakistan. *Universal Journal of Education and General Studies*, 1(3), pp. 72-83.
- Nawaz, A., 2012. Investigating the change management For implementing e-learning projects in higher education. *Journal of Research in International Business Management*, 1(9), pp. 1-11.
- Nawaz, A. & Khan, M. Z., 2012. Issues of Technical Support for e-Learning Systems in Higher Education Institutions. *International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science*, Volume 2, pp. 38-44.
- Nawaz, A. & Kundi, G. M., 2010. Predictor of e-learning development and use practices in higher education institutions (heis) of NWFP, Pakistan. *Journal of Science and Technology*

Education Research, 1(3), pp. 44-54.

Nawaz, A. & Qureshi, Q. A., 2010. Sustained Technical Support: Issue & Prospects for E-Learning In Heis. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 10(9), pp. 32-39.

Neumeier, M., 2013. Using Kotter's change management theory and innovation diffusion theory in implementing an electronic medical record. *Canadian Journal of Nursing Informatics*, 8(1), pp. 1-8.

Nicholson, P., 2007. *Computers and Education : E-Learning, From Theory to Practice*. 1 ed. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.

Njenga, J. K. & Fourie, L. C. H., 2010. The myths about e-learning in higher education. *British journal of educational technology*, 41(2), pp. 199-212.

Nowell, L. S., Norris, J. M., White, D. E. & Moules, N. J., 2017. Thematic Analysis: Striving to Meet the Trustworthiness Criteria. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, Volume 16, pp. 1-13.

Nusrat, W., 2020. *Superior College*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.pakpedia.pk/superior-college/> [Accessed 27 October 2021].

Nybom, T., 2008. University autonomy: a matter of political rhetoric. In: Orebro: Orebro University, pp. 133-141.

Oblinger, D. & Rush, S., 1997. *The Future Compatible Campus*. Bolton: Anker Publishing.

Odor, H., 2018. Organisational Change and Development. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 10(7), pp. 58-66.

Okunoye, A. & Karsten, H., 2002. *ITI as Enabler of Knowledge Management: Empirical Perspective from Research Organisations in sub-Saharan Africa*. Hawaii, IEEE.

Oluwunmi, A. O., Akinjare, O. A., Ajibola, M. O. & Oloke, O. C., 2018. An evaluation of the basic facility needs of private university students in Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 9(9), pp. 476-484.

Oppewal, H., 2010. *Causal research*, s.l.: Wiley International Encyclopedia of Marketing.

Orndoff, C. J. W., 2005. Promising New Tool for Stakeholder Interaction. *journal of Architectural Engineering*, 11(4), pp. 139-146.

O'Sullivan, K., 2008. *Strategic Knowledge Management in Multinational Organizations*. New York: IGI Global.

Pan, Y.-C., Tang, Y. & Gulliver, S., 2013. *Mutual Dependency Grid for Stakeholder Mapping A Component-Based Approach to Supply Chain Participant Analysis*. Stockholm, 14th International Conference on Informatics and Semiotics in Organisation (ICISO), pp. 72-81.

PERN, 2024. *About Us*. [Online] Available at: <https://pern.edu.pk/> [Accessed 15 July 2024].

Papazafeiropoulou, A., Pouloudi, A. & Currie, W. L., 2001. *Applying the stakeholder concept to electronic commerce: extending previous research to guide government policy makers*. Maui, USA, IEEE.

Patton, M. Q., 2015. *Sampling, Qualitative (Purposeful)*. [Online] Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/9781405165518.wbeoss012.pub2> [Accessed 05 February 2022].

Phillippi, J. & Lauderdale, J., 2018. A guide to field notes for Qualitative Research: Context and Conversation. *Qualitative Health Research*, 28(3), pp. 381-388.

Polkinghorne, D. E., 2005. Language and Meaning: Data Collection in Qualitative Research. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 52(2), pp. 137-145.

Pollitt, D., 2004. Training is a never-ending process at Nestle. *Human Resource Management*, 12(6), pp. 27-29.

Pollock, N. & Cornford, J., 2004. ERP systems and the university as a “unique” organization. *Information Technology & People*, 17(1), pp. 31-52.

Prell, C., Hubacek, K., Quinn, C. & Reed, M., 2008. ‘Who’s in the Network?’ When Stakeholders Influence Data Analysis. *Systemic Practice and Action Research*, Volume 21, pp. 443-458.

Presenza, A. & Cipollina, M., 2010. Analysing tourism stakeholders networks. *Tourism Review*, 65(4), pp. 17-30.

Preston, L. & Donaldson, T., 1999. Stakeholder Management and Organizational wealth. *Academy of Management Review*, 3(3), pp. 345-364.

Preston, L. E. & Sapienza, H. J., 1990. Stakeholder Management and Corporate Performance. *The Journal of Behavioural Economics*, 19(4), pp. 361-375.

PTA, 2022. *Telecom Indicators*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.pta.gov.pk/en/telecom-indicators> [Accessed 02 May 2022].

Qamar, K. et al., 2021. CHALLENGES OF E-LEARNING FACED BY MEDICAL TEACHERS AND STUDENTS DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC. *Pak Armed Forces Med Journal*, 71(1), pp. s3-9.

Quinn, D. et al., 2012. Leading change: Applying change management approaches to engage students in blended learning. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 28(1), pp. 16-29.

Qureshi, I. A., Ilyas, K., Yasmin, R. & Whitty, M., 2012. Challenges of implementing e-learning in a Pakistani University. *Knowledge management & e-learning: An international Journal*, 4(3), pp. 310-324.

Qamar, T. & Bawany, N. Z., 2021. Impact of COVID-19 on Higher Education in Pakistan: An Exploratory Study. *International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, Volume 15, pp. 503-518.

Qazi, A. et al., 2021. The Role of Information and Communication Technology in E-learning

environments: A Systematic Review. *IEEE Access*, Volume 9, pp. 45539-45551.

Quinn, D. et al., 2012. Leading change: Applying change management approaches to engage students in blended learning. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 28(1), pp. 16-29.

Quinn, D. et al., 2012. Leading change: Applying change management approaches to engage students in blended learning. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 28(1), pp. 16-29.

Qureshi, I. A., Ilyas, K., Yasmin, R. & Whitty, M., 2012. Challenges of Implementing e-learning in a Pakistani university. *Knowledge Management & e-Learning: An International Journal*, 4(3), pp. 310-324.

Qureshi, I. A., Ilyas, K., Yasmin, R. & Whitty, M., 2012. Challenges of implementing e-learning in a Pakistani University. *Knowledge management & e-learning: An international Journal*, 4(3), pp. 310-324.

Qureshi, Q. A. et al., 2009. Elearning Development in HEIs: Uncomfortable and Comfortable Zones for Developing Countries. *Gomal University Journal of Research*, 25(2), pp. 47-56.

Qureshi, Q. A., Nawaz, A. & Khan, N., 2011. Prediction of the problems, user-satisfaction and prospects of e-learning in HEIs of KPK, Pakistan. *International Journal of Science and Technology Education research*, 2(2), pp. 13-21.

Ramos, T. B. et al., 2015. Experiences from the implementation of sustainable development in higher education institutions: Environmental Management for Sustainable Universities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 106, pp. 3-10.

Raum, S., Rawlings- Sanaei, F. & Potter, C., 2021. A web content-based method of stakeholder analysis: The case of forestry in the context of natural resource management. *Journal of Environmental Management*, Volume 300, pp. 1-9.

Rauf, A. & Shahzadi, S., 2023. Educational Policies: “Issues and Challenges in Implementation”. *International Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 4(3), pp. 128-139.

Reed, M. S. et al., 2009. Who’s in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. *Journal of Environmental Management*, Volume 90, pp. 1933-1949.

Regent University, 2019. *Ph.D. Organisational leadership*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.regent.edu/program/phd-in-organizational-leadership/> [Accessed 23 July 2019].

Richey, M. et al., 2014. A Complex Sociotechnical Systems Approach to Provisioning Educational Policies for Future Workforce. *Procedia Computer Science*, Volume 28, pp. 857-864.

Rienties, B. & Rivers, B. A., 2014. *Measuring and Understanding Learner Emotions: Evidence and Prospects*. Milton Keynes, LACE review papers.

Rodriguez, O., 2013. The concept of openness behind c and x-MOOCs (Massive Open

Online Courses). *Open Praxis*, 5(1), pp. 67-73.

Rothwell, W. J., Stavros, J. M. & Sullivan, R. L., 2015. *Practicing Organization Development : Leading Transformation and Change*. 4 ed. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated .

Roumell, E. A. & Salajan, F. D., 2016. The Evolution of U.S. e-Learning Policy: A Content Analysis of the National Education Technology Plans. *Educational Policy*, 30(2), pp. 365-397.

Rubin, G. J. & Wessely, S., 2020. *The psychological effects of quarantining a city*, London: BMJ.

Ryan, G., 2018. Introduction to postivism, interpretivism and critical theory. *Nurse Researcher*, 25(4), pp. 41-49.

Ryan, T. G., Toye, M., Charron, K. & Park, G., 2012. Learning Management System Migration: An Analysis of Stakeholder Perspectives. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 13(1), pp. 220-237.

Sajjad, S., 2021. Problems, Challenges, and Opportunities of Online English Learning and Teaching During Covid-19 at University Level in Pakistan. *International Journal of Engineering and Natural Science*, 6(1), pp. 78-82.

Salmon, G., 2014. LEARNING INNOVATION: A FRAMEWORK FOR TRANSFORMATION. *European Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, 17(2), pp. 219-235.

Salmon, G., Nie, M. & Edirisingha, P., 2010. Developing a five-stage model of learning in Second Life. *Educational Research*, 52(2), pp. 169-182.

Siddiquah, A. & Salim, Z., 2017. The ICT Facilities, Skills, Usage, and the problme faced by the students of Higher Education. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology*, 13(8), pp. 4987-4994.

Siddiquei, N. L. & Khalid, R., 2017. Emerging Trends of E- Learning in Pakistan: Past, Present and Future. *International Journal of Law, Humanities & Social Science*, 2(1), pp. 20-35.

Stake, R. E., 1995. *The art of the case study research*. California: Sage Publications.

Saidu, A. R., Clarkson, M. A. & Mohammed, M., 2016. E-Learning Security Challenges, Implementation and Improvement in Developing Countries: A Review. *International Journal of Computer Science and Statistics* , 2(2), pp. 20-26.

Samsudeen, S. N. & Mohamed, R., 2019. University students' intention to use e-learning systems A study of higher educational institutions in Sri Lanka. *Interactive Technology and Smart Education*, 16(3), pp. 219-238.

Samsudeen, S. N. & Mohamed, R., 2019. University students' intention to use e-learning systems A study of higher educational institutions in Sri Lanka. *Interactive Technology and Smart Education*, 16(3), pp. 219-238.

Sana, A. & Mariam, H., 2013. Use of Information and Communication Technologies in E-

learning System of Pakistan - a comparison study. *International Journal of Computer Science and Electronics Engineering (IJCSEE)*, 1(4), pp. 528-533.

Sangster, A., Stoner, G. & Flood, B., 2020. Insights into accounting education in a COVID-19 world. *Accounting Education*, 29(5), pp. 431-562.

Sanyal, S. & Hisam, M. W., 2018. The Impact of Teamwork on Work Performance of Employees: A Study of Faculty Members in Dhofar University. *Journal of Business and Management*, 20(3), pp. 15-22.

Sapathai, S. et al., 2020. A Stakeholder Analysis Approach for Area Business Continuity Management: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Disaster Research*, 15(5), pp. 588-598.

Sarker, S., Chatterjee, S., Xiao, X. & Elbanna, A., 2019. The sociotechnical axis of cohesion for the IS discipline: Its historical legacy and its continued relevance. *MIS Quarterly*, 43(3), pp. 695-719.

Sarwar, H. et al., 2020. Self-Reported Effectiveness of e-Learning Classes during COVID-19 Pandemic: A Nation-Wide Survey of Pakistani Undergraduate Dentistry Students. *European Journal of Dentistry*, 14(1), pp. 34-43.

Satria, D., 2022. WHAT MADE IMPLEMENTING EFFECTIVE ELEARNING HARD?: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ilmu Pengetahuan dan Teknologi Komputer*, 7(2), pp. 75-80.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A., 2016. *Research Methods for Business Students*. 7th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.

Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A., 2015. *Understanding research philosophy and approaches to theory development*. Harlow: Pearson Education.

Schachter, H., 2017. ORGANIZATION DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT HISTORY: A TALE OF CHANGING SEASONS. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 41(2), pp. 233-253.

Schulz, R., Isabwe, G. M. & Reichert, F., 2015. Investigating Teachers Motivation to Use ICT Tools in Higher Education. *Internet Technologies and Applications*, pp. 62-67.

Scotland, J., 2012. Exploring the Philosophical underpinnings of Research: Relating Ontology and Epistemology to the Methodology and Methods of the Scientific, Interpretive, and Critical Research Paradigms. *English Language Teaching*, 5(9), pp. 9-16.

Sefotho, M. M., 2015. A Researcher's Dilemma: Philosophy in crafting Dissertations and Theses. *Journal of Social Science*, 42(1), pp. 23-36.

Selwyn, N., 2007. The use of computer technology in university teaching and learning: a critical perspective. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, Volume 23, pp. 83-94.

Senior, 2002. *Organizational Change*. 2nd ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Ltd..

Sfenrianto, S., Hasibuan, A. Z. & Suhartanto, H., 2011. The Influence Factors of Inherent Structure in e-Learning Process. *International Journal of e-Education, e-Business, e-Management and eLearning*, 1(3), pp. 217-222.

- Shahabadi, M. M. & Uplane, M., 2015. Synchronous and asynchronous e-learning styles and academic performance of e-learners. *Procedia- Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 176, pp. 129-138.
- Shahzad, S. K. et al., 2020. Impact of Virtual Teaching on ESL Learner's Attitudes under COVID-19 Circumstances at Post Graduate Level in Pakistan. *English Language Teaching*, Volume 9, p. 13.
- Sharim, K. & Khlaif, Z. N., 2010. An e-learning approach to secondary education in Palestine: Opportunities and Challenges. *Information Technology for Development*, 16(3), pp. 159-173.
- Sharin, A. N., 2021. E-Learning During Covid-19: A Review of Literature. *Malaysian Journal of Media Studies*, 23(1), pp. 15-28.
- Sharpe, L. M., Harwell, M. C. & Jackson, C., 2021. Integrated stakeholder prioritization criteria for environmental management. *Journal of Environmental Management*, Volume 282, pp. 1-8.
- Siddiquei, N. L. & Khalid, R., 2020. Journey towards E-Learning in Pakistan: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Distance Education and E- Learning*, 5(2), pp. 20-44.
- Siddiquei, N. L. & Khalid, R., 2020. Journey towards E-Learning in Pakistan: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Distance Education and E- Learning* , 5(2), pp. 20-44.
- Siddiqui, Z. H., 2007. *Promoting E-Learning in Pakistan: Strategies and Challenges*. Putrajaya, e-Asia Conference and Exhibition.
- Sidorko, P. E., 2008. Transforming library and higher education support services: can change model helps?. *Library Management*, 29(4), pp. 307-318.
- Sidorko, P. E., 2008. Transforming library and higher education support services: can change models help?. *Library management*, 29(4), pp. 307-318.
- Simon, E. J., Janneck, M. & Gumm, D., 2006. Understanding Socio-Technical Change: Towards a Multidisciplinary Approach. *International Federation for Information Processing*, Volume 223, pp. 469-479.
- Slaba, M., 2015. Stakeholder Groups of Public and Private Universities in the Czech Republic – Identification, Categorization and Prioritization. *REVIEW OF ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES*, 15(3), pp. 305-326.
- Sofat, K., Kiran, R. & Kaushik, S., 2015. Organisational change and organisational commitment: An empirical study of IT organisations in India. *Global Journal of Management and Business*, 15(6), pp. 39-49.
- Song, J., Park, S. & Park, M., 2017. Digital literacy of language learners in two different contexts. *JALT call Journal*, 13(2), pp. 77-96.
- Stake, R. E., 1995. *The art of the case study research*. California: Sage Publications.
- Statista, 2020. *Latin America: online learning platforms use during COVID-19 pandemic 2020*, by type. [Online] Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1184275/online-learning-platforms->

[coronavirus-latin-america-type/](#)

[Accessed 13 April 2021].

Statista, 2020. *Purchasing e-learning material online in Great Britain from 2011 to 2019*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/321036/purchasing-e-learning-material-online-great-britain/> [Accessed 13 April 2021].

Stewart, K. & Williams, M., 2005. Researching online populations: the use of online focus groups for social research. *Qualitative Research*, 5(4), pp. 395-416.

Stockley, D., 2004. Strategic Planning for Technological Innovation in Canadian Post Secondary Education. *Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology*, 30(2).

Storberg-Walker, J. & Torraco, R., 2004. "Change and Higher Education: A Multidisciplinary Approach". Austin, Academy of Human Resource Development International Conference, pp. 811-818.

Stouten, J., Rousseau, D. M. & Cremer, D. D., 2018. SUCCESSFUL ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE: INTEGRATING THE MANAGEMENT PRACTICE AND SCHOLARLY LITERATURES. *Academy of Management Annals*, 12(2), pp. 752-788.

Stryker, S. & Burke, P. J., 2000. The Past, Present and Future of an Identity Theory. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 63(4), pp. 284-297.

Sucozhanay, D., Santos, E., De Witte, K. & Euwema, M., 2016. A *STAKEHOLDER MANAGEMENT APPROACH FOR UNIVERSITY CHANGE: A CASE STUDY IN LATIN AMERICA*. Valencia, INTED2016: 10TH INTERNATIONAL TECHNOLOGY, EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT CONFERENCE.

Sumallika, T., Raju, P. V. M., Indira, D. N. V. S. L. S. & Lakshmi, P. R., 2022. An Overview of E-Learning and its Challenges in India. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, 7(2), pp. 314-319.

Superior University, 2021. *About Us- Superior University Lahore*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.superior.edu.pk/about-us/> [Accessed 27 October 2021].

Superior University, 2021a. *The Superior Education- Superior University Lahore*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.superior.edu.pk/the-superior-education/> [Accessed 27 October 2021].

Suzianti, A. & Paramadini, S. A., 2021. Continuance Intention of E-Learning: The Condition and Its Connection with Open Innovation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market and Complexity*, 7(97), pp. 1-14.

Swanson, B. E., 1994. Information systems innovation among organizations. *Management Science*, 40(9), pp. 1069-1092.

Tabassum, F., Akram, N. & Moazzam, M., 2021. Online Learning System in Higher Education Institutions in Pakistan: Investigating Problems Faced by Students During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Web-Based Learning and Teaching*

Technologies, 17(2), pp. 1-15.

Tahrini, A., Hone, K. & Liu, X., 2014. The effects of individual differences on e-learning users' behaviour in developing countries: A structural equation model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, Volume 41, pp. 153-163.

Taylor, J., 2017. *Pakistan Higher Education Commission Vision 2025*, London: Universities UK.

Tekniepe, R. J., 2014. Linking the Occupational Pressures of College Presidents to Presidential Turnover. *Community College Review*, 42(2), pp. 143-159.

Times Higher Education, 2021. *University of Lahore- World University Rankings*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/university-lahore>

[Accessed 11 August 2021].

Times Higher Education, 2021. *University of Management and Technology- World University Rankings*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/university-management-and-technology>

[Accessed 21 October 2021].

Tirziu, A. M. & Vrabie, C., 2015. Education 2.0: E-Learning Methods. *Procedia- Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 186, pp. 376-380.

Todnem By, R., 2005. Organisational Change Management: A Critical Review. *Journal of Change Management*, 5(4), pp. 369-380.

Tomczyk, L., 2021. E-learning in Poland: Challenges, Opportunities and Prospects for Remote Learning during the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Higher Education in Russia and Beyond*, 2(27), pp. 10-12.

Torraco, R. J., Hoover, R. E. & Knippelmeyer, S. A., 2005. Organization Development and Change in Universities. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 7(3), pp. 422-437.

Triscari, J. S., 2008. *Organizational Change? Organizational Development? Organizational Transformation?: Why Do We Care What We Call It?*. St. Louis, New Prairie Press.

Turabik, T. & Baskan, G. A., 2015. The Importance of Motivation Theories in Terms Of Education Systems. *Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 186, pp. 1055-1063.

Turnbull, D., Chugh, R. & Luck, J., 2021. Transitioning to E-Learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: How have Higher Education Institutions responded to the challenge?. *Education and Information Technologies*, Volume 26, pp. 6401-6419.

Udacity, 2022. *About Us*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.udacity.com/us> [Accessed 15 May 2022].

UIOWA, 2019. *Special Collections & University Archives- The University of IOWA Libraries*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.lib.uiowa.edu/sc/archives/faq/faqfirsts/>

[Accessed 23 July 2019].

UMT, 2021a. *About UMT.* [Online]
Available at: <https://www.umt.edu.pk/about-umt.aspx>
[Accessed 21 October 2021].

UMT, 2021b. *Vision and Mission.* [Online]
Available at: <https://www.umt.edu.pk/vision-and-mission.aspx>
[Accessed 21 October 2021].

UMT, 2021. *Introducing UMT.* [Online]
Available at: <https://www.umt.edu.pk/introducing-umt.aspx>
[Accessed 21 October 2021].

University of Lahore, 2021b. *Facts- The University of Lahore.* [Online]
Available at: <https://uol.edu.pk/discover-uol/facts/>
[Accessed 11 August 2021].

University of Lahore, 2021a. *UOL's Medicine and Dentistry Ranked No. 1 Engineering 3rd in Pakistan- University of Lahore.* [Online]
Available at: <https://uol.edu.pk/uols-medicine-dentistry-ranked-no-1-engineering-3rd-in-pakistan/>
[Accessed 11 August 2021].

University of Lahore, 2021c. *Mission & Vision- The University of Lahore.* [Online]
Available at: <https://uol.edu.pk/discover-uol/mission-vision/>
[Accessed 11 August 2021].

University of Lahore, 2021d. *Accreditations- The University of Lahore.* [Online]
Available at: <https://uol.edu.pk/discover-uol/accreditation/>
[Accessed 11 August 2021].

University of Lahore, 2021. *HIStory- University of Lahore.* [Online]
Available at: <https://uol.edu.pk/discover-uol/history/>
[Accessed 10 August 2021].

University of Sargodha, 2020. *Covid 19 Online Psychological Services.* [Online]
Available at: <https://su.edu.pk/news/covid-19-online-psychological-services>
[Accessed 10 October 2021].

University of Sargodha, 2021. *Welcome to SU.* [Online]
Available at: <https://su.edu.pk/aboutus>
[Accessed 10 October 2021].

Uys, P. M., 2010. Implementing an open source learning management system: A critical analysis of change strategies. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 26(7), pp. 980-995.

Virtual University of Pakistan, 2024. *Milestones.* [Online]
Available at: <https://www.vu.edu.pk/AboutUs/Milestones.aspx>
[Accessed 15 July 2024].

Voigt, C., Blomer, L., Kotter, J. & Hoppe, U., 2021. Agile Change to Digital Teaching

- during and after Corona Pandemic for Flipped Classroom Courses: An Overview of Tasks and Responsibilities. *Journal of e-Learning Research*, 1(1), pp. 11-22.
- Varvasovszky, Z. & Brugha, R., 2000. How to do (or not to do) a stakeholder analysis. *Health Policy and Planning*, Volume 15, pp. 338-345.
- Varvasovszky, Z. & Brugha, R., 2000. How to do (or not to do)... A stakeholder analysis. *Health policy and planning*, 15(3), pp. 338-345.
- Wagner, N., Hassanein, K. & Head, M., 2008. Who is responsible for E-Learning Success in Higher Education? A Stakeholders' Analysis. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 11(3), pp. 26-36.
- Ward, T., Monaghan, K. & Villing, R., 2007. MyVLE: A case study in building a universal telematic education environment for a small university. *European Journal of Open, Distance and E-learning*, 10(1), pp. 1-10.
- Waris, A. et al., 2020. COVID-19 outbreak: current scenario of Pakistan. *New Microbes and New Infections*, 35(C), pp. 1-6.
- Watson, D., 2003. *Universities and civic engagement: A critique and a prospectus*. s.l., University of Queensland.
- Weiss, J., 2006. *International handbook of Virtual Learning Environments*. 1 ed. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.
- White, M. & Shellenbarger, T., 2017. Harnessing the Power of Learning Management Systems. *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development*, 33(3), pp. 138-141.
- WHO, 2020. *Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Situation Report -1*, Geneva: World Health Organisation.
- WHO, 2020. *WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19 - 11 March 2020*, Geneva: WHO.
- Wichadee, S., 2014. Significant predictors for effectiveness of blended learning in a language course. *JALT Call Journal*, 14(1), pp. 25-42.
- Wiener, M. & Mehrabian, A., 1986. *Language within language: Immediacy, a channel in verbal communication*. New York: Appleton.
- Williams, C., 2007. Research Methods. *Journal of Business & Economic Research*, 5(3), pp. 65-72.
- Wilson, J., 2013. *Essentials of Business Research: a guide to doing your research project*. 2nd ed. s.l.:Sage Publications.
- Woiceshyn, J. & Daellenbach, U., 2018. Evaluating inductive vs deductive research in management studies: Implications for authors, editors, and reviewers. *Qualitative Research in Organisations and Management: An International Journal*, 13(2), pp. 183-195.
- Xu, W. & Zammit, K., 2020. Applying Thematic Analysis to Education: A Hybrid Approach to Interpreting Data in Practitioner Research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, Volume 19, pp. 1-9.

- Yildiz, E. P., 2021. Academist Perceptions on the Use of Web 2.0 Tools Through Maslow's Needs Hierarchy: A Case Study.. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 4(1), pp. 173-188.
- Yin, R. K., 2015. Case Studies. In: J. D. Wright, ed. *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*. s.l.:Elsevier, pp. 194-201.
- Yin, R. K., 2018. *Case study research and applications: Design and methods*. 6th ed. s.l.:SAGE Publishing Inc.
- Yasin, S. A., Batool, S. S. & Ajmal, M. A., 2019. Leadership in Academia of Pakistan: Perception of Crisis Situation and Solutions. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 34(4), pp. 671-692.
- Yin, R. K., 2015. Case Studies. In: J. D. Wright, ed. *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*. s.l.:Elsevier, pp. 194-201.
- Zubairi, A., Halim, W., Kaye, T. & Wilson, S., 2021. *Country-Level Research Review: EdTech In Pakistan*. s.l.:EdTech.
- Zhang, D., 2003. Powering E-Learning In the New Millennium: An Overview of E-learning and Enabling Technology. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 5(2), pp. 201-212.
- Zhao, Y. et al., 2021. Do cultural differences affect users' e-learning adoption? A meta-analysis. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 52(1), pp. 20-41.
- Zhengxia, L., 2018. *The Impact of Distance Learning on Foreign Language Education*. s.l., Atlantis Press, pp. 1-3.
- Zhu, X. & Liu, J., 2020. Education in and after Covid-19: Immediate responses and long-term visions. *Postdigital Science and Education*, 2(3), pp. 695-699.

Appendices

Appendix 1A

Nodes\Initial Coding\Nodes

Name	Description	Files	References
Centralised Platform (MOODLE)		1	1
Challenges		23	76
Assessment		1	2
Issues & Problems		20	51
Communication and Interaction		4	4
Connectivity Issue		5	5
Cultural Issues		5	5
Debates		0	0
Electricity Issues		2	2
Expensive Modes		1	1
Geographical Impact		1	1
Internet Issues		6	6
Practical Courses		4	4
Question Bank		1	1
Student Engagement		5	5

Technological Issues		6	6
Name	Description	Files	References
Unavailability of Technology		3	4
Unfamiliar		2	2
Weak Infrastructure		2	3
Work Load		2	2
Pandemic		5	5
Resistance to Change		4	5
Staff Readiness		7	8
Technological Literacy		5	5
Change Management		21	64
Acceptance of Change		6	8
Change Implemented		9	10
Motivated Teachers		4	6
Non-Monetary Motivation		6	7
Organisational Change		7	10
Trainings		14	23
E-learning benefits		6	10
External Factors		8	10
External Stakeholder		5	11
HEC		5	10
First University to implement Change in Pandemic		2	2

Name	Description	Files	References
Internal Factors		6	10
Internal Stakeholder		4	4
IT Department		4	4
Learning vs Knowledge vs Skills		5	6
No Resistance		6	8
Plagiarism	Checking the use of Turnitin or other plagiarism software to check the similarity in the assignments and projects	10	12
Turnitin		10	12
Suggestions		4	4
Teachers		3	3
Traditional Pedagogy		3	3
types of e-learning		21	80
2017 ERP System		1	1
Case Based Questions		5	12
Facebook or Whatsapp		6	6
Hybrid Classes		2	3
LMS system		4	5
Moodle		14	21
Multimedia use in Early stage		1	1
Online Classes		4	6
online databases		3	3
Online Examination		5	5

Name	Description	Files	References
Online Invigilation		1	1
Open Book Exam		2	2
Presentation Slides		2	2
Software	Different Softwares such as Zoom, MOODLE, VLE, Google Meet etc.	3	3
Teaching Methods		2	4
Use of MOODLE		4	5
Policies	Rules, regulations and policies proposed by HEC, any policies implemented and used by HEIs	7	25

Nodes\Themes

Name	Description	Files	References
Focus Group	Interviews with student focus group	5	45
E learning issues and assistance	issues and advantages of e-learning	4	19
Technological Support	Support provided to the students by the university related to technology	4	7
Training and Motivational Factors	accessible e-resources, and supporting students' learning approach	5	19
Accessible e Resources		4	5
Supporting Students Learning Approach		4	13
HEC External Stakeholder	It will includes sub themes related to the HEC interview	1	20
Change Implementation Process	It includes those sub-themes which are related to the change implementation process of e-learning	1	4
Collaborations	Partnerships of HEC	1	1

Name	Description	Files	References
and Explorations			
Policies and Regulations	Policy guidelines and regulations mentioned by HEC in their policy guideline documents and interview	1	3
Change Management Model or Process	It will include those themes which shows if there are any existing model or processes used by HEC towards the implementation of e learning in HEIs of Pakistan	1	11
Change Management	Which change management strategies have been used	1	5
Resources	Which resources are used for the implementation of e-learning	1	2
Training and Motivational Strategies	training and motivational strategies used by the HEC towards the change implementation	1	4
Stakeholder Perception	Perceptions of different stakeholders considered by HEC	1	5
Changing Nature of Academic Teaching	How teaching practices are changed due to e-learning	1	2
External Forces	It will depict about environment and all other external forces which affects the implementation of e-learning	1	1
Factors Compromising Learning Process	Those factors and challenges which are hindering the implementation of e-learning	1	2
HOD	Themes related to head of departments or middle level management	5	56
Organisational Support	Support provided by the institute and management	5	33
Lack of Resources	Lack of resources affecting the implementation of e-learning	4	7
Support Towards Change		5	26

Name	Description	Files	References
Implementation			
Stakeholders attitude towards the Use of e-learning & Resources	attitudes of internal stakeholders such as teachers and students will be reviewed	5	11
Training and Motivational Strategies	Techniques or strategies used by the management to implement the change	5	12
Management and Administrative Stakeholders	It will include themes related to Examinations Controller and Business Development Manager of SU, IT Manager From LGU, and Registrar of UOS	5	38
Changing Nature of Academic Teaching BDM	Coding from BDM interview	1	4
Factors Compromising Learning Process and External Forces EC and BDM	coding related to the interviews of EC and BDM SU	2	7
Lever of Change Management Registrar and IT manager	Interview coding from Registrar UOS and IT manager LGU	2	7
Managerial Perspective Registrar and IT Manager	Coding related to managerial practices from registrar and IT manager interviews.	3	5
Resources EC and BDM		2	3
Teachers attitude Towards the use of E Learning EC		1	2
Training and Motivational Factors registrar and IT manager	Coding from the interviews of registrar UOS and IT manager LGU	2	3
Training and Motivational	EC and BDM's interviews will be used for coding related to training and motivational	2	7

Name	Description	Files	References
strategies EC and BDM	techniques		
Teachers	Coding for teachers	13	150
Autonomous or Managed Work	Change was directed through autonomy or through managing the change	10	17
External Forces	involvement of external factors or stakeholders	5	5
Top-level Management	change directed through high-level management	8	12
Change in Academic teaching		13	111
E-learning before pandemic	use of e-learning before pandemic	13	22
E-learning during or after pandemic	E-learning implementation during pandemic and after pandemic	13	52
Factors Compromising Learning Process	It includes different factors which were affecting the learning process and the implementation of e-learning	11	22

Appendix 2

Ethical Approval

25/11/2020

Dear Zaman Javed,

Your application 13680: The Role of Change Management Strategies towards the adoption of E-learning in HEIs of Pakistan., submission 11819, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Title	Comment
What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?	Need to just make it clearer here that the data will also be stored securely on a password protected device in a safe place.

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner

Participant Information Sheet

The Role of Change Management Strategies towards the adoption of E-learning in HEIs of Pakistan

Researcher: Mr. Zaman Javed

Dear Participant

Please take some time to read through the information sheet. If you have any questions at any point, please do not hesitate to ask the researcher, Zaman or contact him at any stage later at

Synopsis

You have been invited to take part in a Doctorate (DBA) research study exploring the role of change management models in implementing e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan.

What you have been asked to do

You have been asked to participate in a confidential and anonymous face-to-face interview session which will last around 30 minutes. This interview will be arranged for a specified time, date and location according to your convenience.

The interview session initially includes the basic questions related to the introduction of e-learning in your university setting. You will be asked questions about the implementation process of e-learning which might include any models or processes to follow during the implementation process or not.

It might also include questions related to the impact of COVID-19 and government involvement in the implementation of e-learning in HEIs. The researcher will also ask about any e-learning technology been used by the institute in the past or after COVID-19 pandemic situation. At the end, you can also provide any suggestions towards the study, and you can also ask questions from the researcher for your clarification.

Your Data

In order to enhance the accuracy of the data, the researcher will record the audio recording of the interview with your permission. Also, with your permission, I may include some quotes from your interview to enhance the reliability of the collected data and to help the researcher to emphasise on a specific point which helps to provide more insights towards the end results of the study. These interviews will be anonymised, and great care will be taken to ensure that any wording or quotation used will not pose any potential risk towards you or the organisation.

The notes and recordings will be kept anonymised and will be stored in an encrypted folder with password protection on it. The recordings and data will only be accessible to the researcher Zaman Javed only.

Lastly, your participation in the study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to answer any question. You may withdraw your participation at any time or after interview session.

Thank you for your kind co-operation.

Zaman Javed

Doctorate in Business Administration (DBA)

Business School

University of the West of Scotland

Email: [REDACTED]

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Skype: [REDACTED]

Appendix 3

INTERVIEW WITH SENIOR MANAGEMENT

Thank you for agreeing on giving me your valuable time for this interview. As my research is related with the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan, I will be asking some key questions related to the techniques being used and also related to the strategies being considered while implementing e-learning.

My first question is:

- Are there any e-learning systems currently being used by this university? If yes, then when it was first implemented or used? If not, then which e-learning technique are under consideration to implement?
- What types of e-learning teaching systems are used in this university? (in case if is it already in use)
- Are there any strategies put into place to evolve the learning and teaching process in this university? (Any strengths or weaknesses related to the strategies)
- Do you believe that the introduction of e-learning represents a significant organisational change for the institution?
- What actions are taken by the senior management in the process of implementation of new learning techniques?
- Are there any management strategies used or considered in the implementation of e-learning in this university?
- If management strategies are used then, how effective were those strategies related to the implementation of e-learning?
- According to your point of view, is there any resistance towards e-learning implementation by considering internal and external factors?
- With the current environment globally and locally there is more emphasis on distance learning than ever before, so how do you think your esteemed University will successfully implement e-learning by considering different stakeholder's perception? (Examples of stakeholders involved will be given after the initial response to this question.)
- How are teachers and researchers equally rewarded for the smooth implementation of new learning and teaching techniques?
- As Higher Education Commission issues directives related to use of distance learning, will it be affecting this University in any matter or not?
- Are there any special measures taken for the quick implementation of e-learning systems due to the covid-19 situation?
- How online assessment tools are helping teachers to assess the progression of the students?

Note

Side questions such as role of Alumni, government, parents and employers will also be asked according to the situation in the interview. It is because the interview will be semi-structured.

Remarks

Thank you again for providing such valuable information. Is there any question would you like to ask, or any suggestions related to my research you would like to give?

INTERVIEW WITH DEPARTMENT HEAD OR MANAGER

Thank you for agreeing on the interview and to provide your useful time. In this interview, I will be asking questions related to your staff development, their needs and any appraisals related to University's strategy to utilise distance learning methods. With the help of your interview, I will be able to see how your department will be able to help your staff members related to the online learning and to also explore the internal and external factors affecting the acceptance or rejection of online learning.

My key questions are:

- Are there any e-learning or online learning techniques are being used by your department in this University?
- Were there any teachers or professors who initiated the process of learning through e-learning in your department?
- Did any of your professors or teachers used groups on Facebook or their YouTube channel to provide off campus learning to their students? (If yes, then when was the first time they initiated this step?)
- Is there any resistance by your staff members related to the use of online teaching and learning?
- Are there any strategies used by your department for staff development related to academics?
- Do you believe that the introduction of e-learning represents a significant organisational change for the institution?
- Are there any appraisal process used to encourage or motivate the staff members to accept the implementation of e-learning? In case of already use of distance learning, any processes used to improve the e-learning in this University?
- According to your point of view, what will be the needs of the academics to initialise the smooth delivery and flexible delivery of online learning projects? (Examples will be given of VLEs, MOODLE, Online conferencing tools etc.)
- Can you provide any recommendations which helps or hinders the academic or non-academic staff in adopting distance learning methods? (for instance, skills, product knowledge, motivation, student's expectations etc.)
- As HEC is increasing the emphasis on online learning, which strategy will be appropriate to implement or enhance the use e-learning in this University? And How will you evaluate that chosen strategy?
- Which processes are taken into consideration to ensure the quick implementation of e-learning system due to COVID-19?

Remarks

Thank you so much for the informative time and interview. Is there anything you would like to ask me or to give me any suggestions related to my research?

INTERVIEW WITH TEACHERS OR STAFF MEMBERS

First of all, thank you for your valuable time. In this interview I will be asking questions related to the use or implementation of online learning.

Key Questions

- Can you please tell me when you started teaching in this University?
- Have you had any experience of teaching before?
- What subjects you teach here?
- Have you used any online learning tool before? Do you know how to use e-learning software or techniques in the process of course delivery?
- To support your teaching, which methods or techniques you use to help your students to provide them more information related to your lectures?
- Which teaching methods you use frequently in your lectures? (For instance, Power-point slides, case studies, articles, VLE, MOODLE etc.)
- Do you believe that the introduction of e-learning represents a significant organisational change for the institution?
- Which factors either internal or external influence your choice of selecting those methods?
- What are the major challenges you are facing, or you will face related to online learning in current academic year?
- Is university providing any assistance towards adopting those changes i.e. use of online learning?
- What are the major challenges faced by you with the immediate implementation of e-learning systems due to COVID-19 situation?
- Which teaching or managerial process have been changed with the introduction of any e-learning system?
- How easier it is to conduct online assessment for the exams conducted online?

Remarks

Thank you so much for the informative time and interview. Is there anything you would like to ask me or to give me any suggestions related to my research?

INTERVIEW SHEET FOR FOCUS GROUP (Students Only)

First of all, thank you for your time to take part in this research discussion group. As due to pandemic and growing demand of e-learning and its implementation in HEIs of Pakistan, I am interested to particularly know about your views on how university is handling with e-learning programs and their implementation. As it is a discussion, I will ask some questions but mainly I will listen to your comments and suggestions which will assist me in writing up the report for the analysis section of this research. The discussion will be audio recorded only and it will be kept in a secure password protected folder which will be destroyed after the analysis and research is completed. Individuals will be kept anonymous in the transcription of this discussion. Shall we begin?

Starting Discussion with Question:

Would everyone introduce themselves by starting to state their first name, your course/degree and your year of study please.

Introductory Question:

Before we start our discussion, let us hear about everyone's opinion related to the term "online learning or e-learning".

Some Key Questions:

Were there any e-learning tools being used in your university before COVID-19?

How e-learning helped you to improve and continue your learning in general during this pandemic and before pandemic as well?

According to your point of view, are there any advantages of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan? For instance, availability of materials, distance learning, easy access to the materials etc.

In your point of view, which internal or external stakeholders affects the successful use of e-learning or its implementation in HEIs of Pakistan?

As the implementation presents change in the organisation, were there any change management strategies used by your university to tackle the challenges aroused by the proper introduction of distance learning?

What are the major problems faced by the students in e-learning methods? For instance, lack of interaction, internet connectivity, designated spaces to attend meetings, maintaining concentration etc.

Is there any support provided by your institute related to e-learning classes and examination?

In your opinion, what would you suggest related to the quality of online learning software or tools used in your institute? Mention any improvements you would like in the delivery of e-learning.

Note

Thank you all for your valuable time and information. Is there anything you would like to ask me or provide me any suggestions related to my research.

INTERVIEW WITH HEC MANAGER

Thank you for agreeing on the interview and to provide your useful time. In this interview, I will be asking questions related to HEC's efforts and assistance provided to the Higher Educational Institutes of Pakistan related to online learning. With the help of your interview, I will be able to see how HEC is helping or will be able to help the HEIs of Pakistan related to the online learning, and to also explore the internal and external factors affecting the acceptance or rejection of online learning.

My key questions are:

- How HEC is helping the Higher educational institutes in improving the quality of education in Pakistan related to private and public both institutes?
- As HEC is the regulatory body in Pakistan, when was e-learning first initiated in Higher Educational Institutes of Pakistan with the help of HEC?
- Are there any specified policies outlined by HEC for the implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan?
- Are there any current strategies put into place for the implementation of e-learning or for the ongoing changes towards e-learning mode of teaching?
- Which processes are taken into consideration to ensure the quick implementation of e-learning system due to COVID-19?
- How effective are the current strategies towards the e-learning implementation or changes in the policy related to e-learning?
- How HEC helps HEIs to reduce the resistance related to the organisational change occurred due to the introduction of e-learning?
- Does HEC consider their stakeholder's perception related to the implementation of policies, such as issuing new policy or rule for the universities and considering the involvement of other stakeholders related to those policies?
- According to your opinion, how HEC can help the HEIs to bring them at one platform related to e-learning or online learning?
- HEC being the regulatory body, in your point of view, what will be the internal and external factors affecting the successful use and implementation of e-learning in HEIs of Pakistan?
- What will be your suggestions related to the smooth implementation and use of e-learning software and techniques in HEIs of Pakistan?

Remarks

Thank you so much for the informative time and interview. Is there anything you would like to ask me or to give me any suggestions related to my research?

INTERVIEW WITH I.T. DEPARTMENT HEAD OR MANAGER

Thank you for agreeing on the interview and to provide your useful time. In this interview, I will be asking questions related to your staff development, their needs and any appraisals related to University's strategy to utilise distance learning methods. With the help of your interview, I will be able to see how your department will be able to help your staff members related to the online learning and to also explore the internal and external factors affecting the acceptance or rejection of online learning.

My key questions are:

- When was e-learning first initiated in this institution?
- Are there any current strategies put into place for the implementation of e-learning or for the ongoing changes towards e-learning mode of teaching?
- How effective are the current strategies towards the e-learning implementation or changes in the policy of e-learning?
- Does new policy or changes in the implementation of e-learning provides any resistance in the staff environment?
- Were there any teachers or professors who initiated the process of learning through e-learning in your department?
- Did any of your professors or teachers used groups on Facebook or their YouTube channel to provide off campus learning to their students? (If yes, then when was the first time they initiated this step?)
- Is there any resistance by your staff members related to the use of online teaching and learning?
- Are there any strategies used by your department for staff development related to academics?
- Do you believe that the introduction of e-learning represents a significant organisational change for the institution?
- Are there any appraisal process used to encourage or motivate the staff members to accept the implementation of e-learning? In case of already use of distance learning, any processes used to improve the e-learning in this University?
- According to your point of view, what will be the needs of the academics to initialise the smooth delivery and flexible delivery of online learning projects? (Examples will be given of VLEs, MOODLE, Online conferencing tools etc.)
- Can you provide any recommendations which helps or hinders the academic or non-academic staff in adopting distance learning methods? (For instance, skills, product knowledge, motivation, student's expectations etc.)
- As HEC is increasing the emphasis on online learning, which strategy will be appropriate to implement or enhance the use e-learning in this University? And how will you evaluate that chosen strategy?
- Which processes are taken into consideration to ensure the quick implementation of e-learning system due to COVID-19?

Remarks

Thank you so much for the informative time and interview. Is there anything you would like to ask me or to give me any suggestions related to my research?

INTERVIEW WITH BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT MANAGER

Thank you for agreeing on the interview and providing me with your valuable time. This interview will be regarding to shed light on the e-learning (online learning) opportunities in your institute along-with foreign universities as well with whom your institute have MOUs signed. This whole interview will be anonymous, and all the data will be saved on a password protected folder which will be only accessible by myself. This data will not be shared with anyone except my supervisor upon his request only.

My key questions are:

- Are you familiar with the term e-learning?
- According to your knowledge, how your institute is contributing towards online education?
- With your understanding about e-learning, what do you suggest your institute is going towards? Such as competitive hybrid modes of learning?
- Do you believe there are any external factors or internal factors which influences the changes related teaching strategies? Such as technological advancements, COVID-19, any partner organisations etc., or policies by governing bodies?
- Have you signed any MOUs with foreign universities?
- Does partner universities with whom you have signed MOUs, share students and teachers in terms of any exchange programs? Or provides any visiting faculty members?
- As there are different MOUs being signed with foreign universities as well, do they share their mode of teaching as well? Such as notes, any softwares for online learning?
- Does your split degree programs are based on virtual mode as well such as only online?
- As we can see there is greater emphasise from external factor i.e., from HEC about implementing online learning or blended learning platforms, do you think your collaboration from partner universities can help in providing new technology or would you prefer in house online learning software?
- According to your point of view, which resources should be beneficial to your institute towards better e-learning experience for the students?
- Lastly, can you please provide your experienced suggestion on how to overcome the issues related to e-learning implementation in HEIs of Pakistan?

